

**Examining the influence of salesperson performance on
anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention:
A study of customer perception in the context of the retail
industry in Vietnam.**

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DEDICATION

This doctoral research is dedicated to my father, Anh Tuan Dang, my mother, Thanh Van Ly, and my friend, Thanh Dao, all of whom have shown me unwavering love and support.

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Love you all

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AUTHOR'S DECLARATION

I, Dang Ly Tuong Vy, affirm that the concepts, research effort, analyses, and findings presented in my PhD thesis *examining the influence of salesperson performance on anticipation of future interaction and repurchase interaction: A study of customers' perception in the context of the retail industry in Vietnam* is completely my own work, except where otherwise acknowledged. Additionally, I declare that there is no material in this thesis has ever before been submitted, in whole or in part, for the granting of another academic degree or certificate. Unless otherwise noted, this thesis is entirely my own original work.

ABSTRACT

This research is primarily concerned with salesperson performance and its influence on customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention.

Salesperson performance is an integral part of the organisation's operating activities. Most of the salesperson's performance studies are related to the development of a sales strategy, salespeople's skills, and experience. Salesperson performance as a signal of service quality, communicates the company's value and quality to customers (Hartline et al., 2003; Nunkoo et al., 2020). Its importance on profitability and organisational success has received positive attention in recent years, however, explanations of salesperson performance and its relation to antecedents, and consequences factors are still limited. Academe and practitioner also realised the relationship between salesperson performance and anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention, but few studies actually support this assumption. This research, therefore, will attempt to fill this gap and make it easier to understand the concept of salesperson performance, its antecedents, and consequences as well as focusing on anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention as a consequence of the consumer perspective.

This study applied mixed methods designs including qualitative and quantitative research. Quantitative research was mainly focused on this study and was reinforced by findings from in-depth interviews of the exploratory phase (qualitative research). The study's conceptual framework was constructed using both the existing body of literature and a qualitative investigation. In the second phase, the framework will be tested by conducting a survey with 385 customers in Vietnam, determining their awareness of the impact of salesperson performance on future interaction and repurchase intention. An appropriate sample size was useful for researchers to examine the problem and come up with comprehensive solutions through performing multivariate analysis of the data. It included exploratory factor analysis (EFA), Cronbach-alpha, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structural equation modelling (SEM). These were the basic techniques used to

help assess the reliability, validity of a scale, as well as to examine the relationship between the structures formed in a study. The application of SEM enabled researchers to analyse survey data and investigate complex relationships in statistical hypotheses. The model demonstrated a good fit with the data collected, and the convergence, discriminant, nominal validity as well as reliability were also guaranteed.

The literature and the statistical results indicate that customer orientation, value-based selling, sales skill, adaptive selling behaviour are the four main factors that have a direct impact on salesperson performance. The relationship between salesperson performance and its consequences was also confirmed through hypothesis testing. Salesperson performance was found to be positively related to anticipation of future interaction and satisfaction with salesperson. Besides, a relationship between anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention has been demonstrated.

This study has contributed significantly to humanity knowledge by showing how salesperson performance positively affects the anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. It provides certain theoretical contributions to literature such as theory development, conceptualisation and measurement, theory testing and generalisation. As for the methodology, this investigation offered a more extensive understanding of the marketing sector, the company's functional quality, and salesperson performance literature. It also provides management implications, supporting managers' understanding of the impacts surrounding salesperson performance, its relationship with the antecedent and consequences factors. This understanding aids managers in considering and developing salespeople's ability to enhance customers' anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. This study's results also have high practical value for researchers to be able to make outstanding findings in the future.

The study results, however, also have certain limitations found in the sampling/analytical and measurement methods. The instructions are provided in the hope of prompting further investigations to strengthen knowledge about salesperson performance and its antecedents and consequences.

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CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

1.1. INTRODUCTION

This first chapter introduces the scope of the thesis and begins by discussing the research background and identifying the gaps in the literature. Section 1.2 presents the research background. Section 1.3 describes the statement of the research problem, where the gaps in the literature are identified. The development and changing of salesperson performance in Section 1.4. Section 1.5 explains the objectives of the research. Then, the methodology that has been followed to answer the research questions and to test the proposed hypotheses is discussed in section 1.6. Section 1.7 describes the significance of the study.

1.2. RESEARCH BACKGROUND

The retail market is increasingly developing and more clearly shaped in society. Besides markets and supermarkets, it is undeniable that shopping mall is becoming more and more popular and necessary in human life, especially in big cities - Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. Salesperson has since become more important in such retail stores (Abeysekera and Wickramasinghe, 2013; Ahmad, 2020). Their mission is no longer merely about selling, but also inspiring, bringing core values to customers and businesses (Zhang and Glynn, 2015; Hochstein et al., 2019). In addition, salesperson must also meet the organisation's requirements, such as establishing relationships with customers, strengthening trust, persuading customers to buy goods with awareness and happiness at the present time and in future (Hazrati et al., 2012). A good salesperson's performance not only brings satisfaction to customers, ensures a higher expectation of future interaction, increases customer repurchase intention as well as ensures revenue and profit for business.

There is a long history of salesperson performance in marketing mentioned in the relevant literature. One of the first and most commonly cited documents is Churchill et al. (1985), who had more than 100 published papers on salesperson performance between

1920 and 1984. Sales performance shows salespeople's behaviour and contribution to organisational goals. Differences in selling behaviours and efforts of salespeople may result from cultural and business practice differences between nations (Dwyer, 1997; Fang et al., 2004). The behaviour of salespeople in Asian countries in general and Vietnam in particular prefer to be consultative and relationship-oriented. Despite their efforts to comprehend the demands of their consumers, Vietnamese salespeople concentrate on discussing their customers' personal lives rather than presenting and discussing products. Additionally, they undergo training with the philosophy of "put blinders over horses' eyes to ride them go straight" and "the customer is always right". It means they are given relatively little information about the products but are expected to sell as much of them as possible. There are many conflicting opinions on sales behaviour between Asian countries like Vietnam and Western countries. Is the sales culture/behaviour in Vietnam effective? A part of customers may be inclined to be more communicative and connected, however, others may feel stifled and uncomfortable while interacting with salespeople by this selling approach. It also causes sales of inappropriate products to customers. Conversely, salespeople in Western countries are well-trained and are more results-oriented (Ballestra et al., 2017; Dunn, 1976; Vadi and Suuroja, 2006).

The impact of the world economic crisis has led to more fierce competition in the global economy in general and the retail industry in particular. As a series of massively established shopping malls, losses and revival, salesperson's performance is focused on as a key factor for the operation of the business, developing customer satisfaction, future interaction and repurchase intention. Customers tend to depend on salespeople as corporate representatives in order to obtain precise information and suitable assistance (Crosby et al., 1990; Howe et al., 1994). However, they are very responsive to the manner in which salespeople behave and communicate with them. Any improper sales behaviour/culture of salespeople may affect customers' perception and their positive relationship with the company. This leads to a question: what is the 'salesperson performance'?

Salesperson performance, also known as sales performance, is one of the popular research constructs in personal selling literature (Miao et al., 2007). It is defined in a variety of ways but is primarily referred to as the salesperson's contribution to an organisation's goals (sales revenue) (Giacobbe et al., 2006). The term 'performance' is applied to measure behaviours - activities that salespeople perform, and results to be gained from behaviour. They are referred to as behavioural performance and outcome performance (Baldauf and Cravens, 2002; Grant and Cravens, 1996; Miao et al., 2007). This research will focus on outcome performance because it is known to be positively associated with the effectiveness of sales force (Atefi et al., 2018).

Academe and practitioners use this concept as a factor to compare a salesperson's ability as well as assess the quality of relationships with customers, whether they are satisfied and willing to interact with future sellers and intend to buy back (Palmatier et al., 2007; Verhoef, 2003).

There are six types that are responsible for the higher production of salesperson performance, including general organisational aspect and a number of personal and motivational aspects such as aptitude, skill level, personality, motivation and role perception (Churchill et al., 1985; Verbeke et al., 2011). The research focuses primarily on salesperson performance, selling products with high margin and the ability to sell more than the determined purposes (Scott, 2009). Performance standards in marketing business are known as factors to measure the ability to complete important activities and tasks set by the company (Kesari, 2014).

The salesperson performance increases the revenue and the value of the organisation, improving salesperson performance is considered an extremely important part for the development of customer satisfaction, relationship between the salesperson and customer, as well as anticipation of future interaction (Blocker et al., 2015; Bahadur et al., 2020; Echchakoui, 2015). Assessing salesperson performance is indispensable in today's business because it not only helps to measure the efforts and achievements of salespeople, but also contributes strongly to customer interaction in the future (Van

Dolen et al., 2004). Yu et al. (2016) study also shows that when future customer interactions are anticipated, the relationship between the long-term effectiveness of salespeople and their performance with customer satisfaction will become even tighter.

Salesperson performance is a factor always mentioned in the business operation. Managers and business generally emphasise the importance of salesperson performance as a component to enhance the value of a company through elements of sales performance. These factors are: (1) Sales strategy (Terho et al., 2015), (2) Sales skills (Basir et al., 2010), (3) Salesperson characteristics (Giacobbe et al., 2006), (4) Experience (knowledge) (Giacobbe et al., 2006), (5) Customer orientation (Goff et al., 1997), (6) Valued-based selling (Terho et al., 2015), and (7) Adaptive selling behaviour (Giacobbe et al., 2006). Thus, why is the salesperson's performance necessary for the business operation?

Sales is a key activity in the entire business system of the company. Salespeople are vital and play an indispensable position in helping companies recognise and address consumer wants as they are the ones who interact directly with customers (Kaynak et al., 2016). The salespeople's capacity for comprehending and satisfying consumer needs may greatly assist companies in producing greater commercial performance (Charoensukmongkol and Suthatorn, 2018; Wong et al., 2015). However, the problem is how the company can evaluate the employee's ability and productivity as well as improve it in a way that is advantageous to the company's development. Therefore, it is essential to evaluate and improve the performance of sales staff in this study. It is the first and essential step to increase the amount of goods sold, profitability; create the ability to satisfy customer needs highly, as well as increase the anticipation of the future interaction and repurchase intention of customer (Baldauf and Cravens, 2002; Shannahan et al., 2017). The higher the ability of business to satisfy customer needs, the greater the repurchase intention of customer (Sohaib et al., 2016). In addition, the cost to attract new customers is 5 - 10 times higher than retaining an existing one (Vijayadurai, 2008). Therefore, once a customer is satisfied with the salesperson, it not only helps the company save costs to attract new customers significantly, but also improves profit and company position. Sofi

et al. (2020) insisted that the level of customer satisfaction with salespeople would be in direct proportion to the company's competitive advantage in the market.

Salesperson performance is the key to a company's business success. It is the combination of working hard and working smart for effective selling (Churchill et al., 1997; Sujan et al., 1994). The salesperson's performance in marketing has also been shown to be associated with customer satisfaction (Bolander et al., 2015; Gomez et al., 2004; Pansari and Kumar, 2017; Mägi, 2003). In addition, Combs (2020) found that positive customer-salesperson relationships were positively related to future purchase intentions as reported by customers. Hence, improving salespeople's performance based on customer satisfaction and developing a competitive strategy, carefully managing employees is a challenge for companies today.

1.3. STATEMENT OF RESEARCH PROBLEM

Salesperson performance greatly contributes to a company's goals and success (Churchill et al., 1985; Lam et al. 2019, Liu et al., 2020). Building and developing relationships between sellers and customers is also always paid attention to and has an impact on business performance. However, some researchers report that about 50% of sellers do not meet the sales target (Palmatier et al., 2012). Therefore, improving salesperson performance is indispensable for business operations. The salesperson performance is closely related to the performance of corporate business strategies (Linh, 2019). The benefits of improving salesperson performance have been shown by previous studies to be positively associated with customer satisfaction: customers gain a better understanding of a company's products / services through salesperson, customers from which trust and desire to interact in the future higher. However, the information provided is not detailed and somewhat vague. The relevance of salesperson performance is a combination of motivation, knowledge and skills in declarations and procedures (Johnson, 2003). Salesperson performance refers to the behaviour individuals engage themselves in or produce that are in line with and contribute to an organisation's goal (Viswesvaran and

Ones, 2017), is the record of outcomes achieved in carrying out the job function during the specified period (Kane, 1986).

Salesperson performance and responsibility are closely related to the long-term performance of an organisation (Buciuniene and Skudiene, 2009; Magdalene, 2022). Moreover, salesperson performance is shown through personal characteristics as well as salesperson's empathy ability, therefore, it helps to quickly access and achieve customer satisfaction, establish long-term relationships, and generate profits (Ahearne et al., 2007; Aggarwal et al., 2005; Delpechitre et al., 2018; McBance, 1995). From the above evidence, it is absolutely convincing to affirm why the business has spent much time and money to learn and improve the performance of day-to-day sales staff better, which reflects benefit from an organisation's profitability growth as well as helping them strengthen a firmer competitive advantage in the market (Pipedrive, 2020; Ruusunen, 2021).

The salesperson's performance affects revenue and the value of a company in the market. It is not only an important part of the organisation's business, but also the most obvious reflection of the organisation's profitability and competitiveness in the business market (eNewsletter, 2011). The positive response of customers to the company is not only because they are satisfied with the quality of the products / services, but also the enthusiasm and honesty of salesperson (Kennedy, 2001). Salesperson performance also shows the effectiveness of the company's business strategy (Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010).

Thanks to effective salesperson performance management, business will be more flexible in allocating resources, and smoothly coordinate the company's strategic plans to meet the needs of their customers (Daugherty et al., 2001), thereby increasing profits and competitive advantage. Thus, improving salesperson performance can be the key to bringing the company closer to their customers. However, it is uncertain to assert the benefits of this concept, since its infrequently used in previous studies as a factor to connect and build customers relationship with business. Therefore, how does salesperson

performance really impact customers' perceptions of their business? This is a question and a big gap omitted in previous marketing studies, which should be proven to have a more complete view of its potential influence on customer relationships.

Although previous researchers (e.g. Baldauf and Cravens, 2002; Johlke, 2006; Jaramillo et al. 2007; Wachner et al, 2009, Walker et al, 1979) paid more attention in researching individual premise factors such as adaptive selling behaviour, aptitude, and sales skills affect salesperson performance, there is little research focusing on the relationship between the construct of salesperson performance, its antecedents and consequences (Boles et al., 2001; Baldauf and Cravens, 2002). Therefore, this study aims to provide a detailed notion of salesperson performance within an organisation, explore the various premise factors that contribute to salesperson's performance, as well as the under-studied consequences of salesperson performance, especially focused on the future interaction expectation and repurchase intention of customer.

A shortage of information exists regarding the development and change of concept salesperson performance. This study, therefore, also strives to track down the development and change of this concept throughout the period from the 1990s to the present 2024.

1.4. THE DEVELOPMENT AND CHANGING OF SALESPERSON PERFORMANCE

Sales, since ancient times, have been an exchange activity due to agricultural commodity surpluses and shortages. Sales gradually developed during the Dark Ages and became the primary driver of economic expansion after Muslim groups started to pursue this profession. It also became a realistic professional choice to become successful rapidly throughout the Renaissance. Nonetheless, selling is still considered a basic form of transaction involving a buyer and a seller (Powers et al., 1987). During the early eighteenth century, the retail system began to form along with the early development of technological inventions. Improvements in sales practices are also emphasised.

Salespeople were employed to implement marketing plans and promote products, which attracted people's interest and became effective. The growth of the sales industry laid a solid foundation for the 20th century's development of relationship marketing concepts, and this significantly influences the way salespeople are perceived by the firm. The value of salesperson during this period received more attention (Powers et al., 1987).

Customer requirements and the professional retail industry evolved fast over time, having a significant influence on business success. Besides, customer relationships came to be highly valued, becoming the primary driving force for sales growth, and salespeople made constant attempts to strengthen customer relationships in order to achieve success. Salesperson performance became popular in the late 1900s and was utilised to assess the quality and effort of sellers. Since then, numerous investigations on performance, focusing on the elements and capabilities needed to achieve effective sales in various settings, have garnered significant scholarly interest and have been studied continuously over the past decades.

From the early study on salesperson performance and aptitude by Oschriin (1918) to studies conducted more than 30 years ago by Teas, which explored the relationship between salesforce performance and motivation. Although aptitude and motivation received a fair amount of attention in these two studies, the empirical evidence linking them to salesperson performance has not been emphasised.

The global economic downturn that began in 1930 has forced businesses to develop their own strategies and impressions in order to compete more successfully, the art of selling towards customer service and satisfaction is promoted. Studies by Appiah-Adu and Singh (1998), Athanassopoulos (2000), Cross et al (2007), Williams (1998) about customer orientation, or by Anderson et al., (2009), Haas et al., (2012), Storbacka et al., (2011) about value-based selling emerge as the primary research trend. According to academics, a salesperson can only really build up a relationship with a customer when they are aware of the customer's needs and values and strive to satisfy the customer's high expectations (Brahmbhatt et al., 2017). The salesperson was becoming more concentrated on sales

strategies that create value for customers and are more customer oriented. Customer orientation is the fundamental driving force behind value-based selling activities (Terho et al., 2015; Silver et al., 2006). Research by the following authors Terho et al., (2017), Singh and Venugopal (2015), and Verbeke et al. (2011) claim that value-based selling and customer orientation have a significant effect on salesperson performance. In addition to merely fulfilling requests from customers, salespeople have since taken part in interactive activities, presenting information and advice to assist customers in better grasping the product or service and their needs.

Interest in personal characteristics arose in the early 1980s with studies by Churchill et al., (1985), or by Vinchur et al., (1998) when they argued that enduring personal characteristics are a collection of diverse characteristics that influence sales behaviours and sales efforts of salespeople. Research also shows the relationship between personal characteristics and sales performance (Barrick and Mount, 1991; Schmitt, 1984; Verbeke, 1994). Along with that, the adaptability of salespeople during this period has also attracted significant attention from researchers such as Weit et al., (1986), Siguaw (1991). In an era of innovation, academics assert that a "one-size-fits-all" sales approach is no longer appropriate for every customer. More varied requirements arise from rapid globalisation. Changing sales behaviour may stimulate more strongly expressed customer desires. Salespeople continually need to seek out opportunities to adapt to consumers throughout interactions and product presentations to attract customers. It serves as the foundation for enhancing customer interactions, sales performance, and the company's ability to maintain a competitive edge.

The importance of sales skills was first acknowledged in the early 1990s of the 20th centuries, coinciding with the robust start of the hyper-globalisation process, was crucial to salespeople's success since many as numerous emerging corporations require excellent skills of salespeople to communicate their goals and core values effectively. Sales skills have arisen as an actively investigated issue in academia with typical works by Churchill et al., (2000), Futrell (2006), Ingram et al., (2004), Rent et al., (2002).

Different factors can have varying degrees of influence on sales personnel performance during each time. The most visible and noteworthy shift in the sales environment to date has been the internet and technology. This creates both opportunities and challenges for salespeople. Salespeople, for example, have access to a variety of technologies and resources that enable them to connect, learn, and track customer demands in order to effectively drive sales growth. The traditional role of a salesperson was to deliver company values to customers through conversation, knowledge, and product introductions (Verbeke et al., 2011). Salespeople and buyers have had excellent interactions and equal influence in the past. However, the explosion of technology and online shopping has weakened the power of salespeople. Customers are becoming more independent in their buying and purchasing decisions because of the abundance of information available online (Hochstein et al., 2019). They can better enlighten themselves about their buying options. This implies that salesperson's opportunities to interact with consumers are limited. Customers gradually become the main pressure point on salespeople (Sheth and Sisodia, 2014).

Salespeople in the digital era must focus on creating relationships and emotional connections rather than just seeking potential consumers and selling (Singh et al., 2019). Salespeople's success stems from their attempts to improve their interaction skills and address customer demands by utilising technology and innovative approaches (Leigh et al., 2014). Despite the fast advancement of information and technology, salespeople and conventional selling tactics will not be replaced, it is critical to strengthen salespeople's abilities in order to execute efficient sales processes (Moncrief, Marshall, & Lassk, 2006; Syam and Sharma 2018).

The changing of the sales performance, as described above, is critical to a company's success. Research on corporate salesperson performance indicates that it is the key to anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention (Baldauf and Cravens, 2002; Rodriguez et al., 2012; Shannahan et al., 2017). Furthermore, the salesperson represents the company (Crosby et al., 1990) and is a bridge to convey service value to customers and allows them to build a positive perception of the company (Gonzalez and Claro,

2019). Companies always aim to form and develop long-term relationships with customers, and such interactions may lead to corporate success (Herjanto and Amin, 2020; Ramsey and Sohi, 1997) and create distance from rivals (Dey et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2016).

In a nutshell, whether in the past or now, evidence gathered from the aforementioned research indicates that sales success plays an important role in communicating the value and quality of a company's services to consumers. A company's sales performance is a solid indicator of a company's ability to provide high-quality services, which helps customers remember and continue to support the company's services. Salesperson performance also contributes to the creation of other business advantages, such as increasing an organisation's value, enhancing its reputation, reinforcing customer trust among countless rivals, and the uncontrollably rapid growth of the media. As a result, it is significant to comprehend the concept of sales performance and how it relates to customer perceptions of the company (anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention).

1.5. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Considering the evidence on the significance of salesperson performance, it is necessary and helpful for the author to investigate further on this content in order to improve the outstanding shortcomings of current studies. This study tries to fill the gaps raised by previous studies (Boles et al., 2001): What are the precursors of salesperson performance identified as having an impact on customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intentions? (Research Question). This study aims to investigate the influence of salespeople's performance on future interaction expectation and repurchase intention of customers in the context of shopping malls in Vietnam.

According to the research aim, four specific objectives are proposed to investigate salesperson performance:

- To understand the notion of the salesperson performance.
- To detect the antecedent factors that are likely to directly affect the salesperson's performance.
- To build a conceptual model of salesperson performance, which demonstrates the relationship between this concept, its antecedent and consequence factors, thereby making relevant empirical evaluation.
- To explore the impact of sales performance on its consequence factors such as anticipation of future interactions and repurchase intention of customer.

Although salesperson performance can potentially play a huge role in developing strong customer relationships and increasing company profits, there is very little research focus on investigating and improving salesperson's performance to meet customer satisfaction goals.

Based on the existence of previous studies, it can be seen that verifiable studies on the effect of sales performance on customer perception and interaction in the future are rare (Echchakoui, 2017; Jamal and Adelowore, 2008; Linh, 2019; Weitz, 1978). This study will attempt to successfully conduct empirical tests to demonstrate the link between the salesperson performance and future customer engagement and repurchase intention. In addition to addressing customer perceptions of salesperson performance and the key factors that have a direct impact on the sales performance from the customer side, this study also investigates the role of improving sales performance on customer evaluation. Thence, two overall research questions were developed for this research, respectively:

Question 1: What are the key factors that have a direct impact on the salesperson's performance?

Question 2: What are the implications of improving a company's salesperson performance on anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention?

The author is expected to provide some useful additions for a wealth of current business knowledge about salespeople's performance, more realistic data for researchers and

practitioners after successfully completing the above research objectives. In this section, the author will also discuss the research design and the methods to be used.

1.6. RESEARCH DESIGN AND ANALYTICAL METHOD

To reach the research goal, two popular paradigms of positivism and idealism will be shown in this study in turn. The first and the main research method used in this research will be quantitative but based on data sources gathered from individual interviews (qualitative) (Churchill et al., 1979; Palmer, 2011). Because of the limitation and unpopularity of the research topic, it requires a more detailed evaluation through a specific company (Ahearne et al., 2005). Applying qualitative research methods through interviews will help: (1) get useful information from the customer's point of view that researchers have not been able to cover before, and better understanding of the phenomena; (2) refine hypotheses and conceptual frameworks more appropriately, (3) purify measures for the questionnaire, as well as (4) increase the reliability of collected data and the richness of conclusions (Churchill, 1979; Foroudi et al., 2017b; Saunders et al., 2007).

It will be suitable to apply qualitative method for the first stage, because of the present lack of understanding of 'salesperson performance' and its relationship to anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention; they need to be identified more deeply and carefully (Saunders et al., 2007). For this reason, Churchill's qualitative paradigm (1979) will be applied in order to collect the necessary data for this first phase through conducting a survey. In addition, to verify the validity of the scale and the instrument design, in-depth interviews will be carried out with key informants (i.e. shopping mall managers, salespeople, experts (lectures), PhD and MSc students who has experiences about marketing). In terms of data analysis, NVivo software will be applied to code, and extract the information gathered from the individual interviews. Using a combination of both qualitative and quantitative methods not only helps create a more comprehensive understanding of the field of research, uncovering the similarities and differences between specific aspects of a phenomenon, but also helps to identify an unknown or less

focused domain in previous studies (Bernardi et al., 2007; Deshpande, 1983; Foroudi et al., 2014, 2017a; Palmer, 2011). Therefore, the author will apply quantitative methods to the second stage of the present study.

In the next stage, a positivist paradigm (quantitative method) will be applied to examine the proposed hypotheses, their relationships, and validation of the scales. A questionnaire to measure each of the constructs of the study will be established based on findings from literature and qualitative research, to quantify, supplement and enhance the first stage. The scales will be purified based on the qualitative and quantitative assessments of the survey questionnaires provided during the study.

The questionnaire will be designed to evaluate the impact of salesperson performance construct on the anticipation of customer's future interaction with the company. The subjects of the research will be asked to indicate the degree of their agreement with each item on a seven-point Likert scale (Bagozzi, 1994) arranged from (1) 'strongly disagree', to (7) 'strongly agree'.

Today's shopping malls can provide customers with a comprehensive purchasing experience through the extensive assortment of stores and services that are accessible (Bodkin and Lord, 1997). Shopping centres offer consumers a lot of choices with a diverse combination of retail stores, from electronics, cosmetics, fashion to cinemas and restaurants. Individual stores, on the other hand, frequently have a far smaller selection of products and concentrate primarily on giving customers a convenient shopping experience with a few specific product lines. In fact, every single store has its own approaches when it comes to engaging with consumers, including strategies and orientations. Additionally, the salespeople's knowledge, skills, and training methods will also differ among stores. Therefore, salesperson performance will vary depending on the specific retail store, and it is challenging to provide a holistic assessment of salesperson performance in the retail industry as a whole. Conversely, learning about the customer purchasing experience at shopping malls in general can give a more comprehensive

picture of salesperson performance in the retail market, rather than focusing on individual stores.

Customers typically visit shopping centres for an assortment of reasons, including to connect and socialise, to purchase necessities, to entertain and relax... People inevitably are bound to have different demands and search for different reasons for shopping. Shopping centres in general not only meet the different needs of customers in terms of product diversity but also provide quality services that satisfy customers. The integration of multiple services and different stores in such a shopping centre has become familiar to consumers, significantly influencing their impression and selection of shopping destinations. However, each customer's perception of a shopping centre is different. This study, by focusing on examining the experiences of customers in shopping centres in general, instead of individual stores - namely the perceptions of Vincom customers in Vietnam, will investigate the customer's awareness and evaluation of the salesperson's characteristics, behaviours, and their efforts in the sales interaction. This will help eliminate the impact of unrelated elements and provide a more precise and comprehensive assessment of salesperson performance.

The reason for choosing Vincom is because it is one of the first retail brand (shopping centre) established in Vietnam in general and Ho Chi Minh City in particular and have a long experience in operating activities in the Vietnam retail market. Along with that, Vincom is a brand of retail premises belonging to Vingroup. Vincom Retail is the company that owns, manages, and operates the most prestigious and largest shopping malls in Vietnam. Targeting mid-end and high-end customers, Vincom offers customers the experience of shopping space, entertainment, modern cuisine, and international-class facilities, contributing to shaping new consumption style for Vietnamese people. After more than 10 years of operation, Vincom has become a symbol of shopping, entertainment, and cuisine of the Vietnamese people. Vincom is currently managing and operating 19 shopping centres across the country with 3 branch brands: Vincom Centre, Vincom Mega Mall and Vincom Plaza (Vincom Retail, 2016). The survey will be

conducted with the participation of Vietnamese customers who are living and working in Ho Chi Minh City. A total of 412 candidates answered questions from Vincom.

The statistical method used for the entire sample in this research is the statistical package for social science (SPSS). To assess the reliability and validity of the scale, the author will apply a basic analysis technique, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and coefficient alpha in the first phase of the research (Aaker, 1997; Churchill, 1979). It will help to organise and shorten the indicators of the observed variables into a more meaningful set of factors (Hair et al., 1998; Pham, 2018). To test the complex relationship of constructs, and the model quality, the author will continue to apply structural equation modelling (SEM) via the Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) tool to help analyse the model with higher accuracy. SEM is a technique for modelling (Steenkamp and Baumgartner, 2000) and is often used with the primary goal of testing statistical hypotheses in marketing (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Sardeshmukh and Vandenberg, 2017).

Two-step modelling approach (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988) will also be used in this study. CFA, firstly, will be applied to assess the significance of each uni-dimensionality construct in the theoretical model, and to exclude observable variables with low latent factors. The structural model fit will also be further verified to assess the relevance of the scale model to the research hypotheses.

1.7. STATEMENT OF SIGNIFICANCE

This study contributes to the treasure trove of modern marketing research with a more specific and standardised concept of salesperson performance. The research finding involves supporting and improving the management capabilities of salesperson performance. It also has a positive contribution in terms of theoretical, methodological, and managerial.

The study's results not only provide a more detailed and practical understanding, adding to the findings of previous related studies on salesperson performance, but also supports

research on the effects of customer satisfaction, and anticipation of future interactions and repurchase intentions. The study also provides an overview of salesperson performance and its possible outcome relationships. Identifying and narrowing down the literature gap based on previous studies can be judged as a success of this study, which is listed as follows:

- There is limited empirical evidence on how to determine salesperson performance (Baldauf and Cravens, 2002; Linh, 2019; Wachner, 2009)
- Little knowledge of the linkages between sales performance, its antecedents, and consequences (Mohr and Bitner, 1995; Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Zhao et al., 2018)
- There is a lack of systematic studies on how salesperson performance affects customer perception (Ekinici and Dawes, 2009; Liao and Chuang, 2004).
- Theoretical developments and explanatory models around the topic of salesperson performance with little search and effort

This research presents relevant evidence to support the relationship between the content of salesperson performance, high customer interaction in the future and their intention to repurchase in the context of Vietnam marketing business. Therefore, it aids in the advancement of the current knowledge base by adding useful findings to earlier investigations. For example, the studies of Kennedy et al. (2001) and Shapiro et al. (2014) stated that sales performance is related to customer perceptions and their repurchase intention, however, they did not seem to test the existence of this linkages. Although there have been numerous studies evaluating sales performance in the recent period (such as Linh, 2019; Nunkoo et al., 2020; Nguyen et al., 2022), few studies related to anticipation of future interaction (Gruner and Homburg, 2000; Lin and Wu, 2011; Lowe et al., 2012). Therefore, this research contributes to the foundation of previous studies by examining the association between the concept of salesperson performance and future interaction and repurchase intention. The theories provided in this study help to broaden the understanding of the concept of sales performance.

The study's theoretical contributions to the body of existing literature provide diverse insights into the salesperson performance. This empirical study is the first attempt to demonstrate the effect of salesperson performance on customer evaluations. It aids in redefining and arousing research investments in the area of salesperson performance. Thence, research can contribute a part to the marketing knowledge by building and examining a scale of the practical impact of salesperson's performance. The study will also apply SEM to verify the complex relationship between observed variables in the model. Consequently, this research enhances a knowledge of salesperson performance and the linkages between sales performance and its antecedent, consequences (anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention). This research also offers a thorough comprehension of the operational implications of relevant concepts for company customer perception. There are three academic implications that arise from this study's theoretical contribution: extending theory based on experimental testing, verifying conceptualisation, measuring research structures, and testing theory and generalisation.

The multi-disciplinary approach is used as the main methodology for this research topic. It helps build a more comprehensive understanding of salesperson performance (Hadorn et al., 2008). It in turn consists of two main stages as follows: (1) qualitative method; (2) self-administered questionnaire (SAQ) to help participants easily complete the answers without the intervention of the researcher and to help to collect information more comprehensively (Wolf and Lavrakas, 2008). SEM will also be used shortly thereafter to analyse the collected data. Thus, it can be said the research supports the advancement of current marketing theory. In addition to the salesperson performance studies by authors (Churchill et al., 1997; Elnaga and Imran, 2013; Sujan et al., 1994; Viswesvaran and Ones, 2017), this research enriches the knowledge of marketing and salesperson performance as a signal of functional quality by evaluating how incorporating salesperson performance affects customers' expectations of future interaction and repurchase intention. This is one of the earliest empirical studies to date to support the notion of salesperson performance and how it affects the anticipation of future interactions and repurchase intentions of customers.

This study also yielded some managerial implications. First, it helps managers to comprehensively understand the broad concept of salesperson performance, which is not only built on the salespeople characteristic, sales strategy, sale skill, experience but also depend on other important factors such as customer orientation, value-based selling, and adaptive selling behaviour. This requires managers to focus more on training and developing sales performance. This study also points out the main factors that directly affect the performance of salespeople, thus, it obviously shows its valuable contributions to managers in bringing success to the organisation. Sales skills should be a top consideration as one of the key factors that create efficiency in sales performance. To survive and increase value, sales managers should be more conscious of the consistency in sales behaviour and interactions of salespeople. This study encourages sales managers to focus on honing and broadening the expertise of salespeople, establishes its own standards of service quality for the company' sales force in order to improve sales performance and create positive customer impression. The study also shows a positive and direct link between sales performance and customer satisfaction with salespeople. Future research should clarify whether the proposed approach for improving the salesperson performance can be similarly applied to firm performance. Furthermore, managers should pay more attention to salesperson performance as a bridge to communicate company values and influence customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention.

CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. INTRODUCTION

Research on salesperson performance and anticipation of future interaction shows that a high salesperson performance will yield a favourable business result for the organisation, such as increase profitability and competitiveness compared with peers (Baldauf and Cravens 2002, Dey et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2016; Talukder and Jahan, 2017).

The performance of salespeople is used to accomplish organisational tasks effectively (Hossain et al., 2016), and create a sustainable competitive advantage in the market (Dey et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2016). Salesperson performance is seen as an important baseline variable that represents the long-term achievement of an organisation (Buciuniene and Skudiene, 2015), and helps company to handle financial problems, product or customer information which could simply be exchanged starting with one organisation and then the next (Talukder and Jahan, 2017).

According to Churchill (1979), Gupta et al. (2010); Hart (2018) and Snyder (2019), several reasons for reviewing literature are as follows: (1) to ensure a clear understanding of the research topic, (2) to identify the main literature in the research topic, (3) to identify different perspectives within the research topic, (4) to draw a coherent and relevant conclusion, (5) to make a clear assertion of the research topic, (6) to propose how to investigate appropriate research problem, (7) to prove the importance of the research topic. From there, it is necessary to review the literature to be able to answer the research questions, which are formed and presented in the first part of this thesis.

2.2. DEFINING THE SALESPERSON PERFORMANCE CONCEPT

Clearly defining a theoretical definition is of utmost importance to being able to formulate a structure, as well as to test a theory favourably (Churchill, 1979). 'Salesperson performance' with a variety of different terms (such as 'employee performance', 'employee commitment', 'staff performance') often used interchangeably in the event that their definitions overlap. However, for this study, 'salesperson performance' will be the term used throughout as the definition and root of this essay.

Performance is behaviours that are assessed as having a positive impact on an organisation's goals (Bolander et al., 2021; Cron et al., 2005; Walker et al., 1979). Measuring and controlling the salesperson's performance is essential to the company's growth, whereby sales tools quickly become available and more popular for manager to easily operate business activities (Linh, 2019; Walker et al., 1977). Definitions of salesperson performance are varied and defined through different lenses. For example, marketing scholars focus on corporate personality and human value, and assume salesperson performance as a signal of quality and value to consumer (Hartline and Jones, 1996; Hartline et al., 2003; Nunkoo et al., 2020). Researchers claim that salesperson performance is one of the main factors of "functional" quality (how service is provided) and is also an important bridge determining the customer's perception of the company's service quality (Bitner, 1990; Schneider and Bowen, 1985; Gronroos, 1983; Parasuraman et al., 1985). The functional aspects of service evoke customer impressions through service attitudes and thoughtful actions of salesperson, which enhance value and deliver memorable customer experiences. In other words, the more positive a consumer's perception of a company, the more favourable engagement they have with the company. This explanation relies on the attribution theory, which relates to perceptions, inferences about the cause, or the way a person assigns emotions or intentions to another so that the behaviour of others can be interpreted and understood in terms of a certain cause (Goodman et al., 1995; Ginder et al., 2021; Weiner, 2012). Attribution theory is commonly applied in marketing literature to identify perceptions, and explanations for

the causes, behaviours of customers, and the process of forming customers' consumption decisions (Folkes, 1984; Heider, 2013; Vrontis et al., 2021; Watson and Spence, 2007).

According to Bitner (1990), Park and Ttran (2018), Nunkoo et al. (2020), salesperson performance is considered a bridge to convey the quality and value of the company to customers. Along with that, attribution theory suggests that an individual's perspective on another person's accomplishment or failure could potentially be assigned to that person's behaviour (Graham, 1991). This statement advocates that a company's salesperson performance can drive future engagement and repurchase intention among customers, and the set of salesperson characteristics, behaviours and skills that can impact a person's viewpoints, emotions, and interpretations of it. Customers' impressions of a company have an impact on their attitudes and behaviours. Attribution theory is applied to research on a company's salesperson performance.

Studies by Miao and Evans (2013) show salesperson performance can be used to process necessary data related to money, products, and customers, without needing too much time for exchange. Furthermore, Magdalene (2022) confirms that salesperson performance has a direct impact on sales volume, productivity, customer loyalty and unpredicted expenses. It is always an important factor to be considered and improved so as to create a sustainable competitive advantage over competitors in the same industry (Dey et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2016). Salesperson performance is also defined as a tool to help capture data about potential customers, better understand them, and thereby finding out the main impact of purchases and incorporate it into the customer purchasing process in a convenient way (Rodriguez et al., 2012).

Marketing academics refer to salesperson's behaviour in definition as a key determinant of their performance (Aqmala and Ardyan, 2019). An individual salesperson's performance can be measured through the total sales volume and the sales goals that he/she achieves (Baker and Sinkula, 1999). At the same time, all salesperson's efforts will directly impact their individual sales performance (Piercy et al., 1998). It is the responsibility of a salesperson in each company to know how to apply the company's

marketing strategy to shorten the distance with customers and make it easier for customers to access company service/ product. Therefore, salespeople's success and their performance will be directly reflected in their sales volume, their contributions to increased profitability, satisfaction, and repurchase intention of customer (Baldauf and Cravens, 2002; Shannahan et al., 2017).

The conceptual definition of salesperson performance is different in studies, and its implications are also attributed to different authors. Most of them are related to a marketing perspective (Churchil et al., 1985; Fred Miao and Evans, 2007), and personal characteristic perspective (Giacobbe et al., 2006; Scott, 2009; Sujan et al., 1994; Wessels, 2011; Walker et al., 1979).

Marketing researchers (Agnihotri and Krush, 2015; Hunt, 1996; Limbu et al., 2016; Motowidlo et al., 1997; Rotundo and Sackett, 2002; Viswesvaran and Ones, 2000) have studied input (behaviour) and output (outcome) aspect of salesperson performance. Research by Sonnentag and Frese (2002) considers employee performance to be used as a measure of results in empirical studies, and as a key determinant of achieving organisational goals (Obiageli et al., 2015). A few studies suggest that salesperson performance is a seller's ability to fulfil his/ her goals and expectations as well as the achievement of the work objectives and the standards set by the organisation (Aqmala and Ardyan, 2019; Bohlander et al., 2001; Maathis and Jackson, 2000; Peterson, 2020; Snell and Morris, 2018). Marketers report salesperson performance as the result of a combination of an individual's abilities, effort, and opportunity (Ferris et al., 2008), which are closely linked with an organisation's success to deliver good service interactions with customers, delighting customers (Obiageli et al., 2015), thereby achieving its goals and competitive advantage in the market (Sonnentag and Frese, 2002).

Salesperson performance occupies an important position for the formation and successful development in the future of all industries in general and the service industry in particular (Magandini and Ngwenya, 2015), and has a direct impact on customer satisfaction, creating future interactions and consumer behavioural intentions (Crosby et al., 1990;

Hartline and Jones, 1996; Yi and Natarajan, 2018). A salesperson's performance immediately determines a customer's perception of service quality to the company (Bitner, 1990; Bowen and Schneider, 1985; Itani et al., 2019; Parasuraman et al., 1985), helping to improve customer attitudes as well as their satisfaction, and enhance the business relationship due to salesperson empathy (Ahearne et al., 2007; Aggarwal et al., 2005; McBance, 1995). Scholars suggested that a salesperson's performance was demonstrated by personal characteristics as well as his/ her contribution to market share, sales of new products and high profits, improved sales volume, sales exceed targets and help supervisors achieve their goals (Herjanto and Franklin, 2019; Helmy and Wiwoho, 2020; Sujana et al., 1994; Wang, 2000)

Besides emphasising the importance of performance, marketing materials target customers as the primary audience and indicates that salesperson performance is used as a key to corporate success, to have a direct influence on perception, satisfaction and repurchase intention of customer, which can have a profound impact on the organisation's economy (Agarwal, 2020; Anderson and Sullivan, 1993; Gomez et al., 2004). Salesperson performance is also known as a sign of service quality, which not only contributes to the difference in customer perception of service quality and value, creating a strong competitive advantage for companies in the market (Dey et al., 2016; Hartline and Jones, 1996; Hossain et al., 2016), but also helping the company to save time and money for finding new customers (Hartline and Jones, 1996). It is mentioned with factors such as sales strategy (sales model, customer prioritisation, segmentation), customer orientation, value-based selling (Goff et al., 1997; Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Kienzler et al., 2018; Terho et al., 2015; Yeo et al., 2019).

Marketing literature refers to salesperson performance with a variety of antecedents factors such as sales skills (interpersonal skills, salesmanship skills, technical skills, marketing skills), sales strategies (sales models, segmentation, customer prioritisation), customer orientation, value-based selling, sales characteristics (empathic ability, cue perception ability, ability to modify), experience (knowledge), adaptive selling behaviour which characterises the salesperson in the customer's perception. It enables customers to

evaluate and decide on future interaction and repurchase intention (Basir et al., 2010; Chawla et al., 2020; Giacobbe et al., 2006). They report that salesperson performance has a direct impact on customer perceptions, behavioural intentions, including customer participation (Bitner, 1990; Keh et al., 2013; Park and Tran, 2018; Ryari et al., 2021). Better performance leads to higher customer satisfaction (Obiageli et al., 2015). Poor salesperson performance will greatly increase customer complaints, and a high likelihood of switching to a competitor in the same industry (Keaveney, 1995; Ohanagorom et al., 2022). Good salesperson performance enhances customer perception of company service quality in the retail environment (Arditto et al., 2020; Darden and Babin, 1994; Gagliano and Hathcote, 1994; Li et al., 2019; Sweeney et al., 1992). Marketers and academics not only say that salesperson performance is a functional quality factor, but also appreciate its importance for building and strengthening customer relationship.

To summarise this discussion, the concept of the salesperson performance is defined as follows: Salesperson performance is defined as an effective tool to capture prospect information, determine customer loyalty, sales volume as well as unpredicted expenses, relates to a company's service quality and plays an important role in building a sustainable competitive advantage (Buciuniene and Skudiene, 2009; Dey et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2016; Nunkoo et al., 2020).

2.3. DEFINING THE ANTECEDENTS OF THE SALESPERSON PERFORMANCE

Previous studies on personal selling literature focused on salesperson performance such as prospecting, face-to-face conversations, and enhanced customer relationships through key factors such as knowledge and capabilities of sellers, sales strategy, customer orientation and so on (Alavi et al., 2019; Gengler et al., 1995).

For a more detailed understanding of salesperson performance, and the antecedent elements of salesperson performance, such as sales strategy (Terho et al., 2015; Johnson and Sohi, 2017; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010), sales skills (Basir et al, 2010; Rentz

et al., 2002; Pettijohn et al., 2007; Wachner et al., 2009), characteristics (Giacobbe et al., 2006; Koponen et al. 2019), experience (knowledge) (Giacobbe et al., 2006; Gengler et al., 1995; Shamsudheen and Mahomed, 2021), customer orientation (Terho et al., 2015; Jaramillo and Grisaffe, 2009; Wachner et al., 2009; Yeo et al., 2019), value-based selling (Kuester et al., 2017; Terho et al., 2017), adaptive selling behaviour (Alavi et al., 2019; Gengler et al., 1995) are discussed. Enhancing mutual interaction with customers through salesperson performance should have key elements, such as sales strategy, sales skills, salesperson's characteristics, knowledge, customer orientation, value-based selling, adaptive selling behaviour. Salesperson performance refers to "a salespersons expertise in their company's products and the market, good communication skill, ability to solve problems, ability to understand and satisfy the buyer's needs, thoroughness and ability to help in ensuring the reliable and fast delivery of orders" (Jobber and Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). These factors help build and develop salesperson performance.

2.3.1. Defining sales strategy

Strategy is a template for the execution of an organisation's actions and is concerned with the rational allocation of resources to achieve their proposed objectives (Snow and Hambrick, 1980). It is conceived at various levels within an organisation, such as the corporate strategy (referring to the business characteristics of the company), the business-unit strategy (referring to the way of operation and competition of a companys' business unit), and functional strategy (referring to maximising business resources in specific functions such as marketing, sales and so on) (Venkatraman, 1989).

Researchers (Campbell-Hunt, 2000; Homburg and Jensen, 2007; Varadarajan and Jayachandran, 1999) suggest that it seems difficult to be able to differentiate between sales and marketing activities due to the degree of overlap between them. However, the sales strategy cannot be confused with the marketing strategy, or other corporate strategies as it focuses on different functions within an organisation. Specifically, the nature of sales strategy is to promote the customer interaction in a specific market segment, identify the appropriate activities, sales technology, and the type of salesperson

to better support for strategic marketing goals (Katsikea et al., 2019; Lane, 2009; Stanton and Spiro, 1959). Agreeing with the above point of view, scholars (Kumar et al., 2008, Zoltners et al., 2009) also show that the functional responsibility of sales strategy is sales effort to all the customers that make up the market segment by allocating sales resources to different groups of customers with different levels of potential value. Therefore, it can be said that the intrinsic value of a sales strategy is how to successfully implement it (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020). Accordingly, scholars (Katsikea et al., 2019; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Terho et al., 2015) suggest that sales strategy is the way in which a company fulfils its marketing objectives through the allocation of resources at the level of customer contact. The involvement of skilled employees is vital to the success of the strategy (Crittenden and Crittenden, 2008). Inyang et al. (2018), Panagopoulos and Avlonitis (2010) and Terho et al. (2015) assert that the scale of a sales strategy is also developed in a multidimensional structure, in which customer segmentation (identifying the right customer group to customise the sales method according to the needs of different segments), customer prioritisation (selecting potential customers based on the value they bring to the company), sales model (combining sales efforts with customer relationship expectations) are three key aspects frequently mentioned for successful implementation of a sales strategy by individual salesperson.

A sales strategy is narrowing the focus to a very important aspect of a successful business - selling. A clear sales strategy will have a favourable effect on a company's real quantifiable profitability. In today's information age, the sales strategy should be considered and carefully adjusted to be able to update information quickly and effectively about market demand (Dong et al., 2018). Managers should develop a plan or specific sales strategy goals about what they want and need to do in the future, such as growth goals, buyer character, sales process, sales specific methods, and so on. A well-thought-out sales strategy will allow the company to address the different needs of its current and potential customers at all different stages. A good and solid sales strategy will produce consistent and repeatable results. It can help alleviate the company cost and use of sales resources more effectively, such as budgets, sales staff with skills and experience that match their goals (Anderson, 2020). In addition, the advantage of the sales strategy is

also an additional aspect to segment the market and help companies to be more flexible in their business operations due to supply-side substitution ability (Gönsch, 2020).

However, the real value of the sales strategy is in its successful execution (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020). Sterling's study (2003, p.27) shows that the performance stage is important and so decisive that "effective implementation of an average strategy, beats mediocre implementation of a great strategy every time". Along with that, both scholars and practitioners have pointed out that salespeople are the key factor in successfully implementing a sales strategy, which requires the salespeople's commitment and knowledge of the company's sales strategy (Crittenden and Crittenden, 2008; Inyang et al., 2018; Johnson and Sohi, 2017; Terho et al., 2015; Zoltners et al., 2009).

From the above statements it can be concluded that sale strategy are the ways and efforts a company performs to fulfil marketing objectives, to increase their profitability and product demand through customer segmentation, customer prioritisation / targeting, development relationship objectives/ selling models, and use of multiple sales channels (Anderson, 2020; Civaner, 2012; Terho et al., 2015).

2.3.1.1. Defining sales models

As mentioned above, selling models, also known as relationship objective, is one of the three main factors that help create a business's sales strategy (Ingram et al., 2002). Selling models range from transactional selling exchanges to collaborative exchanges. It allows salespeople to transform theoretical sales directions into specific sales methods with the aim of reaching and serving customers effectively (De Vincentis and Rackham, 1999; Day, 2000; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Terho et al, 2015).

The formation of a specific sales models as well as the development of appropriate relationship objectives not only brings a better understanding of the salesperson about the needs of customer, improve customer satisfaction and loyalty, but also help develop a lasting interaction between sellers and buyers, and at the same time improve outstanding

sales performance (De Vincentis and Rackham, 1999; Homburg et al., 2008a, 2008b; Katsikea et al., 2019; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010). Furthermore, the existence of sustainable customer relationships allows companies to have a high level of customer awareness, confidence, and commitment in business, thereby minimising potential business damage (Mehta et al., 2006).

The changing market as well as the difference in customer needs are important issues that companies need to grasp in order to gain a competitive position in the market (Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010). The success of a business depends greatly on the ability to adapt their strategy flexibly. Research by Ingram et al. (2002) shows there is an uncertainty in customer preferences. Depending on the different times, customers may easily change their mind, and do not invest in a long-term relationship with the company. In addition, the desired relationship types of a customer vary widely (considered on a scope from the transactional original to the complex collaborative between buyer and seller), and the costs for these relationships also vary from there. Thus, it is important for company to track the different needs between customers, as well as consider between cost and customer relationship values to adjust and use a sales model (Jaworski and Kohli, 1993; Kohli and Jaworski, 1990; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Safar et al., 2018).

In summary, drawn from this discussion, the sales model in this study is defined as follows: selling models play a central role in helping salespeople effectively to match their sales approach and to turn their general customer orientation into customer-specific selling approaches, thereby developing sustainable relationships with customers (Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Terho et al., 2015).

2.3.1.2. Defining customer prioritisation

It can be seen that customer relationship management is a factor that managers are extremely focused on in today's fierce business environment. Therefore, customer prioritisation has also become a very important issue that is always considered in business strategies (MahmoumGonbadi et al., 2019). Customer prioritisation relates to

the differences in the company's incentives and treatment of customers, based on how important the customer is to the company (Davis, 2019; Homburg and Totzek, 2008a). It is described as a tool to help companies effectively manage their customers (Rust et al., 2011). Customer prioritisation allows company to appropriately allocate their resources to different types of customers in order to increase the effectiveness of customer interactions and relationships (Homburg et al., 2008a, 2008b; Leigh and Marshall, 2001; Libai et al., 2020; Ramani and Kumar, 2008). Research by Storbacka et al. (2011) also shows that customer formation and development systematically prioritise help companies and their salespeople categorise customers effectively, make decisions more quickly, salespeople also work harder to attract and retain selected customers, thereby improving sales performance and profitability of the company (Libai et al., 2020).

Customer prioritisation is applied in a variety of ways to different aspects of marketing such as pricing, service delivery treatments and promotions (Davis, 2019). Customer priority level has a huge impact on the characteristics of the long-term supplier-customer relationship (high grade customer - people who can bring high profits to the company, and low-grade customers - people who are less important to the company's growth) (Homburg et al., 2008). Difference in service treatment creates satisfaction and reinforces high-grade customer 's loyalty, but it can lead to disappointment and abandonment of the other group of customers (Haenlein and Kaplan, 2012; Libai et al., 2020).

The essence of a marketing relationship is to maximise the profitability of a company, so there are some who argue that developing a customer priority system only has a positive effect on the relationship of high-grade customers, while the number of those chosen for priority is very small (Homburg et al., 2008). This results in a decrease in overall customer satisfaction (Brady, 2000; Gerstner and Libai, 2006; Kreuzer et al., 2020). Discriminated low-grade customers are often dissatisfied and create bad word of mouth that affects the company's revenue, profitability and long-term growth (Hogan et al., 2003; Kumar and George 2007; Ukanwa and Rust, 2020). Or there are even some legal situations when these groups of customers feel discriminated against (Ukanwa and Rust, 2018). Enterprises should have a balance between low and high-grade customers in

order to minimise potential risk situations (in case high-grade customers leave), and to develop long-term profits for the company.

From the above discussion, the definitions of customer prioritisation are drawn as: customer prioritisation refers to the preferential treatment and the allocation of a company's limited resources to customers based on the economic or strategic value they contribute to the company, help sellers to rate their customers based on the likelihood of repurchasing and effort appropriately, thereby increasing salesperson performance (Davis, 2019; Newman et al., 2018; Storbacka et al., 2011).

2.3.1.3. Defining segmentation

Customer segmentation is a marketing activity that has a direct impact on a company's financial performance (O'Sullivan and Abela, 2007, p. 80). Customer segmentation is known as the categorisation of customers in the marketplace, which is the way a business groups their existing or potential customers into individual group that shares common characteristics (Foedermayr and Diamantopoulos, 2008; Mothersbaugh et al., 2020; Nakano and Kondo, 2018). Since then, a heterogeneous customer market segmented into many separate groups with homogeneous characteristics will help the company easily identify products and better respond to the needs of each different customer group based on company segments (McDaniel, 2018).

Accordingly, a customer segment can be defined as a set of customers that share the same criteria, characteristics of values, preferences, behaviours, needs, gender and so on (Camilleri, 2018; Hirschowitz, 2001; Terho et al., 2015). Some other criteria are also mentioned in customer segment development such as long-term value, profitability or customer buying behaviour (Dogan et al., 2018; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Zoltners et al., 2001). In addition, customer segmentation can be defined as a process of systematic collection and development of customer details for the purpose of identifying individual customers according to each target market of the company (Teho et al., 2015; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Wang, 2022). Setting up market segmentation in

marketing materials is highly regarded and is an important part of marketing strategies (Ernst and Dolnicar, 2018; Dibb and Simkin, 2008; Weinstein, 2004).

This segmentation process is also described as an alternative concept to a product differentiation strategy (Beane and Ennis, 1987; Kinnunen et al., 2019; Smith, 1956). Market-oriented companies often consider and define products based on the customer's point of view rather than their own needs, so they are often more profitable (Bailey et al., 2009; Day, 1994; Zhou et al., 2020). Segmentation is about finding markets for new products, pricing, improving existing products or better understanding of customers (Beane and Ennis, 1987; Wind, 1978). Segmentation is a complex process and has far-reaching consequences for a company's business (Dibb and Simkin, 2008; Foedermayr and Diamantopoulos, 2008; Weinstein, 2006).

Customer segmentation assists organisations in fulfilling and exceeding customer expectations, helps salespeople in gaining a deeper understanding of customer buying behaviours and the types of values they are pursuing, thereby adjusting the resources needed to better interact with customers, and increasing personal sales performance (Camilleri, 2018; Leigh and Marshall, 2001; Terho et al, 2015). In addition, this process also helps businesses in managing diverse market needs, developing different marketing plans suitable for the company's target customer groups and obtaining position in a competitive market (Albert, 2003; Freytag and Clarke, 2001; Gichuru and Limiri, 2017; McDonald and Dunbar, 2004; Simkin, 2008; Septiarini et al., 2020; Wu and Lin, 2005).

Therefore, it is pointed out that the way to build segmentation is to find the differences in the consumer market, understand the criteria and the types of value that customers seek, thereby developing products / services to meet the diverse needs of customers (Camilleri, 2018; Smith, 1996; Shah et al., 2019; Wind and Douglas, 1972; Zeybek, 2018). The method to best segment customers is based on how customers prefer to buy, targeting high-value customer segments (Herhausen et al., 2019; Kansal et al., 2018; Leigh and Marshall, 2001, p. 86), which have the potential to positively affect salesperson's performance and improve sales and profits of the company.

Drawing on this discussion, the customer segment is defined as follows: customer segmentation refers to a company's systematic process to identify and develop a highly granular customer typology that allows to categorise individual customers according to each different target market, help to better understand customers' business needs and value types of customers they are looking for (Camilleri, 2018; Teho et al., 2015; Leigh and Marshall, 2001; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010).

2.3.2. Defining customer orientation

Customer orientation is a core task in marketing management, which explains the salesperson's activities effectively and leads to the company's success (Athanasopoulos, 2000; Brockman et al., 2012; Jaworski and Kohli 1993; Linh, 2019; Pekovic and Rolland, 2016). Customer orientation for decades has remained a prerequisite for frontline salespeople, who are responsible for interacting directly with customers to create business efficiency (Cross et al, 2007; Hughes et al., 2019; Kadic-Maglajlic et al., 2017).

Since then, customer orientations are defined as behaviours that a salesperson demonstrates a customer-oriented culture, and creates customer satisfaction (Pettijohn et al, 2007; Yeo et al., 2019). More specific, it is the salesperson's level of understanding of customer needs, thereby trying to apply marketing theories to sales activities aim to provide valuable advice, and support for customer buying decisions (Feng et al., 2019; Jaramillo et al., 2007; Thakor and Joshi, 2005).

Basically, customer orientation shows the salesperson's attention to customers (Itani et al., 2019; Jaramillo and Grisaffe, 2009; Kadic-Maglajlic et al., 2017; Saxe and Weitz, 1982). A customer-oriented salesperson is always focused on understanding the customer and what they are looking for. They also try to be able to answer questions, evaluate alternatives in order to offer the best solutions and bring good values to customers (Boles et al., 2001; Homburg et al., 2011; Johnston and Marshall, 2005; Singh and Venugopal, 2015; Singh and Koshy, 2011).

The company's senior directors and managers will greatly affect the employee's sales-orientation level (Boles et al., 2001; Pousa et al., 2014a, 2018). If the company is highly oriented, it is powerful enough to have an impact on the entire employee's ability to drive oriented sales, including frontline employees. Therefore, it provides many benefits and satisfies customers' needs.

Instead of using sales tactics or techniques to manipulate customer purchases and potentially harm the interests of customers, a customer-oriented salesperson is the one who can interact with customers and maintain good relationships with customers (Frambach et al, 2016; Gerlach et al., 2016; Jaramillo et al., 2007). They always looking for right solutions for customer needs, aim to advise customers on the most reasonable options, thereby building trust and improving long-term customer satisfaction (Delpechitre et al., 2019; Ehert, 2004; Moncrief and Marshall, 2005; Terho et al., 2015).

Backing up the above studies, salesperson's customer orientation has been shown to be related to customer satisfaction and loyalty (Aburayya et al., 2020; Brach et al., 2015; Kasiri et al., 2017; Li et al., 2019; Pettijohn et al, 2007), have also been shown to be associated with the long-term performance of salespeople and firms (Donavan et al., 2004; Feng et al., 2019; Jaramillo et al., 2007; Pekovic and Rolland, 2016; Rozell et al., 2004; Singh and Venugopal, 2015). Scholars shows that a high level of customer satisfaction from a customer-oriented salesperson leads to repeat purchases and positive word of mouth from customers, thus, it has a positive effect on individual sales performance (Guo and Wang, 2015; Homburg et al., 2009; Singh and Venugopal, 2015).

On the other hand, there are some mixed opinions that have arisen in the process of doing market research. It is thought that customer orientation is an unsustainable factor that can sustain a company's long-term sales performance or success. Or it is only a method to prevent business failure, rather than building up the success of the company (Chen et al., 2018; Singh and Koshy, 2012). Customer-oriented development requires the concentration of a company's limited resources (e.g. finance), at the same time creating a

great challenge for the sales force in finding and developing potential relationships, and its consequence is a decline in business revenues and profits (Homburg et al., 2011; Linh, 2019). In addition, the lack of precision in customer information collection causes many misunderstandings for customer-oriented development (such as inappropriate service provision), this greatly affects salesperson performance and enterprises (Mathieu, 2022). Therefore, it is necessary for the company to accurately define the needs of customers, thereby making efforts to satisfy the customers based on the information gathered, building, and developing effective customer orientation (Athanasopoulos, 2000). From the above discussion, it is possible to conclude about the definition of sales orientation as follows:

Customer orientation is an important factor affecting the performance of salesperson and business. It demonstrates the salesperson's care and efforts to learn how to respond to customer needs, engage in collaborative handling of any objections raised by the customer, help them make the right buying decisions, thereby building trust and lasting relationships (Chen et al., 2018; Delpechitre et al., 2019; Guo and Wang, 2015; Jaramillo et al., 2007; Kasiri et al., 2017; Thomas et al., 2001; Homburg et al., 2011; Singh and Venugopal, 2015).

2.3.3. Defining value-based selling

In severe economic development, the role of the customer is essential to the company's success. Therefore, concepts of customer-directed selling such as salespeople's customer oriented, value-based selling are always interesting and applied by companies. Besides the customer orientation presented above (2.3.2), value-based selling is one of the most popular concepts in the modern business environment. Value-based selling is proven to be a key factor in salesperson performance, assisting the company and salespeople in forming sustainable customer relationships (Terho et al., 2015).

Value-based selling is an effective selling approach based on communication and customer valuation (Terho et al., 2012; Töytäri and Rajala, 2015). Terho et al. (2015)

define value-based selling as a deep understanding of customers as well as proactively improving customers' business operations. In addition to knowing the customer's wants, a complete grasp of product qualities and functionalities from a commercial standpoint is required. Since needs are the concern of the customer, the salesman is the one who fully addresses them (Fang et al., 2008; Henard and Szymanski 2001; Töytäri et al., 2018). It is impossible to supply customer-perceived value without knowing the product's practical details.

Indeed, a product unit might really consist of a variety of elements, characteristics, and information, which are useful to differentiate and determine the value of the product (Van Kleef et al., 2005). Product characteristics can include colour, material, size, features, usage, and durability (Ba et al., 2005). Additionally, customers can rapidly assess these characteristics with their senses. Customers may therefore compare the products of different companies with ease. Products with exceptional characteristics can not only bring high competitiveness and better sales to salespersons but also influence customer satisfaction and their positive perception of the company (ShiYong et al., 2022).

A thorough grasp of product characteristics is essential in sales interactions, however, the "terrorism" of being provided with a lot of information regarding the product's features, uses and characteristics often makes customers feel apprehensive during sales interactions with salespeople. Accordingly, marketing academics (e.g. Gutman, 1982; Myers and Shocker, 1981) state that customers' desires for products are not their characteristics but rather the benefits they bring. Product characteristics reflect what it offers to customers. Product value refers to the benefits and results that customers experience when utilising a product. Each product has different types of value (use value, economic value, and strategic value), and each customer will have different judgements about the value of the product corresponding to their needs (Gutman, 1982). Smart salespeople do not need to talk the hind legs off a donkey about product features in their sales presentation because it may not be helpful in encouraging customer purchases and increasing sales. It is important that they can clearly understand and identify the desired values from the customer's perspective to sell to each respective customer segment (Raja

et al., 2020; Töytär and Rajala, 2015). Helping customers obtain value also creates value for salespeople (Adamson et al., 2012).

Unlike other on-demand sales approaches, value-based selling involves proactive efforts to create potential value for customers. It is the art of selling in which the seller needs to convey the value of the product/service and the distinct benefits that customers can receive from a company's product/service, so that they can be aware of its worthies compared to what they have to pay to get that product/ service. Value-based selling is no longer about selling products or services, nor is it about presentation, but listening (Ho and Alipour 2020; Kienzler et al., 2018; Terho et al., 2012). In addition, it focuses on what the customer wants, their perception of what the company offers, thence leading to strong influences in customers' purchasing decisions, increasing financial returns to the customer as well as improving customer-perceived value (Terho et al., 2015; Töytäri and Rajala, 2015). When it comes to the coincidence or similarity of products from different companies in the same market, salespeople who are able to highlight the value of product/service will help bring success to their company.

Research by Terho et al. (2012) believes that value-based selling's focus is on finding and identifying the best long-term solutions for customers, helping to move from cost-effective savings in the purchasing process to business investment decisions. Value-based selling is not only more profitable for the sale of the company's products and services, but also associated with the salesperson's performance growth and the enterprise's performance. On the other hand, value-based selling is also mentioned as the customer value-oriented method at the salesperson level, helping to transform a company's sales strategy into performance (Terho et al., 2015).

In the context of the present business, value-based selling is concerned with creating sales solutions so that company can work with customer effectively, ensuring to meet customer's values of product and service (Terho et al., 2017). It also helps the company to fully understand their problems and costs, thereby reducing negative impacts and using more rationally the overall resources (finance, human resources), increasing sustainable

sales, profitability, and competitive advantage for the company (de Jong et al., 2021; Mullins et al., 2020; Ulaga and Kohli, 2018). In addition, value-based selling is also considered as a very useful approach for young company because it is easy to take advantage of the close relationship and trust between customer and company to building valuable solutions (Kuester et al., 2017; Reymen et al. 2015).

However, value-based selling is an expensive method as it requires an investment of both company's financial resources and time in order to effectively interact and understand customers, co-create value (Alnakhli et al., 2021; Baumann and Le Meunier-FitzHugh, 2014, Haas et al., 2012; Terho et al., 2012). Value-based selling covers three main aspects, namely understanding the customer's business model, building value propositions for the customer, and conveying value, and is evaluated as a set of valuable possibilities are not easy to replace (Terho et al., 2012; Mullins et al., 2019; Töytäri and Rajala, 2015). Value-based selling is also not the right method to use for all employees, customer, or all situation in sales. Value-based selling operates effectively when its focus is on high potential customers, whose salespeople spend a lot of time and effort researching (Terho et al., 2015). Value-based selling also depends on the sales skills of salespeople (Keränen et al., 2020; Plouffe et al., 2009; Terho et al., 2017). From the above discussions, the definition of value-based selling is:

Value-based selling is a unique selling method that requires seller's initiative and efforts to implement a firm's customer value orientations, listen to and in-depth understand customer issues, focus on conveying the value-in-use potential of the offering for the customer, always sell based on the value offer provides, not the cost, thereby demonstrating the seller's convincing contribution to financial profit of customers, reinforcing the company's profitability and competitiveness (de Jong et al., 2021; Kaufman, 2010; Liu and Leach, 2001; Mullins et al., 2019; Töytäri and Rajala, 2015; Terho et al., 2015; Ulaga and Kohli, 2018).

2.3.4. Defining sales skills

Over the past decade, firms have recognised the value and importance of salespeople as well as the essential skills of a salesperson that can ensure continued sales growth, maximise revenue from existing customers, systematically manage potential customers as well as allowing for stronger growth than competitors in the same industry (Churchill et al., 2000; Amor, 2019; Ingram et al., 2004). A good salesperson can understand the features of the company's products / services, communicate them fluently to customers, oriented customer support as well as developing positive relationships with customers. A salesperson's skills are related to his or her ability to present sales, how to sell suggestions, knowledge of products, how to allocate time and direct customer support (Amor, 2019; Pettijohn et al., 2002).

A salesperson's skills are also considered to be related to their age and gender. Scholars argue that age is an indication of performance, a composite of health, intellectual, and physical factors that are frequently unfavourable and might impact performance (Fu, 2009; Rhodes, 1993). Older salespeople tend to have low expectations, lack the effort to accept new tasks, and often accept what is given to them. Ageing might result in poor decision-making, weakening business performance. In other words, the older the age, the more hindered sales performance is (Avolio et al., 1990; Giniger et al., 1983; Rhodes 1983).

However, the negative aspects of this association remain controversial due to the evidence presented over the past decades (Davies et al., 1991; McEvoy and Cascio 1989). Success and age are unrelated (Rhodes, 1983; Avolio et al., 1990; Gilbert et al, 1991). People typically assume that old salespeople are outdated and incapable of adapting to market improvements in order to succeed. On the other hand, younger salespeople are thought to lack the necessary skills and experience to thrive in sales interactions (Day et al., 1993; Fang et al., 2021; Rosen and Jerdee, 1985). Age will not interfere with sales performance unless we allow it. People of all ages are capable of achieving excellence and imposing age as a measure of ability and performance is improper. Researchers claim

that age disparities may either enhance or diminish a person's capacity to work, depending on the work setting (Kanfer and Ackerman, 2004) or have no discernible effect on a person's performance in the sales sector (Rhodes, 1983).

Similarly, gender, which is related to skills, is also expected to have a strong impact on employee sales performance (Wegman et al., 2018). Men predominate in the sales sector in a very different way than women do. Men tend to be more rational, competent, and capable of making faster decisions, leading to higher performance (Jiang et al., 2012; Tyagi and Wotruba, 1998). They are also more likely to perform task-related activities in comparison to women. Another practical consideration is that women encounter many prejudices in the sales industry, however, they are supposed to outperform men in terms of performance if they can overcome prejudice barriers (Edgar et al., 2021; Green et al., 2009).

There are many different opinions about this relationship, and it is difficult to find any concrete evidence about it because marketing researchers say that the important essence of the sales industry is the ability to communicate, which cannot be determined by age or gender (Muhonen & Torkelson, 2004). Any differences in individual sales performance are likely to be related to their skills/experience rather than their gender/age (Meece and Jones, 1996). Whether male or female, young or old, if they do not have sales ability or poor communication skills, they cannot achieve high sales compared to others.

Today's sales skills are described as an ability that salespeople use to deal positively with customers in the context of personal sales, is the way that a salesperson advise and convince customers every step of the way to make a purchasing decision, as well as handle various situations that occur in the process of communicating with customers in order to maximise profits (Jhamb et al., 2021). This research also shows that people tend to buy with salespeople who make a good impression. Highly skilled salespeople, therefore, help to market products, bring in more revenue and profits than those with little or no selling skills (Koponen et al., 2019; Armstrong, 2009; Van Tien et al., 2021).

Along with that, researchers (Amor, 2019; Peesker et al., 2022; Pettijohn et al., 2002) also argue that a salesperson's sales skill is the degree of proficiency learnt to be able to perform well the sales assigned. Additional tasks such as customer-oriented sales can be overwhelming for inexperienced salespeople. Thus, a well-equipped salesperson with sales skills is more advantageous to perform customer-oriented sales tasks, thereby helping to deliver longer-term results. Therefore, sales skills are also an important determinant of salesperson's performance (Amor, 2019; Churchill et al., 1985, 2000; Rentz et al., 2002).

In other studies of scholars (Churchill et al., 1985; Rentz et al., 2002; Vinchur et al., 1998), overall sales skills are a combination of three distinct aspects as follows: (1) interpersonal skills (the ability to interact and communicate fluently in verbal and nonverbal with customers), (2) salesmanship skills (the ability to present, advise, and initiate and end transactions positively), and (3) technical skills (in-depth knowledge of product features). These skills are evaluated as factors that have a beneficial effect on salesperson performance. Also, marketing skills (Ahearne and Schillewaert, 2000) are also presented as another predictor of salesperson performance.

In other words, sales skills are tied to certain basic tasks, which are often related to procedural knowledge or declarative knowledge, and are general knowledge that salespeople possess (Szymanski, 1988). In addition, sales skills are believed to be visible through salesperson's behaviour, however, it is also related to cognitive and emotional processes (Hargie, 2010). In summary, from the above discussion, a sales skill can be defined as follows:

Salespersons' selling skills demonstrate the seller's ability and their learnt proficiency at performing the tasks required for the sales job, which involves delivering sales presentations, handling sales situations, comprehending their products, and providing customer service oriented (Amor, 2019; Jhamb et al., 2021; Pettijohn et al., 2002; Rentz et al., 2002).

2.3.4.1. Defining interpersonal skills

The concept of interpersonal skills in sales context is dissimilar and revealed by many different researchers. According to Anselmi and Zemanek (1997), interpersonal skills are closely related to communication skills, or the right kind of personality (Abratt and Kelly, 2002), whereas other researchers (Ambady et al., 2006) link interpersonal skills with collaborative and emotional support. Besides ambiguous and elusive statements, a number of studies (Amor, 2019; Homburg and Jensen, 2007; Koponen et al., 2019; Vilela et al., 2007) found that interpersonal skills are related to an individual salesperson's ability to deal with, maintain communication, resolve conflicts, is the ability to persuade, understand customers, listen, and empathise. In addition, the study of Hill et al. (2017) also reported that interpersonal skills are described as extending from the professional (having the knowledge and being trained in an empathic stance) to the personal realm (dealing and solving problems that may occur between individuals in the process of interacting with customers). The above aspects are also found to have a strong link with salesperson performance in order to achieve high sales performance. Anaza et al. (2018), Comer and Drollinger (1999) and Itani et al. (2019) admit that listening skills have great value to a salesperson's success. On the other hand, scholars (Comer and Drollinger, 1999; Delpechitre et al. 2019, Deeter-Schmelz and Sojka, 2003; Limbu et al., 2016; and Plank et al. 1996) show that empathy skills have a positive contribution to overall performance of salespeople. Therefore, these aspects are perceived as effective interpersonal skills and need to be developed by sellers.

The researchers recognised interpersonal skills as a part of skill level, and an indispensable factor in overall salesperson performance (Amor, 2019; Alge et al., 2002; Churchill et al., 1985; Udayana et al., 2019). In addition, Basir et al., (2010), Chen (2019) and Bolander et al. (2015) state that interpersonal skills are abilities for adapting to social situations, for interacting, getting along with others and outgoing. The value of interpersonal skills, therefore, is found to be of utmost importance to success not only on the individual salesperson's level, but it also has a positive effect on the managers/director who possess these skills. The supervisor's performance assessment of one of their

salespeople is also regulated through the salesperson's interpersonal skills (Vilela et al., 2007).

In addition, people are more likely to interact with salespeople with good interpersonal skills (Abratt and Kelly, 2002). An individual who knows how to perform a good interpersonal will not only make a positive impression on the customer, boost customer trust (Abratt and Kelly, 2002; Hardjati and Febrianita, 2019), but also stimulates buying intent (Evan, 1996; Low Foong Peng and Basit, 2018), and increasing buyers' satisfaction (Anselmi and Zemanek, 1997). From these discussions, the following definition of interpersonal skills can be defined:

Interpersonal skill refers to a seller's ability to adapt to situations, resolve conflict, understanding and empathetic with customer as well as perceived observation skills. Interpersonal skills are used in the communication and sales interactions to form and develop customer relationships, thereby creating efficiency and benefits for both the business and the customer (Ahmed et al., 2010; Bolander et al., 2015; Castleberry and Shepherd, 1993; Low Foong Peng and Basit, 2018; Punwatkar and Varghese, 2014, Rentz et al., 2002).

2.3.4.2. Defining salesmanship skills

Salesmanship skills represent skills in selling and are known as one of the essential skills of personal selling, related to the knowledge and skills to be able to sell a product / service of an individual salesperson (Islam et al., 2016). In other words, it is the seller's effort to persuade and influence the buyer directly to drive potential buyers' buying decisions (Amor, 2019). Similar to interpersonal skills, the importance of salesmanship skills is also emphasised in sales presentation, and closing the sale positively (Amor, 2019). In the context of increasingly competitive sales, salesperson with good salesmanship skills will not only make a profit, but their profit will be also much higher than those of inexperienced salesperson.

The ability to negotiate and ask questions, adaptive sales, consulting, communication styles and salesperson cues are key aspects of salesmanship skills (Rentz et al., 2002). Studies also demonstrated the positive association between these factors and salespeople's performance (Futrell, 2006; Leigh and Summers, 2002). Moreover, salesmanship skill is the ability to prospect for potential customer, learn about their needs to select and classify suitable groups of customers, present and customise solutions for each potential customer, solve customer problems and questions based on proposed solutions, and close sales positively (Rentz et al., 2002; Román and Iacobucci, 2010). Identifying the right potential customers and those with high buying intent will help increase sales (Ahearne et al., 2007; Bancha, 2019; Román and Rodríguez, 2015; Zhang et al., 2021).

Effective sales presentation and consulting through understanding and having detailed knowledge about the product / service provided will help the salespersons reach closer to potential customers, gain customer trust and satisfaction, thereby improving personal sales performance (Abdolvand and Farzaneh, 2013; Johlke, 2006). According to Akaeze and Akaeze (2017), the advantage of salesmanship skills is to help form and develop demand for goods, thereby increasing production. This research also recognises that professional sales presentation and knowledge of products / services are extremely important to impress and build trust for customers, to increase their willingness to pay. Therefore, salesmanship skills need to be strengthened by salespeople in order to improve sales performance, sales, and revenue (Akaeze and Akaeze, 2017). Wachner et al., (2009b) also acknowledged the positive impact of salesmanship skill on sales performance.

From the above discussions, the concept of salesmanship skills can be defined as: salesmanship skills refer to the seller's ability to prospect for customers and expand relationships with prospects, present sales messages, persuade purchases and close sales, as well as handling customer objections of sellers (Amor, 2019; Rentz; et al., 2002; Román and Iacobucci, 2010).

2.3.4.3. Defining technical skills

According to Behrman and Perreault (1982), technical skills related to the ability to promptly grasp technology trends of products to facilitate communication with customers. Technical skills are a salesperson's knowledge of the products/ services they are selling, their company's policies, the market, and the competitors they compete with (Islam et al, 2016; Rentz et al., 2002). More specifically, it is the skills and expertise of the salesperson to be able to accurately provide information about features, usage, as well as how to preserve their products / services for consumers (Ahearne and Schillewaert, 2000; Basir et al., 2010; Futrell, 2006). This knowledge can also be about mechanical equipment, information technology, and mathematics (Rathore, 2017).

Technical skills in personal selling seem to be an interesting topic and have received a lot of interest from practitioners and academics, and they also prefer to use a variety of scientific terms for technical skills to be able to demonstrate its functions clearly, such as selling-related knowledge (Høgevold et al., 2021; Verbeke et al., 2011), understanding customers (Rodriguez et al., 2014), industrial and organisational knowledge (Groza et al., 2016). Research on selling-related knowledge also confirmed that it is closely related to sales performance (Rodriguez et al., 2022; Verbeke et al., 2011).

The managers believe that a salesperson should understand and know how to use modern technology skills to be able to handle the necessary situations, as well as find and follow up potential customers (Amor, 2019). Supporting the above point of view, research by Rapp et al. (2006) also acknowledges that individuals possessing technical skills are always knowledgeable about grasping and approaching customers more easily than others, be quick in finding customers, as well as responding to customers' needs in the best way. Flexible price adjustment in certain sales situations is also an intelligent sales technique that a good salesperson applies to increase transaction volume (Jhamb et al., 2021). Researchers (Amor, 2019; Baldauf and Cravens, 2002; Groza et al., 2016) also agree with the importance of technical skills in salesperson performance development.

Technical skills are becoming more and more popular due to the needs of business to find out about market, customer, their competitors are increasing, and how to collect and integrate all this information on an organisation's system is always a matter of managers. Also, the benefits of technical skills are increasingly demonstrated by the effectiveness of interactions between sellers and customers, especially through social media (content management, search engine optimisation (SEO) (Amor, 2019).

Having thorough understanding of technical knowledge and integrating information technology into sales activities (applying sales automation) brings practical service efficiency to the company. It not only creates a competitive advantage over competitors in the market, helps to strengthen trust with customers, increases interactivity, develops closer relationships with customers, but also help improve salesperson's knowledge, adaptability, and their performance (Dawson and Thomson, 2018; Hunter and Perreault, 2006; Islam et al., 2016).

From the above discussion, definitions of technical skills can be drawn as follows: technical skills involve the salesperson's knowledge and expertise to provide information about the design, specification, functionality of a product/ service, or perform a particular task that has relating to methods, processes, and procedure required by company policies (Ahmed et al., 2010, Amor, 2019; DuBrin, 2011; Rathore, 2017).

2.3.4.4. Defining marketing skills

Marketing skills are related to how to plan, predict, make decisions, communicate, and perform (Armstrong, 1988). It involves activities to create, grow market share, and know how to establish relationships with customers (Van Scheers, 2011). Marketing skills are also known as a salesperson's understanding of the operating trend of the company they are working for (Ahmed et al., 2010; Ahearne and Schillewaert, 2000; Buzuayehu, 2019). In addition, the study of authors (Amor, 2019; Baldauf and Cravens, 2002; Basir et al., 2010; Futrell, 2006) also indicated that possession of the necessary knowledge about the

market, services/ products, customers, competitors are considered as important factors to create effective marketing skills of a salesperson.

With the rapid development and change of the business market, sales skills play an important role in salespeople's sales tasks, helping to increase the number of goods sold rather than those who are not possessing this skill (Amor, 2019; Ingram et al., 2004; Schoemaker and Johlke, 2002). It is categorised as a macro skill stream (Amor, 2019) and is predictive of salesperson performance (Ahearne and Schillewaert, 2000). Supporting the above point of view, it is also found that understanding the customer and possessing extensive marketing knowledge helps salespeople respond more acutely in complex environments, thereby increasing performance significantly (Basir et al., 2010; Leigh and McGraw, 1989; Smith and Owens, 1995)

The fact that marketing is the only function that can generate revenue for the entire enterprise, and the majority of business success comes from using the right marketing skills (Cant, 2012). Customers will not be able to support business if they are not aware of information about the products and services that the business provides. Not only for salespeople, even some small and medium enterprises, the manager will be responsible for all company activities, including marketing duties. Therefore, managers should have the necessary marketing skills (e.g. sales) to be able to intervene in the company's marketing field, introduce products / services, and interact more harmoniously with clients (Van Scheers, 2011). Therefore, marketing skills are essential for businesses and managers to maintain balance and to decide for the long-term survival of their business (Bowler et al., 2007). Possessing marketing skills and knowledge not only positively supports salesperson's performance, but also helps them become more confident in their communication, reinforce customer trust and satisfaction, thereby, increasing the interaction between sellers and customers in the future (Amor, 2019).

From these discussions, marketing skills can be defined as follows: marketing skills are essential to create sustainability and survival for businesses, including knowledge of the marketing industry and trends in general such as finding markets, building customer

relationships, planning, creating product/ service, analysing competitor, sales policies and product lines of competitors in the same industry (Ahmed et al., 2010; Armstrong, 1998; Cant, 2012; Van Scheers, 2011).

2.3.5. Defining salesperson characteristic

In the field of personal psychology, personal characteristics are related to an individual's perception of their surroundings (Avila and Fern, 1986), which are characteristic differences formed in a person's thoughts and feelings (Bradberry, 2007). Personal characteristic is understood as motivational factors, influencing an individual's emotions, abilities, and behaviour, and are related to his or her long-term tendency to behave (Blickle et al., 2008; Bartkus et al., 2011; Han, 2020; Penney et al., 2011; Witt and Ferris, 2003). Researchers (Brown et al., 2002; Mowen and Spears 1999) argue that it is an abstract concept that exists at different levels with appropriate contexts. Similarly, each individual will have different personalities, and corresponding to their profession. According to Giacobbe et al. (2006), personal sales is a complex process and requires a harmonious combination of different elements to create successful sales interactions, therefore, in addition to the sales situation, characteristics (ability and behaviour) of the salesperson are essential to achieving effective job goals (Ashill et al., 2020; Harris et al., 2014; Penney et al., 2011).

Different characteristics affect the professional sales activities of salespeople, and lead to different meanings in social network development and task outcomes (Bolander et al., 2015; Nonis and Sager, 2003). Specifically, salespeople's personalities have been shown to have a significant impact on their customer-oriented performance, their adaptive sales ability in diverse sales situations (Penney et al., 2011; Widmier, 2002; Yakasai and Jan, 2015); and overall salesperson performance (Ashill et al., 2020; Echchakoui, 2017; Rothmann and Coetzer, 2003). Furthermore, the personality of salespeople is highly valued by marketing and management researchers and is crucial in the recruitment process of companies (Barrick, 2005; Charoensukmongkol, 2020; Gridwichai et al., 2020). It is hard for managers to accept an irresponsible employee, not inclined to care

and cooperate (empathetic), inability to control or regulate their own behaviour (self-monitoring), as well as cognitive and adaptive perception (cue perception). However, it is possible to be trained or fostered through self-improvement to become a professional salesman. Besides, personal characteristics are also evaluated as indispensable for sales managers to be able to positively influence the formation of salespeople attitudes and acceptance of their goals, aim to deliver high customer satisfaction and value (Chakrabarty et al., 2012), as well as enhance sales performance (Cron et al., 2005; Harris et al., 2014). Thence, it is seen that personality traits play an important role in salesperson performance (Harris et al., 2014; Verbeke et al., 2011). From the above discussion, the definition of the salesperson's characteristic is as follows:

Salesperson's characteristics are differences in thoughts and feelings, expressing the unique traits of each individual, are the motivational factors that can promote a person's ability to perform, has a direct or indirect impact on sales, and is often related to perception, behaviour, and task proficiency such as customer orientation, adaptive sales, empathy, etc (Bradberry, 2007; Bartkus et al., 2011; Carpenter et al., 2009; Han, 2020)

2.3.5.1. Defining empathic ability

Empathy is known as an individual's personality or emotional trait that allows people to put themselves in other people's situations or positions to perceive and evaluate, includes two main ingredients as follows, cognitive and affective perspectives (Agnihotri and Krush, 2015; Anaza et al., 2018; Kerem et al., 2001; Kong et al., 2020; Wondra and Ellsworth, 2015). It is also defined as one's ability to understand and react to others' thoughts, feelings and experiences (Coleman, 1998; Itani and Inyang, 2015; Limbu et al., 2016; Wieseke et al., 2012; Wilder et al., 2014).

In personal sales documents, empathy is seen as an essential and indispensable characteristic for front-line service staff, which determines their performance and success (Bahadur et al., 2020; Costa et al., 2004; Itani and Inyang, 2015; Kong et al., 2020; Matzler and Renzl, 2007). Non-verbal skills in general, and empathy in particular will

help salesperson better perceive and listen to customers' problems, put themselves in the psychology of customers to empathise, share and present their product / service in the most suitable way (Giacobbe et al., 2006, p.12; Limbu et al., 2016; Pilling and Eroglu, 1994).

In addition, empathy is considered a competitive advantage of a service organisation because it shows the organisation's concern for the benefit of its customers (Ahearne et al., 2007; Anaza et al., 2018; Delpechitre et al., 2019). Customer always expects to receive empathy from sellers during service interactions (Fellekson and Salomonson, 2016). Salesperson who possesses a high level of empathy will be more successful in attracting and building close relationships with customer, reinforcing customer trust, satisfaction as well as improving their own productivity compared to less empathetic salesperson (Aggarwal et al., 2005; Bahadur et al., 2018; Bagozzi, 2006; Kane, 2018; Mangus et al., 2020). Empathy makes the interaction between the seller and the buyer more conducive by promoting altruism, cohesion, and harmony among individuals. From there, it positively affects customer purchasing decisions, develops long-term relationships and increases sales performance (Bahadur et al., 2020).

This is also an important relational factor to support the goal's development of the organisation in general and salespeople in particular, reinforcing the mutual relationship between people (Rameson et al. 2012; Whiteside and Barclay, 2016). In the field of business management, empathy can help managers listen and understand employees more deeply, thereby grasping the problem and helping employees develop in the best way (Mencl and May, 2009). In short, the definition of empathy as follows:

Empathy is an emotional trait or an ability that allows sellers to place themselves in others' shoes, to perceive, understand, and identify with the customer's subjective point of view, thereby establishes rapport between a professional and customer (Agnihotri and Krush, 2015; Anaza et al., 2018; Drollinger and Comer, 2013; Keefe, 1978; Kong et al., 2020; Limbu et al., 2016; Sharma, 2001; Wilder et al., 2014).

2.3.5.2. Defining cue perception ability

Cue perception ability is a measurable factor that relates to a salesperson's ability to be aware of situational cues (verbal and nonverbal signals) during customer interactions (McIntire et al., 1999). Salesperson who are able to identify and interpret signals in selling situations (especially nonverbal signals) are more likely to succeed than those who lack this ability (Goolsby et al., 1992; Grikscheit, 1972; Giacobbe et al., 2006).

Gremler and Gwinner (2008) and Puccinelli et al. (2010) concur with the above viewpoint that salesperson who are able to read nonverbal cues will have many advantages. When salespeople are correctly aware of the customer's cues, they can be easier to approach customer and provide more suitable products/ services, thereby increasing the customer's perception of service quality (Kidwell and Hasford, 2014; Lussier and Hall, 2018). In addition, the ability of the salesperson to perceive cues in selling situations also helps to ensure long-term interaction with customers and improve company's profit (Puccinelli et al., 2013).

According to Ramsey and Sohi (1997) and Puccinelli et al. (2013), the ability to perceive customer signals (such as read the effect of customer) is assessed as a higher degree of listening ability in salesperson, help them listen through feeling, empathy, thence responding to customer needs better, leading to building customer's trust, satisfaction, and enhancing the mutual relationships between buyer and seller (Clopton et al., 2001; Hall et al., 1995; Stock and Hoyer, 2005).

In addition, the ability to perceive customer signals also positively supports the success of a service company (Bowen and Schneider, 1985). It also plays a key role in regulating the seller's behaviour towards customers, allowing them to control the influence of using customer-oriented and adaptive selling methods more favourably on performance (Giacobbe et al., 2006; Kidwell et al., 2007; Park and Holloway, 2003; Spiro and Weitz, 1990). Also, people who possess this ability are perceived to be effective leaders, able to

make their subordinates more satisfied, to receive better support and appreciation from them (Elfenbein and Ambady, 2002; Riggio, 2006).

The relationship between cue perception ability and salesperson performance is also raised by researchers such as Elfenbein et al., (2007), Goolsby et al., (1992), Herpertz et al., (2016) and Szymanski and Churchill (1990). However, Giacobbe et al. (2006) states that the ability to perceive diverse signals is essential to salespeople's success in adaptive selling. From the findings, cue perception ability can be defined as:

Cue perception ability is known as an essential salespeople's skill that allows them to perceive situational cues during customer interactions, adjust their own behaviour and provide tailored service, leading to sales adapting efficiency, improving sales performance and long-term customer relationships (Goolsby et al., 1992; Giacobbe et al., 2006; Herpertz et al., 2016; Kidwell et al., 2011; Lussier and Hall, 2018; MacIntyre et al., 1999; Puccinelli et al., 2013; Stock and Hoyer, 2005).

2.3.5.3. Defining the ability to modify self-presentation

The ability to modify self-presentation is an important aspect of self-monitoring construct (Snyder, 1987), which relates to the degree of individuals differences in how they control and adapt their own behaviour to fit the current social environment (Gangestad and Snyder, 2000; Grieve et al., 2020). The ability to modify is the visual and sound signs created by the seller, demonstrates a positive trend of the seller in observing and self-modifying their behaviour, responding to the selling context in order to help implement an efficient service exchange process (Alnakhli et al., 2020; Bande Vilela et al., 2010; Giacobbe et al., 2006). Marketing academics (e.g. Day et al., 2002; Gangestad and Snyder, 2000; Grieve et al., 2020) on the self-monitoring concept also revealed that people with high self-monitoring tend to be more attentive to surroundings and easier to adapt their images to current situations than low self-monitoring who are less interested in social environment.

In the personal selling field, the ability to modify self-presentation is a determinant of adaptive sales (Alnakhli et al., 2020; Weitz et al., 1986), and serves as an important intermediate variable for the relationship between adaptive selling behaviour and salesperson performance (Weitz, 1979, 1981). Improving the seller's ability to modify will enable them to respond better to situational cues, seize opportunities to adjust more effectively in the sales process with customers (Giacobbe et al., 2006). On the other hand, some studies by Spiro and Weitz (1990) and Day et al. (2002) argued that self-modification did not significantly affect salesperson performance. From the above discussion, the definition of the ability of modification is as follows:

Ability to modify self-presentation is an important element of the self-monitoring scale, showing an individual's tendency to self-control and adapt his/ her behaviour to a specific sales context, impact to adaptive sales and sales performance (Alnakhli et al., 2020; Gangestad and Snyder, 2000; Giacobbe et al, 2006; Grieve et al., 2020; Lennox and Wolfe, 1984; Rank et al., 2009).

2.3.5.4. Defining experience

According to Webster (1983), experience is defined as the things an individual experienced and observed through any particular situation / event. On the other hand, Knutson and Beck (2004) stated that experience is a vague concept and difficult to define because it is related to many different factors, along with human personality. In addition, the research of Cutler and Carmichael (2010), Godovykh and Tasci (2020) and O'Dell (2007) report that experience is a series of phenomena that occur constantly and are involved by an individual.

In the field of personal selling, experience as an intermediate that helps to regulate relationships between sales force perceptions and behaviour (Harindranath et al., 2019; Rapp et al., 2008; Singh and Das, 2013). It is also defined as the salesperson's investment in their job to gain more advantage in sales skills and sales performance (Fu, 2009; Groza and Groza, 2018). The authors (Franke and Park 2007; Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Singh

and Das, 2013, 2015) demonstrate the positive effect in the mutual relationship between experience and salesperson performance. According to Ahearne et al. (2010); Terho et al. (2013), salespeople with little or no experience will be clearly seen through their sales performance. The more sales experience increases, the higher the sales performance growth rate (Pöyry et al., 2021; Verbeke et al., 2011).

There is a positive effect between experience on the antecedent of salesperson performance such as customer oriented and adaptive selling (Harindranath et al., 2019; Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Singh and Das, 2013). A salesman who has been through many different sales situations, has learnt about both successes and failures will not only understand the products/ services as well as the needs of different types of customers, but also know how to apply appropriate sales methods to improve customer interaction, solve service problems more acutely and effectively, thereby improving sales performance (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020). In addition, experience plays a practical role in regulating the relationship between salesperson's performance and knowledge (Anderson, 1983; Matsuo and Kusumi, 2002).

An individual's selling skills or knowledge are better improved thanks to experience. The more the seller's experience, the closer the relationship between knowledge and performance (Matsuo and Kusumi, 2002). In addition, the "ten-year rule of necessary preparation" popularised by researchers also emphasises that it takes about 10 years for humans to practise and positively improve performance at work (Ericsson, 1996; McDaniel et al., 1988; McEnrue, 1988; Schmidt et al., 1986;). Therefore, it can be seen that experience is an essential factor for the development of professional knowledge and performance of salespeople. With the above statements, the definition of experience can be construed as follows:

Experience (knowledge) is related to perceived human competence and plays a dual role in its relationship with performance, which assists sellers in improving task-related selling efficiencies, broaden the scope and depth of the different sales contexts, types of

customers, as well as the sales strategy to better meet customer needs and gain their trust (Giacobbe et al., 2006; Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Pöyry et al., 2021).

2.3.6. Defining adaptive selling behaviour

Adaptive selling is related to a salesperson's ability to perceive and regulate behaviour during customer interaction to match the characteristics of the target customer (Chai et al., 2012; Franke and Park, 2006; Limbu et al., 2016; Peranginangin and Kusumawardhani, 2018; Wong and Tjosvold, 2015). Adaptive selling behaviour is a change in sales tactics, communication style, and appearance of the salesperson (Giacobbe et al., 2006; Yeo et al., 2019).

Adaptive selling behaviour is considered as a highly strategic selling method because it requires salespeople to go through a process of acquiring knowledge related to potential customers, thereby building strategy, presenting tactic to suit different customer and specific sales context (Crittenden, 2015; Limbu et al., 2016; Park et al., 2010; Sigauw, 2015). Research by Kohli and Jaworski (1990) shows that customers are always dominated by products / services of the company's competitors. Therefore, in addition to customer information, collecting and understanding competitor characteristics and their products will also be a great advantage for salesperson to effectively implement adaptive selling behaviour (Andzulis et al., 2012; Itani et al., 2017; Rapp et al., 2015).

Scholars (Charoensukmongkol and Suthatorn, 2020; Giacobbe et al., 2006; Limbu et al., 2016; Singh et al., 2017) identified adaptive selling behaviour as the mediating factor between sales ability and salesperson performance. In other words, it plays a positive role for the development of salesperson performance (Kwak et al., 2019). A highly adaptable salesperson can easily grasp customer needs and customise the sales strategy, accordingly, thereby increasing sales, building quality relationship with customer as well as sales performance (Amenuvor et al., 2021; Itani et al., 2017; Jaramillo et al., 2007; Predmore and Bonnice, 1994). Supporting that point of view, the researchers (Peters and Bodkin, 2022; Román and Iacobucci, 2010; Wood et al. 2008; Yurova et al., 2017) also

show that salesperson's skills and experience have a huge impact on customer purchase intentions. Since then, implementing adaptive sales in salespeople brings trust and satisfaction to customers as well as improves sales staff's performance (Amenuvor et al., 2021; Itani et al., 2017; Rippé et al., 2016).

Customers tend to be more appreciative and more likely to engage with salespeople who apply adaptive selling skills (Hughes et al., 2013; Chen and Jaramillo, 2014). Practically, salesperson with good adaptive selling skill is always attentive to customer signals, better understand the tastes of customer and easily come up with suitable solutions to address customer needs (Franke and Park, 2006; Itani et al., 2017; Pandey and Charoensukmongkol, 2019; Román and Martín, 2014; Wong et al., 2015). In short, practicing adaptive selling plays an important role in personal sales success. It not only supports the interactive relationship between salespeople and customer, develops customer satisfaction, but also improves employee and company performance (Pyun, 2017; Peranginangin and Kusumawardhani, 2018; Rakesh et al., 2017; Sing and Das, 2013; Weck and Ivanova, 2013). From the above statements, the definition of adaptive selling behaviour is:

Adaptive selling behaviour (ASB) is a dynamic approach for selling, where sellers will go through an interactive process that involves collecting information and listening to customer requirements, thereby changing behaviour, messages, sales strategies, as well as appropriate communication tactics to better respond to the increasing customer demand, ensure sales performance, and develop long-term relationships with customers (Hughes et al., 2013; Itani et al., 2017; Limbu et al., 2016; Pandey and Charoensukmongkol, 2019; Pyun, 2017; Peranginangin and Kusumawardhani, 2018; Rocco and Whalen, 2014).

2.4. DEFINING THE ANTICIPATION OF FUTURE INTERACTION CONCEPT

Anticipation of future interaction concerns the perceptions and desires of buyers to see the seller again in the future when their needs arise (Kennedy et al., 2001). In other words, it is the degree of customer willingness to pay for the company's products / services and positive word of mouth to other customers. The expectation of a future interaction is directly proportional to the customer's perception of the current interaction relationship. The higher the customer's expectation, the more favourable the current relationship between the seller and the customer, and conversely, the lower the expectation reflects the dissatisfaction of the customer in the current relationship with the seller (Min et al., 2020; Sarmiento et al., 2015).

In sales management documents, customers are known as collaborators with the company to co-create value and deliver business success (Delpechitre et al., 2018; Payne et al., 2009; Le Hau and Thuy, 2016). Interpersonal interaction and co-creation are interdependent because it is key for creating value, helping company to develop certain benefits of customer satisfaction and loyalty (Delpechitre et al., 2018; Navarro et al., 2016; Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004; Payne et al., 2008). Salespeople and their ability to present and interact are always especially interested by customer. This not only shows the characteristic and perception of the employee, but also greatly affects the customer's emotion, which motivates customer to continue buying in the future (Bateman and Valentine, 2021).

Impression and satisfaction with the seller help strengthen and maintain a long-term relationship (Crosby et al. 1990). Along with that, belief is also an important factor to create a sustainable relationship (Böhm et al., 2020; Kennedy et al., 2001). As the seller creates higher trust in the customer relationship, this will lead to the customer's desire to continue interacting with the current seller rather than searching and switching to a newcomer (Ashraf et al., 2020; Morgan and Hunt 1994; Nadeem et al., 2020; Kennedy et al., 2001).

The above views can support that the anticipation of future interaction is intimately tied to customer trust, satisfaction as well as the seller's relationship orientation (Delpechitre and Beeler, 2018; Herjanto and Amin, 2020; Tam and Wong, 2001; Guenzi and Georges, 2010). Thence, the anticipation of future interaction also plays an important role in developing positively relationship between customer satisfaction and retention, promoting the company's business activity (Herjanto and Amin, 2020; Ramsey and Sohi, 1997). In short, anticipation of future interaction is defined as:

Anticipation of future interaction is the goal of sales, related to customer satisfaction perceptions, their beliefs and desire to stay or leave in the current relationship with salesperson (Delpechitre et al., 2018; Kennedy et al., 2001; Navarro et al., 2016). It plays an important role in maintaining and developing customer relationships, improving business operations (Bateman and Valentine, 2021; Herjanto and Amin, 2020).

2.5. DEFINING THE REPURCHASE INTENTION

Repurchase intention is defined as the ability to buy a particular product/ service once again from the same company in the future (Balakrishnan et al, 2020; Bojei and Hoo, 2012; Chang et al., 2020; Javed and Wu, 2020; Khalifa and Liu, 2007; Swoboda and Sinning, 2020), or is the degree of customer loyalty to a brand in the market (Chauke and Dhurup, 2017; Chaudhuri and Holbrook, 2001; Wu and Chang, 2007). Regarding the customer's perspective, repurchase intention is the level of willingness, the psychological commitment of the customer to continue buying, and maintaining a good relationship with the company (Anderson, 1994; Blut et al., 2015; Chou and Hsu, 2016; Herjanto and Amin, 2020; Kuan et al., 2008). Additionally, it is also known as the subjective customer judgement to refinance a company's product and has a direct impact on customer purchase (Anh et al., 2020, Chen and Chen, 2017; Filieri and Lin, 2017; Fang et al., 2011; Hsu et al., 2014; Wu et al., 2014)

According to researchers (Anh et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2016; Hsu et al., 2014; Shin et al., 2013), despite being a dependent, repurchase intention not only plays an important role in determining the company's loyal customer, but also helping the company manage and consolidating operational strategy, thriving in the market (Chou and Hsu, 2016), because the cost of finding new customers is 6 times higher than maintaining existing customers (Eklof et al., 2020; Nguyen-Phuoc et al., 2020; Vijayadurai, 2008). In addition, the intention to buy back also positively supports revenue growth and shareholder value in the company (Bindroo and Echambadi, 2016; Larivière et al., 2016).

Repurchase intention attached to customer experiences and emotions during service interactions (Cho, 2015; Chen et al., 2016; Graciola et al., 2018; Su et al., 2016; Shank and Robinson, 2019; Yi and La, 2004). Customer who has good feelings and positive experiences with the company often has higher levels of satisfaction, thereby, strongly influencing their intention to buy back with the company (Ariffin et al., 2016; Gounaris and Boukis, 2013; Shank and Robinson, 2019). Some researchers also demonstrated a positive relationship between customer satisfaction and repurchase intention (Anh et al., 2020; Brady and Robertson, 2001; Javed and Wu, 2020; Liao et al., 2017; Rose et al., 2012)

In addition to customer experiences and emotions, repurchase intention is found to be influenced by price fairness, price pleasure, or even information from people who have not yet used the company's product/ service such as key opinion leaders (KOLs) - who have a certain influence on the mass media today (Ho and Chung, 2020). The company's profitability and success depend greatly on its loyal customers and their intention to buy back (Hellier et al., 2003; Kim et al., 2012; Rahayu, 2021; Safa and Von Solms, 2016; Tsai and Huang, 2007). Thus, it is important to be aware of the impact of potential factors on a customer's repurchase intention in order to plan appropriate development strategies. From the above discussion, the definition of the repurchase intention is:

Repurchase intention is an important factor showing customer satisfaction with service interactions, related to the subjective judgement of customers to make decisions to

continue using the same company's services in future (Chang et al., 2020; Hellier et al., 2003; Javed and Wu, 2020; Khalifa and Liu, 2007; Swoboda and Sinning, 2020). Repurchase intention helps determine customer loyalty, reinforce operational strategy and revenue growth (Anh et al., 2020; Bindroo and Echambadi, 2016; Chou and Hsu, 2016).

2.6. SUMMARY

Today, both scholars and practitioners are aware of the significance of salesperson performance and its antecedent's elements in identifying a company's goods and/or services, distinguishing them apart from rivals, and informing customers about their value, reliability, and quality. Practitioners and scholars have long been intrigued by the company's salesperson performance. There is a wealth of literature in this topic. This theoretical assessment of the organisation's salesperson performance highlights the value of the salesperson's performance as a powerful tool for communication, as a crucial bridge to highlight the calibre of the company's services, and as an integral part of the customer's upcoming interactions (Bitner, 1990, Park and Tran, 2018).

In this chapter, seven antecedent factors in the field of salesperson performance were discovered. The sales strategy element is concerned with the company's salesperson performance through establishing sales models, customer prioritisation and segmentation. This factor reflects the idea that salesperson performance management should concentrate on different areas such as identifying different demand segments, prioritising customers according to their expected value, combined with tailoring sales approaches to create lasting customer relationships. Customer orientation is concerned with the activities and perceptions of the salesperson towards the customer, emphasises the importance of understanding consumers to their satisfaction and communicating the company's services quality. Value-based selling plays an important role in the sales interaction of the salesperson and the customer. The concentration should be on salesperson performance management with regard to the customer's value and financial return. Besides, the sales skills factors focus on the salesperson's ability and proficiency and describe the tangible aspects that may be observed via the salesperson's interactions with customers to

demonstrate the company's service quality ideals. Moreover, sales characteristics and experiences represent a significant impact in sales interactions between stakeholders. Sales characteristics highlights the intersection between different knowledge domains. It indicates that salesperson performance management should pay particular attention to various aspects such as empathy, ability to recognise customer signals, and self-monitoring during sales interactions. The experience factor is important in aligning the salesperson's perception and behaviour and determining the influence in communicating company values to customers. Finally, adaptive selling behaviour recognises the salesperson's efforts in the sales approach by referring to the content of the ability to perceive, and to tailor sales behaviours and strategies, indicate how the salesperson's performance is communicated to the company's customers.

The conceptual framework of the study will be presented in the next chapter, along with the formation and explanation of the research hypotheses. Following that, the relationship between salesperson performance and relevant variables will also be addressed.

CHAPTER III: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH HYPOTHESE

3.1. INTRODUCTION

Based on chapter II, it can be seen that the research on salesperson's performance topic is not that simple, and sometimes the research results are highly dependent on various factors such as time and research context. For the current research topic, the theoretical gaps of salesperson's performance have been handled through the expansion of understanding and evaluating salesperson performance to a broader scope such as profitability, and the economic success of a business. This is useful for further research. However, the main concern is the complexity of the research topic, and the researchers still used a single approach to evaluate it. This thesis will focus on salesperson performance as well as its impact on anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention of customer.

Through the findings of the literature review chapter, a hypothetical model of salesperson performance will be established. It includes the antecedent of sales performance and its consequences. There are 12 constructs reviewed in this study, namely: sales strategy, customer orientation, value-based selling, sales skill, salesperson characteristic, experiences (knowledge), adaptive selling behaviour, salesperson performance, satisfaction with salesperson, trust in salesperson, anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention.

Next, a hypothetical model based on consumer awareness will be proposed, along with testing and evaluation of a fairly large number of related hypotheses. There are 5 parts included in this chapter, respectively: 3.2 research framework and hypotheses' development; 3.3 the relationship between salesperson performance and its antecedents; 3.4 the main benefits of salesperson performance (consequences); and 3.5 summary of conclusions.

3.2. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESE DEVELOPMENT

Salesperson performance increases a company's competitiveness in the market and plays a vital role in performing effective organisational tasks (Hossain et al., 2016; Dey et al., 2016) by connecting sales strategies, skills sales, characteristics, experience, customer orientation, value-based selling and adaptive selling behaviour of the salesperson (Basir et al., 2010; Chawla et al., 2020; Echchakoui, 2017; Indrawati, 2016; Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Kienzler et al., 2018; Limbu et al., 2016; Nuryakin, 2018; Rodriguez et al., 2022; Singh et al, 2017; Terho et al., 2015). To manage and improve salesperson performance, it requires a close understanding of performance attributes (in terms of salesperson performance as indicators of service quality). In addition, the methodological system of salesperson performance such as in-depth interviews contain some limitations. Academics and practitioners are increasingly emphasising the importance of salesperson performance, and this has led to the progressive development of salesperson's concept studies starting in the 1920s.

However, it is still lacking empirical studies on salesperson performance from a consumer's perspective. A lack of awareness of the research phenomena 'salesperson performance' leads to ideas of pluralistic study, which combine qualitative and quantitative approaches to investigate an uninteresting or poorly defined subject (Deshpande, 1983).

Previous researchers tended to apply experimental methods to acquire more particular insights into the topic of interest, salesperson performance. This research, contrarily, aims to develop a conceptual model from customer perceptions, and efforts to prove the role and relationship between the different factors that affect salesperson's performance. Therefore, in order to explain more clearly the conceptual literature on salesperson performance, this study will select relevant variables from different models with the most prominent method.

The theoretical framework of research will be the basis for implementing a mixed method. According to Carson et al. (2001), Goldsmith (2021), when describing the research framework, qualitative research is found to be more relevant when it is inclined to discover what surrounds a phenomenon. However, academics (Echchakou, 2017; Rodriguez et al., 2020) have applied quantitative research to assess sales performance using an experimental but well-validated questionnaire. There have been previous studies that show the importance of salesperson performance as the first stage in the process of developing a service quality that has an impact on people's favourable perceptions of a company (Zhang et al., 2019; Zeithaml et al., 1988).

However, very few studies have been conducted that address the impact of salesperson's performance on the factors needed in order to manage and improve salesperson's performance favourably. Almost previous studies have shown the importance of salesperson's performance to shape customer satisfaction and future interaction and repurchase (Buciuniene and Skudiene, 2015), and create a competitive advantage, business profits of the company (Dey et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2016). However, there has not been any systematic research that clarifies the impact of salesperson's performance on future interaction and repurchase intention. Therefore, a conceptual framework at the consumer level will be presented in this study and provide the relevant hypotheses to the role of consequences of salesperson performance.

In addition, this research also contributes to the foundation of previous studies by investigating the effects of antecedent factors of salesperson performance on explaining variations in customer's future interaction and repurchase interaction. Based on attribution theory, a conceptual framework built into this research from the consumer perspective (Figure 3.1) to verify the relationships identified in the literature. Specifically, the conceptual framework will present: (i) the connection between the concept of salesperson's performance and its related factors; (ii) its benefits to the business; (iii) theoretical and experimental relationships between variables. The relationship between the constructs and the related hypothesis will be discussed in the following section.

Figure 3. 1: The conceptual framework

3.3. THE SALESPERSON PERFORMANCE AND ITS ANTECEDENTS

In this section, the study will present some key factors related to salesperson's performance. They will be factors that predict, motivate, or impair salesperson's performance, which are perceived in service interactions with customers. There are six main factors mentioned in literature review that help shape the salesperson's positive performance. These are found as predictors of salesperson performance: sale strategy, customer orientation, valued-based selling, sales skill, salesperson characteristic, experience, and adaptive selling behaviour.

Employee performance is an indispensable factor for organisation's effectiveness (Hameed and Waheed, 2011; Dey et al., 2016), which plays an important role to increase productivity, profitability, and competitiveness of business in the market (Ashraf and Javed, 2014; Hossain et al., 2016), reinforcing corporate value for consumers (Badrianto and Ekhsan, 2019). Despite the importance and benefits of salesperson performance to the company, as well as the existence of various studies on the subject, there are still some opinions that salesperson performance has not been given sufficient attention and favourably improved. Therefore, sales strategy has attracted a lot of attention from researchers and is considered as one of the main aspects in forming salesperson performance (Cron et al., 2014; Ingram et al., 2002; Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Katsikea et al., 2019; Terho et al., 2015; Zoltners et al., 2009).

3.3.1. Sales strategy

Sales strategy emphasises interaction with the company's external environment and their resources in order to create and develop performance (Venkatraman, 1989). As discussed in Chapter II, sales strategy is how a company identifies target groups of customers and interacts with them through the allocation of sales resources at a face-to-face customer level (Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Zoltners et al., 2009). Sales strategy is a functional factor that is important not only for the sales process, sales interface with customer, but also for organisational productivity and profitability (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Piercy, 2010; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010), is essential for company to communicate and influence

customers' purchasing power, assist in effective implementation of marketing strategies (Berry, 2003). Although the study of sales strategy and its elements is limited, it is still undeniable the need to implement customer segmentation, customer prioritisation, and establish a relationship objectives model (Ingram et al., 2012; Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Terho et al., 2015), which are considered as three main aspects of the sales strategy helps promote the success of sales exchange operations and salesperson's performance (Terho et al., 2015).

Customer segmentation is the best method that successful companies use to develop a detailed customer classification system that identifies target groups of customers (Khalili-Damghani et al., 2018; Ramani and Kumar, 2008). A clear customer segmentation strategy not only assists the company to have a better understanding of customer behavioural diversity, but also helps them determine favourably the types of value that customer want, from there, company can use resources reasonably and economically for their business operations, effectively develop customer relationships and improve salesperson performance (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Leigh and Marshall, 2001; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Wu and Lin, 2005). High-grade customer groups will also be more easily identified through the segmentation process, and this is also the motivation for salespeople to perform value-based selling more aggressively (Terho et a; 2015). Because of the high demand and value awareness of these customer groups, salespeople can be more advantageous in making a sales presentation, offering the potential value of the product/service, attracting customer interest effectively, therefore, leading to increased revenue, salesperson performance as well as competitive advantage in the market.

According to Homburg et al. (2008), customer prioritisation is a strategy that a company uses to identify and treat a specific group of customers based on their purchasing power and profitability they bring to the company. Customer prioritisation drives salespeople's value-based selling behaviour. High-grade customers spend more and brings more benefits to the company and salespeople; therefore, it motivates salespeople to access and provide value-added services. Investing in value-based selling brings high economic efficiency to prioritisation strategy, demonstrates a positive attitude in communication between sales staff

of the business and consumers, is the basis for customer satisfaction, thus, leading to increased sales and salesperson performance (Libai et al., 2020; Storbacka et al., 2011).

As the next important dimension of a sales strategy, sales model is systematically related to the setting of relationship goals, allowing salespeople to identify customer needs, transforming customer orientation into different behaviours to suit each type of needs, satisfying customer, and creating sustainable relationship in the future (Katsikea et al., 2019; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010). The better the salesperson's ability to convert the customer orientation, the better the salesperson's performance (Terho et al., 2015). In order to implement different sales processes in a sales strategy, it requires a reasonable allocation of company resources as well as flexibility in the salesperson's approach to customer, therefore, it is easy for customer-oriented salespeople to identify and adapt behaviours effectively for each type of customer, leads to high results in meeting diverse customer needs and improving sales performance (Autry et al., 2013; Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020).

In general, sales strategy is an important content and needs to be considered in order to make a good sale and create high profits for the business. Sales strategy should be clearly planned and continuously adjusted to keep up with trend and the real demand of customer (Dong et al., 2018). Sales strategy is not only the basis for valuable customer reviews on how they are satisfied with the company's products / services, but also helps distinguish the company from its competitors in the market (Riesterer, 2019). An effective sales strategy with specific goals (i.e. product positioning, growth, customer behaviour and needs, sales processes and methods) can have a strong impact on the needs of customer, increase company's profitability and competitive advantage (Civaner, 2012; Gould, 2012; Kuosa, 2017; Abed and Haghghi, 2009). The above discussion highlights the important role of the sales strategy to the company's operation, is the main factor influencing customer orientation and value-based sales. Therefore, the first two hypotheses of the study are:

H1: Sales strategy has a positive effect on the salesperson's customer orientation.

H2: Sales strategy has a positive effect on salesperson's value-based selling.

3.3.2. Customer orientation

Since the customer needs is constantly changing, a number of researchers have stated that customer orientation is becoming increasingly important and has profound implications for a company's success, only knowledgeable and customer-oriented company can survive and grow sustainably (ELSamen and Akroush, 2018; Pekovic and Rolland, 2016; Tseng and Su, 2013). Customer orientation is a positive approach to connect with stakeholders. Therefore, a business's senior manager needs to have a thorough understanding of customer orientation and its effects to be able to effectively develop customer relationships (Athanasopoulos, 2000). A high level of customer orientation is associated with customer satisfaction and their repurchase ability (Guo and Wang, 2015; Singh and Koshy, 2012; Singh and Venugopal, 2015). The studies of authors (Freeman, 2010; Mullin et al., 2014; Román and Iacobucci, 2010) also acknowledge the positive effects of customer orientation on customer satisfaction and the overall value of the company. Customer orientation in salespeople leads to sales-oriented interactions by finding the right customers and favourable sales closing (Goudge et al., 2017; Homburg et al., 2011). Customer-oriented salespeople are always more inclined to advise and support customers enthusiastically than the others. They are also more likely to respond to diverse customer needs and act on those needs by proactively adopting behaviours that facilitate customer value (Goad and Jaramillo, 2014; Itani et al., 2019; Terho et al., 2012). This is evidenced by the increasing number of sales calls that involve value-based selling. The salesperson's sales orientation is adopted before engaging in customer interaction and persuasion, helping to form mental guidelines for reacting and dealing with different customer needs (Dweck, 2006). These orientations are crucial, serving as the fundamental driving force behind value-based selling activities (Pöyry et al, 2021; Terho et al., 2015; Silver et al., 2006; Verbeke et al., 2011). Customer orientation drives sales of salespeople (Williamson et al., 2018; Zablah et al., 2012). Implementing customer orientation allows them to grasp customer needs more thoroughly, which leads to more confidence in sales interactions, better ability to complete sales tasks, more effectively convey the value of products/services to customers, and resulting in excellent performance (Chen et al., 2015; ELSamen and Akroush, 2018).

Customer orientation affects perception and buying decision of customer. As Singh and Venugopal (2015) stated, customer orientation is not simply to close the sale and make a profit, it is also the ability to support, recommend items that fit the needs and actual circumstances of the customer. As a result, customers are more likely to purchase and be more satisfied with the company's service quality, they may even suggest more positively to others to come to the salesperson's company, and the salesperson performance has also increased since then (Yeo et al., 2019). It needs to be focused on building customer orientation for today's company because of its challenges to their revenue and profitability (Feng et al., 2019; Pekovic and Rolland, 2016). Customer needs is constantly changing over time, therefore, negligence in collecting customer information can lead to misdirection, which not only greatly affects company resources but also leads to negative reviews from customer, thereby reducing sales performance and company image. Overall, it is undeniable the role of customer orientation for customer perceptions and its significant impact on the quality of sales interactions (Aburayya et al., 2020; Franke and Park, 2006; Jaramillo and Grisaffe, 2009; Tseng, 2018). Therefore, a good customer-oriented strategy requires harmonious coordination of the functional parts of an organisation, and especially the high degree of accuracy in collecting customer information that can facilitate the long-term development of customer-interaction relationships and firm's profit. Corresponding to the above discussion, it can be argued that customer orientation is the main factor of salesperson performance, is closely related to customer perception. Thus, develop a hypothesis as follows:

H3: Customer orientation has a positive effect on salesperson's performance.

H4: Customer orientation has a positive effect on value-based selling.

3.3.3. Value-based selling

To be able to adapt and thrive in today's business environment, managers have changed from product-focused sales to engaging in value-based selling (Mullins et al., 2020; Töytäri and

Rajala 2015). Value-based selling plays a pivotal role in assisting salespeople to understand and define the customer's business model, deliver value propositions, communicate value (Kienzler et al., 2018; Terho et al., 2015). It is as a solution to help companies effectively interact and respond to the value of products/services for customers (Terho et al., 2017). Value-based selling is appreciated by academics not only for its ability to generate customer's growth and financial value, but also for the positive influence it has on the salespeople performance (Aberdeen Group 2011; Davies, 2017; Mullins et al., 2020; Terho et al. 2017).

Value-based selling is an effective method to build and develop lasting relationships with customers (Kienzler et al., 2018; Terho et al., 2012, 2015; Töytäri and Rajala, 2015), focuses on the importance of the seller-customer interaction to create value, and is an integral part of value co-creation logic (Baumann and Le Meunier-FitzHugh, 2014; Haas et al., 2012; Itani et al., 2022; Liu and Zhao, 2020). It requires salesperson to collaborate with their customers to develop effective offerings and communicate how their company can contribute to their customers' success. Thus, in various literatures, it is identified as a key ingredient of successful salesperson behaviours as well as their sales performance (Baumann and Le Meunier-FitzHugh, 2014; Mullins et al., 2020; Terho et al., 2015).

In addition, focusing on selling value means saving costs for customers (Mullin et al., 2019). Salespeople with good value-based selling abilities can help customers make informed purchasing decisions so that they can significantly save on costs associated with predictable processes, thereby forming customer satisfaction and trust (Terho et al., 2015). More broadly, investing in value-based selling not only improves new product productivity, increases salesperson performance, but also strengthens business operations. Possessing high value-based selling capabilities allows salespeople to identify, promote, and improve customer awareness of new products, increasing adoption and their demand for these products (Adamson et al., 2012, Keränen and Jalkala, 2013; Kuester et al., 2017; Reymen et al. 2015) more easily. When a high-value offering is made, the customer should have the incentive and compelling reason to buy even at a price premium (Töytäri et al., 2011). This leads to

positive contributions to company's revenue growth and their own sales performance (Fu et al., 2010; Sjöblom, 2016). From the above findings, the hypothesis is:

H5: Value-based selling has a positive effect on salesperson's performance.

3.3.4. Sales skills

Researchers (Ford et al., 1987; Jhamb et al., 2021) found that sales skills are knowledge owned by salespeople, which helps them to achieve their sales goals in a favourable way, is an important factor in promoting competition among salespeople (Yang et al., 2016). According to Pettijohn et al. (2002), sales skills help salespeople allocate sales time and identify ways to support customers more effectively. Jhamb et al. (2021) also acknowledge that sales skills are the basis for forming exchange relationships in business, helping to bring better impressions to buyers. Salespersons need to improve their sales skills continuously to approach and serve customers more professionally. This not only helps customers feel more satisfied when owning the company's product/service, but also helps the company improve profit (Armstrong, 2009; Malau, 2017; Terho et al., 2015). Good application of sales skill has positive implications for salesperson performance because it helps seller demonstrate their strength and professionalism in selling, thereby establishing trust and persuading buyer effectively (Chen and Jaramillo, 2014; Hardjati and Febrianita, 2019; Singh and Venugopal, 2015; Singh et al., 2017).

In addition, as discussed in literature review, there are several key aspects of sales skills such as interpersonal skill, salesmanship skill, technological skill, and marketing skill, which can positively or negatively impact customer perception. For example, not all seller have the same communication skills, nor are they all able to provide good benefits to customer and resolve conflicts in sales interactions effectively (Barsil et al., 2010; Wachner et al., 2009), accordingly, comprehension and effective use of interpersonal skills can increase sales and improve customer communication of both company values and the advantages of products/services (Borg and Johnston, 2013; Islam et al., 2016; Hargie, 2010). In addition, the value of interpersonal skill becomes even more important to managers as it allows them

to communicate and influence employees, support for the development of relationships both inside and outside the company (Beenen et al., 2018).

Likewise, salespeople who have salesmanship skills and technical skills have an upper hand in finding and approaching potential customers, driving their buying decisions and generating revenue (Amor, 2019; Román and Rodríguez, 2015). Possessing high quality of sales skills not only supports the growth of the company's goods needs and competitive advantage, but also allows salespeople to establish trust with customer, reinforce their decision-making, as well as enhance sales performance (Abdolvand and Farzaneh, 2013; Akaeze and Akaeze, 2017; Groza et al., 2016; Islam et al., 2016).

Besides, marketing skills are no exception because they have a strong impact on business revenue. Researchers (Kimura et al., 2019) agree that possessing a wealth of customer knowledge helps salespeople to be more successful. Using proficient marketing skills allows salespeople to be confident and responsive to work in complex environment, to understand and support customer effectively, thereby increasing customer interactions and sales performance (Amor, 2019; Basir et al., 2010; Van Scheers, 2011). In accordance with the above discussion, it can be argued that sales skills are a key element of salesperson performance, having a strong influence on consumer perception. Therefore, the hypothesis is given as follows:

H6: Sales skills have a positive effect on salesperson performance.

3.3.5. Sales characteristics

According to Han (2020); Penney et al. (2011), salesperson characteristics or personality traits related to an individual's aptitude and perception of his surroundings, are the psychological factors that are relatively stable to help form a successful salesperson. In another study by Barrick and Mount (1991), Lounsbury et al. (2003), salesperson characteristics are highly valued by managers, especially important as "general mental ability" in the recruitment process. Salesperson characteristic is a well-known multi-

dimensional concept, as a factor that reflects the salesperson himself in work performance, which can help salespeople more easily reach customers and close sales (Barrick, 2005; Janowski, 2018).

In addition, the important factors discussed in chapter II such as empathetic ability, cue perception and modification ability also partly highlighted the value and necessity of personality for salespeople. These characteristics refer to salesperson's good feelings, concern and understanding to customers (empathy), the ability to perceive and identify different signals in customer interaction (cue perception), and self-adjusting behaviour in a positive way to suit different sales situations (modification). Employee empathy is also highly valued by researchers for its positive impact on sales behaviours such as listening and sharing (Anaza et al., 2018; Wondra et al., 2015), adaptive sales (Amenuvor et al., 2021; Spiro and Weitz, 1990). A salesperson who empathises with customers will be able to put themselves in other people's positions to think, perceive, and more effectively support their customers' purchasing decisions. As Ahearne et al. (2007, p. 606) said, empathy describes the employee's concern for the customer's interests, which stimulates positive social interactions (Anaza et al., 2018). Thus, this not only causes favourable effects on trust and long-term customer relationships, but also represents a higher degree of adaptive sales behaviour of employees (Anaza et al., 2018; Bahadur et al., 2018; Bahadur et al., 2020).

Moreover, the ability to perceive cues during customer interaction is also highly valued in the personal selling field, providing many advantages for successful sales (Giacobbe et al., 2006; Puccinelli et al., 2010). Cue perception ability is a higher level of customer listening (Clopton et al., 2001), related to the salesperson's sense and responsiveness in each customer interaction situation. A successful salesperson can always assess situations from the customer's perspective, approach the customer in the right way, and close the deal at the right time. Some researchers (Drollinger and Comer, 2013; Delpechitre et al., 2018) stated that good perception of situational cues can help salesperson read and understand cues in customer behaviour, thereby approaching and providing products and services that best suit the needs of customers. This improves customer satisfaction, purchasing decisions, as well as

exhibiting a higher degree of adaptive selling behaviour (Herpertz et al., 2016; Kidwell et al., 2007; Stock and Hoyer, 2005).

Similarly, the ability to modify self-presentation is also one of the important dimensions of self-monitoring and was found to have a positive relationship with adaptive sales and sales performance (Alnakhli et al., 2020; Deeter-Schmelz and Sojka, 2007; Spiro and Weitz, 1990). It is considered as the moderator in the relationship between adaptive selling behaviour (ASB) and salesperson performance (Weitz, 1981). An individual with a high ability to modify self-presentation can flexibly adapt to different sales situations, adjust their behaviour and image in the way that they expect to be seen by others so that he/ she can approach and respond well to the needs of customers, and effectively implement the service exchange process. As a result, salespeople with great ability to modify self-presentation are more likely to engage better in adaptive selling, achieve higher performance and be more successful than those who lack this ability. From the above discussion, we argue that salesperson characteristics act as important moderators in the relationship between adaptive sales behaviour and salesperson performance, having a strong influence on consumer perception. Therefore, the hypothesis is put forwards as follows:

H7: Sales characteristics have a positive effect on adaptive selling behaviour.

3.3.6. Experience

The salesperson's experience is becoming increasingly essential and indispensable in today's era. It is a factor to create sales effectiveness and competitive advantage for the company as experience helps sellers adjust their behaviour and perceptions in customer interactions; and, especially in the face of today's high customer demand, only organisations with experienced salespeople can satisfy customers and sell effectively (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020). Experience is key to customer relationships. Experience allows sellers to interact more easily with customers, dealing better with sales situations. Seasoned experience of sales staff is emphasised through the studies (Rapp et al., 2006; Sign et al., 2013; García-Chas et al., 2015). Rich experience means increasing work knowledge, developing better adaptive sales,

thereby building relationships with customers effectively, increasing sales performance (Giacobbe et al., 2006; Groza and Groza, 2018).

The seller's experience influences the customer's perception and decision to buy. In other words, salespeople with different experiences will be able to perform different jobs with different meanings. Specifically, authors (Agnihotri et al., 2009; Pöyry et al., 2021) found that experience is positively correlated with employee performance in adaptive sales. In addition, today's companies focus on using modern technology tools such as CRM (digital tools) to build sales strategies and reach customers (Nelson et al., 2020). This also requires high experience from the sales staff to be able to use these technology tools well and exploit customer information effectively. Unlike employees with little or no experience, salespeople with a lot of experience can be proficient in contact with technology tools, easily track consumer buying behaviour as well as capture the needs of prospects (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Ogilvie et al., 2018). Furthermore, these salespeople have a deep understanding of adaptive selling, more effectively combining the benefits gained from the CRM tool, leading to sales success and increased performance (Hughes et al., 2013; Rapp et al., 2015). Therefore, it can be seen that the role of experience is important to salespeople, tied to employees' ability to use sales technology and efficiency in adaptive selling. From the above findings, the next hypothesis is:

H8: Experience has a positive effect on adaptive selling behaviour.

3.3.7. Adaptive selling behaviour

Adaptive selling is essential for business today, and several researchers have shown its influence on overall customer perceptions of company value (Ahearne et al., 2005; Alavi et al., 2019; Jaramillo et al., 2007). Adaptive selling behaviour is an important antecedent to forming and improving salesperson performance (Kimura et al., 2019). Adaptive selling is used in companies as a sales strategy to read customer mind and behaviour (Verbeke et al., 2011). Adaptive salespeople are more likely to comprehend their customers' requirements and desires in any circumstance (Limbu et al., 2016). Additionally, they want to

communicate more effectively with consumers and cater to the various demands of potential clients (Amenuvor et al., 2021). Thence, customers also have positive thoughts and are more engaged with sellers because they perceive the concerns and benefits during the transaction process. Adaptive selling not only has a powerful impact on sales, increases customer trust and satisfaction, but also aids in establishing loyalty, enhancing future purchase intent, as well as maintaining strong relationships with customers (Chen and Jaramillo, 2014; Kaynak et al., 2016; Román and Martín, 2014; Rakesh et al., 2017; Sergio and Pedro, 2014; Weck and Ivanova, 2013).

Adaptive selling is indispensable for a salesperson's success because of its importance in fostering long-term positive relationships with customers (Baptista, 2014; Kara et al., 2015; Speakman and Ryals, 2012). It has a great impact on salespeople's flexibility in communication, listening, presentation, and problem-solving based on the type of customer and their actual needs (Agnihotri et al., 2017; Chen and Jaramillo 2014). A number of studies (Jaramillo et al., 2007; Itani et al., 2017; Sign and Das, 2013) also demonstrate a positive relationship between adaptive sales and salesperson performance. Adaptive selling can also help make a difference to the business operation, especially for today's retail business. It enables senior managers to more closely exploit and track customer and salesperson's data, training in-depth their salespeople so that they can adapt to the needs of customers flexibly (Charoensukmongkol, 2020). Therefore, participation in adaptive selling needs more and more attention. Organisation with different business forms should exploit different customisations to build a sustainable relationship with customer. Scholars (Keillor et al., 2000; Rakesh et al., 2017) on adaptive selling behaviour shows that it can help to create an effective impression on customers under specific situations. Therefore, based on the discussion about the implications of adaptive sales, its relationship to salesperson performance and the suitability for the research context, the hypothesis is given as follows:

H9: Adaptive selling behaviour has a positive effect on salespeople's performance.

3.4. BENEFITS OF THE SALESPERSON PERFORMANCE (CONSEQUENCES)

A thorough understanding of how to maintain and grow relationships in customer interactions is extremely important for companies in today's competitive environment. Organisations are increasingly placing more emphasis on salesperson performance as a core factor for measuring their success and competitive advantage over their industry peers (Hossain et al., 2016). Salesperson performance is important to ensure all plans and goals are accomplished and the company continues to grow in a positive direction.

In essence, salesperson performance plays a crucial role in driving seller-customer interaction efforts (Bagozzi, 1980). The more outstanding the performance, the higher the customer's perception of the company's quality. The next section discusses the anticipation of future interaction as the primary outcome of sales performance. Sales performance will also be particularly emphasised as an important factor in shaping the customer's anticipation of future interactions as well as repurchase intentions.

3.4.1. Salesperson performance and anticipation of future interaction

Anticipation of future interaction is considered a goal of many business and relationship encounters, related to the nature of the intended relationship between customers and salespeople, in which demonstrates a customer's desire to stay or leave in relation to a seller who previously served them, if there is a need for repurchase (Kennedy et al., 2001; Crosby et al., 1990). Anticipation of future interaction studies focus on the effects of sales behaviour on customers' intention to interact as well as the relationship between sellers and buyers (Román and Iacobucci, 2010). Different customers will have different perceptions of the company's service quality. Service quality was found to have a significant influence on customer relationship quality, satisfaction, and future interaction intentions (Chi et al., 2020; Han and Hyun, 2015; Oh and Kim, 2017). It plays an important role in determining a company's distinctive qualities and enhancing its competitive advantage over its peers (Gogoi and Jyoti, 2020).

As an important part of relationship marketing, salespeople should know "whether purchases are intensifying or waning, expanding or contracting" (Dwyer et al., 1987, p.24), how to achieve high sales performance and organisational goals (Chakrabarty et al., 2013). Research by Hung et al. (2003) and Obiageli et al. (2015) states that salesperson performance is associated with good interaction and good service delivery, is the focal point for the formation of customer perceptions and is the decisive factor for the achievement of organisational goals. Good interpersonal interactions have also been shown to have a positive effect on the desire to maintain relationships and interdependence between partners (Håkansson, 1982).

Customers' perception of the company must be based on the quality of services they are provided with, those related to their long-term value and aligned with the central goals of the organisation (Dutton, et al., 1994; Ryu and Han, 2010). The salesperson's dynamism throughout the sales interaction enhances the customer's awareness and assessment of the salesperson's efforts to create a long-term commitment (Frazier, 1983). Salespeople's high effort is intrinsically linked to customer satisfaction and their ability to continue a relationship (Biong, 1993; Fornell 1992; Kranton 1996).

Anticipation of future interaction is found to be an important feature in the relationship between seller and buyer and influences the bargaining behaviour between the two parties (Rubin and Brown, 1975). It is considered a good signal for the growth of sustained customer connections with the company (Dewnarain et al., 2019; Oliver, 1997). Salesperson performance can play an important role in influencing that intention (Netemeyer et al., 2005). This leads to the following hypothesis:

H10: Salesperson performance has a positive effect on customer' anticipation of future interaction.

3.4.2. Anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention

Salesperson performance as an indicator of service quality and a company's value to customers (Hartline et al., 2003; Nunkoo et al., 2020), and is an important factor in shaping competitive advantage for the company (Dey et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2016). Repurchase intention of customers is extremely important, is the basic expression of customer loyalty (Mittal and Kamukura, 2001). Customers with the intention to repurchase in the future often bring greater value to the company than the initial purchase (Griffis et al., 2012), which increases the likelihood of revenue growth, shareholder value, and can positively influence a company's long-term development strategy in the market (Bindroo and Echambadi, 2016; Chou and Hsu, 2016; Larivière et al., 2016).

Salesperson performance has a positive impact on company goals and growth (Bolander et al., 2021; Johnston, 2003), which has great implications for loyalty and repurchase of customers (Buciuniene and Skudiene (2015). In addition to competitive advantage, it can enhance profitability and positively impact customer perception (Baldauf and Cravens, 2002). Organisations tend to invest in customer retention rather than acquiring new customers because it is less expensive (Spreng et al., 1995; Eklof et al., 2020) and satisfied customers are often loyal and likely to make repeat purchases (Reynolds and Beatty, 1999; LaBarbera and Mazursky, 1983; Patterson and Spreng, 1997).

The relationship between customers' perception, their satisfaction and trust in the service provided as well as the intention to repurchase in the future is shown through social interaction theory. Social interaction is a driver of behaviour (Yin et al., 2019), involving trust and reciprocation (Blau, 2017). Research by Blau (2017) also shows that the customer's relationship with the company is formed based on their perception of fairness and balance in the process of negotiated exchange or reciprocation. Therefore, it can be said that when the perception (customer satisfaction) for the company's services is compatible with their expectations, trust and reciprocation will be formed in the future. Accordingly, a customer's

future repurchase intention is a composite of service satisfaction (Javed and Wu, 2020), retailer trust and perceived risk (Yin et al., 2019).

Sales behaviour and performance of salespeople act as important mediators for the formation of motivation and perception of sales performance outcomes. The repurchase intention of customers is the key to determining the success of a business, related to the subjective judgements and evaluations of customers to stay and maintain long-term relationships with current service provider leave them in the future (Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003; Jones and Taylor, 2007; Hellier et al., 2003). Customer tends to form intention to continue using based on perceived usefulness of products/services for their needs (Bhattacharjee, 2001; Davis et al., 1989). Customer trust in retailers also drives customer repurchase intentions (Gefen et al., 2003; Zboja and Voorhees, 2006).

Customers repurchase intention is the result of trust, satisfaction (Rose et al., 2012; Khalifa and Liu, 2007) and the experience that an individual has over a period of time (Igbariavet al., 1995). Furthermore, the trust that customers gain with the company is due to the experience with the company's products and services (Amyx et al., 2016; Walter et al., 2000) and the level of interaction (Prentice et al., 2019; So et al., 2016, Van Doorn et al., 2010). These behaviours also contribute positively to the identification of loyal customers for the company. Salesperson interaction intensity not only promotes customer trust by giving customers useful information and enabling them to predict potential outcomes (Shadab, 2012), but it also reflects salespeople's efforts in retaining positive communication with customers, thereby fostering a dedication to a long-term relationship (Herjanto and Amin, 2020).

There is a difference between a customer's intended future interaction and their repurchase intention. Anticipation of future interaction is considered cognitive, emotional (Hollebeek et al., 2011; Vivek et al., 2014) and/or customer behaviour with a company (Hollebeek et al., 2014; So et al., 2016a, So et al., 2016b), reflects a stable relationship (Sarmiento et al., 2015). On the other hand, repurchase intention is "customer persistence probability" (Davidow,

2003) or a consumer's actual ability to act (Dodds et al., 1991) to purchase a product/service based on their prior experience (Cho, 2015).

As stated by Ho and Chung (2020), interaction as a form of driving customer perception towards the company, and high engagement also leads to higher loyalty (Palmatier et al., 2006). The customer's anticipation of future interaction is recognised as the consequence of a productive interaction relationship, which is positively related to the customer's repurchase intention (Zhang et al., 2008). Furthermore, in studies of customer loyalty and repurchase intention, the frequent interaction of sellers and customers described in terms of sharing product information and knowledge can help build a close relationship between seller and customer, which increases customer confidence and intention to repurchase in the future (Agag and El-Masry, 2016; Cho, 2015). Proximity positively affects attitude (Gwinner et al., 1998). Also, research by De Wulf et al. (2001) reported that close relationships tend to influence the future repurchase intention of customers.

From the above discussion, it can be seen that the higher the level of interaction, the more positively the customer's perception and evaluation of the company will be, since then, trust is strengthened and an intention to repurchase in the future is formed. Therefore, the following hypothesis would be formulated as follows:

H11: Anticipation of future interaction has a positive effect on customer's repurchase intention.

3.4.3. Salesperson performance and satisfaction with salesperson

Customer satisfaction with the salesperson is defined as a result of a business meeting between seller and buyer, demonstrating the subjective customer perception and assessment before and after using a company's product/ service (Amyx et al., 2016; Crosby et al. 1990; Liang and Chen, 2009; Roos et al., 2006; Román and Iacobucci, 2010), and has a major impact on the future customer needs and the firm's profit (Anderson et al., 1994; Bhattacharya et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2019). Salesperson performance should increase

customer satisfaction with salespeople because it is likened to an important bridge to convey value and improve customers' perception of the company's service quality (Bitner, 1990; Hartline et al., 2003; Nunkoo et al., 2020).

Salesperson performance is a combination of a seller's ability, effort, and opportunity to provide good experiences on service interactions for customer (Obiageli et al., 2015). It is also related to the salesperson's behaviour, judgement and assessment of the sales situation (Ilgen and Schneider, 1991). These activities and behaviours of salespeople are vital in selling interaction to satisfy customer demands and have been proven to have a favourable influence on customer impression and their satisfaction with salesperson (Bettencourt and Brown, 1997; Hartline et al., 2003; Oliver and Swan, 1989b) as well as firm growth performance (Klep et al., 2013). It also demonstrates the success of the seller-buyer relationship (Bateman and Valentine, 2019). Salespeople who pay attention to customer demands, behave in a trustworthy manner, and sympathise with and understand customer needs are important aspects driving customer engagement intention and cultivating long-lasting ties (Beatty et al., 1996; Dewnarain et al., 2019; Schneider and Bowen 1999).

According to Crittenden (2015), Itani et al. (2017), Wong and Tjosvold (2015), high customer orientation and good adaptive sales behaviour of salespeople can increase customer satisfaction through clearly understanding customer needs, adjusting strategies, messages, and approaches to better suit the tastes of buyers. Research by McFarland et al. (2006) emphasises that adaptive salespeople can use or modify behaviours at will to attract interaction-oriented buyers. Besides, researchers (Futrell, 2008; Oliver and Swan, 1989; Román and Ruiz, 2005) acknowledge that the positive salespeople's behaviour is also proportional to customer satisfaction. Limbu et al. (2016) also stated that successful salespeople know how to put themselves in the customer's situation, and understand the customer's problems, thereby solving the needs and forming satisfaction in the customer's mind. Thus, the above behaviours not only enhance the ability to communicate with customers, help to effectively solve customers' problems with the company's products and services, but also can promote purchasing decisions quickly, and therefore, enhancing customer satisfaction. From the above discussion, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H12: Salesperson performance is positively related to customer satisfaction with salespeople.

H13: Satisfaction with salesperson has a positive effect on anticipation of future interaction.

3.4.4. Salesperson performance and trust in salesperson

Customer trust in salesperson is associated with the seller's entrepreneurial abilities defined as the customer's belief, expectation in the seller's attitude and honesty to provide benefits consistent with customer's expectations (Crosby et al., 1990; Sengupta et al., 2000; Sumaedi et al., 2015). It represents the customer's desire to continue working with that seller in the future when the need arises instead of switching to a new one (Morgan and Hunt, 1994). According to Román and Ruiz (2005), a customer's trust in a seller is an invaluable asset to help maintain and grow a relationship and is not based on a single interaction. Trust, in other words, is developed through many interactions between the seller and the buyer, in which the customer feels the seller's competence, responsibility, fairness in the transaction, as well as the seller's interest and sincerity towards them. Scholars (Amyx et al., 2016; Walter et al., 2000) show that trust in salespeople represents the customer's preference, positive perception, and desire to continue dealing with sellers in the future. Customer satisfaction is also the foundation for trust in salespeople (Garbarino and Johnson, 1999; Román and Ruiz, 2005).

Establishing customer trust in the first stage of the interaction process is extremely important; and ethical, value-based, or empathetic selling behaviours can be prominent behaviours that have a strong impact on salesperson performance and help gain customer trust. Cultivating and adjusting appropriate sales behaviours is necessary for salespeople to establish and maintain long-term customer interactions with the company (Hansen and Riggle, 2009; Román and Ruiz, 2005). From previous discussions about adaptive sales behaviour, or the ability to listen to customers, researchers demonstrate that adaptive salespeople have the ability to capture and understand customer signals promptly, apply the right tactics, and solve customer problems effectively (Limbu et al., 2016).

Furthermore, a salesperson who focuses on value-based sales can easily gain customer trust through listening and deep understanding of customer problems, thereby helping them make the best choices, addressing their long-term needs as well as effectively saving costs (Terho et al., 2012). Or, possessing empathy also helps salespeople gain customer satisfaction (Aggarwal et al., 2005; Iyer and Muncy, 2004). Sellers with high empathy always know how to care and share their views, and customers are more likely to feel sincerity from these sellers than those who are not empathetic. Salesperson empathy increases feelings of trust and reduces anxiety and promotes information sharing by customers (Kwon and Suh, 2004). Researchers have also acknowledged a correlation between these behaviours and trust in salesperson (Beatty et al., 1996; Kennedy et al., 2001). These behaviour increases sales performance, the level of customer evaluation and trust in salespeople, significantly supports the customer's intention to interact in the future (Alavi et al., 2019; Kaynak et al., 2016; Rakesh et al., 2017; Rippé et al., 2016).

Besides, scholar (Huarng and Yu, 2019; Lee and Dubinsky, 2003) reported the higher the customer satisfaction with the seller, the greater the repeat purchase intention. It helps build loyalty and fosters their desire to continue interacting in the future (Min et al., 2020; Ramsay and Sohi, 1997). Researchers (Aggarwal et al., 2005; Fornell 1992; Reynolds and Arnold 2000; Reynolds and Beatty, 1999) also support this correlation. These discussions put forwards the following hypotheses:

H14: Salesperson performance has a positive impact on customer trust in salespeople.

H15: Trust in salesperson has a positive effect on customer's anticipation of future interaction.

H16: Satisfaction with salesperson has a positive effect on trust in salesperson.

3.5. SUMMARY

By examining the importance of salesperson performance on consumer perception, this study gives certain implications to the development of a shopping mall. This study provides a more holistic view to see if the more positive a customer's perception of salesperson performance is, the more positive the customer's intention to engage in future and repurchase intention. This chapter has reviewed the literature on the salesperson performance and integrated insights from different fields in order to construct the conceptual framework illustrated in Figure 3.1. The relationship between salesperson performance and its antecedents and consequences is explored based on the literature, and important hypotheses are given in Table 3.1 and Figure 3.1. The hypotheses and conceptual framework revealed the varied connections between the study constructs in the integrative framework presented. The next chapter describes the research design which is used to increase construct scales and test the suggested model.

Table 3. 1: List of research hypotheses based the research questions

Hypotheses	
RQ: What is the impact of specific antecedents of salesperson performance on anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention data?	
Question 1: What are the factors that influence salesperson performance?	
H1	Sales strategy has a positive effect on the salesperson's customer orientation.
H2	Sales strategy has a positive effect on salesperson's value-based selling.
H3	Customer orientation has a positive effect on salesperson's performance.
H4	Customer orientation has a positive effect on value-based selling.
H5	Value-based selling has a positive effect on salesperson's performance.
H6	Sales skills have a positive effect on salesperson performance.
H7	Sales characteristics have a positive effect on adaptive selling behaviour.
H8	Experience has a positive effect on adaptive selling behaviour.
H9	Adaptive selling behaviour has a positive effect on salespeople performance.
Question 2: What are the main influences of salesperson performance on anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention?	
H10	Salesperson performance has a positive impact on customer' anticipation of future interaction.
H11	Anticipation of future interaction has a positive impact on customer's repurchase intention
H12	Salesperson performance is positively related to customer satisfaction with salespeople

H13	Satisfaction with salesperson has a positive impact on anticipation of future interaction
H14	Salesperson performance has a positive impact on customer trust in salespeople
H15	Trust in salesperson has a positive impact on customer's anticipation of future interaction
H16	Satisfaction with salesperson has a positive impact on trust in salesperson

CHAPTER IV: METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH DESIGN

4.1. INTRODUCTION

The objective of this chapter is to present and explain in detail the selection of research methodologies and design that are used in the essay to assess reliability and validity of hypothetical relationships, as well as the conceptual model developed in the research. In order to clarify the problems raised in the research question and to prove the experimental nature of the proposed model, the layout of this chapter will be formed as follows: Section 4.2 describes the research design as well as presents the rationale for the selection of the current research methodology. Section 4.3 presents research design and data collection methods. Exploratory fieldwork, overview of quantitative, qualitative, and sampling studies are presented in sections 4.4 and 4.5. The population study, size, and sampling method, as well as questionnaire design are presented in 4.6 and 4.7 respectively. In 4.8 describes the data analysis and processing methods, as well as the statistical software and tools used for the study. Finally, the issues related to ethics and the reliability of the research are also considered in section 4.9, accompanied by a summary for the entire chapter.

4.2. JUSTIFICATION OF THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology or paradigm is a series of systematic operations that are designed to support investigation and evaluation of phenomenon in a most comprehensive way based on research results (Bryman, 2012; Lincoln and Guba, 2000). Choosing the right research method is extremely important, allowing researchers to quickly gather data with more accurate results, and is seen as an indispensable procedure for each author's study (Kumar, 2018; Snyder, 2019; Saunders et al., 2009).

Paradigm has a great significance in marketing research as it relates to the researcher's belief about their worldview (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006; Morgan, 2007). Paradigm is defined as thoughts, or a set of researchers' beliefs about an object, specific research topics they are

interested in, and it influences the view, implementation, and results of that study (Jonker and Pennink 2010; Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Some researchers argue that research paradigm is a particular construct of researcher beliefs and perceptions, or a process with a series of highly precise stages to guide the author's research actions (Denzin and Lincoln, 2000; Guba and Lincoln, 1994; Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017)

According to Guba and Lincoln (1998), research paradigm can be distinguished in different ways through the three main philosophical aspects that are closely related, such as epistemology, ontology and methods. Epistemology is the assumption that researchers use to investigate the truth or relationship between human knowledge and acquiring knowledge, it is related to the nature and forms of knowledge in the world (Hiller, 2016; Sheth and Parvatiyar, 2002). It assists in establishing and shaping authors' beliefs about research data, providing broader insights to answer the research issue. Ontology is the assumption that is made to consider the nature and meaning of an objective reality that really exists (Schalley et al., 2019; Scotland, 2012). Ontology not only provides important insights into the things that constitute the world (Scott and Usher, 2011) but also plays an important role in forming orientations to approach research problems effectively (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). The methodology paradigm is a systematic set of different methods, approaches, or processes used in different research contexts to understand the real world; it is concerned with the techniques and questions utilised in an investigation to gather valuable knowledge in order to answer the research problems (Creswell, 2003; Guba and Lincoln, 1998; Gupta et al., 2011).

Different researchers with different philosophical views and research topics will have dissimilar methodological choices. It is necessary to define and apply research philosophy in scientific research to help the researcher in the formation and development of new ideas and knowledge from research content (Saunders et al., 2009; Žukauskas et al., 2018). There are four classification trends of research philosophy that are often proposed by the authors in their studies, namely: positivism, interpretivism/ constructivism/ idealism/ phenomenology, realism, and pragmatism (Corbetta, 2003; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003).

- a. Positivism is known as the natural science approach, the most popular and the oldest method up to now. Positivist approaches are perceived as a measurable social factor, often used to analyse, and respond to real-world problems, and have a significant effect on the behaviour of an individual (Collins and Hussey, 2009). Positivism is used in social studies to develop new knowledge related to a particular topic by applying the deductive method and quantitative research which is highly structured and objective (Creswell, 2003). Accordingly, close-ended questionnaires, structured interviews, and official statistics are often the methods used for positivism. Also, hypotheses testing, measuring the influence and relationship between variables are also suitable processes that are commonly applied in this approach (Fisher, 2004).
- b. Interpretivism is related to empathic stance and people's perceptions of the real society they live in (Saunders et al., 2007, 2009). Interpretivism in social studies developed to seek and better understand the meaning of the subjective experiences of individuals during their social interaction (Carson et al., 2001, p.5; Guba and Lincoln, 1989; Neuman, 2003). Interpretivist research, therefore, focuses mainly on interacting directly with the participant. Besides, according to Deshpande (1983), the outside world is likened to a qualitative model. Interpretivism approaches typically involve inductive hypotheses and humanistic qualitative methods (Altheide et al., 2011; Guba et al., 1994). Thus, the unstructured interview (in-depth interview), observing the participant are the common methods used to perform for interpretivism.
- c. Realism research philosophy is mainly based on human senses, related to abstract concepts, perspectives, and statements about the independence of the real world in human perception. In other words, only observations can help people to understand and approach reality (Blackburn, 2005).
- d. Pragmatism is a research reflexive, used in scientific studies to address the questions and problems under investigation and provide opportunities for future practice (Morgan, 2007). Pragmatic approach focuses on the meaning of knowledge and practical behaviour in a particular context, beliefs, and possible consequences (Alise

and Teddlie, 2010; Biesta, 2010). Pragmatism often comes with a mixed method of quantitative and qualitative research as a pragmatic approach that these researchers use to shed light on the actual behaviour of participants.

Table 4. 1: Research paradigms

	Positivist	Phenomenological	Realism	Pragmatism
Basic beliefs	The world is external, objective and perceived	The world is socially constructed and subjective	The world is socially constructed and under constant influence of intrinsic.	The world is ambiguous, constantly debated over its usefulness in different situations
Preferred methods include	Observer is independent	Observer is part of what is observed		
	Science is value-free	Science is driven by human interests	Science plays an important role	Science is value-free
	Focus on facts	Focus on meanings	Focus on observation to approach reality	Focus on practical action and change
	Look for causality and fundamental laws	Try to understand what is happening	Try to understand social factors and real life	Learn about human behaviour, predict the causes and consequences of different behaviours
	Reduce phenomenon to simplest elements	Look at the totality of each situation		
	Formulate hypotheses and then test them	Develop ideas through induction from data		
		Taking large	Small samples	Methods chosen must

	samples, survey, experiment	investigated in depth (interview) or over time	fit the subject matter, quantitative or qualitative, interview, focus group, observation	or qualitative can be used (interview, survey), which is fit the purpose or subject matter
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In scientific study, positivism and interpretivism are the two main epistemological assumptions and are also encouraged by Deshpande (1983) and Foroudi et al. (2021) to use together to be able to approach the research topic in the most accurate way as well as avoiding method-bias, causing variation in the responses (not due to the actual tendency of the participants) when using only a single paradigm in the investigation. Research by Rosenhead and Mingers (2001) also suggests that each different paradigm and research method can provide different answers and important aspects of reality, thus, focusing on both positivism and interpretivism paradigm will provide a more general and accurate view of the current research topic.

Combining two models in the research positively supports the author's research. First of all, it helps to form and develop a new scale suitable for measuring elements in marketing research. Using idealism and qualitative methods for the first stage of this investigation (in-depth interview) helps to pinpoint the core variables that are influencing salesperson performance, and whether salesperson performance can have an impact on customer satisfaction and purchasing power. What are the main effects of salesperson performance as a functional quality factor on the purpose of meeting customer satisfaction? Applying qualitative research also allows the author to collect the necessary preliminary information for the research topic, create and verify the reliability of the scale to help test the hypotheses (quantitative research) later. Next, using the positivism paradigm will help test the proposed hypotheses and their relationship, as well as verify the scale in the study to allow the author to collect and interpret data objectively, improve research reliability and comprehensiveness (Bryman, 2006).

In order to choose a suitable paradigm for the research topic, research questions and objectives are always the prerequisites that need to be carefully considered. The following

are some of the prerequisites for applying the qualitative method (inductive) for this inquiry. First, there are several appropriate scales identified to measure the performance of salespeople in shopping malls. The elements of strategy, personality traits, or skills of salespeople are diverse and have different effects on sales interaction results, however, it has not been focused on in-depth investigation and hampered by a lack of overall size (Chaker et al., 2018; Rentz et al., 2002). Therefore, it is necessary to apply the idealism paradigm at the initial stage of the study through qualitative research (interview) in order to find out the effect of strategic factors, and salesperson's skills on salesperson performance.

Current research focuses on the statement of Rodriguez et al. (2012) on salesperson performance as a tool to obtain information and capture the purchasing needs of potential customers, and researches (Baldauf and Cravens, 2002; Buciuniene and Skudiene, 2015; Dey et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2016) that salesperson performance gives a great advantage to the company, has a direct effect on sales, productivity, and sustainable competitiveness in the same industry. Besides, because the study does an investigation of customer perceptions towards the shopping mall, therefore, it is necessary to carry out qualitative research to develop the scale and determine the relationship between salesperson performance and its implications for the customer's anticipation of future interactions and repurchase intention. This also assists with further theory and hypothesis testing steps.

In addition, for the claims of Bitner (1990), Hartline et al. (2003) and Nunkoo et al. (2020), salesperson performance as a signal of a company's quality and value to its customers, is an important bridge to raise awareness of customers about the company's service quality, quantitative methods (hypothetico-deductive) will also be considered and applied in this study in order to be able to quantify, test, and more rationally complement the above theories rather than qualitative research (creating theory).

Table 4. 2: Comparison between qualitative and quantitative approach

	Quantitative Research	Qualitative Research
Purpose	<p>Deductive: deals with numbers and statistics</p> <p>Used to test or confirm theories and assumptions.</p> <p>Can be used to establish relationships between variables, and generalisable facts about a topic.</p> <p>Interface from sample to population</p> <p>Common methods: experiments, observations, surveys with closed-ended questions.</p>	<p>Inductive: deals with words and meanings</p> <p>Used to understand concepts, thoughts or experiences of people.</p> <p>Allow to gather and explore in-depth insights on unknown topics.</p> <p>Inductive development of theory</p> <p>Common methods: experiences, or unanticipated events, ideas.</p> <p>interviews with open-ended questions, observations</p>
Research questions	<p>Variance questions</p> <p>Focus on a concept, truth or topic being investigated.</p> <p>Analyse differences between concepts, the degree or frequency of different variables</p> <p>Find out the causes, test hypotheses, and how the effects between the variables.</p> <p>Causality (factual)</p>	<p>Process questions.</p> <p>Focus on discovering and understanding the experiences and meanings of an objective.</p> <p>How and Why</p> <p>Learn about the intend or future outcome around a context or topic.</p> <p>Hypotheses are seen as part of the conceptual framework.</p> <p>Causality (physical)</p>
RESEARCH METHODS		
Relationship	Objectivity/ reduction of influence (research as an extraneous variable)	Use of influence as a tool for understanding (research as part of process)
Sampling	Probability sampling to make statistical inferences. Establishing valid comparisons	Purposeful sampling to gain more insight in the information-rich case
Data collection	Highly objective Structured data collection methods Development of research instruments or test based. Standardisation	Highly subjective Unstructured/ semi-structured data collection techniques Not instruments or tested based, inductive development of strategies.

Data analysis	The data collected can be counted (numerical data)	Adapting to particular situation The data collected cannot be counted (videos, texts, images).
	Statistical analysis. Finding is conclusive and usually descriptive in nature. Statistical hypothesis testing Conversion of textual data into numbers or categories	Non-statistical/ Textual analysis (memos, coding, connecting) Grounded theory Narrative approaches
Reliability/Validity	Reliable Technology as instrument (the evaluator is removed from the data)	Valid Self as instrument (the evaluator is close to the data)
Generalisability	Generalise the findings from a sample to an entire population. The outsider's perspective Population oriented	Generalise the findings is not expected. The insider's perspective Case study oriented

Source: Maxwell and Loomis (2003, p. 190) and Steckler *et al.* (1992).

4.3. SELECTION OF RESEARCH APPROACH

From the above discussion, pluralism research approach will be selected for application to this study. It can be considered as the most ideal method to approach and gain a richer and more comprehensive view of the research problems (Mingers, 2001). Moreover, focusing on positivist approach only to analyse real problems of society will cause certain limitations to the research results, instead, the non-positivist methods also is highly appreciated by researchers for its positive effects on the research process, overcoming weaknesses and promoting the strengths of each method (Deshpande, 1983; Mingers, 2001). Therefore, the research topic will be approached in a perfect way when combining these research methods together.

Combining a variety of methods such as in-depth interviews, questionnaires will actively support the author in exploring and expanding knowledge of events and research topics (Johnson et al., 2007; Palmer and Gallagher, 2007). With the increasingly complex development of real society, researchers often tend to use mixed methods to collect and analyse quantitative and qualitative data in the same research to achieve reliable results and enhance the value of the research topic (Creswell and Clark, 2017; Gupta et al., 2011). The mixed method is evaluated as a harmonious combination between quantitative research in order to measure and test theories (Creswell, 2003), and a part of qualitative research (interview) to gather certain reliable data.

Mixed methods are used in current research to provide positive contributions to the research topic. It allows the collection of quantitative and qualitative data in succession, effectively facilitating the validation of findings throughout the course of the study (Creswell et al., 2003; Längler et al., 2019). Along with that, the above study also shows that mixed method is also applied more flexibly at different stages of investigation (initiation, implementation, integration, and interpretation) instead of at the first stage (data collection) as before. Using the mixed method not only allows the researcher to take full advantage of the potential advantages of quantitative and qualitative method, but also helps to provide more complete evidence in depth and breadth of investigation, improve the reliability and validity of the current research topic (Bryman, 2006; Koller et al., 2017).

Content analysis is a useful method used in this study to analyse qualitative data, interpret, and make valid inferences to convert qualitative data into quantitative data. Following this method, Bryman (2006) provided two schemes to support the merging of both quantitative and qualitative methods by classifying and coding documents. The first scheme is inspired by Greene et al. (1989), and is regarded as an advantage because of its parsimony, "it boils down the possible reasons for conducting multi-strategy research to just five reasons, although the authors' analysis revealed that initiation was uncommon" (Bryman, 2006). Qualitative research plays an important role in this method, allowing researchers to gain a clearer understanding of the complex real world, develop and expand research based on information gathered from participants. Quantitative content analysis helps to summarise and generalise a

large amount of data collected (Bryman, 2017). The weakness of this method is that it only allows the encryption of primary and secondary data (Bengtsson, 2016). Therefore, the 2nd scheme was formed by Bryamn (2006) with the rationales, and they are presented in Table 4.3 as follows:

Table 4. 3: The rationale for combining quantitative and qualitative methods

<u>First scheme</u>	
Triangulation	Convergence, corroboration, correspondence, or outcomes from various techniques. The emphasis in coding triangulation was on improving reliability and exploring the corroboration between quantitative and qualitative data.
Complementarity	Seek an advanced, clear, thorough explanation that can specifically construct and illustrate a phenomenon from one method with results from another.
Development	Seeks to employ the results of one approach to develop or inform the other, where the term "development" has broad connotations including sampling, implementation, and measurement decisions.
Initiation	Seeking out inconsistencies and paradoxes, fresh viewpoints on conceptual frameworks, and synthesising research questions or findings from one approach with questions or findings from another.
Expansion	Seeks to extend the breadth and range of inquiry by applying various methods to various inquiry components.
<u>Second scheme</u>	
Triangulation or greater validity	Refers to the conventional perception that qualitative and quantitative approach could be integrated to triangulate findings and allow them to be mutually corroborated. It was not coded as triangulation if the term was used as a synonym for integrating quantitative and qualitative research.
Offset	Relates to the idea that both quantitative and qualitative research approaches have advantages and disadvantages and that by integrating them, the researcher may balance out certain deficiencies and get from the advantages of

	both approaches.
Completeness	Refers to the idea that utilising both quantitative and qualitative approaches might allow the researcher to generate a more holistic account of the field under investigation.
Process	Quantitative research offers an account of social life's structures, whereas qualitative research delivers a sense of the process.
Different research questions	It is argued that quantitative and qualitative approaches may address respective research questions, nevertheless, this item was only coded if the authors made this claim expressly.
Explanation	The results produced by one method are used to assist in the interpretation of the results produced by the other method.
Unexpected results	Refers to the idea that quantitative and qualitative research can be productively integrated when one produces unexpected results that can be explained by using the other.
Instrument development	Refers to instances where qualitative research is used to form questionnaire and scale items – for example, to come up with more appropriate wording or more in-depth closed responses.
Sampling	Refers to instances where one method is applied to assist the process of sampling favourably.
Credibility	Refers to the idea that using both methods helps to ensure the integrity of the results.
Context	Refers to situations where the combination is rationalised in terms of qualitative research, offering deeper contextual insights, valuable external findings, or broad relationships between variables found through a survey.
Illustration	Refers to the application of qualitative data to explain quantitative results, usually known as putting "meat on the bones" of "dry" quantitative findings.

Utility or improving the usefulness of findings	Refers to the case that integrating the two methods would be more advantageous for practitioners and others, this tends to be more common in articles with applied emphasis.
Confirm and discover	Relates to the value of using qualitative and quantitative data to develop and test hypotheses in a single project, respectively.
Diversity of views	This comprises two relatively distinct rationales, including merging participant and researcher viewpoints through qualitative and quantitative research respectively, and discovering correlations among variables using quantitative research.
Enhancement or building upon quantitative/qualitative findings	This refers to creating more or adding to quantitative or qualitative findings through collecting data according to a qualitative or quantitative method.
Other/unclear	
Not stated	

As stated above, this study combines both positivist and partial realism approaches, so it is necessary to develop an empirical investigation (in-depth interview), as well as conduct quantitative research (questionnaires) to in turn clarify the salesperson performance conceptual model, analyse and generalise findings in a large sample of the investigation. On the other hand, according to author (Creswell et al., 2003), quantitative research is the main approach, which may be prioritised for implementation rather than qualitative research in order to test related theories. The procedures of mixed methods are also illustrated in figure 4.1 as follows:

Figure 4. 1: Mixed methods procedures

In order to improve the validity of the investigation, an inductive approach should be used before the main survey, together with the method of collecting qualitative data to generate hypotheses and purify measures for the questionnaire. Quantitative research is recommended by researchers at an early stage of the investigation (Deshpande, 1983; Gupta et al., 2011). Also, in order to review and test the core theory of current research (salesperson performance is a signal of company's quality and value), quantitative approach is prized rather than qualitative approach at this stage (Foroudi, 2012).

From the above discussions on paradigm positivism and the mixed method, the qualitative approach mentioned in this study was in-depth interview with marketing managers, PhD, MBA students, all of whom are all Vietnamese people living and studying in both Vietnam and the UK and having experience about marketing. Marketing specialists (students/academics) are invited to participate in interviews because of their strong marketing knowledge base and academic perspective. They can provide a wealth of useful information related to the research topic through the knowledge gathered from their excellent academic research. In-store salespeople and managers, who have abundant expertise and practical experience in the field of marketing, can grasp trends and have good customer awareness. The interviewees were marketing specialists (student, academic), and in-store salespersons,

managers not only provided a great source of information on the current research topic that benefitted the development of the framework and the main survey, but also showed the importance of research as proof of the strong connection between academic research and real-life markets. Qualitative research is a suitable method and is particularly invested in this research because the concepts of salesperson performance are still ambiguous and of little interest, qualitative approaches are used to make this construct more clearly defined. Besides, to explore a new field that is little or unknown, researchers also recommend a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods (Deshpande, 1983; Zinkhan and Hirschheim, 1992) to conduct analysis on consumers based on the research questions.

A questionnaire was developed for the main survey in this study. Research relied on previous literature to determine its scope and measure for the anticipation of future interaction, repurchase intention, customer satisfaction with salesperson, trust in salesperson, sales strategy, sales skills, and salesperson characteristics. Instead of single-item scale, a multi-item scale developed in this study based on Churchill's (1979) study to measure consumer attitudes towards a variety of marketing constructs related to salesperson performance, with the aim of increasing measurement reliability and developing a closer relationship between scales. Figure 4.2 below shows the steps in measurement scale development.

Figure 4. 2: Steps in measurement scale development

Source: Churchill (1979, p. 66).

4.4. THE FIRST PHASE (QUALITATIVE FIELDWORK)

Qualitative approach is suitable for research with the aim of discovering and understanding more about what is involved in a phenomenon (Carson et al, 2001). Hence, an exploratory study is built in the first phase to identify and better understand research issues and questions (Zikmund et al., 2003). Because there have not been any studies that provide a valid scale with high reliability in salespeople performance, this study was based on Churchill's (1979) recommendations to build a complete scale. According to Dacin and Brown (2002) and Churchill (1979), exploratory research should be developed in the first stage of research in order to: (1) develop more understanding about research topics, (2) in-depth understanding on salesperson performance, anticipation of future interactions and repurchase intention of customer, (3) gaining practical insights and assessing the relevance of the study, (4) get better insights on the information and research questions, thereby forming hypotheses and purify measures for a questionnaire.

Exploratory research, usually referred to as experience survey, involves exploring ideas and people's thoughts about a problem or phenomenon. In order to be able to accurately identify the nature of a problem and develop related hypotheses, it is usually started with a broad study, and subsequently focused down to research development (Saunders et al., 2007). Some techniques such as exploratory research, literature search, in-depth interview are commonly used to generate sample items and reflect a construct (Churchill, 1979). Accordingly, this study has also applied interviews to explore the salesperson performance construct in shopping malls.

The in-depth interviews positively support researchers' investigation, providing a new and useful insight into existing data (Palmer, 2011; Ritchie et al., 2003). It not only provided this research with valuable information for a deeper understanding of the research issue but also helped to add new data to the literature review (the outstanding benefits of this method are presented in Table 4.4). On the other hand, due to the limitation of exploratory research in terms of sample size (Malhotra and Birks, 2000), a questionnaire (quantitative research) will

also be developed based on these qualitative data to be able to collect a larger amount of data needed and bring more objective results for this research (Churchill, 1979).

Table 4. 4: Application for in-depth interviews

In-depth interviews	
Nature of data	<p>For generating in-depth personal accounts</p> <p>To understand the personal context</p> <p>For exploring issues in depth and in detail</p>
Subject matter	<p>To understand complex processes and issues e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Motivations, decisions -Impacts, outcomes <p>To explore private subjects of those involving social norms</p> <p>For sensitive issues</p>
Study population	<p>For participants who are likely to be willing or able to travel</p> <p>Where the study population is geographically dispersed</p> <p>Where the population is highly diverse</p> <p>Where there are issues of power or status</p> <p>Where people have communication difficulties</p>

Source: Ritchie *et al.* (2003)

4.4.1. Overviews the planning, management and data interpretation of the qualitative stage

Based on discussions of Bazeley (2007), Bryman and Burgess (1994) on different approaches to performing qualitative research (narrative, ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory, and case study research), this study start with grounded theory to test data. To analyse the

qualitative data, a process of coding was used and guided by the conceptual framework developed on the basis of the literature. The codes are built through the creation of a general understanding of the phenomenon or main construct (salesperson performance), the antecedent of salesperson performance, and the customer's future interaction concept. This sets the framework for coding and analysing the data. In addition, the researchers (Ageeva et al., 2019; Foroudi et al., 2021; Palmer and Gallagher, 2007) also show that building codes are of great help in solving research questions, problems, hypotheses or key variables identified in the study.

Coding of the narratives was initially implemented based on the open codes process and the constructs defined in the literature. The list of codes should be based on the conceptual framework, research questions and issues, hypotheses, or key variables in the study (Miles and Huberman, 1994). It is necessary to write a memo for each interview transcript before doing the coding. Coding data allows researchers to find, compare and detect samples that require further investigation more easily. In addition, it supports analysis of data from interview transcript and situates the process within approaches to qualitative analysis (Foroudi et al., 202; Weston et al., 2001). With descriptive coding, the collected data will be gathered with the emergence of topical ideas and related to the same content (Brown et al., 2019; Malhotra and Birks, 2000). Based on research by Lincoln and Guba (1985), it is essential to "devise rules that describe category properties and that can, ultimately, be used to justify the inclusion of each data bit that remains assigned to the category as well as to provide a basis for later tests of replicability" (p. 347). This procedure guaranteed that the theoretical concepts that arose from the first round of coding could be presented in the data in a methodical manner (Esterberg, 2002). Researchers (Esterberg, 2002; Huberman and Miles, 1994) discovered three steps of coding analysis: open coding, axial coding, and selective coding. The researcher followed the authors' instructions (Esterberg, 2002; Huberman and Miles, 1994) while coding the qualitative data. The emergent data's dependability is improved by the three steps of coding. Table 4.5 explains the steps of the coding process.

Table 4. 5: The stages of coding process

Stages of coding process	
Open coding	First stage of grounded theory coding process, through which concepts are identified.
Axial coding	Second stage of grounded theory coding process, through which second order categories are inductively derived from first order concepts generated during the open-coding process.
Selective coding	Final stage of grounded theory coding process, through which emergent theory is identified and refined, and the emergent themes are integrated.

The creation of open codes was the initial step in the data analysis process. The open codes were analysed and classified into higher ideas until the key categories were discovered. The open code started with a line-by-line analysis of the texts (interview transcripts) and marking portions where the salesperson performance, anticipation of future interaction, repurchase intention, and relationship between the salesperson performance and anticipation of future interaction were discussed and coded to either the starting list or new open codes developed during the process. The transcripts were carefully reviewed twice, each time with great attention, to identify patterns in the texts that were related to the literature. Each sentence was compared to the previous sentences, and open codes for similarities and differences. If the codes were identical or nearly identical, they were coded in the same way. If the codes were too different, the new sentence was tagged with a different label. The primary goal of open coding is to discover similar or dissimilar patterns in the texts from those found in the related literature. After each interview transcript was open-coded, the researcher examined the open codes and added further comments and memos to strengthen the analysis. The axis code was born as a result of this.

Axial coding, which seeks to describe the relationship and contrast between the primary categories and subcategories in order to identify patterns within the texts, is the second step of data analysis. Following all open coding, systematic axial coding began (Balmer, 1996). As a unique method, axial coding has the virtue of not distorting data analysis. By considering all the open codes inside a single scenario, axial coding was maximised. Axial coding is a technique that involves continuous comparison. Axial code was generated based

on differences and similarities of the collected data in open coding. The open codes were compared to each other and to the produced axial codes once the axial code was generated. This procedure aids the researcher in creating a new axial code, changing current ones, or merging them.

The last stage of coding, selective coding, seeks to include the developing theory. The most difficult phase in grounded theory analysis is selective coding. It is important to explain the phenomena in a parsimonious manner in order to create a hypothesis that can finally match the facts (Strauss and Corbin, 1998). Spiggle's research (1994) suggests that selective coding "involves advancing to a higher level of abstraction with the generated paradigmatic constructs, specifying relationships, and outlining a core category or construct around which the other categories and constructs revolve and that relates them to one another" (p. 495). According to Strauss and Corbin (1998), the association between these axial codes served as the starting point for the selective coding process. Because of the complexity and necessity of explaining phenomena, this step is considered the most challenging and perplexing of grounded theory analysis.

There are three additional approaches used besides the standard theoretical coding process such as question asking, writing memos, comparison: 1) evaluating the research questions as a general guideline, 2) re-examining the open codes and raw data while comparing axial codes, and 3) discussing the codes with supervisors and specialists to determine their fitness and relationship. The researcher was able to determine the primary causes and repercussions of salesperson performance, by interpreting the review of the data.

The QSR NVivo software Version 12 was ideal for data management and attaining outcomes in order to give a thorough and improved synthesis and interpretation of the information obtained. It has proved beneficial for diagramming and assisting the researcher in seeing the entire text, allowing to understand the inter-relationships of the codes promptly (Welsh, 2002). It also allows the storage and retrieval of information (Esterberg, 2002). In qualitative data analysis and management, the researcher understands the importance of both manual and technological tools, and employs both (Welsh, 2002). The data is collected and linked

together by encrypting the information and gathering it at the nodes. These data are evaluated for the content of exacting nodes that would affect the interactions between thematic notions. The nodes (themes) were also considered for consistency, and the qualitative data analysis was carried out. Utilising this software ensures analytical rigour. NVivo enables in-depth data analysis and addresses the validity and reliability of research findings. Additionally, it ensures that the study procedure is more methodical, detailed, and careful (Alam, 2020; Bazeley, 2007). NVivo includes capabilities for recording, data storage, retrieval, and connecting ideas, as well as analysing and interpreting data patterns. The programme incorporates a huge variety of tools into a symmetrical, accessible, and precise structure. NVivo's usage as a computer-assisted qualitative data analysis programme enables more trustworthy, simple, precise, and transparent data analysis (Gibbs, 2002).

The code has been developed more than once (Weber, 1985) by another researcher to reach a consensus on identifying themes, in order to test the dependability of the coding based on content analysis. A study method known as content analysis allows researchers to draw replicable and reliable conclusions about the context of their findings. According to Patton (2001), the qualitative analyst's search for patterns, themes, and categories is a creative endeavour that involves making thoughtful decisions about what is truly relevant and meaningful in the data (p. 406). The researcher analysed each word and phrase using the coding method, enabling for consideration of any potential interpretations that the speaker may have assumed or intended (Ageeva et al., 2019; Weston et al., 2001). Weston et al. (2001) suggested that researchers can adopt code development approaches from previous research directions to attempt to find phenomena, marks the beginning and the end of the phenomenon in the collected data set (Patton, 2001; Strauss and Corbin, 1998). All interview data of each participant were collected and compiled by the researcher in the form of transcripts. This enables to maintain terminology and continuity with earlier work. The interpretation of the data was then given together with the pertinent study framework.

With the growing number of different conceptual and methodological approaches to studying human behaviour, data quality is considered very important in the social sciences (Ritchie et al., 2003). Validity and reliability are two characteristics that influence how a study is

designed, how the data are analysed, and how the study is judged. However, there is no consistency on what reliability and validity are in qualitative research. In order to confirm the reliability of the study, an assessment of its "trustworthiness" is essential. The concept of establishing truth through evaluations of validity and reliability is supported by the trustworthiness perspective (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). According to Seale (1999) the: "trustworthiness of a research report lies at the heart of issues conventionally discussed as validity and reliability" (p. 266). Instead of using a statistically random sample, the researcher prefers to use a theoretical sample to increase the likelihood of comparing concepts and their properties to find similarities and differences, as well as allowing to identify categories, differentiate, and determine the extent of their variability (Strauss and Corbin, 1998, p. 149).

Lincoln and Guba (1985) argue that "there is no validity without reliability, an expression of the former validity is sufficient to establish the latter reliability" (p. 316). Reliability indicates long-term stability and validity means well-founded for determining the strength of the data. The accuracy with which research methodologies and procedures create data is referred to as reliability, and it is a result of the validity of a study (Patton, 2001).

The triangulation approach is used in qualitative research to investigate how qualitative researchers' perspectives affect a study's validity and reliability, and thus to eliminate bias and boost the study's honesty. Triangulation in the study of Creswell and Miller (2000) is known as: "a validity procedure where researchers search for convergence among multiple and different sources of information to form themes or categories in a study" (p. 126). The approaches utilised in this study to promote trustworthiness are listed in Table 4.6.

Weber (1985) states that in order to validate the coding's dependability through content analysis, the researcher determined the stability when the content was encrypted more than once. In addition, one independent coder with extensive qualitative research expertise and no prior knowledge of the study was used to examine the reliability of the emergent categories of the salesperson performance.

Table 4. 6: Meeting the criteria of trustworthiness

Traditional criteria	Trustworthiness criteria	Techniques employed to ensure trustworthiness
Internal validity	Credibility	Quality access (the researcher was provided with an office desk, computer, access to company intranet, email address, freedom of talking to and interviewing anybody, freedom of getting any company documents, including lots of confidential strategic documents.) and extensive engagement in the field.
		Multiple triangulations Peer debriefing Constant comparison
External validity	Transferability	Detailed description of the research setting Multiple cases and cross-case comparison
Reliability	Dependability	Purposive and theoretical sampling Cases and informants' confidentiality protected. Rigorous multiple stages of coding
Objectivity	Confirmability	Separately presenting the exemplar open and axial codes. Word-by-word interview transcription Accurate records of contacts and interviews Writing research journal Carefully keeping notes of observation Regularly keeping notes of emergent theoretical and methodological ideas

Source: Lincoln and Guba (1985)

4.4.2. Interview

To accomplish the objective, interviews will be conducted in this study to identify the key components required in evaluating the salesperson performance construct. In-depth interviews with top managers in shopping malls were performed as part of this study, which enabled the researcher to gain a better knowledge of the topic as well as collect data on the participant's attitudes and behaviours (Palmer and Gallagher, 2007; Shiu et al., 2009). The interview guide in this study was designed using a subject guide that generally described the salesperson performance as the area of interest, balanced the interview with the important

themes, and promoted coherence in the conversations. The researcher contacted shopping malls in Vietnam in order to find eligible respondents for in-depth personal interviews and to justify the quantity of participants. The researcher localised the top shopping malls to find the ideal person(s) to contact about the topic of the study. They were asked if they wanted to participate in the research. All 15 shopping malls, 11 salespeople and 8 specialists approached responded by mail or email, however, due to the busy schedules of those contacted, there were 15 in-depth interviews conducted.

According to Churchill (1999), Ritchie et al. (2003), most interviews will be conducted face-to-face with each participant based on the time and place they specify in order to get a clear and comprehensive picture of the salesperson's performance, leading to a better grasp of the research objective. However, due to unforeseen outbreaks of the COVID pandemic, interviews will instead be conducted via phone and Skype in order to maintain social distancing and ensure the safety of participants and researcher. It would be ideal for interviews to be conducted in English to simplify the challenges of translation, transcription, and time constraints. However, because all participants were Vietnamese, interviews were conducted in Vietnamese based on the interviewee's choice to provide the most convenient and accurate information. The average duration for the interviews was an hour and all of them were taped and transcribed verbatim to guarantee dependability (Andriopoulos and Lewis, 2009; Lemon and Hayes, 2020). Due to ethical issues, recording will be paused if the participant does not feel comfortable or does not allow the interview to be recorded. Written notes were subsequently taken.

In-depth interviews conducted in this study were semi-structured, direct, undisguised, and personal interviews with the aim of uncovering core motivation, belief, attitude, and sentiments about the issue (Deeter-Schmelz et al., 2008). Semi-structured in-depth interviews are a common and dependable source of information in qualitative research (Raworth et al., 2012). This method is likened to a flexible conversation between the researcher and the interviewee, in which a set of open-ended questions is predetermined and followed by a series of probing questions that capitalise on the response and go further into the issue of concern (Adams, 2015; Roulston and Choi, 2018). According to Roberts (2020), open-ended

questions are frequently utilised in exploratory research, which allows participants to freely articulate their thoughts and experiences. This type of questioning enables participants to respond to interview questions using their own words, without being constrained by predetermined texts or categories. It helps collect open-ended data, probe for new ideas and insights to delve deeper into the research problem and generate relevant hypotheses (Roulston and Choi, 2018). Before the interviews, the researcher translated interview questions into Vietnamese to facilitate in-depth personal interviews. Besides, Vietnamese interviews were transcribed and then translated back into English, double-checked, and verified for translation accuracy so that it can accurately communicate the participants' meanings and ensure the reliability of the research (Yunus et al., 2022). Interpreters need to be knowledgeable in both original and targeted languages as well as the translation procedure, the surrounding cultures, and contexts. The researcher can personally compare the translation with the original data if he or she is bilingual (Gawlewicz, 2019). During the interviews, a question sheet was also used so that it can be easily checked and ensured for the full disclosure of the topics of interest (Appendix 4.1).

Following the research of Easterby-Smith et al. (2002), researchers should dress appropriately to promote themselves as professionals rather than students. In addition, the researcher applied a variety of methods to create trust with the participants. In-depth interviews allow researchers to delve thoroughly to uncover new information, develop new facets of an issue, and capture vivid and accurate narratives that are based on personal experience (Burgess, 1982, p. 107). The flexibility of in-depth interviews allowed questions to be raised on a broad range of topics. Personal interviews are frequently utilised in marketing research, Roberts (2020) and Sekaran (2003) asserts that this technique is simply adaptable to make sure that people providing responses comprehended the questions.

In fact, the results collected in qualitative research are in words, free-form and non-numerical, such as attitudes or perceptions. According to research by Fishbein and Ajzen, (1975) and Shiu et al. (2009), attitudes are also assessed as an essential factor for researchers to be able to predict, and better understand people's psychology towards the events, or research topics. Attitude is also a factor to measure the characteristics of salespeople as well

as customer perception and satisfaction, enable participants to evaluate the attributes of a salesperson's characteristics and skills, and customer engagement as well. Besides, to be able to assess a dimension of attitude, the researcher prefers to use the fixed-response alternative question, which is considered a good choice to collect highly reliable data, because the responses were predefined and limited to the alternatives stated (Malhotra and Birks, 2000, p. 210).

According to Balmer (2001), marketing researchers place a greater focus on exploratory research, which begins with a scenario analysis conducted through interviews with corporate executives and managers (Churchill, 1979). Qualitative methods are also applied by researchers to investigate in-depth issues in a less structured format and incorporate the experiences, feelings, and opinions of respondents in their research (Malhotra and Birks, 2000). Qualitative research assists in gathering more detailed information to better comprehend the salesperson performance concept. Table 4.7 shows the details of the interviewees.

Table 4. 7: The details of in-depth interviews with expert and managers

Interview Date	Organisation	Interview position	Interview approx. duration
03.09.2021	Shopping mall in Binh Tan District	Sales Executive	60 min.
11.09.2021	Shopping mall in District 1	Sales Manager	90 min.
12.09.2021	Shopping mall in District 5	Sales Executive	30 min.
21.09.2021	Shopping mall in District 7	Salesman	30 min.
03.10.2021	Nor. University	Doctoral Researcher	60 min.
13.10.2021	EHCM. University	Professor	60 min.
16.10.2021	Shopping mall in District 1	Area Sales Manager	60 min.
20.10.2021	Shopping mall in Tan Phu District	Sales Executive	30 min.
20.10.2021	Nor. University	MBA Student	90 min.
23.10.2021	Shopping mall in District 1	Sale Supervisor	45 min.
27.10.2021	EHCM. University	Doctoral Researcher	30 min.

31.10.2021	LB. University	MBA Student	60 min.
02.11.2021	Shopping mall in District 2	Salesman	45 min.
03.11.2021	Shopping mall in District 1	Sale Manager	90 min.
05.11.2021	Shopping mall in District 1	Salesman	30 min.
Topics discussed			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The understanding of salesperson performance. - The factors that influence salesperson performance. - Their experience of what they understand the salesperson performance and its influences on anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. - Discussion of customer orientation, value-based selling, adaptive selling behaviour and whether it influences the salesperson's performance. - Discussion of sales strategy, salesperson skills, salesperson characteristics and experience in their organisation. - The influence of salesperson performance on satisfaction with salesperson - The influence of salesperson performance on trust in salesperson - The main perceived impacts of salesperson performance. 			

Source: The researcher

Note: All official organisation names used above have been kept anonymous to ensure confidentiality.

4.5. THE SECOND PHASE (RESEARCH INSTRUMENT AND SCALE DEVELOPMENT)

The purpose of this section is to provide accurate and reliable measurements of the theoretical construct by combining information from current literature and qualitative research. There are many items that were produced in the first period, however, several of these items were eliminated for the purpose of parsimony since they were similar or equivalent. In addition, items developed from qualitative research were also considered by a group of academics and eliminated any extraneous measures to verify that the items were reflective of the scale's domain.

The next section depicts how the information was integrated into the questionnaire development.

4.5.1. Specifying the domain constructs

The initial stage in questionnaire development is to determine the content domain, which is generally accomplished by examining relevant literature and conducting qualitative investigations (Vedel et al., 2021). Based on the researcher's knowledge, no studies have yet produced a reliable, legitimate scale for measuring salesperson performance. This thesis will address the vacuum in this field. Following Churchill's (1979) paradigm in the development of improved measurements, a collection of items culled from literature, interviews, and researcher has been developed to represent the constructs' domain. The operational definition of the focus construct (salesperson performance) and its parameters were provided and detailed in the literature review (see section 2.2, 2.3, 2.4 and 2.5) in order to find the best measurement.

This study is mainly to look into the effects of salesperson performance on customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. As a result, salesperson behaviours, skills and experiences, salesperson performance, customer satisfaction and repurchase intention all included in the literature review. The scales for domains and items are gathered from a variety of marketing and management journals, including *Journal of Marketing Research*, *Marketing Letter*, *Industrial Marketing Management*, *European Journal of Marketing*. The conceptual framework, therefore, is also generated from literature review based on the theoretical knowledge gained (see Figure 3.1 in Chapter III).

4.5.2. Generation of measurement items

Following the paradigm of Churchill (1979), item generation was identified as the next step in the questionnaire development process. To develop the scale, research by DeVillis (2003) suggested: 1) minimising excessive length, 2) increasing the readability level of each item, 3) avoiding double-barreled items, 4) eliminating confusing pronoun references, and 5) avoid positively and negatively phrased items (pp. 66-70). Also, to create the measuring items, the researcher combined information from the literature and data derived from qualitative research (such as interviews with leading experts and managers on the research topic)

(Churchill, 1979). The items that typified each construct are a multi-item scale and developed from the existing literature.

The single items, based on research conducted by Churchill (1979), generally have significant "uniqueness or specificity in that each item seems to have only a low correlation with the attribute being measured and tends to relate to other attributes" (p. 66). An attribute typically considered appropriate, and fulfilling is judged to be more acceptable and can lead to a more positive attitude towards the object. An attribute that is not regarded as fulfilling, meanwhile, might be viewed as unfavourable, leading to an increased negative attitude towards the object (Freling et al., 2010). In addition, the single items contain considerable measurement error and might elicit inaccurate answers in the same way, therefore "the same scale position is unlikely to be checked in successive administrations of an instrument" (Churchill, 1979, p. 66).

Qualitative research was conducted in this study to find fresh insights that could not be captured by just examining the relevant literature. The literature review is followed by interviews with top managers and specialists. A multi-item scale is recommended to be used for each construct (Churchill, 1979). Researchers have emphasised the need to focus on the measurement's reliability and validity in marketing research (Churchill, 1979; Kotabe, 1990; Zaichkowsky, 1985). There are certain scales developed by researchers following prior studies with a high degree of reliability and validity. Related items were also scrutinised and narrowed down, those were reduced to a minimum to prevent redundancy in the measurements and excessive length in the questionnaire.

There were a total of 93 items created throughout the initial item creation process, including the following measurement items: 8 items for salesperson performance, 4 items for sales models, 4 items customer prioritisation, 5 items for segmentation, 5 items for interpersonal skills, 5 items for salesmanship skills, 5 items for technical skills, 3 items for marketing skills, 7 items for customer orientation, 6 items for value-based selling, 4 items for empathic ability, 4 items for cue perception ability, 3 items for ability to modify self-presentation, 5 items for experience (knowledge), 6 items for adaptive selling behaviour, 5 items for

satisfaction with salesperson, 4 items for trust in salesperson, 4 items for anticipation of future interaction, 6 items for repurchase intention. Table 4.8 below lists the specific constructs and the number of items initially created.

Table 4. 8: The constructs and number of initial items

Constructs		No. of initial item
Salesperson performance		8
Sales strategy elements	Sales models	4
	Customer prioritisation	4
	Segmentation	5
Sales skills elements	Interpersonal skills	5
	Salesmanship skills	5
	Technical skills	5
	Marketing skills	3
Salesperson characteristic elements	Empathic ability	4
	Cue perception ability	4
	Ability to modify self-presentation	3
	Experience (knowledge)	5
Customer orientation		7
Value-based selling		6
Adaptive selling behaviour		6
Anticipation of future interaction		4
Repurchase intention		6
Satisfaction with salesperson		5
Trust in salesperson		4

Table 4.9 shows the main constructs and their measurement items, as well as the qualitative research (see also Chapters 2 and 3 for the literature review).

Table 4. 9: The construct's domain and items in the literature

Construct	Measurement items	Major references
Selling model		
	The salesperson employs different selling models for selling to different customers.	Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Panagopoulos and Avlonitis (2010); Terho et al. (2015) and also supported by the qualitative research
	The salesperson considers customer preferences when setting relationship objectives and develop selling models.	Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Panagopoulos and Avlonitis (2010)
	The salesperson considers the costs and value associated with the customer when setting relationship objectives and develop selling models for the customer.	Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Panagopoulos and Avlonitis (2010); Terho et al. (2015) and also supported by the qualitative research
	The salesperson has adapted the selling process to meet the customers' different goals	Terho et al. (2015)
Customer prioritisation		
	The salesperson prioritises customers based on their expected importance to the firm	Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Terho et al. (2015) and also supported by the qualitative research
	The salesperson targets their selling efforts to different customers	Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Katsikea et al. (2019); Terho et al. (2015) and supported by the qualitative research
	The salesperson develops specific selling strategies for each targeted customer.	Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Katsikea et al. (2019)
	The salesperson focuses on communication and service quality to promote customer interaction.	The qualitative research
Segmentation		
	The salesperson identifies prospective customer groups based on the expected lifetime value/profitability of each customer to the firm.	Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Panagopoulos and Avlonitis (2010); Terho et al. (2015)
	The salesperson identifies specific customer groups based on the buying behaviour	Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Panagopoulos and Avlonitis (2010); Terho et al. (2015) and supported by the qualitative research
	The salesperson identifies specific customer groups based on the customers' uses of products/services.	Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Panagopoulos and Avlonitis (2010) and also supported by the qualitative research
	The salesperson identifies specific customer groups based on the value that customer expects to receive from buying products/services.	Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Panagopoulos and Avlonitis (2010) and also supported by the qualitative research

The salesperson segments customers based on the preference	The qualitative research
Customer orientation	
The salesperson tries to give customers an accurate expectation of what the product/service will do.	Jha et al. (2017); Periatt et al. (2004); Terho et al. (2015) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson tries to figure out what a customer's needs are.	Periatt et al. (2004); Terho et al. (2015) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson has the customer's best interest in mind	Periatt et al. (2004); Terho et al. (2015)
Every customer problem is important for the salesperson	Donavan et al. (2004); Jha et al. (2017) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson makes every customer feel like he/she is the only customer	Donavan et al. (2004); Jha et al. (2017)
The salesperson tries to achieve their goals by satisfying customers.	Periatt et al (2004)
The salesperson tries to capture and update customer trends	The qualitative research
Value-based selling	
The salesperson cares about the customers' processes, focuses on developing relationships and connecting with customers post-purchase so customers don't feel forgotten	Kienzler et al. (2019) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson is interested in how the customers use products/services	Kienzler et al. (2019)
The salesperson actively demonstrates to customers the financial impact of working with them.	Terho et al. (2015) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson uses a value-based selling approach.	Terho et al. (2015) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson works towards improving customers' bottom line.	Terho et al. (2015) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson always actively listens and give the sincerest advice to customers	The qualitative research
Interpersonal skill	
The salesperson has the ability to control and regulate their nonverbal emotional expressions	Basir et al. (2010); Castleberry et al. (1999); Plouffe et al. (2009); Singh et al. (2017); and also supported by the qualitative research

The salesperson has awareness and understanding of the nonverbal communication of others	Basir et al. (2010); Castleberry et al. (1999); Plouffe et al. (2009); Singh et al. (2017); and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson has the ability to manipulate others and control the situation	Basir et al. (2010); Duke (2002); Plouffe et al. (2009) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson has the ability to relate to people with diverse backgrounds	Castleberry et al. (1999); Duke (2002); Høgevold et al. (2021); and also supported by the qualitative research
The salespeople are calm and professional in delivering their sales presentations	Høgevold et al. (2021) and also supported by the qualitative research
Salesmanship skills	
The salesperson has the ability to convince customers and close the sale	Plouffe et al. (2009); Singh et al. (2017) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson has in-depth knowledge company's procedures	Rentz et al. (2002) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson has the ability to observe customer reactions to their presentations and customise the selling approach	Rentz et al. (2002) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson provides prompt feedback in dealing with escalation	Rentz et al. (2002)
The salesperson has the ability to get buy-in	Ahearn et al. (2007); Rentz et al. (2002); Basir et al. (2010) and also supported by the qualitative research
Technical skills	
The salesperson has knowledge of the customers' markets and products	Plouffe et al. (2009); Rentz et al. (2002); Singh et al. (2017) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson has knowledge of the company's procedures	Plouffe et al. (2009); Singh et al. (2017)
The salesperson has knowledge of business activities	Basir et al. (2010); Rentz et al. (2002) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson has knowledge of the product line, including product features and benefits	Rentz et al. (2002)
The salesperson understands product specifications	Basir et al. (2010)
Marketing skills	
The salesperson has a wealth of information on	Basir et al. (2010); Myers et al. (2011) and also

industry trends and important events	supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson has a lot of knowledge about social media and digital tools	Myers et al., (2011)
The salesperson has the skills to create and build long-term relationships with customers	Akroush and Abu ELSamen (2012) and also supported by the qualitative research
Empathy	
The salesperson is available to assist when customer expresses concern about a serious problem exists	Basir et al. (2010); Giacobbe et al. (2006)
The salesperson has the highest level of empathy with respect to the needs of customers	Anaza et al. (2018) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson demonstrates a sincere interest in my customers.	Basir et al. (2010) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson put himself in the customer's shoes to advise and solve the problem	Giacobbe et al. (2006) and also support by the qualitative research
The salesperson can understand and share with customers	The qualitative research
Cue perception ability	
The salesperson can always tell when customer do not really understand what they have said by observing the customer's eyes, expressions and behaviour	Giacobbe et al. (2006) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson seems to have a strong sense that enables him to identify the customer's true mood	Giacobbe et al. (2006) and also supported by the qualitative research
Is related to the salesperson's cognitive ability, judgement and experience	The qualitative research
The salesperson can easily reach out and participate in customers' buying process and make customer happy	The qualitative research
Ability to modify	
The salesperson has the ability to control the way he comes across to the customer, depending on what the situation calls for	Giacobbe et al. (2006); Høgevold et al. (2021); Lennox and Wolfe (1984) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson has good vision and flexibility in dealing with clients	The qualitative research
The salesperson understands their own strengths and weaknesses	The qualitative research
Experience (knowledge)	
The salesperson has many years of experience in the industry	Dixon et al. (2001); Rapp et al. (2006) and also supported by the qualitative research

The salesperson has the ability to distinguish between different kinds of customers	Hall et al. (2015); Homburg et al. (2009); Shannahan et al. (2015) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson has the ability to identify and analyse customer needs	Hall et al. (2015); Homburg et al. (2009); Shannahan et al. (2015) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson can easily reach customers and close the sale	The qualitative research
The salesperson can adapt perception and behaviour to work with different clients	The qualitative research
Adaptive selling behaviour	
The salesperson can easily modify their sales approaches from situation to situation.	Alnakhli et al. (2021); McFarland (2019); McIntyre et al. (2000); Robinson et al. (2002) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson is very sensitive to the needs of customers.	McFarland (2019) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson tries to understand how one customer differs from another	Alnakhli et al. (2021)
The salesperson has a clear understanding of the product, potential customers and competitors	The qualitative research
The salesperson has the ability to customise prices to meet different sales situations	The qualitative research
The salesperson shows care and respect for the needs of clients.	The qualitative research
Salesperson performance	
The salesperson succeeds in meeting the sales target	Evans et al. (2007); Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Kock (2017); Piercy et al. (2001); Singh et al. (2017) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson succeeds in creating sales revenues	Evans et al. (2007); Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Kock (2017); Piercy et al. (2001); Singh et al. (2017) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson sells high-profit margin products	Evans et al. (2007); Inyang and Jaramillo (2020); Singh et al. (2017) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson identifies major accounts in the	Evans et al. (2007); Singh et al. (2017)

territory and sells to them	
The salesperson makes effective presentations to customers	Piercy et al. (2001) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson understands customer needs and work processes	Piercy et al. (2001) and also supported by the qualitative research
The salesperson succeeds in expanding the network of customers	Kock (2017) and also supported by the qualitative research
Customer's satisfaction with salesperson	
I have an extremely effective working relationship with the salesperson	Homburg and Stock (2005); Rapp et al. (2006)
I will continue to do business with the company even if its prices increase somewhat.	Cronin et al. (2000); Homburg and Stock (2005); Rapp et al. (2006) and also support by the qualitative research
I appreciate the expertise and behaviour of the seller	Cronin et al. (2000) and also support by the qualitative research
I prefer to purchase the product he/ she introduces	Cronin et al. (2000) and also support by the qualitative research
Is the customer's subjective evaluations of the company's products/services	The qualitative research
Trust in salesperson	
I trust this salesperson to a large extent	Doney and Cannon (1997); Homburg and Stock (2005); Kennedy et al. (2001); Palmatier et al. (2007); Ramsey and Sohi (1997); Strutton et al. (1996)
I believe that this salesperson is fair and honest with us	Doney and Cannon (1997); Garbarino and Johnson (1999); Homburg and Stock (2005); Kennedy et al. (2001); Palmatier et al. (2007); Ramsey and Sohi (1997) and also support by the qualitative research
The salesperson is reliable because he is mainly concerned with the client's interests, rather than his own.	Garbarino and Johnson (1999); Kennedy et al. (2001); Strutton et al. (1996)
The salesperson is sincere with me.	Doney and Cannon (1997); Palmatier et al. (2007); Ramsey and Sohi (1997) and also support by the qualitative research
Anticipation of future interaction with salesperson	

I am willing to discuss business with this salesperson again.	Crosby et al. (1990); Evans et al. (2008); Lusch and Brown (1996); Román and Iacobucci (2010) and also supported by the qualitative research
I plan to continue doing business with this salesperson.	Crosby et al. (1990); Román and Iacobucci, (2010); Lusch and Brown (1996)
I will purchase from this salesperson again.	Crosby et al. (1990); Román and Iacobucci (2010) and also supported by the qualitative research
I have a good impression of the company's service and will come back in my next purchase	The qualitative research
Repurchase intention	
I will most likely buy this service again from the company in the future if I need something similar	Khalifa and Liu (2007); Mende et al. (2013); Pavlou and Fygenon (2006); Sirohi et al. (1998)
I plan to continue purchasing products/ services from the company	Eggert and Ulaga (2002); Khalifa and Liu (2007); Kim et al. (2012); Pavlou and Fygenon (2006); Sirohi et al. (1998) and also supported by the qualitative research
I intend to recommend the company products that I regularly use to people around me	Kim et al. (2012) and also supported by the qualitative research
I will come back in the future because the salesperson is honest and can understand my preferences well.	Eggert and Ulaga (2002); Kim et al. (2012) and also supported by the qualitative research
I won't buy it again because I had a bad service experience from the salesperson.	The qualitative research
I would like to work with this salesperson on my next purchases	The qualitative research

4.5.3. Purifying measurement scales

Purifying the measuring scales based on Churchill's (1979) paradigm was carried out in the third phase to facilitate questionnaire development. Churchill (1979) states that the calculation to purify the measurements, to some extent, is connected to the measuring model used. Validity, in essence, is also understood as "the degree to which what the researcher was trying to measure was actually measured" (McDaniel and Gates, 2006, pp. 224-227). There were two validity tests conducted during the initial phase, and prior to the main survey of this study, which were face validity and content validity. Essentially, they are all subjective and

give an indicator of the questionnaire's sufficiency. Content validity is a judgemental term and relates to the extent to which a particular group of items accurately represents a content domain that the study is seeking to measure (Kerlinger, 1973).

To check the validity and importance of the items in the questionnaire, the initial version was developed and discussed with 6 different subjects consisting of marketing faculty and members from universities in Vietnam and the UK, who are familiar and knowledgeable with the issue and rated for content validity utilising judging methods (Bearden et al., 1993; Zaichkowsky, 1985). They were asked to remark on the items' appropriateness and evaluate word usage, including spelled correctly, clearly, without jargon; their contributions were then applied in conjunction. The experts were questioned on the significance of each statement, as well as recommend which items should be kept (Lichtenstein et al., 1990). The items used in the instrument were also required to be considered in order to know how specific it is to the area under investigation. Academics functioned as domain judges for a scale in prior research. The main outcomes of this procedure represent the 'informed' judgements of subject-matter experts (Green et al., 1988; Unkelbach and Greifeneder, 2018). As the content of a measuring instrument, both substance, matter and topics are mentioned as associated with the characteristic being measured (Green et al., 1988). Table 4.10 shows a review of the benefits and limits of content analysis.

The questionnaire after adjustment was checked by 5 experts to consider face validity or if the items measure what they are supposed to measure. The experts were requested to complete the questionnaire and provide feedback on whether it looked to assess the desired construct, as well as the phrasing, layout, and ease of competing. Items collected from the literature and from qualitative interviews with participants such as managers and lecturers were cross-checked with each other. Experts also advise using the present tense for all statements because the research topic is towards customer perception. This is also the reason for using present tense in all research statements.

Table 4. 10: Summary of benefits and limitations of content analysis

Benefits	Limitations
Flexibility of research design i.e. types of inferences	Analyses the communication (message) only
Supplements multi-method analyses	Findings may be questionable alone, therefore, verification using another method may be required
Wide variety of analytical application	Underlying premise must be frequency related
May be qualitative and/or quantitative	Reliability – stability, reproducibility, accuracy of judges
May be automated – improves, reliability, reduces cost/time	Validity – construct, hypothesis, predictive and semantic
Range of computer software developed	Less opportunity to pre-test, discuss mechanism with independent judges
Copes with large quantities of data	Undue bias if only part data is analysed, possibly abstracting from context of communication
Unobtrusive, unstructured, context sensitive	Lack of reliability and validity measures reported, raising questions of credibility
Development of standards applicable to specific research, e.g. negotiations	

Source: Harwood and Garry (2003, p. 493).

The baseline measurement for the "sales model" was based on research (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Terho et al., 2015). The authors (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010) suggested that the customer orientation was 'the salesperson considers customer preferences when setting relationship objectives and develop selling models'. However, scholars recommended that it is synonymous with 'the salesperson employs different selling models for selling to different customers'. As a result, 1 item was removed from the study questionnaire. Furthermore, experts suggested that the item ("the salesperson focuses on communication and service quality to promote customer interaction") was inconsistent with the "customer prioritisation" construct. Therefore, 1 item was removed. Similarly, items ("the salesperson identifies specific customer groups based on the customers' uses of products/services") and ("the salesperson segments customers based on the preference") were found to be duplicates with 'the salesperson identifies specific customer groups based on the buying behaviour'. Therefore, 2 items were eliminated. Scholars (Chen et al., 2018; Delpechitre et al., 2019; Guo

and Wang, 2015; Homburg et al., 2011; Jaramillo et al., 2007; Kasiri et al., 2017; Thomas et al., 2001; Singh and Venugopal, 2015) measured "customer orientation" by 'the salesperson has the customer's best interest in mind'. However, the interviewees proposed that it is synonymous with 'the salesperson tries to figure out what a customer's needs are'. As a result, 1 item was removed from the study questionnaire. The experts commented that "the salesperson is interested in how the customers use products/services" was inconsistent with the "value-based selling" construct. Therefore, 1 item was removed.

The item that was endorsed by authors (Basir et al., 2010; Castleberry et al., 1999; Plouffe et al., 2009; Singh et al., 2017): 'the salesperson has awareness and understanding of the nonverbal communication of others' and items was endorsed by authors (Castleberry et al., 1999; Duke, 2002; Høgevoid et al., 2021): 'the salesperson has the ability to relate to people with diverse backgrounds' were also removed because did not represent "interpersonal skill" construct. Similarly, several items measure "salesmanship skill" ("the salesperson has in-depth knowledge company's procedures"), ("the salesperson has the ability to observe customer reactions to their presentations and customise the selling approach"), and items for "technical skill" construct ("the salesperson has knowledge of the company's procedures"), ("the salesperson has knowledge of business activities") were also excluded from the list of related items because they did not represent construct. Scholars (Myers et al., 2011) measured "marketing skill" by 'the salesperson has a lot of knowledge about social media and digital tools'. However, the experts suggested that "digital tools" are not appropriate to use when talking about the marketing skills of salespeople. For this reason, the item was agreed upon by the academia's suggestion as "... has a lot of knowledge about social media". In addition, interviewees and experts also believed that 'the salesperson has the highest level of empathy with respect to the needs of customers', and 'the salesperson can understand and share with customers' has the same meaning as 'the salesperson put himself in the customer's shoes to advise and solve the problem', therefore, therefore, they should be combined into one item, as recommended by experts. The item "cue perception ability" measured by 'the salesperson can always tell when customer do not really understand what they have said by observing the customer's eyes, expressions and behaviour' item, however, experts recommended that "tell" is rather ambiguous. As a result, the item was reworded as follows

'... can always identify customer needs quickly when the customer may not clearly explain what they want'. Additionally, the item ("the salesperson seems to have a strong sense that enables him to identify the customer's true mood") was also dropped as being synonymous with the item discussed above.

15 items were excluded from the questionnaire based on the assessment of the experts and scholars interviewed. Therefore, it can be seen that the items were fully validated for lexicality by the participation of academics before conducting the questionnaire pilot test. The constructs and the number of items reduced are shown in Table 4.11.

Table 4. 11: The constructs and the number of final items and the items for the pre-test

Constructs		No. of initial items	Final items for pilot study
Salesperson performance		8	7
Sales strategy elements	Sales models	4	3
	Customer prioritisation	4	3
	Segmentation	5	3
Sales skills elements	Interpersonal skills	5	3
	Salesmanship skills	5	3
	Technical skills	5	3
	Marketing skills	3	3
Salesperson characteristics elements	Empathic ability	4	3
	Cue perception ability	4	3
	Ability to modify self-presentation	3	3
	Experience (knowledge)	5	5
Customer orientation		7	6
Value-based selling		6	5
Adaptive selling behaviour		6	6
Anticipation of future interaction		4	4
Repurchase intention		6	6
Satisfaction with salesperson		5	5
Trust in salesperson		4	4

According to Malhotra and Birks (2000), piloting a questionnaire should be done before it is officially deployed. The purpose of this pilot test is to fine-tune the questionnaire to ensure that all unwanted errors are eliminated, making it easier for participants to answer the question (Saunders et al., 2007), resulting in a more successful field survey for the research. The pre-test research was utilised to improve and develop the measuring instrument, and the measurements were tweaked to provide reliable and valid results.

According to Brown et al. (2019), interval scales and scores on the Likert-type scale is a popular psychological measurement tool in social marketing research, fixed at 0 - strongly disagree, and 7 - strongly agree. Because of its outstanding features in the basic answer distribution, the Likert-type scale is preferred to be used in measuring the majority of item instruments to determine participants' opinions, behaviours, and perceptions about research topics (Bagozzi, 1994). The respondents are consumers, and they can choose from a range of possible answers in a particular question/statement based on their level of agreement or disagreement.

To enhance construct variance and minimise measurement error variance, some scholars also recommend increasing the number of scale points by substituting the commonly used five-point Likert scale with a seven-point Likert scale. Items collected from the quantitative results were modified and submitted to scale purification through the questionnaire (Churchill and Peter, 1984; O'Neill and Palmer, 2004) (see Table 4.2)

Table 4. 12: Measurement items of the theoretical constructs and the codes

Construct	Items wording	Items codes
Salesperson performance	The salesperson succeeds in meeting the sales target	SPP1
	The salesperson succeeds in creating sales revenues	SPP2
	The salesperson succeeds in expanding the network of customers	SPP3
	The salesperson identifies major accounts in the territory and sells to them	SPP4
	The salesperson sells high-profit margin products	SPP5

Sales model	The salesperson makes effective presentations to customers	SPP6
	The salesperson understands customer needs and work processes	SPP7
Customer prioritisation	The salesperson employs different selling models for selling to different customers.	SAM1
	The salesperson considers the costs and value associated with the customer when setting relationship objectives and develop selling models for the customer.	SAM2
	The salesperson has adapted the selling process to meet the customers' different goals	SAM3
Segmentation	The salesperson prioritises customers based on whom are expected importance to the firm	CUP1
	The salesperson targets their selling efforts to different customers	CUP2
	The salesperson develops specific selling strategies for each targeted customer	CUP3
Interpersonal skill	The salesperson identifies prospective customer groups based on the expected lifetime value/profitability of each customer to the firm	SEG1
	The salesperson identifies specific customer groups based on the buying behaviour	SEG2
	The salesperson identifies specific customer groups based on the value that customer expects to receive from buying products/services	SEG3
Salesmanship skill	The salesperson has the ability to control and regulate their nonverbal emotional expressions	IPS1
	The salesperson has general speaking skills	IPS2
	The salesperson has the ability to manipulate others and control the situation	IPS3
	The salesperson is calm and professional in delivering their sales presentations	IPS4

Technology skill	The salesperson has the ability to convince customers and close the sale	SAS1
	The salesperson provides prompt feedback in dealing with escalation	SAS2
	The salesperson has the ability to get buy-in	SAS3
Marketing skill	The salesperson has knowledge of the customers' markets and products	TES1
	The salesperson has knowledge of the product line, including product features and benefits	TES2
	The salesperson understands product specifications	TES3
Empathic ability	The salesperson has a wealth of information on industry trends and important events	MAS1
	The salesperson has a lot of knowledge about social media	MAS2
	The salesperson has the skills to create and build long-term relationships with customers	MAS3
Cue perception ability	The salesperson is available to assist when customer expresses concern about a serious problem exists	EMA1
	The salesperson demonstrates a sincere interest in my customers.	EMA2
	The salesperson put himself in the customer's shoes to advise and solve the problem	EMA3
Ability to modify self-presentation	The salesperson can always identify customer needs quickly when the customer may not clearly explain what they want	CUA1
	The salesperson can easily reach out and participate in customers' buying process and make customer happy	CUA2
	The cue perception ability is related to the salesperson's cognitive ability, judgement and experience	CUA3
	The salesperson has the ability to control the way he comes across to the customer, depending on what the	AMS1

Experience	situation calls for	
	The salesperson has good vision and flexibility in dealing with clients	AMS2
	The salesperson understands their own strengths and weaknesses	AMS3
Customer orientation	The salesperson has many years of experience in the industry	EXP1
	The salesperson has the ability to distinguish between different kinds of customers	EXP2
	The salesperson has the ability to identify and analyse customer needs	EXP3
	The salesperson can adapt perception and behaviour to work with different clients	EXP4
	The salesperson can easily reach customers and close the sale	EXP5
Value based-selling	The salesperson tries to give customers an accurate expectation of what the product/service will do	CUO1
	The salesperson tries to figure out what a customer's needs are	CUO2
	The salesperson makes every customer feel like he/she is the only customer	CUO3
	The salesperson tries to achieve their goals by satisfying customers	CUO4
	The salesperson tries to capture and update customer trends	CUO5
	Every customer problem is important for the salesperson	CUO6
Value based-selling	The salesperson cares about the customers' processes, focuses on developing relationships and connecting with customers post-purchase so customers don't feel forgotten	VAS1
	The salesperson actively demonstrates to customers the financial impact of working with them.	VAS2
	The salesperson uses a value-based selling approach.	VAS3
	The salesperson works towards improving customers'	VAS4

Adaptive selling behaviour	bottom line.	
	The salesperson always actively listens and give the sincerest advice to customers	VAS5
	The salesperson can easily modify their sales approaches from situation to situation.	ADS1
	The salesperson is very sensitive to the needs of customers.	ADS2
	The salesperson tries to understand how one customer differs from another	ADS3
	The salesperson has a clear understanding of the product, potential customers and competitors	ADS4
	The salesperson shows care and respect for the needs of clients.	ADS5
Satisfaction with salesperson		
	I have an extremely effective working relationship with the salesperson	SWS1
	I will continue to do business with the company even if its prices increase somewhat.	SWS2
	I appreciate the expertise and behaviour of the seller	SWS3
	I prefer to purchase the product he/ she introduces	SWS4
	Satisfaction with salesperson is the customer's subjective evaluations of the company's products/services	SWS5
Trust in salesperson		
	I trust this salesperson to a large extent	TRS1
	I believe that this salesperson is fair and honest with us	TRS2
	The salesperson is reliable because he is mainly concerned with the client's interests, rather than his own.	TRS3
	The salesperson is sincere with me.	TRS4
Anticipation of future interaction		
	I am willing to discuss business with this salesperson again.	AFI1
	I plan to continue doing business with this salesperson.	AFI2
	I will purchase from this salesperson again.	AFI3
	I have a good impression of the company's service and will come back in my next purchase	AFI4

Repurchase intention	
I will most likely buy this service again from the company in the future if I need something similar	REI1
I plan to continue purchasing products/ services from the company	REI2
I intend to recommend the company products that I regularly use to people around me	REI3
I will come back in the future because the salesperson is honest and can understand my preferences well.	REI4
I won't buy it again because I had a bad service experience from the salesperson.	REI5
I would like to work with this salesperson on my next purchases	REI6

Source: Developed for the current study by the researcher

4.5.3.1. Quantitative assessment: pilot study

Adjustment of the questionnaire for testing the hypotheses in the research will be initiated after the end of the qualitative research process. The researcher combined the participants' contributions to make the necessary changes and came up with a complete questionnaire for the field survey (Gupta et al., 2011; Malhotra and Birks, 2000), to help evaluate the validity of the constructs as well as the reliability of the scale through pilot test (Saunders et al., 2007).

4.5.3.1.1. Pilot study

Pilot test, also known as pre-testing software, is frequently used in the process of forming questionnaires and research instruments to verify their conditions before being applied in actual surveys (Malhotra and Birks, 2000). Pilot test is recommended for use in market research for the purpose of looking at important bases in the purification of instruments including assess the clarity of words/statements, form, layout, difficulty of the question, response rate of respondents, time to complete the questionnaire (Denscombe, 2007; Malhotra and Birks, 2000; Ticehurst and Veal, 2005). Pilot test, according to Welman and

Kruger (2001), helps to refine the questionnaire, correct for errors, and avoid ambiguous items, which may cause difficulty for the participant in the process of answering the question, as well as helping to ensure convenience during data recording (Saunders et al., 2007). Along with that, it also helps to measure the time, clarity and reliability of construct and manipulation checks (Malhotra, 1999). Pilot test supports fine-tuning the measurement instruments in a more reasonable way to build validity and reliability for the scales, whereby, the participants do not face any difficulty in the process of answering the survey (Saunders et al., 2007).

After two months of distributing the questionnaires, from March to May 2021, the researcher collected 77 questionnaires, of which 27 were unsatisfactory due to incomplete data and poor quality of answers were eliminated. In the end, 50 complete questionnaires were collected. Demographic profile of consumer's pilot test is shown in Table 4.13. Following that, a thorough questionnaire testing and piloting procedure was implemented.

As a small-scale test, the researchers (Malhotra and Birks, 2000; Sheatsley, 1983) recommend that between 20 and 40 participants respond to the questionnaire in order to obtain an accurate assessment, and effectively carry out the final survey. Therefore, 50 people including experts and members of universities in Vietnam participated to pilot test for the questionnaire. These people were also not invited to the final survey to ensure the objectivity of the survey results (Haralambos and Holborn, 2000).

Table 4. 13: Demographic profile of consumer’s pre-test sample (N=50)

Sample size (N)	N	%
20 to 29 years	16	32
30 to 39 years	29	58
40 to 49 years	3	6
50 to 59 years	1	2
60 years old or more	1	2
Total	50	100
Male	25	50

	Female	25	50
	Total	50	100
	Undergraduate	3	6
	Postgraduate and above	47	94
	Total	50	100
	Top executive or manager	2	4
	Craftsman	1	2
	Student	47	94
	Total	50	100

There are 50 questionnaires gathered during the purification of items in the instrument to check 1) validity and 2) reliability to guarantee that measures are error-free and lead to consistent outcomes (Peter, 1979, p. 6). Cronbach's alpha, considered as a measure of the reliability of the scale, was used to determine if a set of variables is consistent for what they are supposed to measure (Cronbach, 1951). Before starting the main survey, it is critical to create and test the measure used for the reliability (Sileyew, 2019). Validity requires reliability as a prerequisite. Furthermore, in the pilot test, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was used to minimise the number of items and determine patterns in the data (De Vaus, 2002). The scale has good reliability when the value of Cronbach's alpha ranges from 0.6 to 0.8 and less than 0.95 (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). Authors (De Vaus, 2002; Hair et al., 2019; Nunnally, 1978) also states that it will be extremely suitable for most research applications when the alpha coefficient is greater than 0.6. The item would be eliminated, nevertheless, if the corrected item-total correlation coefficient was less than 0.3 (Kim and Stoel, 2004; Streiner, 2003). SAM1, CUP2, SEG1, CUO2, CUO3, IPS2, SAS2, TES1, and MAS1 were removed for item-total correlation coefficient was less than 0.3 (see Table 4.14).

Table 4. 14: A summary of item purification process

Construct	Items dropped	Reasons for dropping the items
SAM	SAM1	Corrected item-total correlation coefficient was less than 0.3
CUP	CUP2	Corrected item-total correlation coefficient was less than 0.3
SEG	SEG1	Corrected item-total correlation coefficient was less than 0.3

CUO		0.3
	CUO2	Corrected item-total correlation coefficient was less than
	CUO3	0.3
IPS	IPS2	Corrected item-total correlation coefficient was less than
		0.3
SAS	SAS2	Corrected item-total correlation coefficient was less than
		0.3
TES	TES1	Corrected item-total correlation coefficient was less than
		0.3
MAS	MAS1	Corrected item-total correlation coefficient was less than
		0.3

Source: Developed by the researcher

Following the research of McDaniel and Gates (2006, p. 222), after removing items, the researcher tested the reliability of the constructs, especially the amended items, to see if it produced positive results, and "the measure no random errors" and "provide consistent data". An essential stage in this process is to look at how participants responded to survey questions/items relevant to the constructs described in the conceptual framework. According to the researchers, the questionnaire, also known as an investigation, to measure psychological differences, requires adequate reliability and validity (Churchill, 1979; Hair et al., 2014).

Research by Hair et al. (2014) suggested that a reliability test is useful in assessing consistency between the number of measurement items that are used to measure a single variable (split-half method). This is correlated with the same respondent's score on the same measurement item at two distinct times (test-retest) (Ticehurst and Veal, 2005). Reliability positively supports measurement consistency, accuracy, as well as preventing bias (error-free) of the reproducibility of reproducing measurement instruments over diverse sample and time frames. Cronbach's alpha, following research by Cronbach (1951); Nunnally (1978); Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), is a popular reliability measure that is chosen for use in a variety of statistical techniques because of the simplicity with which it may be calculated and widely accepted in academic study. From the result table 4.15, it can be seen that the Cronbach's α coefficients of the scales satisfied the requirement for Cronbach's alpha

reliability, which were larger than 0.60 (ranged from 0.648 and above) (Hair et al., 2019; Sekaran, 2003). The results of reliability testing, and analysis of constructs are shown in the following Table 4.15.

Table 4. 15: Reliability measures and for each construct on the basis of the pilot study

Constructs	Cronbach's alpha	Items	Correlated item- total correlation	Cronbach's alpha if the items deleted	Mean	Std.D
Sale model (SAM) (2)	0.866					
		SAM2	0.763	. ^a	5.16	1.856
		SAM3	0.763	. ^a	5.38	1.915
Customer prioritisation (CUP) (2)	0.868					
		CUP1	0.767	. ^a	5.38	1.905
		CUP3	0.767	. ^a	5.34	1.88
Segmentation (SEG) (2)	0.843					
		SEG2	0.731	. ^a	5.58	1.727
		SEG3	0.731	. ^a	5.46	1.854
Interpersonal skills (IPS) (2)	0.753					
		IPS1	0.605	. ^a	5.34	1.189
		IPS3	0.605	. ^a	5.52	1.282
Salesmanship skills (SAS) (2)	0.648					
		SAS1	0.48	. ^a	5.3	1.199
		SAS3	0.48	. ^a	5.94	1.202
Technical skills	0.787					

(TES) (2)					
	TES2	0.649	. ^a	5.48	1.313
	TES3	0.649	. ^a	5.38	1.338
Marketing skills	0.776				
(MAS) (2)					
	MAS2	0.641	. ^a	5.4	1.325
	MAS3	0.641	. ^a	5.42	1.144
Empathic ability	0.793				
(EMA) (3)					
	EMA1	0.6	0.757	3.88	1.534
	EMA2	0.738	0.604	4.04	1.84
	EMA3	0.591	0.766	3.88	1.547
Cue perception ability	0.747				
(CUA) (3)					
	CUA1	0.548	0.693	3.76	1.465
	CUA2	0.637	0.584	3.6	1.678
	CUA3	0.542	0.698	3.78	1.595
Ability to modify self-presentation (AMS)	0.74				
(AMS) (3)					
	AMS1	0.479	0.774	3.8	1.738
	AMS2	0.544	0.684	3.92	1.412
	AMS3	0.699	0.493	3.86	1.539
Experience	0.835				
(EXP) (5)					
	EXP1	0.599	0.813	5.26	1.397
	EXP2	0.712	0.78	4.6	1.678
	EXP3	0.504	0.836	4.94	1.391
	EXP4	0.676	0.791	5.06	1.476
	EXP5	0.697	0.785	4.76	1.546

Customer orientation	0.858				
(CUO) (4)					
		CUO1	0.726	0.81	4.52 1.403
		CUO4	0.726	0.809	4.24 1.422
		CUO5	0.568	0.87	4.74 1.382
		CUO6	0.8	0.775	4.24 1.598
Value-based selling	0.883				
(VAS) (5)					
		VAS1	0.81	0.836	4.66 1.334
		VAS2	0.741	0.853	4.7 1.298
		VAS3	0.667	0.87	4.84 1.201
		VAS4	0.611	0.882	5.28 1.107
		VAS5	0.775	0.845	4.74 1.352
Adaptive selling behaviour	0.92				
(ADS) (6)					
		ADS1	0.807	0.901	5.24 1.756
		ADS2	0.818	0.899	5.22 1.73
		ADS3	0.636	0.923	5.62 1.537
		ADS4	0.795	0.903	5.58 1.703
		ADS5	0.774	0.906	5.44 1.618
		ADS6	0.805	0.901	5.32 1.671
Salesperson performance	0.949				
(SPP) (7)					
		SPP1	0.846	0.939	5.4 1.641
		SPP2	0.817	0.941	5.38 1.615
		SPP3	0.835	0.94	5.34 1.52
		SPP4	0.71	0.95	5.7 1.515
		SPP5	0.848	0.939	5.24 1.744
		SPP6	0.863	0.938	5.4 1.578
		SPP7	0.869	0.937	5.74 1.601
Satisfaction with	0.876				

salesperson (SWS) (5)					
	SWS1	0.693	0.853	4.22	1.941
	SWS2	0.742	0.843	5.22	1.67
	SWS3	0.636	0.865	5.04	1.714
	SWS4	0.646	0.866	4.1	2.053
	SWS5	0.833	0.816	4.44	1.991
Trust in salesperson (TRS) (4) 0.868					
	TRS1	0.803	0.799	4.22	1.447
	TRS2	0.807	0.793	4.26	1.601
	TRS3	0.802	0.796	4.32	1.531
	TRS4	0.491	0.918	4.72	1.539
Anticipation of future Interaction (AFI) (4) 0.845					
	AFI1	0.737	0.778	4.86	1.443
	AFI2	0.59	0.84	4.36	1.336
	AFI3	0.75	0.774	4.52	1.344
	AFI4	0.655	0.816	5.36	1.481
Repurchase intention. (REI) (6) 0.934					
	REI1	0.84	0.917	4.74	1.496
	REI2	0.846	0.916	4.56	1.704
	REI3	0.746	0.929	4.56	1.567
	REI4	0.838	0.918	4.78	1.489
	REI5	0.827	0.919	4.68	1.647
	REI6	0.737	0.93	4.54	1.46

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

According to Chandon et al. (1997) and Hair et al. (1998), exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is a useful method for condensing a large set of observed variables into a smaller set with more significant and more manageable factors. EFA assists in investigating factorial structures by considering three basic assumptions: the absolute sample size, the correlation

coefficient in correlation matrix, and the sampling adequacy (Hair et al., 1998, pp. 98-100). Performing EFA also helps to ensure the correct upload of individual items for the respective elements. Through the results table 4.16, all factor loadings were high (≥ 0.5), and no garbage items were found because they were removed in the previous Cronbach's alpha testing to ensure high reliability (Churchill, 1979).

Table 4. 16: Reliability measures for each construct on the basis of the pilot study

Constructs	Cronbach's alpha	Items	Correlated item-total correlation	Mean	SD	EFA Final loading
Salesperson performance	.949					
		SPP7	0.846	5.4	1.641	.896
		SPP6	0.817	5.38	1.615	.892
		SPP5	0.835	5.34	1.52	.875
		SPP1	0.71	5.7	1.515	.872
		SPP3	0.848	5.24	1.744	.859
		SPP2	0.863	5.4	1.578	.842
		SPP4	0.869	5.74	1.601	.729
Sales model	.866					
		SAM3	0.763	5.16	1.856	.873
		SAM2	0.763	5.38	1.915	.873
Customer prioritisation	.868					
		CUP1	0.767	5.38	1.905	.875
		CUP3	0.767	5.34	1.88	.875
Segmentation	.843					
		SEG2	0.731	5.58	1.727	.730
		SEG3	0.731	5.46	1.854	.730
Customer orientation	.858					
		CUO1	0.726	4.52	1.403	.894
		CUO4	0.726	4.24	1.422	.806

	CUO5	0.568	4.74	1.382	.799
	CUO6	0.8	4.24	1.598	.607
Value based selling		.883			
	VAS1	0.81	4.66	1.334	.879
	VAS5	0.741	4.7	1.298	.836
	VAS2	0.667	4.84	1.201	.798
	VAS3	0.611	5.28	1.107	.714
	VAS4	0.775	4.74	1.352	.651
Interpersonal skills		.753			
	IPS3	0.605	5.34	1.189	.858
	IPS1	0.605	5.52	1.282	.740
Salesmanship skills		.648			
	SAS3	0.48	5.94	1.202	.756
	SAS1	0.48	5.3	1.199	.685
Technical skills		.787			
	TES2	0.649	5.48	1.313	.805
	TES3	0.649	5.38	1.338	.805
Marketing skills		.776			
	MAS2	0.641	5.4	1.325	.800
	MAS3	0.641	5.42	1.144	.800
Empathetic ability		.793			
	EMA2	0.6	3.88	1.534	.947
	EMA1	0.738	4.04	1.84	.665
	EMA3	0.591	3.88	1.547	.652
Cue perception ability		.747			
	CUA2	0.548	3.76	1.465	.831
	CUA1	0.637	3.6	1.678	.651
	CUA3	0.542	3.78	1.595	.638
Ability to modify self-presentation		.740			
	AMS3	0.479	3.8	1.738	.989

	AMS2	0.544	3.92	1.412	.639
	AMS1	0.699	3.86	1.539	.528
Experience .835					
	EXP2	0.599	5.26	1.397	.803
	EXP5	0.712	4.6	1.678	.787
	EXP4	0.504	4.94	1.391	.739
	EXP1	0.676	5.06	1.476	.668
	EXP3	0.697	4.76	1.546	.550
Adaptive selling .920 behaviour					
	ADS2	0.807	5.24	1.756	.864
	ADS1	0.818	5.22	1.73	.848
	ADS6	0.636	5.62	1.537	.841
	ADS4	0.795	5.58	1.703	.835
	ADS5	0.774	5.44	1.618	.813
	ADS3	0.805	5.32	1.671	.662
Satisfaction with .876 salesperson					
	SWS5	0.693	4.22	1.941	.912
	SWS2	0.742	5.22	1.67	.804
	SWS1	0.636	5.04	1.714	.753
	SWS4	0.646	4.1	2.053	.692
	SWS3	0.833	4.44	1.991	.682
Trust in .868 salesperson					
	TRS3	0.803	4.22	1.447	.907
	TRS2	0.807	4.26	1.601	.890
	TRS1	0.802	4.32	1.531	.870
	TRS4	0.491	4.72	1.539	.512
Anticipation of .845 future interaction					
	AFI3	0.737	4.86	1.443	.851
	AFI1	0.59	4.36	1.336	.837
	AFI4	0.75	4.52	1.344	.718
	AFI2	0.655	5.36	1.481	.639
Repurchase .934					

intention					
	REI2	0.84	4.74	1.496	.884
	REI1	0.846	4.56	1.704	.877
	REI4	0.746	4.56	1.567	.873
	REI5	0.838	4.78	1.489	.864
	REI3	0.827	4.68	1.647	.772
	REI6	0.737	4.54	1.46	.760

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

Through the preliminary evaluation results, it can be seen that the measurement scales of this study meet the requirements of reliability and validity. The questionnaire design was finalised with 69 items.

4.6. MAIN SURVEY

Survey is one of the essential measurement methods commonly used in applied social research today. By using a self-administered questionnaire, which consisted of a series of closed-ended and open-ended questions that participants could easily answer on their own without an interviewer, the study collected important data for the main survey from Vietnamese consumers of shopping malls in Vietnam from October to December 2021. Non-random/ convenience sampling technique (McDaniel and Gates, 2006) was also applied in this study. Sampling methods and sample sizes are also clarified in the following paragraphs.

4.6.1. Target population and sampling

According to Bryman and Bell (2007, p. 182), the sample is composed of the population segment selected for the survey. The researcher applies sampling procedures in order to obtain statistics and generalise the findings to a broader population. The "research population" refers to the larger group of which the sample is a subset. Malhotra and Birks (2000) state that a sample is a group of elements drawn from a population that reflects the research topic and is assumed to have strong external validity (Churchill, 1999; Malhotra and Birks, 2000). Sampling should be carried out carefully, describing accurately and clearly the

characteristics of the population since sampling frame error, population specification error, and selection error can all bias the sample design (McDaniel and Gates, 1993). The characteristics of the participants' gender, age, and education level were all required to be included in the questionnaire. The population in the study by Bryman and Bell (2007) is known as “the universe of units from which the sample is to be selected. The "unit" here can be any region, country, company... but not necessarily the people sampled. As a result, the study's population is referred to more widely, as the population of the entire country (p.182).

The majority of studies require large amounts of data from diverse population sizes, although researchers seldom survey the whole community. Using samples from the target population is standard procedure. The sample population consists of a group of participants drawn from a broader population for survey purposes (Taherdoost, 2015; Salant and Dillman, 1994). The main advantage of sampling is saving money and time. The population sample needs to be representative of the whole population so the researcher can generalise or make useful inferences from this sample to the untested population. The sample survey allows for the collection of critical information from a small number of respondents in order to explain the features of the total population. Small sample size is difficult to give accurate answers to research questions. On the contrary, large sample size will cost researchers a lot of time and resources, a higher degree of accuracy can be achieved but only to a minimum. During the design phase of any study, the sample size must be decided. According to Salant and Dillman (1994), there are four important factors to decide on sample size: 1) the amount of sampling error that may be allowed; 2) population size; 3) the population's diversity in terms of the characteristics to be investigated; and 4) the smallest subgroup in the sample for which estimation is required.

The sampling approach is distinguished by scholars (Bryman and Bell, 2007) into two main categories, probability, and non-probability sampling. Probability sample is a sample in which subjects are randomly selected, each subject in the population has an equal chance of being selected as a representative sample. With this population-selective approach, it is typically anticipated that a representative sample is more likely to be obtained. Probability sampling also helps to minimise sampling error (p. 182).

Accordingly, these scholars define a non-probability sample as a sample that is not approached in a random way and is selected according to the subjective judgement of the researcher. This means that the units in the population do not have an equal chance of being selected as a representative sample (Bryman and Bell, 2007, p. 182). Non-probability sampling can be convenient sampling, purposive sampling, or snowball sampling to explore and learn more about a certain feature of the population. This study applies the non-random sampling/convenience sampling approach, which is one of the most prominent and widely applied sampling methods in business and management compared to probability sampling (Bryman and Bell, 2007, p.198).

The main population of this study is the Vietnamese customers of shopping centres in Ho Chi Minh City Vietnam. The survey was also conducted in Vietnamese, took place over a 2-month period, from October to December 2021, and focused on customers' perceptions of salesperson performance and its effects on customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intentions at those shopping malls in Vietnam. Various data collection methods were applied in this study. Through convenience sampling to choose individuals who were conveniently available, 1240 questionnaires were sent out as part of the study. And according to Denscombe (2007), It is a challenge to be able to get all the answers from every contact attempted in a survey. The questionnaire and its online link were emailed to participants in March 2022, and responses were requested within the following month. As a result, 197 questionnaires were answered out of 500 questionnaires, 32 of which were obtained through phone interviews. In addition, 500 questionnaires were also sent to the researcher's friends along with acquaintances living around. However, data collection under this method (postal survey) often has a low response rate, as well as not high accuracy due to the distance between the researcher and the participant.

183 questionnaires were collected face to face at Vincom shopping centre in Vietnam. The researcher enlisted the help of shopping centre managers to be able to reach their customers and obtain the necessary data for this research topic. According to Churchill (1999), face to face survey is also favoured in large-scale surveys because of its advantages over mail and

telephone surveys, about the complexity and quality of the data collected, ensure the ability of the target participant to complete the questionnaire. Snowball sampling is a non-probability sampling used as a distributive method to enlarge the sample size for research and ensure that representative samples can contain the most knowledgeable informants. This method is implemented by asking the first objects in the population to recommend the next objects that can provide more detailed information and satisfy the sampling needs of the study (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Mweshi and Sakyi, 2020). In addition, Stevens (1996) recommends that a precise statistical analysis data sample should include more than 300 respondents. The research collected a total of 412 questionnaires, of which 27 questionnaires were discarded due to large amounts of missing data. After trying to increase the response rate, 385 questionnaires were completed and can be used for analysis.

There are a total of 11 pages of the survey questionnaire, along with a cover letter attached to the front cover following the recommendation of Dillman (2000). In addition, research by Armstrong and Overton (1977) states that non-response bias depends on respondents' interest in survey questionnaire items. Those interested in the field surveyed tend to respond more easily and vice versa (p.2).

4.6.2. Appropriate number of participants

This section will go through the methods that are most typically used to determine a suitable sample size. It is difficult and takes time to choose an appropriate number of participants for a sample size. According to Hair et al. (2014), the primary technique employed is associated with data analysis procedures or techniques, and there are five key considerations that determine sample size in SEM to produce credible estimates (Raykov and Widaman, 1995) are: 1) 'multivariate data distribution', a greater ratio of responses to parameters is required when dealing with non-normal data (i.e. 15:1). 2) With the maximum likelihood (ML) method, the recommended sample size is between 150 and 140 responses. Besides, the sample size should also vary from 150 to 400 responses if the structural equation modelling (SEM) is employed in research, which is based on the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) method. However, this MLE method is not suitable when the sample size is larger

than 400, the results of the goodness-of-fit measures will also get worse (Hair et al., 20014). 3) In the case of 'model complexity', the general rule of sample size is SEM with a model of five structures or less than 5, the sample size can be computed with a modest sample size of 100 to 150, if each construct is measured by more than 3 items and its communalities value are higher than 0.6. If any model possesses constructs with less than 3 items, or has modest communalities values between 0.45 and 0.55, the recommended sample size is 200. However, for models with more than 6 factors, there are some constructs that are measured by less than 3 items, and the value of communalities is low, the sample size requirement in this case should be higher than 500 (Hair et al., 20014). 4) 'Missing data,' if there is a chance that more than 10% of the data may be missing, the sample size should be raised. 5) 'Average error variance of indicator', if the items communalities are smaller than 0.5, larger sample sizes are required.

Following the research of Roscoe (1975), there are some basic principles to determine the optimal sample sizes in behavioural research investigations based on an examination of acceptable confidence levels. 1) For the majority of studies, is an appropriately representative number of samples. 2) If researchers have more than one group (e.g. male and female), each group must have at least 30 participants. 3) When using multivariate analysis, the sample size should be at least 10 times the number of variables in the study. Also, to achieve highly reliable results, Stevens (1996) recommends that there should be 15 instances per construct. Meanwhile, Bentler and Chou (1987) state that if the data is regularly distributed, the researcher only needs at least 5 cases for each parameter. 4) For a basic experiment, the optimum sample size should be 10 to 20 people. According to Comrey and Lee (1992), sample sizes are rated as follows: sample size with 50 participants is very bad, 100 is bad, 200 is acceptable, 300 is good, 500 is very good, and 1000 is considered an excellent sample size.

From the foregoing, it can be said that there is no precise limit to sample size determination in the methodology literature. Along with that, there is no evidence or empirical study that fully demonstrates the effects of salesperson performance on customer perception (Echchakoui, 2017; Katsikeas et al., 2018; Liao and Chuang, 2004; Zang et al., 2020), this

study is, therefore, the most comprehensive and rigorous test to understand the associations between study constructs. Through the application of SEM technique, an empirical ratio of at least five observations per estimate parameter (Bollen, 1989) and communalities values are greater than 0.5 (Hair et al., 20014) has also been offered. Taking the above into consideration, the sample size determined in the research is 385 participants.

4.7. QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

A salesperson's performance is closely tied to the functional quality of a company and influences future engagement and repurchase intentions. Thus, it is important to evaluate how salesperson performance works in the case of a particular company. A related company was assigned to the participants to conduct the assessment and respond to the questionnaire. According to Ahearne et al. (2005); Bhattacharya and Elsbach (2002), the Vietnamese participants were asked to name the most appealing Vietnam shopping malls, and the Vincom (Saigon Centre) was selected for this investigation following a similar strategy.

From the analysis in the literature and the above conceptual model, the questionnaire in this study was designed to be concise in order to make it easier for participants to answer the questions as well as high accuracy for the collected data. In support of this, research by Schaefer and Dillman (1998) affirms that the questionnaire has a clear structure and layout that provides convenience and comfort for the participants to complete it effectively.

A filter question was chosen to start the questionnaire to investigate how familiar the participants were with the company mentioned (Krosnick, 2018). The questionnaire included statements to assess the participants' attitudes about the mall, the performance of the salespeople there, and the intention to engage in the interaction as well as the intention to make a repeat purchase. Participants were also able to express their spontaneous views by answering questions about salesperson performance at Vincom ('How would you describe the salesperson's performance at Vincom?') and ('What does salesperson performance at Vincom mean to you?' and 'In your opinion, what should Vincom adjust to their employees?'). To the

attitude scales, participants need carefully complete the questionnaire to confirm that they understand and answer the questions (Churchill, 1999).

Accordingly, the Likert popularity scale is preferred to be used in marketing studies generally and this study particularly, which requires participants to score their level of agreement or disagreement in order to evaluate attitudes regarding the salesperson performance. Attitude scale is used to explore an individual's beliefs and perceptions. Attitudes towards oneself, others, a range of activities and circumstances may all be measured (Gay, 1996). A seven-point Likert scale, as recommended by Churchill and Peter (1984), was also selected for this survey instead of the five-point Likert scale to reduce measurement error variance and boost construct variance. In essence, the five-point scale is a rather coarse method for thoroughly and accurately collecting relevant data for study. Despite the emergence of simplicity and convenience, the five-point Likert scale remains limited in capturing the more detailed responses that participants desire to reflect (Russell and Bobko, 1992). Increasing scale steps facilitate the increasing of reliability. Specifically, the seven-point Likert scale was found to be more stable and function more optimally than the five-point scale overall (Diefenbach et al., 1993, p 189; Finstad, 2010). Although it can take more time and effort to organise the data collected, the seven-point Likert scale is always appreciated for its accuracy and ease of use by providing slightly more options (strongly disagree and strongly agree) for participants to give even more precise and granular responses about the emerging phenomenon under study (Miller, 1956). The advantage of the seven-point Likert scale is being able to detect smaller differences. It was also discovered to have a greater correlation with t-test findings (Lewis, 1993). As mentioned above, the participants were consumers at the shopping mall, and the questions were all employed interval scales and scores on the Likert type scale (anchored by 0, strongly disagree and 7, strongly agree) according on how much the customer understanding of the scenarios (Shiu et al., 2009, p. 421; Wright et al., 2021). Follow by Welman and Kruger (2001), statements with only two options, 'strongly disagree' and 'strongly agree', were also carefully considered for use in the survey.

Based on valuable previous research in this field, salesperson performance has been likened to a signal of quality and value to customers (Hartline and Jones, 1996; Hartline et al., 2003;

Nunkoo et al., 2020), have a significant impact on sales volume and customer loyalty (Buciuniene and Skudiene, 2015), constituting company success, improving attitudes, and satisfaction of customers (Obiageli et al., 2015). In addition, customers' trust with the company is formed from their perceptions with the quality of the company's products and services (Amyx et al., 2016) and interactive experiences (Prentice et al., 2018, 2019; So et al., 2014). It can be seen that there is a gap between salesperson performance and future interaction intentions and customer repurchase intentions. To be able to investigate the effects of salesperson performance and its factors on customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intentions, the degree of match between employee performance were generated in the customer's mind and combined with the participants' responses to their satisfaction with the salesperson, trust in salesperson was measured as absolute difference scores. The manner in which a person perceives themselves is linked to the manner they express themselves in social circumstances. Thus, investigating the correlations between salesperson performance and future customer involvement intentions gives crucial data on attitudes and behaviours that managers can use to mold and develop more effective tactics in target markets. The main survey yielded the observed values for consumers' perceptions with salesperson performance and their interaction intention.

Demographic information of the participants including age, gender, occupation was also identified and distributed at the end of the questionnaire to help the researcher can categorise existing consumers' concerns and perceptions, accurately measure their satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the salespeople performance at the shopping mall.

Following the preliminary analysis, the questionnaire was adjusted to make it easier for participants to complete it (Saunders et al., 2007; Sekaran, 2003). And to ensure a high response rate, the official questionnaire that was distributed consisted of (eleven) pages, attached with a cover letter (Schaefer and Dillman, 1998) (see Appendix 4.2). General instructions as well as a pledge of secrecy are also provided in the front sheet. The questionnaire layout was assessed by experts.

4.8. DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES AND STATISTICAL PACKAGES

There were three steps to data analysis in this study. The first stage involves refining the content and scale based on the data gathered from qualitative and quantitative research. At the second stage, the scales were then validated using the quantitative data that was obtained from the primary survey. And then the final model was put to the test in the third stage.

Research by Churchill (1979) suggested that multi-item scale development is employed for each construct will help to boost reliability and reduce measurement errors. The researcher also recommends multi-item scales over single-item measures. Therefore, a triple approach was used for data analysis.

- a. A data reduction technique, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was used in both the pilot and the main research to minimise the number of items to a smaller set and to define any patterns in the data (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Maskey et al., 2018). The coefficient alpha was used to examine the quantitative data received from the collected data in order to determine the reliability of the scale and the instrument's quality (internal consistency) (Churchill, 1979; Peter, 1979; Parasuraman et al., 1998; Vaske et al., 2017).
- b. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was applied on the main survey data to verify the measurement properties of the current scales' validity (Brown, 2015; Credé and Harms, 2019; Hair et al., 1998); it is a good tool to have if scales need to be built for further investigation in structural modelling and utilised to check the theory of the underlying latent variables (Hair et al., 1998).
- c. Structure equation modelling (SEM) is used to test relationships between hypotheses as well as to prevent potential associations between structural models and measurements (Hair et al., 2014; Ringle et al., 2020).

Many scholars have endorsed the usage of SPSS 27.0 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) (Field, 2013; Pallant, 2020; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2014). SPSS was employed as the first stage of data analysis for a variety of research purpose (Abu-Bader, 2021; Norusis, 1999; 1993) as follows: 1) coding, editing, checking missing data, 2) testing the normality, linearity, multi-collinearity, and outliers of the research assumptions (Skewness and Kurtosis of data were considered for a normal data distribution), 3) indicating the central tendency and dispersion of research variables through calculating the mean, standard deviation, and analysing frequencies, 4) descriptive analysis was carried out for exploratory factor analysis employing a sample overview (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007), 5) the data is subjected to a reliability test to determine the instrument's validity and reliability (Churchill, 1979; Peter, 1979), the refinement is based on reliability and dimensionality. The test was performed to evaluate the scales used to measure the structures and to refine the measurements (Churchill, 1979).

Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) 24.0 was utilised as a unique graphical interface to assess the quality of the suggested measurement model and hypothesised structural model. It is applicable to perform a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structural modelling (Byrne, 2001; Hung, 2021). The characteristics of the following approaches are addressed in detail in the following section: exploratory factor analysis (EFA), coefficient alpha and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and for scale development and validation structural equation modelling (SEM) for model assessment. The rationale for using these methods is also highlighted.

4.8.1. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and coefficient alpha

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is a fundamental and effective approach for determining scale validity in the initial stages (Haig, 2014; Netemeyer et al., 2003). EFA is a highly data-driven theory-building (exploratory approach) and a practical scale used in research investigations to decrease the number of observed variables (indicators) to a smaller, more meaningful, and manageable set (Crede and Harms, 2019; Hair et al., 1998).

Exploratory factor analysis assures that "each individual factor accounts for the difference of at least one unique variable" (Hair et al., 1998, p. 103). It assists in understanding the structure of a certain field by recognising components that are independent of one another (Hair et al., 1998, 2010). EFA is also used for the purpose of investigating the data and notifying the researcher about the pool of feasible factors that are well representative of the data (Hair et al., 2010). EFA is also perceived as a preliminary analytical procedure to prepare data for SEM (Liu et al., 2019; Steenkamp and Trijp, 1991). Before conducting the factor analysis and reliability test, the items for each construct were evaluated. In both the pilot and the main study, exploratory factor analysis was also used to minimise the number of items and detect any patterns in the data (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Wang et al., 2019). Conducting EFA in research also allows examining the factor structure of each variable in the conceptual framework and proposes a variety of dimensions related to the underlying conceptions (Churchill, 1979).

The principal components approach was used to extract factors (Hair et al., 2014; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). This approach was regarded as the total variance (i.e. common, mean, unique and error variances) to determine the least number of factors required to explain the largest amount of variance. As a solution, an orthogonal Varimax rotation approach was considered for use in this study, which is especially valuable for reducing the number of variables to a smaller group of qualitatively uncorrelated variables. Following that, Hair et al. (1998) states that these variables are utilised in a subsequent prediction method. Eigenvalues was used in determining the number of elements to extract (Hair et al., 1998) and were specified using the latent root criteria (eigenvalue >1.00).

4.8.2. Structural equation modelling (SEM)

Follow the research of Hair et al. (2014), this study applied structural equation modelling (SEM) with the Amos software package to isolate relationships for each dependent variable in order to obtain a more comprehensive view of the numerous influences and relationships in this study. The proposed conceptual framework was evaluated using the literature study and then the hypotheses were tested using a structural equation model.

SEM is basically a set of statistical procedures developed for the purpose of analysing a set of relationships between numerous independent or dependent variables, and they can even be continuous or discrete (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). SEM can be considered to have the strongest explanatory power. Both exogenous and endogenous variables can be factors or variables that can be measured in the same way.

According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2007, p. 676), structural equation modelling is also known by the following terms causal modelling, causal analysis, simultaneous equation modelling, analysis of covariance structures, path analysis, or confirmatory factor analysis. The last two are two distinct kinds of SEM. There are several reasons for deciding to use SEM in this study (Hair et al., 2014; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). First, basic statistical methods are only useful for a certain number of variables and cannot deal with the complex phenomena or theories covered in the research, while SEM can test these complex phenomena. SEM is the only special analytical technique that enables multiple dependent relationships between observable indicators and the unobserved/latent variable (i.e. by using the measurement model) implemented concurrently and completely. It also allows for testing the relationships among latent variables (i.e. by using the structural model) by computing multiple regression equations, which is superior to a variety of other statistical techniques (i.e. SPSS) that only investigates only a single relationship at a time. Second, unlike EFA with exploratory technique, SEM is known as a confirmatory technique because it expresses the specifications of a model. Third, SEM is useful in determining the reliability, validity, and unidimensionality of each construct separately. Fourth, an advantage that makes SEM superior to other multivariate methods is its ability to estimate both direct and indirect relationships. Fifth, SEM not only gives some good estimates of measurement error, but also facilitates hypothesis testing for inferential purposes. Sixth, by using latent variables in the calculation of measurement errors, SEM can help determine the overall goodness-of-fit to assess the measurement model. Seventh, SEM permits problems regarding multiple regression analyses of factors to be answered.

4.8.2.1. Stages in structural equation modelling

There are two stages to perform SEM data analysis in this investigation. As for the first stage, the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) for each construct is applied to assess the measurement attributes of the model's underlying latent variables. The measuring model is employed for the following compelling reasons:

- a. The measurement model represents the causal relationships between observable indicators (variables) and associated latent constructs (variables) (Anderson and Gerbing, 1982; Chau, 1997; Foroudi et al., 2021; Malek et al., 2021) as for the unidimensionality assumption. The unidimensionality, according to Garver and Mentzer (1999), is evaluated by the overall fit of the confirmatory model. It is also described as a set of indications with only one underlying construct (Hair et al., 1998). Confirmatory factor analysis evolved from exploratory factor analysis, to evaluate another crucial attribute as well as the unidimensionality of scale (Steenkamp and van Trijp, 1991). Also in this step, a confirmatory measurement model was applied to define the strong relationships between the observed variables and the corresponding constructs (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988), in order to guarantee that the standardised factor loading values were more than 0.5 or above. The purpose of the confirmatory factor analysis was to assess whether each group of items was internally consistent (Parasuraman et al., 1998).

- b. The validity and reliability of the construct have an important implication for theory testing in the future. Following EFA, CFA also enables to calculate a composite reliability estimate, which is an additional evaluation of the reliability of a construction (Gerbing and Anderson, 1988, Hair et al., 1998).

For the second stage, a structural model was employed to assess the development of a measurement that validates the associations between a construct and its indicators, as well as an evaluation of the structural model to account for the fortuitous associations between latent

construct (Anderson and Gerbing, 1982). All of the constructs can be measured using latent variables, observable variables, or a mix of both.

4.8.3. Evaluating the fit of the model

CFA has a significant contribution to the validation phase because it has complete control over the description of the construct's indicators, offering a statistical evaluation of goodness-of-fit and dimensionality for the specific measurement model (Hair et al., 1998). Accordingly, the research of Hair et al. (2014) indicates that CFA was conducted for the purpose of validating measurement factors found within a set of variables in a theoretical model.

Bollen (1989) claims that unidimensional measures are commonly assumed for examining reliability (Bollen, 1989). Novick and Lewis (1967) argue that the standard marketing reliability index, coefficient alpha, undervalues the reliability of a multidimensional measure. Along with that, research by Hunter and Gerbing (1982) states that for the successful application of the coefficient alpha and for assessing the goodness-of-fit of any model that considers theoretical, statistical, and practical aspects, unidimensionality is necessary. As indicated in the methodological literature on CFA, the absolute fit indices, incremental fit indices, and model parsimony indices were utilised and detailed further below.

First, both the incremental fitness index as well as the absolute fit index were employed in this study. According to Hair et al. (1998), the absolute fit index is to test both structural and measurement models. These indices reflect the extent to which the hypothetical model reproduces the sample data. The goodness-of-fit indices help to assess the measurement models' nomological validity. Absolute fit indices do not employ an alternative model as a reference point. Some of the selected absolute fit indices are presented in detail as follows:

- a. Chi-square (χ^2) is one of the testing methods commonly applied in the field of economic and social research to measure the goodness-of-fit. It is known as the first measure of goodness-of-fit given in the Amos output. According to Hair et al. (1998),

low chi-square index (χ^2) presents no significance, which means a good fit. In addition, the chi-square test is applied to the measurement of both the actual matrix and the prediction matrix, from then on, it can be said that there is no significant difference between the actual matrix and the prediction matrix when chi-square is low (no significance). The significance of the p-value is the likelihood of the study's results, indicating a significant difference between a model and a null model in terms of goodness-of-fit. The null is generally '0' in statistics. According to MacLean and Gray (1998), when the p-value is high or greater than 0, it means that the null hypothesis is rejected with a high probability of being incorrect. Conversely, when the p-value is low or close to 0, the null hypothesis being rejected occurs with a low likelihood of being incorrect in reaching that conclusion. In statistics, it is not supposed to exist the difference between the two actual and predicted matrices ($p > 0.05$). Since chi-square is found to be highly sensitive to sample size, this fit simply employed to test the overall goodness-of-fit of the research model has been criticised (Hair et al., 2014; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

According to Kline (1998), a chi-square (χ^2)/ df ratio is 3 or less, this highlights the model's acceptable fit. Chi-square is particularly sensitive to sample size when the number of observations is more than 200. When the data deviates from normalcy, the chi-square is then higher than what would be predicted from error in the research model. There are no specific rules established to determine the minimum acceptable standard of chi-square (χ^2), also known as T. As determined by Hair et al. (1998), chi-square is an index showing the initial fit for structural models, which is recommended to be used in conjunction with other indices. This index is provided in SEM findings on a regular basis.

- b. The goodness-of-fit index (GFI) was developed by researchers Joreskog and Sorbom (1982) as the first measure of a research model to generate a fit statistic that was less susceptible to sample size. The GFI calculates the sample covariance matrix's relative amount of variance and covariance, which is defined through the population covariance matrix, for the purpose of determining how well the model fits when

- compared to the null model. The values of the GFI are between zero (0) and one (1), with values around 1 or near to 1 representing a good fit. The goodness-of-fit index is set to 1 if it is more than 1, otherwise, is set to 0 if it is less than 1. Specifically, the value of the GFI must be between 0.9 and 1.00. Values range from 0.80 to 0.89, indicating that the fit is reasonable and acceptable (Doll et al., 1994), whereas values below 0.8 should be excluded (Tanaka and Huba, 1985). The variance represents the core concept of measuring a model's goodness-of-fit.
- c. The adjusted goodness-of-fit Index (AGFI) is valuable in evaluating competing models, used to adjust the GFI value according to degrees of freedom in the model compared with the null model's degrees of freedom (Hair et al., 1998). The GFI and AGFI are chi-square-based computations that are degree-of-freedom independent. Because the AGFI allows the GFI to be adjusted according to degrees of freedom, models with more parameters, therefore, have lower values. The AGFI is equivalent to the GFI in that it substitutes the mean sum of squares for the total sum of squares. The AGFI must be higher than 0.90, reflecting an appropriate fit (Bentler and Bonett, 1980). The AGFI values ranged from zero (0) to one (1) and were regarded to be a good fit when its values of 0.9 or above, specifically between 0.9 and 1.00 (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2014; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). Besides, values between 0.80 and 0.89 describe an acceptable fit.
- d. Root-mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) is an exceptionally useful criterion for assessing model fit. The RMSEA index, according to Steiger (1990), quantifies the degree of freedom difference between the sample and fitted covariance matrices, and is susceptible to a large number of parameters (MacCallum et al., 1996). RMSEA focuses on assessing population disparities rather than sampling. As defined by Hair et al. (2014), RMSEA reflects the degree to which a model fits a population (p. 748). The RMSEA with a value less than 0.05 is considered a good fit, value till 0.08 suggests an acceptable fit. Meanwhile, a value over 0.08 is regarded as an inadequate and inappropriate fit (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2014; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

Second, the incremental fit indices compute how well the provided models fit the null model (Hair et al., 2014). A number of incremental fit indices are included in this study as follows:

The normed fit index (NFI), also known as the Bentler-Bonett index, is a metric used to analyse nested models (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). NFI can compare the research model with a previously proposed model without taking the degree of freedom into account. According to Hair et al. (2014), NFI helps evaluate the degree of improvement of a research model compared to the baseline model in terms of fitness. Moreover, NFI is also useful in comparing the chi-square (χ^2) value of the research model with the independence model (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2014; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). The NFI index, on the other hand, does not account for degrees of freedom and undervalues the fit in small samples (Byrne, 2001). The comparative fit index (CFI) is supposed to be an enhanced version of the NFI (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2014; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

The comparative fit index (CFI) measure depends on the non-centrality measure. It is set to one, if the index is higher than one, otherwise, to zero if the index is lower than one. CFI is seen as a good fit for values near to one (Bentler, 1990). Following the research of some scholars such as Byrne (2001); Hair et al. (2014); Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), CFI is determined based on the average magnitude of the data's correlations. The CFI will not be particularly high if the average correlation between variables is not very strong.

The Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) or non-normed fit index (NNFI) is the last prominent index mentioned in this investigation. The Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) is not only used to compare the chi-square value of the research model with the independence model, but also examines both models' degrees of freedom (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2014; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). And similar to CFI, TLI is based on the average size of the data's relationships. The TLI will not be particularly high if the average correlation between variables is not very strong. It is recognised as a mathematical comparison with the null model as a reference to effectively measure the theoretical model (Hair et al., 2014). TLI with a value of 0.9 or greater is regarded great, 0.8 is deemed reasonable (Gerbing and Anderson, 1992). TLI is a

specific example for parsimony correction, although its actual purpose was not designed to do so. Table 4.17 displays the findings of the best fitting model.

Table 4. 17: Results of the best fitting model

	Type	Acceptance level in this research
Coefficient alpha (α)		$\alpha > 0.7$ adequate and > 0.5 is acceptable
Standardised Regression Weight	Unidimensionality	Beta > 0.15
Chi-square (with associated degrees of freedom and probability of significant different) (df, p)	Model fit	$p > 0.05$ (at α equals to 0.05 level)
Normed chi-square (/df)	Absolute fit and model parsimony	$< /df < 3.0$
Normalised fit index (NFI) Non-normalised fit index (NNFI) Comparative fit index (CFI)	Incremental fit Compare your model to baseline independence model	Values above 0.08 and close 0.90 indicate acceptable fit
Goodness-of-fit index (GFI)		0.90
Adjusted goodness-of-fit (AGFI)		0.90
Root means square error of approximation (RMSEA)	Absolute fit	0.08

Source: Developed from Hair *et al.* (2014)

4.8.4. Unidimensionality

Unidimensionality is an important quality for measurements since it is indispensable but not sufficient for construct validity (Gerbing and Anderson, 1988). Cronbach (1984) classified "a set of things as 'unidimensional' if their order of difficulty is the same for everyone in a population of interest" (p. 116). Anderson and Gerbing (1988) state that a unidimensional item (indicator) possesses a fundamental structure, and a unidimensional measure is made up of unidimensional items or indices. In addition, in order to isolate measurement concerns (the relationship between construct and observed variables) and structural concerns (the

connection between structures) of the research model, unidimensionality was commonly assumed for the research model estimated with structural equation analysis (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988).

Anderson and Gerbing (1982) advocated applying the structural equation analysis theories of external and internal consistency to operate the unidimensionality. Besides, Kenny (1979) indicated that consistency is the structural equation model that is compatible with the data. Consistency developed by Anderson and Gerbing (1982), containing 2 indices of X (x_1 and x_2), is assigned to internally consistent whether the relationship between them is the same as the relationship with their construct X. In terms of external consistency, it is recommended by items that "cluster together in a matrix of sorted or ordered similarity coefficients" (Anderson and Gerbing, 1982, p. 458). For an index of X and an index of Z, x and z are externally consistent, whether or not the relationship between x and z is the same as that of their construct, x with X, z with Z, as well as X with Z. Accordingly, unidimensionality occurs when X is internally and externally consistent. In fact, it is not much difference between coefficient alpha (α) and the reliability of latent variable (ρ) for sufficiently unidimensional constructs (Gerbing and Anderson, 1988). The coefficient alpha might be used to measure the reliability of a multi-dimensional scale roughly.

4.8.5. Composite reliability assessment

Following authors Gerbing and Anderson (1988), Hair et al. (1998), CFA provides an additional estimate of composite reliability, typically construct's reliability. Composite reliability is a new measure that evaluates the internal consistency of the observed variables, suggesting the presence of a latent construct (Hair et al., 2014). Composite reliability is preferred to be used in assessing the overall reliability of the scale for each latent variable in it (Hair et al., 1998). According to Hair et al. (2014), the composite reliability value should be at least 0.7, which shows the consistency of all measurements for the same latent construct (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). Besides composite reliability, Cronbach alpha is another popular measure of construct's reliability, which is used to evaluate unidimensionality (indices correlation) with their latent constructs (Hair et al., 2014).

4.8.6. Average variance extracted (AVE) assessment

The average variance extracted (AVE) is a common measure used to evaluate the variance in the latent variable (LV), meaning the amount of variance recognised through the latent variable is related to the variance owing to random measurement error (Dillon and Goldstein, 1984; Fornell and Larcker, 1981). AVE, in other words, is defined as a measure of a set of items' error-free variance. The construct reliability found in the AVE indexes is higher than that of the composite reliability (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). To justify utilising a construct and assure the validity of the research scale under consideration, the average variance extracted (AVE) gauges the amount of overall variance recorded by the indices regarding measurement error and its value must be 0.50 or greater (Hair et al., 1998). According to Fornell and Larcker (1981, p.46), a value less than 0.50 represents that the variation owing to measurement error is larger than the variance obtained by construct, and the construct's validity is then doubtful.

4.8.7. Nomological validity

In the process of theoretical formulation and evaluation, there are three common forms to evaluate the validity of the scale that have attracted the attention of researchers as follows: nomological, convergent and discriminant validity (Bagozzi, 1980; Gerbing and Anderson, 1988; Steenkamp and Trijp, 1991). Nomological validity is considered an important step to evaluate the hypothesised relationship between the distinct constructs as well as the empirical relationship between those construct measurements (Peter, 1981; Peter and Churchill, 1986). Nomological validity is associated with the measure's expected behaviour, and it investigates how well the construct behaves in theoretical and empirical terms (Peter, 1981; Peter and Churchill, 1986). The goodness-of-fit indices are employed to assess the measurement models' nomological validity (Steenkamp and Trijp, 1991).

4.8.8. Convergent validity

The term "convergent validity" is concerned to the construct's homogeneity. It represents the degree to which independent measures of the same construct converge or are favourably associated with other measures of the same construct (Gerbing and Anderson, 1998; Malhotra and Birks, 2000; Peter and Churchill, 1986). According to Anderson and Gerbing (1988), convergent validity can be determined based on construct reliability. It is also associated with the internal consistency of each construct item, i.e. there can be high or low correlation (Fornell and Larckers, 1981). To be specific, item reliability, composite reliability, and average variance extracted are typical indicators representing convergent validity (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Convergent validity was performed to test the t-value and significance of the factor (Chau, 1997). Convergent validity was determined through a strong correlation between constructs (Chau, 1997; Shiu et al., 2009). Specifically, if the measure's reliability value is 0.7 or higher, convergent validity is acceptable, however, it is more than 50% error variance error if the reliability of the measurements is larger than 0.85 (Nunnally, 1978).

4.8.9. Discriminant validity

According to scholars (Chau, 1997; Malhotra and Birks, 2000; Peter and Churchill, 1986), discriminant validity refers to the degree of difference as well as weak correlation between the measure of the observed construct and other constructs. If there is a negative relationship between the measurement of experiment and the constructs, this is referred to be discriminant (Shiu et al., 2009). With the value of the correlation between two constructs considerably less than 1.00, discriminant validity is determined (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988; Bagozzi et al., 1991).

Researchers Anderson and Gerbing (1988) described that "discriminant validity can be assessed for two estimated constructs by constraining the estimated correlation parameter between them to 1.00 and then performing a chi-square difference test on the values obtained for the constrained and unconstrained model" (p. 416). Discriminant validity occurs when the data fit of the restricted model is worse than that of the unrestricted model (Homburg et al., 1999). To be able to measure discriminant validity, Fornell and Larcker (1981) recommended

applying the comparison between the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct and the square correlation between them.

The squared correlation between two LVs only needs to be less than one of the two AVEs, which implies that there is more error-free (extracted or internal) variation in the constructs than variance shared with other constructs (r^2). In addition, the internal correlation between them is also more than that of other constructs, which indicates the existence of discriminant validity of the target variance retrieved (Fornell and Larcker, 1981).

To summarise, validity as a key component of the research process (Garver and Mentzer, 1999), should demonstrate unidimensionality (Steenkamp and Trijp, 1991), reliability, nomological validity, convergent validity, and discriminant validity (Peter, 1981; Steenkamp and Trijp, 1991) of research constructs so that this research can undertake structural model evaluation effectively.

4.9. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Ethical issues should always be clearly and carefully considered in the conduct of academic research. All of this is based on detailed criteria and guidelines from the University of the West of Scotland ethics form. It is important to grasp the basic knowledge and principles of ethical research and how they affect research. There are indeed a variety of ethical considerations that all researchers take into account (Jowell, 1986). Researchers need to perform their study in a professional way and in accordance with a particular and meaningful topic. This research focuses on the four most significant aspects.

First, the right of subjects concerns the statutory protection of social investigative groups by avoiding needless disruption, seeking consent from those under investigation, and respecting the groups' privacy. Second, the study must be conducted in an ethical manner that clearly defines the research topics. The third point to consider is the need of being aware of social and cultural differences. Fourth, providing complete information about the methodologies promotes public trust in their reliability. Fifth, questionnaires invariably disrupt people's

privacy, and this is reflected in the covering letter (see Appendix 4.3). All interviews were recorded unless there is an objection from one or a few participants. The University of the West of Scotland gave its authorisation to undertake this research based on the foregoing.

4.10. SUMMARY

The viewpoint, technique, and methodology employed in the study have been presented in this chapter to assess the operability of the model and the hypotheses proposed in Chapter III. To increase the trustworthiness of the findings, multiple methods were combined and used together. For the purposes of this research, a salesperson performance measuring scale was created that relies on Churchill's (1979) paradigm. Also, a qualitative approach was employed in the first phase to better capture customer perception of the salesperson's performance.

A complete and appropriate questionnaire was generated for this study from the qualitative findings (interviews). A pilot study with 50 participants (academic participants) was conducted to confirm the validity and reliability of the research instrument. Furthermore, a seven-point Likert scale was also applied to better capture the participants' attitudes towards salesperson performance with the level of agreement or disagreement expressed in detail. In term of quantitative research (second phase), the researcher surveyed with a self-administered questionnaire and collected 412 answers from Vincom customers living and working in Vietnam market. The questionnaire was constructed utilising the steps of content and operational items related to the study's objective, as well as suitable phrasing and layout manipulation. The data was gathered using two methods: a self-administered, phone and face-to-face interview and an email questionnaire survey. The following points have been addressed in relation to data collection: the unit of analysis, the construction of a survey instrument, and the data analysis methods utilised such as exploratory factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, and structural equation modelling have all been covered. Finally, ethical issues to be considered in the study were highlighted.

CHAPTER V: QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

5.1. INTRODUCTION

The significance of the methodology utilised in this research was highlighted in the preceding chapter. Qualitative research, following the research of Aaker et al. (2001), suggests that unstructured methods of inquiry empower respondents to pick their own interpretations, leading to more likely emergence of new discoveries. In this section, the findings of interviews with managers from shopping malls in Vietnam, experts and PhD, MBA students with marketing background will be presented, in relation to the objectives indicated below:

This research attempts to acquire more comprehensive knowledge to enhance the understanding of salesperson performance and how it affects customers' anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. The results of qualitative research are comprised of the following in-depth interviews with 15 salespeople and managers of the shopping malls along with marketing experts. The selection of interviewees and the nature of the interviews, as well as the planning, administration, and data interpretation for the qualitative stage were detailed in Chapter IV. Section 5.2 contains the outstanding results of the qualitative investigation. The conclusion is presented in section 5.3.

5.2. RESULTS OF THE QUALITATIVE STUDY

The key purpose of undertaking qualitative research is to participate in the research development process that explores deeper knowledge rather than evaluating superficial aspects. This section reflects the results obtained and provides data to support the current research's evolving themes on the salesperson performance, its antecedents, and consequences for anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention.

This study's content analysis has revealed seven salesperson performance elements and two factors that affect the relationship between anticipation of future interaction and repurchase

intention. These elements were identified in this research. For instance, sales skill as an important element highlighted by the scholars (Churchill et al, 1985; Rentz et al., 2002; Jhamb et al., 2021; Vinchur et al., 1998). Salesperson characteristic is acknowledged by literature (Blickle et al., 2008; Carpenter et al., 2009; Han, 2020; Penney et al., 2011; Witt and Ferris, 2003), sales strategy (Katsikea et al., 2019; Lane, 2009; Spiro et al., 2008), adaptive selling behaviour (Crittenden, 2015; Giacobbe et al., 2006; Limbu et al., 2016; Park et al., 2010; Siguwaw, 2015), satisfaction with salesperson and trust in salesperson are determined as consequences of the salesperson performance. In consonance with the literature researched in Chapter two, participants emphasised the importance of a positive salesperson performance, observed that it impacts customer perception to the organisation, since then underlined its primary significance in recruiting and maintaining talent.

5.2.1. Salesperson performance

Salesperson performance is a crucial variable that has a significant impact on how customers are perceived. Regardless of the fact about limitations in the study scope, the relevant literature and interviewees both specifically refer to the crucial role of this construct. The present study reinforces the importance of salesperson performance derived from earlier research findings.

According to the qualitative study's findings, salesperson performance is a key component of "functional" quality, which can determine customers' perceptions of a company's service quality. Along with that, respondents' textual analyses reveal a concentration on the salesperson's efforts and effectiveness in accomplishing the company's goals, approach, and customer service which impact customer perception. The following remarks reflect a sales executive's opinion on this source of information:

“It is like a scale to evaluate the quality of the service, how to process the orders, how to receive the requirements and serve customer...”. (LT)

An MBA student also commented that:

“Salesperson performance is how an employee completes the required tasks, which is directly related to the quality and efficiency of their output... It can also be said that the performance of each individual seller plays an important role in reflecting the quality and value of the company, having a direct influence on the success or failure as well as company development path...”.
(HAB)

The above comments are compatible with scholarly research (Bitner, 1990; Hartline and Jones, 1996; Hartline et al., 2003; Nunkoo et al., 2020; Obiageli et al., 2015) on corporate personality and human values. They claim that salesperson performance is closely linked to the success of the organisation, demonstrating the company’s quality of service interactions and their value to customers. In addition, sales supervisor and doctoral researcher said that:

"... how the service is delivered to the customer, whether the customer is satisfied and will continue to support the company in the future or not, all depends on the salesperson's performance because they are the very important frontline people that communicate directly with customers. Their efforts through sincerity, reliability in the conversation, exploring the needs and feelings of customers will help deliver quality service to the customer..."
(NK).

“... is the result of effort and ability to accomplish desired goals.... they are directly communicating with the customer so their work performance will have a significant impact on the customer experience. Even if we have high-quality products and services, businesses will not be able to develop sustainably without a high-performing staff. High-performing employees bring good experiences to customers, creating favourable development as well as strong competitiveness for businesses compared to other competitors in the same market and vice versa...”. (HA)

The above statement is observed to be consistent with the study (Buciuniene and Skudiene, 2015; Dey et al., 2016; Frese, 2002; Hossain et al., 2016). A key aspect of salesperson performance that was explored was the seller's efforts. It can be said that the foundation for providing good service quality and developing the competitiveness of enterprises should be studying how to manage sales staff performance, promoting their efforts to reach and communicate effectively with customers. Salesperson performance, in accordance with research (Buciuniene and Skudiene, 2015; Bolander et al., 2021; Johnston and Marshall 2006; Obiageli et al., 2015; Walker et al., 1979), can be seen in terms of the seller's efforts to provide good customer service interactions, customer satisfaction, which positively affects the revenue, competitive advantage of the organisation. The following area sales manager and sales supervisor quotes exemplify this idea:

"... is the quality of the sales staff's work and the operational efficiency of the company. The strong efforts of the sales staff greatly influence the development of interactive relationships with customers and their loyalty. It is also linked to the long-term profitability of A..." (TV)

"...how well a salesperson completes work according to a plan or within a certain period. The salesperson's efforts are tied to the development of ongoing relationships with customers. I can easily judge their value to the organisation based on their performance. High or low level of performance, more or less effort can be clearly seen in the amount of time spent on sales interactions, i.e. the maximum time to get the job done effectively..." (HA)

Salesperson performance is used as a universal tool to operate business operations, helps achieve competitive advantage, and can influence the customer's perceptions of your organisation (Buciuniene and Skudiene, 2015; Linh, 2019; Miao and Evans, 2013; Rodriguez et al., 2012; Walker et al., 1977). For example: "Salesperson performance as an indicator to evaluate the ability to perform sales work of each salesperson. With these metrics, I will be able to see if the salesperson is really doing a good job... whether they can meet the sales

target for the month, and this is one of the important factors to do the appraisal at the year-end... and make some arrangement to assist the salespersons and coach the team".

Interviewees considered salesperson performance as an indicator of a company's quality, and salesperson performance needs to be high and improve over time in order to provide and ensure quality service and value of the company. "... we create a culture of reasonable rewards, always encouraging employees to share their views, which are related to progress, deadlines, expectations and available resources to be able to provide positive energy in the working process, help employees innovate and improve their performance better day by day", and also "... There are benchmarks and SLAs for quality control, especially the management team has dashboards to evaluate the team's effectiveness". Or "The first priority is time management. I do not allow the salespersons to work without any plan and set some tasks daily/weekly to help to reach the monthly target performance... look over the team how to perform their work such as the attitude, or did they follow the sales script to approach the customers... understand and get feedback from the salespersons on how they connect to the customers, also, open mind to communicate with them". Management states that salesperson performance acts as a central force that motivates business' success should be monitored in a timely manner so that employees are motivated to accomplish their goals effectively and strengthen customer interactions. The following quotations reflect that:

"... salespeople interact directly with the potential customer; they have the advantage of being able to glean personal knowledge that will aid them in delivering their sales pitch and tailoring their offerings to their audience. A salesperson will present for the company. Their performance will directly affect the customers' perceptions of company image". (ATD)

"I always make sure they know the product well, update the trends on the market, let them speak out any problems and answer their questions... Our sales staff work very well to find potential customers, they are flexible in approaching customers and always know how to bridge the gap between customer needs and company products. The salespeople at my company also

act as real professionals. They possess good knowledge of the company's products and always actively advise customers to make completely rational decisions. Well, and as you know this affects the trust and satisfaction of customers in our company. Positive customer feedback and word-of-mouth increased. Our company has achieved a certain success when it is known by more people and, for example, the growth of sales in recent years". (BX)

"... we emphasise learning and professional training in the company culture... always has a process of training and professional development on a regular basis to expand the product knowledge of the sales staff, consistently develop the principles of competition..." (LT)

To ensure high performance of salespeople and continuous improvement over time, it requires the involvement and close attention of the top management towards salespeople. Most experts assume that salesperson performance plays an important role in the successful growth of a business and there is an expectation of high performance of salespeople related to their positive behaviours. For example, MBA students and salesman revealed that salesperson's behaviour tied is to their performance levels:

"Frontline salespeople are like the backbone of the company's services with a core role in ensuring that the company's products and services in an evolving age are delivered to customers efficiently. All behaviour of sales staff must show respect for customers and should be considered carefully because it can cause customers to evaluate the company negatively". (HAB)

" I will not go back to any shopping mall or store if any employee behaves poorly. Because I won't feel comfortable while shopping". (HN)

"...Because all of us are located at the high-end shopping mall and all customers come to the shopping mall are not for buying only but also expected professional and delighted experience. If we provide a high-standard

image, it definitely will influence the customers' feeling of the shopping mall". (MP)

Regarding what salespeople produce to customers and what they do (selling behaviour), how to manage salesperson's performance is considered the most important issue (Linh, 2019; Walker et al., 1977; Zallocco et al., 2009). The results obtained from the participants demonstrate their awareness of the importance of management on this topic. A salesperson's performance should bring positive perceptions to customers about the seller, the company, and the product/service they receive. The following comments from managers reflect this view:

"Good management of the salespeople's performance provides a lot of advantages to the company when operating in the marketplace. We will have a strong sales system along with a great sales team, smooth sales operations, and more sales opportunities thanks to the support of the necessary tools in finding potential customers, allows to increase revenue twice or even three times compared to competitors who lack this. Forecasting revenue and profit for each quarter is more accurate..." (TV)

"... It's important to make sure your salespeople understand how their individual goals affect the overall business goals... regularly organise employee performance reviews to easily monitor the progress of the sales team". (AD)

"Customer perception is something very important that can make or break your brand. This perception mostly comes from the experiences of customers when they use the products or when interacting with the company's sales staff. I am sure that you will not be dissatisfied with the company when receiving enthusiastic and professional service from the sales staff, right? Would you like to complain when receiving professional advice and proper attention from the sales staff? and then leave with products that fit your needs. That's why I

said; besides product quality, salesperson performance also significantly affects customer satisfaction. The number of products in the invoice, sales as well as monthly and quarterly profits also shows how effectively the salesperson interacts with the customer” (BX).

Experience (knowledge) was also one of the factors found in the interviews with the participants. Statements about salesperson experience and skills are found to be related to salesperson performance. Experience is essential for salespeople, it helps to convey the product quality and value that the company wants to provide to customers, make a good impression and build customer interactions (Giacobbe et al., 2006; Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020). Those documents acknowledged the need for experience as a key element for customer relationships. The following discussion by sales executives and sales managers shows its relevance to salesperson performance:

"Professional knowledge and skills of employees will show the service quality of the company. We invest more in training our staff to accommodate our customers' interactive experiences" (AD)

"The performance of the salesperson is the most important issue in demonstrating the quality of the company's service. It is important that the knowledge, skills, and behaviours of salespeople must be cultivated in order to satisfy customers well and make a good impression on them... It's not only reflecting the quality of labour resources but also demonstrating the success of the company's business operations, enhancing our competitive advantage in the market" (BD).

"Salesperson performance is absolutely essential to measure; it seems all companies have an employee performance appraisal system. It is undeniable that high performance enhances reliability, and it is easy to create a positive impression in the minds of customers. A good salesperson knows how to interact, drive customer purchases, and strengthen their relationship with

customers. Our sales team is regularly trained with professional sales knowledge and skills, that's why besides selling effectively, our sales team always does a great job in building relationships, retain long-term customers, and increase word of mouth, reputation as well as profits for the company" (LT).

5.2.1.1. Antecedents to salesperson performance

Based on the qualitative findings, the accompanying section highlights the aspects that determine a salesperson's performance.

5.2.1.1.1. Sales strategy

Sales strategy has a practical significance in today's businesses to be able to access market needs quickly, promote customer interaction, improve competitive advantage and profit for the company (Dong et al., 2018). Therefore, the essentiality of sales strategy has been emphasised by researchers to maintain a competitive advantage in today's fierce market (Katsikea et al., 2019; Lane, 2009; Spiro et al., 2008). The sales strategy was found in the comments of the interviewees as a significant factor to differentiate and affirm the company's brand. For example, "we have always defined a clear strategy to differentiate our shopping mall from our competitors", "the level of competition in this industry is relatively high, so affirming the brand is always what we aim for". "Customers not only choose products because of their intrinsic features but also care about the feelings and values that can be received from the product and the brand. Therefore, as a manager, the orientation to attract customers, as well as the return rate must be focused", and "strengthen customer service training, invest in organising events, or a month-long campaign with prominent brands to bring different and interesting interactive experiences to customers when they come to the shopping mall".

Along with its three main components such as sales model, customer prioritisation and segmentation, a number of published studies on the relationship between sales strategy, its

main components and salesperson performance (Anderson, 2020; Gönsch, 2020; Ingram et al., 2012; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Niraj, 2016; Terho et al., 2015). The qualitative interviews presented below reflect the relationship between these parameters.

Selling model which acts as a key component to the success of the sales strategy (Ingram et al., 2002). The complex needs of customers are tracked, and considered through sales models, or development of relationship objectives that positively support customer relationships and strengthen sales performance (Katsikea et al., 2019; Libai et al., 2020; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010). The views from the participants all emphasised the importance of the sales model as well as its positive influence on the company's competitive advantage. The following statements by professors reinforce this source of information:

"I do not encourage rigidity in the company's operations, because it always comes with failure. Small changes in technology or the economy can have a significant impact on the company if we are not flexible enough to adapt to them. I prefer a highly flexible model for technology improvement activities and fine-tuning corporate policies to gain a competitive advantage" (HK).

The participants' comments also emphasise that the model fit provides a high-quality employee performance. The following quotes from sales supervisors demonstrate this:

"... Flexibility creates a more dynamic and productive working environment... there should be a transformation or at least adding flexibility to the company's operating model instead of simply being follow a rigid working model. For example, this model will promote salesperson's contribution to the achievement of company goals. Flexibility allows salespeople to learn quickly, leverage technology to proactively monitor changes in customer and market needs, make quick customer-oriented decisions. It is also easier for companies to identify new opportunities, form and launch new initiatives and projects, and satisfy customers in a better way" (PB).

“... I still have to appreciate the rigid model and its advantages. The highly flexible model may be more suitable for high-tech companies or industries than the retail industry. The rigid model in my opinion brings stability and security to the company's operations. It helps me to manage everything smoothly and systematically, including my sales staff, their work productivity from there will also be guaranteed. Also, the stability of the model will also be a great advantage to help the company survive in any situation or challenge” (NK).

In term of customer prioritisation, one of the main components that is always carefully considered in the development of a company's business strategy (MahmoumGonbadi et al., 2019), related to pricing, differences in the way firms treat and promote customers (Homburg and Totzek, 2008a; Homburg et al., 2008 p.114). It is also a useful tool for systematically managing customers and allocating resources effectively to develop interactive relationships, increase customer loyalty as well as sales performance (Homburg et al., 2008a, 2008b; Libai et al., 2020; Ramani and Kumar, 2008; Rust et al., 2011). Participants agreed to prioritise customers so that they can properly focus their resources and maintain a competitive advantage. As mentioned by participants, “human resources, their level of knowledge and skills are closely related to the characteristics of the business, so we pay great attention to investing in human resources to be able to maintain a sustainable competitive advantage”, and also, “... focus our activities on the most profitable segment, ... driving customer engagement throughout the buying decision journey”.

“Because of our customer-oriented strategy, personnel training and communication are two aspects we focus on. As you know, customer interaction is very important. Normally, customers leave with a bad experience when they feel they're not being treated properly without telling you what's going on or giving you an opportunity to fix it. Also, customers are often "overwhelmed" by so many choices, but they tend to be more open-minded when considering a recommendation from a friend, feedback, or a share on social networks. Therefore, a salesperson's ability to interact with

customers, along with social media campaigns, once invested in the right way, can help a company reach customers effectively and spread positive messages about the company's products and services” (BĐ).

Customer segmentation is also an equally important component of a company's strategic operations (Dibb and Simkin, 2008). It has been described as the systematic process of finding a market for a new product (Beane and Ennis, 1987), identifying specific customer information and values, thereby aligning resources, and managing the diverse needs of the market effectively (Terho et al., 2015; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010). Comments from sales managers express their views on the importance of segmentation:

“It is really important because we based on the customer preference to plan the CRM. For example, we can focus on social media if our customers’ market segment is young adults. Our customers are working in professional industries and have a high income; therefore, we provide tailor relationship strategy to every customer such as to send greeting card or catalog with their name on it” (TV).

“Segmenting customers, identifying the right target market allows the company to understand customer behaviour and needs. We can easily come up with offers and marketing strategies that are tailored to different audiences, increase positive customer experience and company competitiveness, along with minimising the loss of time and costs” (AD).

5.2.1.1.2. Customer orientation

Customer orientation as an element of salesperson performance is important because it reflects the salesperson's behaviours and efforts to satisfy customers and bring success to the company (Brockman et al., 2012; Jaramillo et al., 2007; Linh, 2019; Pekovic and Rolland, 2016; Thakor and Joshi, 2005). Previous research has focused on customer orientation as a prerequisite for salespeople to create business performance and develop customer

relationships (Chen et al., 2015; ELSamen and Akroush, 2018; Guo and Wang, 2015; Lam et al, 2010). Similarly, in the current study, sales executives also shared their opinions and affirmed the importance of customer orientation for current business market:

“The current retail industry in Vietnam is growing rapidly and making a very important contribution to the country's economy. Most brands have improved their sales and service skills for customers, especially high-end and mid-tier retail companies, but there are still many other retailers that focus solely on making deals rather than building customer relationships. I think it's better for us to learn its importance, because if a company can maintain a relationship with its customers through a friendly smile, sincerity and empathy, as well as always focusing on the best interests of customers, it will not only encourage them to come back to support the company and increase sales but also save costs for the company to carry out marketing, advertising and up-selling” (LT).

“Due to the complicated evolution of the epidemic, and changes in the transaction needs of customers, as a real estate company, we always try to understand the needs and expectations of our customers during this difficult period. We have made the necessary changes to be ready to serve and bring the best experience to customers such as using more online sales platforms, regularly organising projects for sale on software like Landsoft in order to help customers easily connect with the company, the interaction process between the seller and the buyer can take place more smoothly without having to meet face-to-face. We always take the needs and problems of our customers seriously.” (BĐ).

“... The trend of modern consumers is towards the environment. Most of them are concerned about climate change and the environment and want to use less plastic to protect the environment. Grasping this, our company is gradually making some changes from trying to sourcing standard and sustainable to

building a production process that is pollution-free, and has no negative impact on the environment, distributing recycled, environmentally friendly products to consumer, and as you can see, these changes received a lot of support as well as a lot of positive feedback from consumers...” (ATD).

5.2.1.1.3. Value based selling

Haas et al. (2012), Terho et al. (2015) emphasise the importance of value-based selling as demonstrated through the behaviours and efforts of salespeople. This is important because businesses need to create impressions and sales solutions that deliver high value to customers (Kuester et al., 2017; Terho et al., 2017; Reymen et al., 2015). Participants in the follow-up interviews said:

“We always focus on the value that customers receive. You know, although most customers care about price, most of them don't just consider price when making a purchasing decision, they consider value (the difference between cost and value they receive). Therefore, besides providing good quality products, we also creating an impressive sales interaction environment with enthusiastic and responsible advice from sales staff, as well as connecting with customers after a purchase so they don't feel forgotten” (ATD).

“Diversity of items and different prices for customers to choose from. Of course, the quality of products is always our focus to bring a good experience to our customers no matter what the price point. Balancing the financial interests of our customers and the quality of the products/services provided is always important to us.” (MP).

“Customers don't buy the product; they buy the value that the product brings to them. If the seller knows how to highlight the product's value and give useful advice and match the customer's expectations, they will have a good impression of the brand and the seller...” (AD)

Value-based selling is an effective customer approach that can create long term relationships with customers and strongly support the development of salesperson performance (Mullins et al., 2019; Terho et al. 2015; Töytäri and Rajala, 2015). Sales executives comments also emphasised that value-based selling can help sellers connect effectively with customers and increase sales performance:

“Value-based selling can help sellers connect effectively with customers in a high extent. Normally, customers feel satisfied after purchasing so they will come back with us next time. Some companies over advertise their goods that lead to customers' displeasure, and they lose many potential customers. In fact, quality of goods is the key factor to build a long-term relationship with customers” (LT).

“We always consider customer satisfaction and trust as the company's striving goal. That's why we always focus on product quality, value connection and sustainable relationship with customers by support services and after-sales care” (BD).

“Value-based selling is about delivering value to customers, not just selling products. If the seller doesn't focus on value, the only thing the customer will know may be the price. Once faced with high prices and not being provided with clear information about the features, and the value that the product brings, the customer may immediately walk away and have no intention of returning. Meanwhile, customers will always have a special affection for the seller when they receive helpful and sincere advice from the seller about the value that the product brings, the product's support for daily life, or even the after-purchase service provided by the company. Customers will pay less attention to the price and choose to buy from that seller, helping them to increase sales instead of buying from others” (ATD).

5.2.1.1.4. Sales skills

Sales skills have practical significance in today's sales work of salespeople to be able to communicate fluently, support customers quickly, improve interactive relationships and maximise profits for the company (Jhamb et al., 2021). Therefore, the necessity of selling skills has been emphasised by researchers through four main components: interpersonal skill, salesmanship skill, technical skill and marketing skill in order to maintain a competitive advantage in the fierce market (Churchill et al., 1985, 2000; Futrell, 2006; Ingram et al., 2004), as mentioned in Chapter II. A number of reputable scholars (Chen and Jaramillo, 2014; Singh and Venugopal, 2015; Singh et al., 2017) have also studied the relationship between sales strategy and salesperson performance through a variety of approaches.

According to the results found from the qualitative interviews, interpersonal skills as an essential skill of salesperson performance, are embedded in the customer's perception to make the necessary judgements and decisions during the sales interaction. Interpersonal skills focus on the seller's proficiency, expertise, ability to listen, understand, and solve customer problems that affect their perception of the business. The following quotes from professional salespeople specifically express their views on this information:

"...The success of this process depends on interpersonal communication as the most fundamental activity of a salesperson. It is a tool to foster customer trust and perception of service quality. We often communicate and judge others by words and eye contact during interaction, for example, if a salesperson does not make eye contact with you during a sales presentation, it means disrespect and create an impatient image of that seller in your mind, do you want to continue interacting with or even buy that person's product?" (LL).

“Obviously in a strong extent, interpersonal skill can effectively influence communication to others, not only in work but also in daily life... Good interpersonal skills help salespeople facilitate their sales presentations as well as convince customers to believe in what they want to offer. We can also

reconcile differences, better understand, and empathise with other people's points of view, strengthen relationships. It also helps to solve problems and conflicts at work effectively, especially before it gets really serious. ... lack of communication skills is really a disaster with countless problems occurring, you will not be able to fully solve it on your own and come up with a satisfactory result. This will greatly affect your own and your team performance...” (MP)

Having a definite influence on a customer's future engagement and repurchase intention requires the involvement and effort of a salesperson. Interviewees consider salesmanship skills to be an important factor in sales performance and seem to expect higher sales performance when the salesmanship skills of employees are high. The results of qualitative research are consistent with previous studies (Futrell, 2006; Fu and Elliott, 2013; Wachner et al., 2009b) on the relationship of salesmanship skill and salesperson performance. The following quotes from the sales supervisor professor reflect this source of information:

“It directly affects the outcome. Even if two salespersons are saying the same information of products to the customers, the tones, attitude, and body language are the main factors to affect the customers to make decisions. And these are the main reasons to affect the shopping experience of the customers...” (HK).

“... If you can convince a potential buyer to buy something he hasn't really decided to buy yet, even if you just need to get him to think about it positively, you're already successful. I appreciate employees who possess this skill, they master the knowledge of the sales process, know how to observe, and attract customers in sales presentations, are flexible in prospecting and solve problems effectively. Furthermore, they can stimulate customers to buy and interact more in the future, helping to connect consumption and production. It is also very helpful for them to be more productive and help companies thrive” (HA).

Technical skill is an essential sales skill that is of interest to participants and is found in qualitative interviews. Comments on technical skills are considered an indispensable skill of a salesperson, especially during the current outbreak of the COVID pandemic, it creates opportunities to approach and build customer relationships. Sales managers and sales executives have said about it as follows:

"... gain insight into customer profiles, needs, and issues that drive purchase decisions. The pandemic will almost slow down the development of businesses, however, that does not mean that we cannot take advantage of it as an opportunity to review company and competitor performance, evaluate sales methods, the variety of products, the means of support to increase sales and market share" (ATD).

"The pandemic has caused changes in lifestyles and ways of shopping, it has also helped create new needs, new shopping markets and sales approaches. We take advantage of technology and social networking sites to reach and understand customers better, providing images, information, using to optimise product search, adjusting sales strategies and products in order articles to satisfy the needs of the market in a period of many changes... We implement customer support and consulting programmes, organise online conferences with the participation of executives and experts to provide deeper product knowledge and resolve customer issues" (TV).

Marketing skills are important macro skills that demonstrate a seller's understanding of company performance trends, which play a role in predicting salesperson performance (Ahearne and Schillewaert, 2000). It allows salespeople to be more agile and flexible to support customers in diverse sales contexts, helping to strengthen customer trust and engagement (Amor, 2019; Basir et al., 2010; Van Scheers, 2011). Comment from participants mention the importance of marketing skills: "Good marketing skills help salespeople communicate information and values of products, well form customers'

perceptions of brands or products", and also, "... once these skills are properly trained, it will help us to capture market trends effectively, convey the company's message to customers in a more impressive way, adding value to relationships with stakeholders". Furthermore, "... most of our customers confess they were persuaded to buy a product or service by watching a company video...", "...marketing skills for me as an essential tool to help improve competitiveness in today's modern society".

"... We all understand how important our customers and stakeholders are to the success of our business. To be able to easily access and develop relationships with stakeholders, communication and product introduction skills are not enough, marketing skills are also the development and creation of ideas, especially listening to diverse points of view, negotiating, consulting, and persuading. These skills show that you care about your stakeholders and their importance... easily garnering their sympathy, building closer relationships, and getting support from stakeholders" (LT).

In brief, these observations were reinforced by researchers (Churchill et al., 1985, 2000; Ford et al., 1988; Rentz et al., 2002), who asserted that sales skills have a directional relationship to salesperson performance.

5.2.1.1.5. Sales characteristics

Sales characteristic plays an important role in the performance of salespeople, helping to achieve job performance (Churchill et al., 1985; Penney et al., 2011). It can affect the level of customer orientation, adaptive sales (Penney et al., 2011; Widmier, 2002) and employee sales performance (Echchakoui, 2017; Kland, 2012). From the comments of the interviewees, characteristic as a contributing factor to customer satisfaction and business success. For example, "it is the key component to decide who can have the best performance and become successful", "work effectively and have positive thinking. They have good sales knowledge and skills, understand the job pressure with sales target and the salary are related to sales performance", "very flexible and confident in their interactions and problem-solving,

persuasion, and building trust", "Good skill, knowledgeable, good listener. They are creative and always pay close attention to customer's needs".

The three main components in salesperson characteristics are empathic ability, cue perception ability and ability to modify self-presentation. Participants reported that a salesperson's characteristics containing empathy would provide a high-quality customer relationship. This information is presented as follows, provided by the participants: "... empathy improves mutual understanding and trust. Empathy doesn't mean you agree, it means you understand the speaker's point of view, and put yourself in the customer's shoes to give appropriate advice. So when the customers receive the empathetic from the salesperson, the trust and openness will be improved" and "... once we show sincerity, customers are willing to spend more on their goods because they may consider salesperson as a familiar rather than a stranger", "Employees with great empathy will be more active in supporting activities and helping customers make the right purchase, it helps to strengthen the relationship between the seller and the buyer, increasing the sales as well as the performance of the seller", "sometimes kindness and empathy are all that make an individual become a lifetime customer of your company".

Findings in the current study reveal that cue perception ability as an element of the salesperson characteristic is important because it reflects the salesperson's cognitive ability in customer interaction situations (McIntire et al., 1999; Puccinelli et al., 2013). Interviewees expressed their views on cue perception ability and its effects on sales performance (Elfenbein et al., 2007; Herpertz et al., 2016). The following statements by the supervisor corroborate this finding:

"... Sometimes having good product knowledge and being persistent in recommending the product is not a good way to close the deal. It is important to know how to listen, judge situations based on customer signals, and seize the right time to easily get orders, improve sales and your own performance"
(HA)

"... it is an important ability in sales... The customers have their own standard in their mind and are not 100% honest to tell all their needs and wants to the salespeople. So, salespersons are required to read and understand customer body language, pay attention to their eye contact, speaking tone or attitude. These signals help salespersons to know if customers are confused or not interested in the product they are trying to recommend, whether customers feel comfortable interacting with them. From there, the salesperson will know how to correct behaviour and convey information to make customers feel more comfortable or focused, easily providing the most suitable products and services to customers" (PB).

The ability to modify self-presentation is an important factor reflected in how employees communicate and behave. It shows the tendency of salespeople to work actively, pay attention to the surrounding context to control their own sales behaviour appropriately (Alnakhli et al., 2020; Grieve et al., 2020; Lennox and Wolfe 1984; Rank et al., 2009), this is also concurred by managers. The ability to modify self-presentation can increase adaptive sales and sales performance (Weitz, 1979, 1981). The participants' comments stated, "I am confident with controlling my attitude as well as adjusting my behaviour according to different sales situations", "they control their personal emotions well, enthusiastic in communication, they know how to use eye contact and hand gestures with customers to make the conversation more comfortable, but still give the customer a feeling of satisfaction and being respected when making a purchase".

"Self-regulation is how sellers manage their emotions and actions. The more self-regulating, the better salespeople can control their sales behaviour, which leads to higher sales performance" (LL).

"Salespeople with good self-control and self-regulation are always very hardworking, able to clearly understand their own strengths and weaknesses, they are visionaries and extremely flexible in handling different sales

situations. These employees are commendable as they consistently achieve high sales rates, with very positive sales performance" (ATD).

5.2.1.1.6. Experience

Experience plays an integral part in supporting a salesperson's performance, although it may not act as a major factor (Groza and Groza, 2018; Terho et al., 2013). Scholars (Harindranath et al., 2019; Rapp et al., 2008; Singh and Das, 2013) pay attention to experience as an important factor to modulate salesperson perceptions and behaviour. For the current study, the managers' comments on the salesperson's experience are illustrated as follows:

"There is nothing like experience, the more you practise, the more proficient you will become. Experiential salespeople know what they need to do in different situations. They can assess customer needs including the function, budget, product type and how to speed up order closing, including the worst cases. They can really work well with difficult or abusive customers, easily grasp customer's motivations, which inexperienced sellers cannot do" (AD).

"Experience represents an individual's values. Experienced sellers are good at sales interaction skills and have the ability to improvise situations quickly and satisfy customers, so their adaptive selling skills also improve over time, and this has a positive effect on that seller's performance" (TV).

Experience is a factor that has a great influence on customer perception, as the following interviewed salespeople stated:

"Professional knowledge and skills of employees will show the service quality of the company. No customer can trust a seller who lacks skills and experience..." (LL).

"The more information customers know about the product they want to buy, the more likely they are to buy it. With 5 years of sales experience, I am confident that I can communicate the features and values of the product to customers in the most clear and sincere way, ready to answer customers' inquiries as quickly and thoroughly as possible. Customers will always tend to trust and continue to accompany the company when their problems are supported extremely quickly with full of valuable information" (MP).

5.2.1.1.7. Adaptive selling behaviour

Adaptive selling is vital in today's businesses to gain customer trust and satisfaction, build long-term interactive relationships, and improve employee performance (Pyun, 2017; Perangnangin and Kusumawardhani, 2018; Rippé et al., 2016; Sing and Das, 2013). As one interviewee stated, "adaptive selling requires a customised approach for each customer type, sales situation, and feedback received. It can be said that a well-adapted salesperson will always be very sensitive to customer needs, skilful and agile in the sales process, well presented product values to customers. They can easily create a positive customer experience that fosters feelings of happiness, prompt purchase as well as helps to generate more potential customers as well as develop a good relationship between seller and buyer".

“...Even if all customers have a similar preference but their requirements are all different based on their life or work. Therefore, adjusting sales behaviour, talking, listening to all customers, and understanding their needs are important and considered as the key point of all industries. Remember that customers will not buy your product if your story is not attractive, the attitude is not sincere and especially does not build the initial trust... For a long-term relationship, showing sincerity and building trust is essential. Customer needs are probably simpler for FMCG items (consumer goods), however, for items like real estate, feeling and trust are very important. A good salesperson's ability to adapt creates a positive connection with customers, helping them to

feel that they are unique and have been served with appropriate services” (AD).

“Adaptive selling involves a more consultative approach. To possess the ability to sell adaptively, salespeople must undergo intensive training courses, understanding the products they are selling to the market and can sensitively judge customer psychology to adjust sales methods accordingly. So, there's no reason why salespeople with good adaptability can't improve performance and develop good customer relationships” (BX).

5.2.2. Consequences of the salesperson performance

According to the literature review, a salesperson's performance might result in a number of different outcomes. A good salesperson's performance has been connected to favourable results including increased customer's expectation of future interaction and repurchase intention.

5.2.2.1. Determinants of salesperson performance: anticipation of future interaction

Anticipation of future interaction has been noticed in previous research as an important and consequential feature of salesperson performance because the anticipation of future interaction represents positive customer perception and their desire to interact in the future (Kennedy et al., 2001), which evokes a favourable relationship between the customer and the seller, driving corporate success (Min et al., 2020). In fact, qualitative research reveals how salesperson performance impacts customers' perceptions and their intentions to interact in the future. These findings are also supported by academics (Obiageli et al., 2015; Román and Iacobucci, 2010; Simintiras and Cadogan, 2010). The following are some of the points from salespeople and sales executives about this relationship:

“Know how to grasp customer signals and psychology well, sell based on product value, and always try to find the right solution for customers in any

situation rather than making excuses for it. This will make an important contribution to creating the best customer service and giving customers a good impression of the company” (LT).

“Honesty, enthusiasm, and responsibility are my working concepts. I always do my best to support my clients and based on my own experience I always help them come up with the best solutions that they can benefit from. And for me, showing sincerity and empathy in handling situations is the best way to gain trust and promote customer interaction. As a result, my customers always come to me proactively when they have a need to buy” (PAD).

“...the sales team is an essential and important component of increasing customer engagement than ever before. Our company always invests in improving and training knowledge skills for sales staff on a regular and professional basis. It is impossible when we are just trying to sell valuable products without having a professional sales team to reach and support customers when needed. A customer's first impression and interactive experience is crucial to their future return” (BĐ).

“My recent client is an indecisive person, and it seems her perception of colour is not very clear. She couldn't choose the colour of her own evening gown, nor could she distinguish between orange and pink. I approached and asked a few questions about the factors involved such as whether she will attend any upcoming events, what colour will her handbag and shoes be, and introduced her to some popular dress patterns for reference. She finally chose a suitable dress based on my recommendation. She also came back 2 weeks later with her sister and also recommended our services to a colleague in the company” (MP).

In short, the customer's anticipation of future interaction reflects a salesperson's performance and company service quality; a salesperson's performance can impact the customer's

perception of a company's products/services and assist them to create expectations for future interactions.

5.2.2.2. Determinants of salesperson performance: satisfaction with salesperson

Scholars are becoming increasingly interested in consumer perception to salesperson (Arditto et al., 2020; Hultman et al., 2019; Ryari et al., 2021). Customers often tend to be based on their satisfaction with salespeople when it comes to creating perceptions about products and companies (Blessing and Natter, 2019; Babin et al., 1999). Satisfaction with salesperson can be considered as the degree to which a customer likes or dislikes a seller's service offering during an interaction. Salesperson behaviours and attributes have recently attracted the attention of many researchers (e.g. Grosso et al., 2018; Ferguson et al., 2021).

Customer satisfaction with salespersons and firms has been shown to be influenced by corporate service quality in previous marketing research (Blut et al., 2016; Gounaris et al., 2010; Prentice, 2013). For example, "... we can retain customers' attention because we have better customer service", "Majority of customers return simply because of their buying experience. They are not only satisfied with the products I recommend, but also enjoy interacting with me because of the enthusiasm and empathy I have for them. There is no denying the importance of product quality, but customer service still plays a huge role here". Along with that, customer satisfaction with salesperson has been shown to depend on salesperson performance (Hartline et al., 2003; Nunkoo et al., 2020; Prentice et al., 2020). Similarly, the comments from MBA students and professor demonstrate its influence on salesperson performance.

“If a customer cannot enjoy the moment during the buying process or receives a bad experience from the store staff, it triggers negative emotions, and can change their satisfaction levels right away even when they have found the right product for their needs” (HAB)

“Skills can be trained, but personality will have a greater influence on sales performance. Enthusiasm, dynamism along with good skills are required qualities for a service provider. A good salesperson will be able to motivate customers to buy with empathy and sincerity in communicating product value, satisfied customers will not hesitate to purchase even if the price of the product seems higher than expected. The company will not be able to get customers if the seller is incompetent and does not make efforts in consulting and helping customers make appropriate purchasing decisions. Positive customer reviews are all based on their impressions of their interactions with the company. So, a good salesperson's performance increases customer satisfaction with salesperson, reinforcing their confidence in the company's service quality” (HN).

“To me, employee performance not only shows their value to the company, but also reflects the care and value that the company strives to convey to customers. A good-performing salesperson knows how to communicate and raise customer awareness of the company's product value, ensure satisfaction, and connect positively with customers...” (HK).

5.2.2.3. Determinants of salesperson performance: trust in salesperson

Customer trust in salespeople is incredibly practical and crucial for businesses to gain attention and position themselves in the customer's mind. Thus, many marketing researchers highlight the importance of the relationship between salesperson performance and customer trust in the salesperson to maintain a competitive advantage in today's fierce market (Friend et al., 2018; Itani et al., 2019; Papparoidamis et al., 2019). In the remarks of the participants, a high salesperson performance was mentioned as a contributing element to customer trust and satisfaction. For example: "... the quality of the products is a postulate, however, because the seller is the person who directly interacts with the customer, treats and takes care of the customer. So once the customer is well taken care of, their trust not only for the sales staff but also the company is increased".

"Let customers freely experience products/services, provide trial products, along with the professionalism and friendliness in conveying information and product functions are what we aim for employees to build trust for customers, always make them feel secure and satisfied when dealing with the company"
(TV)

"The service attitude of the staff is one of the factors that win the trust of customers easily. Customer trust starts from simple things, it can be a friendly smile, a thank you, or sincere advice... Small actions have a great effect in creating an impression. good image for customers. Our employees are always taught that very carefully" (AD).

The stronger a salesperson's performance, the higher the customer's trust in that salesperson, according to participants. Companies aim to develop positive relationships with their clients. Customers are more inclined to support a firm in the future if they have trust in the salesperson rather than solely in the brand. Companies invest in training salespeople to boost their sales performance and bolster their success in the marketplace. Sales managers and sales executives commented as follows:

"Performance represents a seller's ability to interact in a business environment. The higher the personal selling ability, the greater the customer's trust" (BX).

"If you want sales, you have to build sales trust. If the customer believes that you are someone that they can trust, they are more likely to put their own reputation on the line to refer you to other customers" (AD)

"The first factor that affects the trust and buying psychology of customers is product information. Providing clear information, making efforts to give suggestions, and providing positive support policies for customers will quickly convince customers to buy and trust. Employees with higher sales

performance will be able to close orders more quickly and gain customer trust, promoting repeat purchases" (TV)

"A salesperson has high trust from customers, their performance is obviously better than others because customers are willing to spend on what they advertise" (BD).

5.2.2.4. Determinants of salesperson performance: repurchase intention

Customers repurchase intention is influenced by their anticipation of future interactions as a result of salesperson performance. The significance of repurchase intention becomes clearer when customers are satisfied and trust the product and the company (Javed and Wu, 2020; Yin et al., 2019). One sales supervisor exemplified the importance of customer repurchase intention:

"The repurchase intention of customers is not only based on their trust with the brand but also on their expectation and satisfaction with the salesperson. When customers have positive experiences with the company, or specifically with a salesperson, they are more willing to share with others and come back next time, or even ask to be served by that salesperson again. Talking about Thorn Beauty, we always innovate and appreciate the value that customers bring, that is why our customers are always willing to share their positive experiences and return periodically because they have trusted the service staff, trust in skills, advice as well as the knowledge from the company's staff, at the same time, the staff also understand the customer's preferences, they can always deliver exactly what the customer expects. This connection with customers drives the company's performance and revenue" (PB).

As a result, salesperson performance can have a favourable impact on the company and increase customers repurchase intentions (Bolander et al., 2021; Buciuniene and Skudiene, 2015). It has also been suggested that the higher the customer's anticipation of future

interaction, the greater their repurchase intention. Comments from an MBA student demonstrates this:

"I am sure that well-trained employees deliver high performance, which is a very important component here being able to create a positive customer relationship, influence the customer's intention to repurchase and intend to interact in the future. Customer interaction here can also refer to the frequency of their sharing and word of mouth about the company's information and service quality. High engagement is associated with high intention to repurchase in the future" (HN).

Applying a qualitative approach in the first phase of the study helped to produce a wealth of information about the topic under investigation, which was used to build the second quantitative study. The current research's most important discovery was that it helped to clarify the following research questions: RQ1 – What are the key factors that have a direct impact on the salesperson's performance? RQ2 – What are the implications of improving a company's salesperson performance on anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention? The assessment of the literature has resulted in the establishment of the research conceptual framework and the hypotheses to be tested in the quantitative phase. Therefore, the following research framework is the result of the literature.

5.3. SUMMARY

The qualitative research was finished with an explanation of the data analysis and interview outcomes. The research aim (to build a thorough knowledge of salesperson performance and its implications on anticipating future interactions and repurchase intention) and research questions were presented in this chapter. First, the data analysis and interview findings were described. The findings were organised according to the major themes found in the associated literature. A framework model of the implementation and determinants of the salesperson performance has been constructed on the basis of the literature reviews and qualitative study.

CHAPTER VI: DATA ANALYSIS

6.1. INTRODUCTION

To attain the research objectives, the relationship between independent and dependent variables is analysed and specified in this chapter. Chapter 4 covers the full range of research methodology utilised in the thesis. This chapter is dedicated to the empirical analysis that underlies the research and provides the research findings from the main research covered in the previous chapters. The processes for preparing, editing, coding, and reviewing the data are described in Section 6.2. The acquired data's normality, linearity, multi-collinearity, and outliers are discussed in Section 6.3. The non-response bias is demonstrated in Section 6.4. Following that, the findings were re-evaluated using confirmatory factor analysis, as described in Section 6.5. Section 6.6. highlights structural equation modelling (SEM) that were used to examine the assumed relationships between the constructs in the conceptual framework, as well as to evaluate the overall goodness-of-fit between the suggested conceptual model and the gathered dataset. Section 6.7 concludes with a summary of the chapter.

6.2. MAIN SURVEYS

According to Sekaran (2003), survey questionnaires are used in the majority of marketing and social science research investigations. The main survey was carried out in this study aimed at collecting data for scale purification and hypothesis testing. All data were collected in Ho Chi Minh, Vietnam, and the samples are typical of the whole population. The characteristics of sex, age, education level, as well as marital status are mentioned in the questionnaire. Table 6.1 summarises the demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Table 6. 1: Demographic profile of the VINCOM CUSTOMER compared with the main population figures (N=385)

Sample size (N)	N	%
Age		
20 to 29 years	114	29.6
30 to 39 years	199	51.7
40 to 49 years	55	14.3
50 to 59 years	16	4.2
60 years old or more	1	.3
Total	385	100.0
Gender		
Male	160	41.6
Female	225	58.4
Total	385	100.0
Education		
Undergraduate	18	4.7
Postgraduate and above	367	95.3
Total	385	100.0
Occupation		
Top executive or manager	11	2.9
Lawyer, dentist or architect etc.	1	.3
Office/clerical staffs	7	1.8
Worker	6	1.6
Civil servant	1	.3
Craftsman	7	1.8
Student	352	91.4
Total	385	100.0

A total of 412 Vietnamese consumers responded to the questionnaire survey. However, several of them confirmed that they had never heard of Vincom Centre Shopping Mall before. Specifically, there were 385 individual participants who agreed that they “have heard of Vincom Centre Shopping Mall before”, accounting for nearly 94% of the sample. The information provided in Table 6.1 shows that females dominate the total number of valid participants, constituting 58.4% of the sample, while males account for 41.6%. However, it can be said that no large distinction between the number of female and male participants in

the survey can be found, implying that there are no gender biases towards statistical results regarding salesperson performance in anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention in Vietnam's retail industry. It can also be explained that both male and female customers have possessed similar perceptions and behavioural intentions regarding the salesperson's skills, characteristics, and performance. Hence, this study's data analysis may be accurate and reliable for individual customers of both genders. All participants were over 20 years old, namely 30 to 39 years (51.7%). In addition, the results also revealed that these people all held a degree of Postgraduate and above (95.3%). Therefore, the collected data can present customers repurchase intention and behaviour towards Vincom's salesperson performance more accurately since people with low education and under 20 years of age may have limited perception of the importance of salesperson characteristics and skills.

6.2.1. Data preparation

6.2.1.1. Data coding and editing

As Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) stated, the collected data must go through the editing process to ensure both their consistency and completeness. Missing data, also known as missing values, and patterns of missing data are both considered more common and serious problems than the amount missing. The obtained data was evaluated, and each item was coded and entered into an SPSS data sheet (Hair et al., 1998; Vaus, 1996). After coding, the data editing took place to confirm that the coding procedure was completed correctly. Furthermore, any values that are out of range are thoroughly checked.

6.2.1.2. Data screening and characteristics of the sample

Data accuracy is essential to be able to analyse and derive valid results from participants' responses. Before performing multivariate analysis, SPSS 27.0 was utilised in this study to perform data input accuracy checks. According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), screening and evaluating all data prior to analysis helps to strengthen the researcher's confidence in the integrity of the analysis as well as guarantee the validity and reliability of the results.

Inconsistency checks and missing responses are two important factors listed in the data cleaning and screening procedure.

Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) highlight four primary reasons for screening data before doing a multivariate analysis as follow: 1) the accuracy of the data collected, as well as an assessment of factors that may influence the correlation between the variables. 2) Screening for missing data helps to assess how it affects the results and how to cope with it. The amount of missing data was less important than the pattern of missing data (the data set was tested to find missing values, significantly missing values in the questionnaires and neutral or extreme responses for all questions will also be eliminated before going to the analysis process). 3) The impact of extreme values (also known as outliers) on the analysis was investigated. 4) The multivariate analysis procedure was conducted based on the assumptions; the appropriateness of the data as well as the assumptions were evaluated before proceeding with the procedure. Figure 6.1 shows the screening of the data before performing the analytical procedure. There is a data screening checklist that is also followed by the researcher (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

Figure 6. 1: Suggested routine for parametric data analysis

Source: Tabachnick and Fidell (2007)

6.2.1.3. Missing data analysis

The primary survey data was first checked for missing values. As Hair et al. (1998) stated, the examination of the missing data reflected the preliminary analysis, which has the potential to distort the results and cause trouble. Finding patterns in missing data is therefore essential to avoid potential biases. According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), the significance of missing data is determined by the pattern of the data, the amount of data missing, and the reason for the data's missing. There are two types of missing data that were reported by Hair et al. (2014): 1) the data that is designated as ignorable missing data, which is the random missing data process. 2) the missing data that cannot be defined as ignorable arises in a variety of circumstances for a variety of reasons. Accordingly, the missing data is divided into two categories: known and unknown processes (Hair et al., 2014). First, this process is known and occurs during data entry, which forms invalid codes, missing data also occurs when the measurement system fails, and participants did not complete the entire questionnaire. It seems difficult for researchers to control these circumstances, but certain solutions may be relevant if the missing data is discovered to be random. Second, unknown missing data processes are considered more difficult to ascertain and address. Most occurrences of this process are directly tied to the participant. For example, participants are often more likely to refuse to answer some sensitive or private questions. Researchers can grasp this fact and always try to limit them in the process of questionnaire design and data collection. But this means that the researcher has to find a way to solve the missing data. According to Hair et al. (2014), it is however not insurmountable when the pattern of missing data is random, there may be solutions available that the researcher can apply to relieve their impact.

According to Hair et al. (2014) and Field (2009), it is not mandatory for researcher to disregard missing data in the event that respondents missed providing data for some of the questions, on the other hand, the next phase in the procedure should be conducted and it is important for the researcher to assess the significance of the missing data. As Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) stated, there are 2 ways to check for missing data in this case. Firstly, approaching the amount of missing data predicated on incidence includes Missing

Completely At Random (MCAR), Missing At Random (MAR) or known ignorable, and Missing Not At Random (MNAR). Missing values that are spread randomly within a data matrix cause less significant concerns than missing values that are not distributed randomly. Along with that, the non-randomly missing values have an impact on the generalisability of outcomes. Hair et al. (1998) discussed that missing data in a non-random pattern is quite possible since there is a significant difference between the missing and non-missing values by the consequence of the preceding test. Second, tying up with the amount of missing data. The amount of missing data was found to be less crucial than the outline of the missing data, according to the study by Tabachnick and Fidell (2007).

6.2.1.3.1. Determining the extent and patterns of the missing data

Following the discussion of the above scholars, the SPSS with Expectation-Maximisation (EM) technique was applied to discover missing data for all 69 items in the actual survey (see details in Appendix 6.1). The obtained results demonstrate that no missing data was discovered. This implies that the questionnaire is comprehensive and confidential. Therefore, all participants provide full answers when participating in the survey. It also means that the questionnaire is suitable and applicable in real-life cases. There is no missing data nor is it necessary to test the pattern or apply remedies for this problem.

6.3. ASSESSMENT OF NORMALITY, OUTLIERS, LINEARITY, AND MULTI-COLLINEARITY

6.3.1. Testing the normality assumption

It can be said that normality is one of the important and indispensable assumptions of multivariate analysis, especially in structural equation modelling (SEM). For that reason, a normality test was performed in this study as a follow-up to the data coding step to guarantee that the data are within the range of the normality assumptions. Graphs and statistical approaches were used to assess the normality of data in this study. The normal probability plot (P-P plot of the regression standardised residual), as presented by Tabachnick and Fidell

(2007), is a popular graphical technique used to evaluate the approximate normal distribution of a data set. The data is plotted according to the theoretical standard and normally the points are distributed in a straight line. Through the results of the graph analysis, a number of variables with moderate to high deviations from normality were revealed and considered carefully in the data analysis. The data on the normal probability plot can be presented as a grouped (histogram plot) or as individual points. There are variables that having a significant nonlinear association, the correlation coefficient r is close to zero, but they do not gather around a straight line. The probability plots analysis, therefore, helps detect variables that deviate from normality. Besides, evaluating normal probability plots visually seems to be preferable in the case of larger sample sizes (Hair et al., 1998). Accordingly, these data are not expected to have substantial departures from normality. Supporting this, the study by Hair et al. (2014) and Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) suggests that once the degree of deviation from normality is considerable, the test results are not satisfactory. After analysing the figures visually (Appendix 6.2), it can be seen that the data in this study are evenly distributed around a straight line, which means that observing the sample is not necessitate any adjustment (transformation of the data). In addition, multivariate normality analysis through the normal probability plot also showed normal results (see Figure 6.2). Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Walk (K-S) was also an important test used in this study, which Field (2009) found to be suitable for determining the general shape of a distribution and evaluating the degree of deviation from the normal distribution. It is also known as a non-parametric test of equality of one-dimensional probability distributions that relies on a prediction of the minimum distance. Accordingly, it is appropriate to be able to assess a sample (one-sample K-S test) or two samples (two-sample K-S test) using a reference probability distribution. A large deviation has a low p-value. Therefore, when the significant result ($p < .05$), the distribution under consideration is considerably deviated from the normal distribution.

Figure 6. 2: Multivariate normal P-P plot of regression standardised residual

This statistical method is considered in the study through both item level (Appendix 6.3) and constructs level (Table 6.2). According to the findings, it can be seen that no normal distribution can be found in the study. Since the sample size is significantly large and p-value of K-S is very small, statistical results from K-S and S-W may not be reliable. However, researchers (Pallant, 2007) asserted that the K-S test's volatility is rather typical in big sample sets.

Table 6. 2: Test of normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
SPP_mean	0.113	385	0	0.966	385	0
SAM_mean	0.327	385	0	0.789	385	0
CUP_mean	0.317	385	0	0.799	385	0
SEG_mean	0.334	385	0	0.784	385	0
CUO_mean	0.148	385	0	0.909	385	0
VAS_mean	0.069	385	0	0.98	385	0
IPS_mean	0.193	385	0	0.918	385	0
SAS_mean	0.183	385	0	0.923	385	0
TES_mean	0.19	385	0	0.917	385	0
MAS_mean	0.196	385	0	0.909	385	0
EMA_mean	0.107	385	0	0.949	385	0
CUA_mean	0.104	385	0	0.95	385	0
AMS_mean	0.337	385	0	0.751	385	0

EXP_mean	0.165	385	0	0.899	385	0
ADS_mean	0.166	385	0	0.889	385	0
SWS_mean	0.117	385	0	0.968	385	0
TRS_mean	0.111	385	0	0.967	385	0
AFI_mean	0.133	385	0	0.931	385	0
REI_mean	0.052	385	0.014	0.991	385	0.025

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

The Jarque and Bera test is another important visual test of normality, used to check if data has skewness and kurtosis that meet the requirements of normally distributed or not. Skewness is a measure of the degree of deviation in the distribution. It is used to clarify the distribution's balance and to show the shape of the data distribution (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). The skew value of the distribution is zero. The higher the absolute value of the skewness, the more asymmetric the distribution is. A skewed variable has a meaning that is not located in the centre of the distribution (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). Kurtosis is a measure of the degree of tails in a distribution, used to indicate the flatness or peaks of the curve in the distribution, or can also measure outliers of the distribution. Kurtosis determines how the data are clustered around the centre of the distribution (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). The skewness and kurtosis values of the normal distribution are both zero. However, according to Hair et al. (2014), the negative skewness has a curve that is extended to the right and the tail is greatly extended to the left. A Kurtosis index greater than 0 represents a peaked distribution with a high and pointed central part and a thick and short tail. Conversely, a Kurtosis index less than 0 implies that the distribution is too flat. According to Foroudi (2012), "non-normal kurtosis produces an undervalue of the variance of the variables". However, the kurtosis, negative skewness, or positive skewness values cannot indicate anything except that they are within normal range, then the fundamental nature of the considered constructs will be present (Pallant, 2007, p. 56). Through the analytical results of this study, which are presented in Appendix 6.4, it can be seen that not all examined variables' range are acceptable for both skewness and kurtosis values, however, some variables that were found to be within the acceptable range for skewness and Kurtosis values (i.e. $< \pm 3$ (Hair et al., 2014); and non-normal distribution may be observed in the study.

6.3.2. Outliers: univariate and multivariate examination

Following Hawkins (1980) recommendation, an outlier is an observation that is not in the general trend compared to the rest of the data set. In addition, an outlier is known as "a case with such an extreme value on one variable (a univariate outlier) or such a strange combination of scores on two or more variables (multivariable outlier)" (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2006, p. 72) The term "outlier" in statistics can be understood as an observation that is out of the ordinary and is significantly different from other variable values. Outliers can be an important issue because when a dataset has too many outliers, they reduce the accuracy of statistical estimates (Hair et al., 1998). Observations in this case could be considered unrepresentative of the population and eliminated from the analysis. The data, according to statisticians, should be checked regularly to find outliers, as it can provide useful information regarding data. Besides, Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) argue that research should be cautious when applying the methods of determining outliers because there can be misunderstandings between discordant random data and outliers.

According to Hair et al. (1998) and Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), outliers are often very low or very high values and can distort the normality of the data. Outliers can be divided into two types: univariate outliers, which are outliers that occur when viewed in a single variable, and multivariate outliers, which occur when two or more variables are combined (Kline, 2005). Nevertheless, the literature does not adequately define extreme values or their tolerance. Univariate outliers were identified by gathering items together to symbolize a single construct. The observed values were also converted into standardised scores (z-scores) using the statistical software SPSS (Hair et al., 2006; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). As a rule, for sample sizes less than 80, outliers are determined if the standard score for the sample size is ± 2.5 or higher. The standard score for sample size is possibly 4 for large sample sizes (Hair et al., 2006, p.75). Furthermore, with a sample size greater than 80 (385), outliers are revealed if its standard score is ± 3.0 or higher (Hair et al., 2006; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). The approach is used with interval and ordinal level variables that are handled as metric variables, but it is not used with nominal level variables. The obtained results showed that univariate outliers appeared in the study data (Appendix 6.4), thus, they were left for

additional investigation. The descriptive statistics feature of SPSS was used to identify the univariate outliers once the items were combined into a single structure. The values of each observation were processed into a standard score (z-scores) (Hair et al., 2009).

Mahalanobis D2 is a fairly common method for determining multivariate outliers for research, which measures the similarity of several conditions to a set of known conditions (Hair et al., 2014). Mahalanobis D2 mentioned in the study by Hair et al. (2014) and Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) as a multidimensional version of a z-score. The value of $D2/df$, as recommended by Hair et al. (2014), if it exceeds 2.5 for small sample sizes, and exceeds 3 or 4 for large sample sizes, is likely to be counted as an outlier. In addition, conservative statistical test of significance ($p < 0.001$ or $p < 0.005$) can be combined with the Mahalanobis distance method which has the larger D2 value for a case result in a smaller corresponding probability value, then it can be deemed an outlier (Hair et al., 2014; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

The value of Mahalanobis D2 was determined through linear regression analysis. This study employed a function of SPSS 27.0 “1-CDF CHISQ (quant, df)”, where $quant = D2$ and $df = 18$ to determine the t-value of significance. The function provided a value from the chi-square distribution, i.e. D2, with a degree of freedom smaller than the quant. The analysis results from Table 6.3 show that there was 12 examined case in the dataset that has a p-value < 0.001 , implying that mild outliers were found in a total sample size of 385. These cases would be removed from the dataset before taking further analyses.

Table 6. 3: Multivariate outlier detection

Count	Case of outlier	Mahalanobis D2	p-value
1	22	76.5112	0
2	25	49.20282	0.0001
3	82	42.90959	0.00082
4	88	60.76521	0
5	93	48.30531	0.00014
6	139	53.18602	0.00002

7	184	63.51988	0
8	290	58.34821	0
9	298	56.39398	0.00001
10	318	54.83231	0.00001
11	320	46.41235	0.00026
12	339	42.71459	0.00088

6.3.3. Linearity and multi-collinearity

The assumption of linearity is that there is a straight-line relationship between the dependent variable and each of the independent variables (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). According to Hair et al. (2012), it is critical to evaluate the relationship between variables in order to detect any deviations that might alter the correlation. Furthermore, the importance of linear is reinforced when Pearson's r , in fact, detects only linear correlations between variables and ignores nonlinear interactions (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). In this study, the researcher tested the relationship between the variables through the mentioned research question. It is very difficult to determine the linearity of the latent variables. The simplest way to check for linear correlations is to create scatterplots and then visually evaluate them for linearity (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

The linearity and multi-collinearity of salesperson performance constructs were evaluated using Pearson's correlations matrix which significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), as well as all examined variables are scattered close to the centre, having a linear relationship (see figure 6.3). Pearson's correlation was also used to build the bivariate correlation matrix. According to research by Hair et al. (2009), Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) on the assumption of multicollinearity, there is no highly bivariate correlation between the independent and dependent variables (0.90 or higher). The results of the correlation matrix are presented in Table 6.4. In addition, as Hair et al. (2006) stated, multi-collinearity can also be considered through the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and tolerance effect. The multi-collinearity is significant when the VIF index is greater than 10 and tolerance is lower than 0.1 (Pallant, 2007).

Figure 6. 3: Salesperson performance constructs scatter plot matrix

Source: Analysis of survey data

Table 6. 4: Descriptive statistics and correlation matrix for the constructs

	SPP_mean	SAM_mean	CUP_mean	SEG_mean	CUO_mean	VAS_mean	IPS_mean	SAS_mean	TES_mean	MAS_mean	EMA_mean	CUA_mean	AMS_mean	EXP_mean	ADS_mean	SWS_mean	TRS_mean	AFI_mean	REI_mean
SPP_mean	1	.317**	.359**	.308**	.413**	.306**	.315**	.317**	.316**	.278**	.321**	.233**	.376**	0.079	.242**	.107*	0.056	.118*	-0.015
SAM_mean	.317**	1	.830**	.895**	.321**	.193**	.186**	.228**	.227**	.178**	.378**	.410**	.521**	.255**	.443**	-0.01	-.107*	-0.009	0.047
CUP_mean	.359**	.830**	1	.891**	.333**	.174**	.191**	.213**	.226**	.193**	.352**	.423**	.485**	.294**	.415**	-0.003	-0.062	-0.018	0.048
SEG_mean	.308**	.895**	.891**	1	.288**	.191**	.173**	.231**	.212**	.174**	.343**	.435**	.507**	.265**	.429**	0.006	-0.086	-0.016	0.041
CUO_mean	.413**	.321**	.333**	.288**	1	.249**	.179**	.197**	.186**	.193**	.240**	.243**	.331**	.139**	.362**	0.016	-0.04	0.058	0.001
VAS_mean	.306**	.193**	.174**	.191**	.249**	1	.308**	.295**	.312**	.287**	.229**	.215**	.232**	0.099	.234**	0.003	0.018	0.004	0.094
IPS_mean	.315**	.186**	.191**	.173**	.179**	.308**	1	.816**	.870**	.863**	.208**	.140**	.235**	0.038	0.089	-0.012	0.035	0.04	0.001
SAS_mean	.317**	.228**	.213**	.231**	.197**	.295**	.816**	1	.869**	.869**	.191**	.170**	.249**	0.067	.121*	0.045	0.045	0.062	0.023
TES_mean	.316**	.227**	.226**	.212**	.186**	.312**	.870**	.869**	1	.865**	.221**	.165**	.246**	0.042	.153**	-0.013	0.071	0.044	-0.012
MAS_mean	.278**	.178**	.193**	.174**	.193**	.287**	.863**	.869**	.865**	1	.191**	.153**	.216**	0.058	.104*	-0.03	-0.004	0.048	0.017
EMA_mean	.321**	.378**	.352**	.343**	.240**	.229**	.208**	.191**	.221**	.191**	1	.429**	.691**	.153**	.303**	-0.016	-0.015	0.06	0.083
CUA_mean	.233**	.410**	.423**	.435**	.243**	.215**	.140**	.170**	.165**	.153**	.429**	1	.694**	0.1	.257**	-0.007	-0.003	0.067	0.029
AMS_mean	.376**	.521**	.485**	.507**	.331**	.232**	.235**	.249**	.246**	.216**	.691**	.694**	1	.171**	.340**	0.018	0.013	0.07	0.096
EXP_mean	0.079	.255**	.294**	.265**	.139**	0.099	0.038	0.067	0.042	0.058	.153**	0.1	.171**	1	.255**	-0.057	-0.011	0.041	0.008
ADS_mean	.242**	.443**	.415**	.429**	.362**	.234**	0.089	.121*	.153**	.104*	.303**	.257**	.340**	.255**	1	-0.016	-0.034	0.014	0.019
SWS_mean	.107*	-0.01	-0.003	0.006	0.016	0.003	-0.012	0.045	-0.013	-0.03	-0.016	-0.007	0.018	-0.057	-0.016	1	.130*	.121*	0.017
TRS_mean	0.056	-.107*	-0.062	-0.086	-0.04	0.018	0.035	0.045	0.071	-0.004	-0.015	-0.003	0.013	-0.011	-0.034	.130*	1	0.006	-0.069
AFI_mean	.118*	-0.009	-0.018	-0.016	0.058	0.004	0.04	0.062	0.044	0.048	0.06	0.067	0.07	0.041	0.014	.121*	0.006	1	0.073
REI_mean	-0.015	0.047	0.048	0.041	0.001	0.094	0.001	0.023	-0.012	0.017	0.083	0.029	0.096	0.008	0.019	0.017	-0.069	0.073	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (Pearson correlation sig. (2-tailed)).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

In this study, the VIF and tolerance effects were calculated, respectively, based on a multiple regression approach that included a collinearity diagnostic option, respectively. The VIF results obtained in this case indicate the existence of multi-collinearity, and the regression results may be insignificant and unreliable. However, assume that REI is a dependent variable of the study. It can be seen that when the tolerance scores are larger or equals 0.5, VIFs of examined variables significantly vary between 1 and 2. Therefore, the tolerance effect is high, and multi-collinearity would not be a problem in the empirical regression model.

Table 6. 5: Regression for observing VIF and tolerance effect

	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	Tolerance	VIF	B	Std. Error
(Constant)	2171	,536				4,047	,000
SPP_mean	-,046	,079	-,042	,500	1,998	-,581	,561
SAM_mean	-,076	,055	-,095	,543	1,842	-1,388	,166
CUP_mean	,050	,057	,062	,518	1,931	,886	,376
SEG_mean	-,007	,055	-,007	,737	1,357	-,119	,905
CUO_mean	,079	,069	,062	,865	1,155	1,147	,252
VAS_mean	,084	,061	,089	,605	1,653	1,373	,170
IPS_mean	-,066	,074	-,054	,708	1,412	-,899	,369
SAS_mean	,073	,065	,068	,713	1,403	1,129	,260
TES_mean	-,008	,082	-,006	,753	1,327	-,097	,922
MAS_mean	,028	,082	,021	,652	1,535	,341	,733
EMA_mean	-,078	,055	-,073	,931	1,074	-1,400	,162
CUA_mean	,039	,070	,036	,608	1,645	,554	,580
AMS_mean	-,111	,053	-,132	,646	1,547	-2,103	,036
EXP_mean	-,047	,123	-,023	,719	1,391	-,383	,702
ADS_mean	,201	,095	,120	,802	1,247	2,128	,034
SWS_mean	,233	,061	,218	,782	1,278	3,810	,000
TRS_mean	-,048	,046	-,059	,790	1,266	-1,038	,300
AFI_mean	,038	,060	,043	,555	1,803	,638	,524

Dependent variable: REI

6.3.4. Homoscedasticity/ homogeneity

Homoscedasticity, also known as homogeneity of variances, is an assumption of equal or similar variance values in the different groups being compared. Homoscedasticity is considered as one of the important assumptions when performing multivariate linear regression because of its sensitivity and potential for bias in multivariate analysis results. (Hair et al., 2006). Errors in homoscedasticity are developed from the non-normality of some variables in the data set or the combination of one variable with the transformation of another. According to Field (2009), Pallant (2007), to demonstrate homoscedasticity, Levene's test was used in this study to measure equality between variances, which is significant at $p\text{-value} \leq .05$. As a result, the heterogeneity of variance seems to be quite conservative (Hair et al., 2006).

Assume that gender is the factor variable. The observed results in Table 6.6 show that the p -values of AMS are significantly less than 0.05, implying that equal variances failed to be assumed. Therefore, this variable violates the homogeneity of variances required for an ANOVA test. Meanwhile, the variances of other examined cases are robust and homogeneous. Further parametric statistical tests can be significantly employed in the research.

Table 6. 6: Levene's test of homogeneity of variances

	Levene statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
SPP_mean	,456	1	383	,500
SAM_mean	,181	1	383	,671
CUP_mean	,559	1	383	,455
SEG_mean	1,103	1	383	,294
CUO_mean	,006	1	383	,939
VAS_mean	,001	1	383	,978
IPS_mean	,069	1	383	,793
SAS_mean	,234	1	383	,629
TES_mean	,070	1	383	,792
MAS_mean	,728	1	383	,394

EMA_mean	1010	1	383	,316
CUA_mean	,011	1	383	,917
AMS_mean	7,092	1	383	,008
EXP_mean	,040	1	383	,842
ADS_mean	,296	1	383	,587
SWS_mean	1,060	1	383	,304
TRS_mean	,018	1	383	,894
AFI_mean	,045	1	383	,833
REI_mean	,217	1	383	,641

Source: Analysis of survey data

6.4. NON-RESPONSE BIASNESS

The most important part of the statistical survey process is that the number of samples collected must be representative of the population. Non-response bias is interpreted as a large amount of missing data, which occurs when there is a significant difference between those who responded to the survey and those who did not (Churchill, 1979). Non-response bias is a fairly common problem in statistical research, which often occurs when information about all subjects in the sample cannot be obtained. It may include participants who forgot to return the survey and participants who refused to answer all the questions given or even refuse to participate in the survey. It can also happen when the questionnaire cannot reach all the initial desired samples (Saunders et al., 2007). As Sekaran (2003) suggestion, to minimise non-response bias, the researcher's commitment to the confidentiality of the information collected is important.

According to Lambert and Harrington (1990), the Mann-Whitney U-test was considered to be used in this study to assess the likelihood of any potential non-response bias through early response (first 50 observations returned) or late response (last 50 observations returned) of the participant. In this study, grouping variable “Gender” is used to run Mann-Whitney U test for examining whether there exist any differences between late and early respondents. In accordance with table 6.7, Mann-Whitney U p-value of SAM_mean, SEG_mean, TES_mean is less than 0.05. The equal distribution of these variables is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference of sales models, ability to modify self-presentation, and satisfaction

with salesperson between male and female participants in the research.

Table 6. 7: Mann-Whitney U-test observing non-response biasness

	SPP_mean	SAM_mean	CUP_mean	SEG_mean	CUO_mean	VAS_mean	IPS_mean
Mann-Whitney U	16712.5	15623	16320.5	15912	16974.5	17367	16796
Wilcoxon W	29592.5	28503	29200.5	28792	29854.5	30247	29676
Z	-1.198	-2.39	-1.677	-2.109	-0.962	-0.589	-1.134
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.231	0.017	0.093	0.035	0.336	0.556	0.257
	SAS_mean	TES_mean	MAS_mean	EMA_mean	CUA_mean	AMS_mean	EXP_mean
Mann-Whitney U	16449.5	15413.5	16793	17950	16784.5	16349	16159.5
Wilcoxon W	29329.5	28293.5	29673	43375	29664.5	29229	41584.5
Z	-1.458	-2.435	-1.135	-0.047	-1.136	-1.658	-1.728
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.145	0.015	0.256	0.963	0.256	0.097	0.084
	ADS_mean	SWS_mean	TRS_mean	AFI_mean	REI_mean		
Mann-Whitney U	17030.5	16197	15938.5	17708	17401		
Wilcoxon W	29910.5	29077	28818.5	30588	30281		
Z	-0.905	-1.679	-1.921	-0.274	-0.557		
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.366	0.093	0.055	0.784	0.577		

a. Grouping Variable: gender

6.5. FACTOR LOADING AND DATA ANALYSIS

Factor analysis (FA) is a useful statistical method for discovering the underlying factors (latent variables), as well as investigating the relationships between the different variables under study (observation variables) (Alkarkhi and Alqaraghuli, 2018). Factor analysis is often used to reduce data. In other words, it aims to simplify an initially complex set of variables into a smaller set of variables in the form of factors (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). Factor analysis (FA), according to Field (2009) and Hair et al. (2009), is often used in the following basic cases: 1) to better understand the structure of variables, 2) to reduce a set of interdependent variables into a smaller and more significant set of variables that still contain most of the original information, 3) to build a questionnaire to evaluate the underlying variables.

Factor analysis focuses on evaluating fundamental dimensions where variables appear to gather together in a significant manner. This can be accomplished by examining for factors that are substantially associated with a set of other factors but do not associate with factors outside of that group (Field, 2009). According to Hair et al. (2006), there are two concerns that factor analysis can be used to address: 1) to determine the main entities to be analysed in the study as well as the correlation structure between variables or participants, 2) to obtain both summarised and reduced data and to integrate individual variables into groups that may collectively reflect the underlying dimensions.

According to Nazarian et al. (2017), EFA is an exploratory factor analysis with the main function of discovering latent factors, because there are no a priori constraints on the pattern of correlations between the observed measures and the latent variables. Meanwhile, CFA is confirmatory factor analysis with the main function of confirming the factors built from the theory, because researchers need to predetermine all crucial aspects of the factor model (i.e. number of factors, patterns of relationships between factors, and indicators). EFA in its nature is about discovering and identifying observed variables with no measurement error, which leads to less accurate and unreliable estimates. However, since the CFA identifies observed variables with measurement error, resulting in more accurate estimates and a

greater likelihood of errors being avoided. The scales' convergent and construct validity are evaluated in the following section.

According to Hair et al. (2006), factor analyses are carried out by determining the correlations (or covariance) between factors using a specified set of factors that are significant (positively or negatively). Factor analysis includes two basic types, which are exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). EFA and CFA have in common that they are both data reduction techniques and are also useful for grouping variables. However, as Hair et al. (2006) stated, EFA is more about figuring out how constructs in their nature are affecting a set of responses, whereas CFA investigates if a specified set of constructs is impacting responses in a predictable manner. Following Field's (2009) recommendation, CFA requires a strong empirical foundation to specify and estimate factor models to test hypotheses. Accordingly, CFA analysis is often used in the later stages of scale development or structural determination, after baseline data in a group have been collected through previous EFA analysis. SPSS 27.0 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) was used in this study to perform the EFA analysis (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

6.5.1. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

Hair et al. (2006, 2009) asserts that EFA is a quantitative analysis method for evaluating the relationships of variables in a data set and characterising them in the form of the common fundamental factors. EFA analysis, as stated by Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), is appropriate for determining the factor structure, assessing the important values of the scale as well as discovering the basic common structure for a group of observed variables. The size of a group of observed variables is considered in the process of implementing EFA to determine whether a factor in the set can represent most of the remaining variations. There are several default processes for extracting and rotating factors that are assigned in statistical data analysis software, including SPSS 27.0. And principal component analysis (PCA) is one of the popular extraction methods used to help develop solutions for EFA. PCA is used to summarise the observed variables that are included in factor analysis, and to help reduce a large number of observations to a smaller number of major factors (Fabrigar and Wegener,

2011; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). Accordingly, Hair et al. (2006) claimed that PCA is useful in extracting the maximum variances in a data set so that it is possible to extract the highest variance for the first component, and the lowest variance for the last component.

Following factor extraction, identifying the number of load variables per factor through the rotated loading matrix is a critical accompanying process to create a simple structure and facilitate the interpretation of factors. Accordingly, some researchers (Field, 2009; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Hair et al., 2014) indicate that orthogonal and oblique rotation are the two main preferred rotation methods. According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), orthogonal rotation method is appropriate to use when the factors are independent of each other. This approach minimises the number of high-loaded variables per factor and simplifies the interpretation and reporting outcomes. Also, oblique rotation method is considered for large data sets, when two or more extracted factors are correlated. This method makes it simpler to describe and explain the manifest variables (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) and Pallant (2007), Varimax rotation is considered one of the Orthogonal factor rotation methods commonly used in statistics to maximise the variance of loadings on each factor, minimise low correlations as well as clarifies the relationship between the factors. Varimax allows the transformation of the original factors into new factors that are easier to interpret (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). This technique is also predisposed to reallocate variance among factors, the variance is obtained from the first extracted factors and dispersed among the following ones to make them roughly equal in meaning. Reporting and interpreting results from the orthogonal rotation method is considered to be significantly easier than the oblique rotation method because of uncorrelated factors.

‘Latent root criteria’, screen test criteria’ and ‘percentage of variance criteria’ are the 3 criteria considered in this study when conducting factor extraction. Field (2009) suggested that assessing the variability in variance for variables is crucial to be able to perform well the factor extraction process. Communality, as Hair et al. (2014) recommendation, is the estimated proportion of variance detected in a particular variable with an allowable value

between 0 and 1. Also, communality describes the average degree of variation between variables through the measurement model. A variable whose variance is fully explanatory or whose variance is not specific has communality of 1. In contrast, a variable with a completely unexplained variance (share nothing with the rest of the variables) has a communality of 0 (Field, 2013). Communality can be assessed based on factor loading in a model of numerous constructs. Its value, according to Hair et al. (2017) must then be greater than 0.5 to be considered ideal, or a larger sample size is needed if this is not the case. For models in which constructs have only 3 items or less, or communality value of 0.45 to 0.55, the sample size of the study should be greater than 200 (Hair et al., 2017). However, when communality is less than 0.45, the ideal sample size should be 300 or more. The cut-off value of communality (0.3) may also be considered in some cases for sample size (Pallant, 2007).

In addition, Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin and Bartlett's test was also conducted in this study to ensure the adequacy of the factor analysis results (Field, 2009). The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) is a measure of the suitability of data for factor analysis (Norusis, 1993). Following the recommendations of Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), the KMO's measures of sampling adequacy need a value of 0.6 or more as a sufficient condition to perform EFA, which shows the correlation between items in terms of significance. On the other hand, a KMO value less than 0.6 reveals that the data set is ineligible to proceed further in the EFA process. Bartlett's test of sphericity, as Hair et al. (2006) stated, used to examine how observed variables are correlated and whether they are ideal for factor analysis. The test is acceptable when the significance value of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is less than 0.05 (Shkeer and Awang, 2019).

EFA was applied in this study for items obtained from literature and from qualitative research, including 69 items related to salesperson performance evaluated to support 11 theoretically established constructs. In regard to all examined variables, the adequacy score of KMO test is equal to $0.902 > 0.6$ is consistent with the sampling level. Also, the p-value of Bartlett's test reaches zero, implies that all examined variables are valid and appropriate ($BTS = <0.001$) (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007) (see in table 6.8). Eigenvalue is a common criterion for determining the number of factors in EFA analysis, and only those factors with an Eigenvalue of 1 or greater are significant (Field, 2009). Accordingly, there are 12 factors in

this study with eigenvalue > 1 and items loaded separately in different components. Five items (i.e. EMA1, CUA2, ADS3, REI3, REI6) with low reliability, which had the value of Cronbach's alpha < 0.3 were eliminated in this round.

Table 6. 8: KMO and Bartlett's test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.902
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	20031.999
	df	2016
	Sig.	0

The following Table 6.9 shows that the communality of the variables retained in the factor loading is above 0.6. It can be seen that variation between all examined items range between 0.618 and 0.879. This implies that these items satisfy acceptable values of explanation. Therefore, they are viewed as sufficient variables in the study. They may also fit well with the rest of the items in the same component (Hair et al., 2006).

Table 6. 9: Communalities shared by individual items

Variables	Initial	Extraction	Variables	Initial	Extraction	Variables	Initial	Extraction
SPP1	1	0.666	IPS1	1	0.729	ADS4	1	0.717
SPP2	1	0.762	IPS3	1	0.774	ADS5	1	0.845
SPP3	1	0.679	SAS1	1	0.758	ADS6	1	0.879
SPP4	1	0.798	SAS3	1	0.777	SWS1	1	0.657
SPP5	1	0.785	TES2	1	0.798	SWS2	1	0.761
SPP6	1	0.766	TES3	1	0.807	SWS3	1	0.694
SPP7	1	0.795	MAS2	1	0.807	SWS4	1	0.81
SAM2	1	0.775	MAS3	1	0.802	SWS5	1	0.807
SAM3	1	0.801	EMA2	1	0.745	TRS1	1	0.674
CUP1	1	0.77	EMA3	1	0.808	TRS2	1	0.765
CUP3	1	0.836	CUA1	1	0.748	TRS3	1	0.724
SEG2	1	0.831	CUA3	1	0.817	TRS4	1	0.828
SEG3	1	0.86	AMS1	1	0.8	AFI1	1	0.667
CUO1	1	0.665	AMS2	1	0.818	AFI2	1	0.773

CUO4	1	0.778	AMS3	1	0.853	AFI3	1	0.718
CUO5	1	0.785	EXP1	1	0.63	AFI4	1	0.839
CUO6	1	0.783	EXP2	1	0.654	REI1	1	0.7
VAS1	1	0.618	EXP3	1	0.686	REI2	1	0.773
VAS2	1	0.643	EXP4	1	0.745	REI4	1	0.686
VAS3	1	0.64	EXP5	1	0.75	REI5	1	0.836
VAS4	1	0.706	ADS1	1	0.69			
VAS5	1	0.764	ADS2	1	0.75			

Extraction method: principal component analysis.

Note: SPP = salesperson performance, SAM = sales model, CUP = customer prioritisation, SEG = segmentation, CUO = customer orientation, VAS = value based-selling, IPS = interpersonal skill, SAS = salesmanship skill, TES = technical skill, MAS = marketing skill, EMA = empathetic ability, CUA = cue perception ability, AMS = ability to modify self-presentation, EXP = experience, ADS = adaptive selling behaviour, SWS = satisfaction with salesperson, TRS = trust in salesperson, AFI = anticipation of future interaction, and REI = repurchase intention

According to Hair et al. (2006), Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), the total variance explained is 50% or higher indicating that the EFA model is appropriate. There are 69 components in total in the EFA analysis. However, only 12 components have eigenvalue larger than 1. Therefore, all examined variables are loaded separately in 12 different components. Those with Eigenvalue less than 1 should be eliminated from the study for further analyses. The results from table 6.10 show that the highest variance extracted by items into a construct reaches 22.011%. Meanwhile, total variance for all valid items with eigenvalue > 1 constitutes more than 75.6% of the whole variance (see column cumulative %), higher compared to suggestions. The scree plot test also shows 12 components that contribute to the bulk of variance in the study.

Table 6. 10: Total variance explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	14.087	22.011	22.011	14.087	22.011	22.011	6.361	9.938	9.938

2	5.761	9.001	31.012	5.761	9.001	31.012	5.642	8.816	18.754
3	4.425	6.914	37.926	4.425	6.914	37.926	5.31	8.296	27.05
4	3.5	5.468	43.394	3.5	5.468	43.394	4.796	7.493	34.543
5	3.361	5.252	48.646	3.361	5.252	48.646	3.773	5.896	40.44
6	3.094	4.834	53.48	3.094	4.834	53.48	3.732	5.832	46.271
7	2.87	4.484	57.964	2.87	4.484	57.964	3.483	5.442	51.713
8	2.818	4.403	62.367	2.818	4.403	62.367	3.332	5.206	56.919
9	2.371	3.705	66.072	2.371	3.705	66.072	3.008	4.7	61.619
10	2.313	3.614	69.686	2.313	3.614	69.686	3.002	4.691	66.31
11	2.056	3.212	72.898	2.056	3.212	72.898	2.997	4.683	70.993
12	1.752	2.738	75.636	1.752	2.738	75.636	2.972	4.643	75.636
13	0.709	1.108	76.745						
14	0.612	0.956	77.701						
15	0.596	0.932	78.633						

Extraction method: Principal component analysis (There were 69 items checked, but the table only displays 15 observations to be representative).

The scree test is used in multivariate statistics to identify the number of factors extracted by eigenvalues in which the scree plot is a graphing tool that illustrates the eigenvalues of factors or principal components in an analysis, used to select the maximum number of components or related factors that should be retained. The eigenvalues of these factors are always distributed descending from left to right, following a downward curve to a linear decreasing pattern (Hair et al., 2006). As the plot on screen descends negatively, the first factor with the highest eigenvalues is determined, the following factors have moderate but declining eigenvalues, and the last few factors with modest eigenvalues (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). To screen the number of factors to be extracted through eigenvalues, as Hair et al. (2014) stated, it is important to identify the inflection point of the factors, the point at which the slope of the curve changes dramatically (clearly flattened). Through the scree plot test results from Figure 6.4, it is easy to see the clear division between 11 and 13. Components one to twelve have the Eigenvalue larger than 1, implies capturing more variance than the rest of the components, whose Eigenvalue scores fluctuate close to zero.

Figure 6. 4: Scree plot of all the dimensions

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

It is crucial to determine the appropriate loading for each variable for the specific factor (Hair et al., 2010, 2014). According to academics, items loading greater than 0.3 is sufficient and appropriate, a loading factor of 0.4 is stable, and greater than or equal to 0.5 is practically significant (Costello and Osborne, 2005; Stevens, 2002). Its minimum acceptable threshold is 0.3, therefore, factors loading below should be disregarded (Churchill, 1979; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). Additionally, the sample size and statistical significance both have an impact on the loading factor (Hair et al., 2014). Given the research's sample size of 385, the factor loading was above 0.5, which is deemed appropriate (Çokluk et al., 2010; Hair et al., 2010). From the results obtained in Table 6.11, it can be seen that items were loaded on their corresponding constructs. The factor loading values of examined variables vary from 0.728 to 0.908, which meets the criteria of factor loadings, as recommended by Hair et al. (2014) and Pallant (2007).

Table 6. 11: Factor loadings

Items	Component											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
MAS2	0.885											
MAS3	0.874											
TES3	0.87											

IPS3	0.862		
TES2	0.858		
SAS3	0.853		
SAS1	0.847		
IPS1	0.822		
AMS2	0.857		
AMS3	0.851		
AMS1	0.831		
CUA3	0.828		
EMA3	0.8		
EMA2	0.799		
CUA1	0.78		
SPP7	0.844		
SPP6	0.843		
SPP5	0.841		
SPP4	0.823		
SPP2	0.808		
SPP1	0.755		
SPP3	0.75		
SEG2	0.843		
SEG3	0.837		
CUP3	0.814		
CUP1	0.792		
SAM3	0.792		
SAM2	0.79		
ADS6	0.859		
ADS5	0.852		
ADS4	0.785		
ADS2	0.768		
ADS1	0.728		
SWS4	0.891		
SWS5	0.888		
SWS2	0.866		
SWS3	0.821		
SWS1	0.799		
EXP5	0.85		
EXP4	0.833		

EXP3								0.811				
EXP2								0.77				
EXP1								0.76				
VAS5									0.835			
VAS4									0.798			
VAS3									0.76			
VAS2									0.746			
VAS1									0.742			
AFI4										0.908		
AFI2										0.872		
AFI3										0.838		
AFI1										0.803		
REI5											0.906	
REI2											0.867	
REI1											0.817	
REI4											0.817	
TRS4												0.905
TRS2												0.865
TRS3												0.831
TRS1												0.806
CUO2												0.823
CUO4												0.818
CUO3												0.806
CUO1												0.75
Cronbach's	.958	.955	.941	.952	.921	.910	.879	.869	.885	.881	.880	.885
a												

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalisation.

a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

Note: SPP = salesperson performance, SAM = sales model, CUP = customer prioritisation, SEG = segmentation, CUO = customer orientation, VAS = value based-selling, IPS = interpersonal skill, SAS = salesmanship skill, TES = technical skill, MAS = marketing skill, EMA = empathetic ability, CUA = cue perception ability, AMS = ability to modify self-presentation, EXP = experience, ADS = adaptive selling behaviour, SWS = satisfaction with salesperson, TRS = trust in salesperson, AFI = anticipation of future interaction, and REI = repurchase intention

In order to improve the accuracy when testing constructs theoretically, the researcher has divided these constructs into two groups as follows: 1) the salesperson performance and its components (sales strategy, sales skills, sales characteristics, experience, customer orientation, value based-selling, and adaptive selling behaviour), 2) the main benefits of the salesperson performance (satisfaction with salesperson, trust in salesperson, anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention). Since there are many constructs in the model that need to be examined, Menon et al. (1996) claimed that the fewer measurements, the more reliable the results are. Following the determination of internal consistency, the loading factors were respectively evaluated based on Cronbach's alpha measure (Nunnally, 1978), which demonstrates the consistency of the components with their related items (Cronbach, 1951).

6.6. STRUCTURAL EVALUATION OF THE MODEL

6.6.1. Basic concepts of structural equation modelling (SEM)

6.6.1.1. Introduction

Structural equation modelling (SEM) is one of the most complex and flexible statistical analysis techniques used to analyse multidimensional relationships between variables in a model (Haenlein and Kaplan, 2004). According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2006), structural equation modelling (SEM) is also known as causal modelling, path modelling, covariance structures analysis, or confirmatory factor analysis.

Structural equation modelling (SEM) allows the researcher to test a set of regression equations at the same time, which can powerfully address the requirements related to principal component analysis (PCA), factor analysis, linear regression, or analysis of variance. In particular, SEM is also used to estimate measurement models and the structural models of multivariate analysis (Hair et al., 2006). The variables in SEM are related to each other, can directly or indirectly affect each other through intermediate variables, helping to develop a causal relationship between the model's variables. A change in one variable leads

to a change in another variable, which is expressed through internal consistency as measured by Cronbach's Alpha coefficient.

6.6.1.2. Types of models in SEM

As a type of SEM, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) has basic characteristics related to specific aspects of theoretical modelling. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) focuses on measurement models, specifically examining the relationship between observed variables and latent variables (factors) (Byrne, 2013; Gupta et al., 2011; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

Besides, many marketing scholars focus on the two-step modelling approach and claim that two-step approach provides the basis for evaluating pattern coefficients; develops a framework for predicting the presence or absence of response variables, as well as for comparison with substantive models to make inferences about theoretical constructs and their interrelationships (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988; Cheung, 2015, Hair et al., 2006). Accordingly, to implement this approach, the researcher conducted 2 stages respectively as follows: 1) a confirmatory test of the measurement model to determine the causal relationship between the observed variable and the latent variable. Construct validity was also adopted with the CFA during this period (Hair et al., 2006); 2) a test of structural model (regression path analysis) to clarify the correlation of causal hypotheses between measured constructs.

6.6.1.3. Practical consideration for SEM

Since SEM is one of the complex techniques that use the combination of quantitative data and correlation assumptions (cause - effect) into the model; and is especially used in the advanced stage of the research process, therefore, it requires preparation and careful consideration of practical aspects before being applied to research (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

6.6.1.3.1. Sample size

Besides the usefulness of SEM in analysing the causal relationships of complex models, SEM also causes many difficulties for researchers in the process of using when determining the appropriate sample size. The sample size reflects the study population. Larger sample sizes lead to lower sample error estimates, higher population representativeness and model accuracy (Hair et al., 2014). According to scholars (Comrey and Lee, 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013), instead of using raw data, SEM tends to rely on covariances as input, which is less stable when estimating with small sample sizes. The large sample size required in SEM is based on the complexity and number of items measured in the model, model misspecification and estimation procedure (Hair et al., 2006, 2014; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). However, there is no universal method or limit for determining sample size in SEM. As Hair et al. (2006) recommendation, for a model with fewer than 5 constructs, more than 3 items per construct, and communality greater than 0.6, a sample size between 100 and 150 can be considered appropriate. The sample size is 200 or more when the communality ranges from 0.45 to 0.55 (Hair et al., 2006; Kline, 2015). However, 200 samples are still too small for a complex model. The required sample size should be 500 for models with 6 or more constructs and communality less than 0.45 (Hair et al., 2006, 2014). For this study, the sample size is 385, with communality all over 0.5, so sample size is not a significant issue to consider.

6.6.2. One-step or two-step approach

The two-step approach is a popular method with a combination of measurement modelling and structural modelling. This method has always been highly appreciated by researchers (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988; Hair et al., 2006; Kline, 2015), and was considered in this study as its significant advantages. The two-step approach allows researchers to quickly form useful inferences and comparisons between the proposed model and the alternative model. The measurement model is to test the unidimensionality, solve the relationship between latent variables and its measures, and measure the model's reliability and validity. Besides,

structural models support the determination of causal relationships according to the theory proposed between latent variables in the path diagram.

The one-step approach, according to Anderson and Gerbing (1988), was used to estimate the measurement model and structural model. This approach specifically allows to assess model's overall fit without taking into account separate measurement and structural models (Hair et al., 2006). The one-step approach is considered ideal when the model is formed from substantial theoretical arguments and the items are carefully constructed from previous research (Hair et al., 2006; Fornel and Yi, 1992). However, compared with the two-step approach when applied to studies, the one-step approach is less preferred because it is challenging to meet the criteria for good model fitting (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988).

6.6.3. Basic model evaluation

As many scholars' recommendation, the two-step approach was applied in this study through AMOS 24 to: 1) evaluating the measurement model (outer-model), which determines the causal relationship between latent variables and measured items; 2) assessing the structural model (inner-model), which defines the degree of causality between the latent variables based on path coefficients (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988; Cheung, 2015, Hair et al., 2006; Kline, 2015). The analysis results of these two models are explained in turn as follows:

6.6.3.1. Step one: measurement model results

Testing the measurement model is a part of model evaluation in which CFA is used as a key tool to measure the reliability (Cronbach's α and composite reliability) and validity of the model (convergent and discriminant). Factor analysis is applied in the stage of measurement model to assess the load of measured items on their constructs (Barbara, 2001). The confirmatory measurement model, as stated by Hair et al. (2006), determines the correlation between measured items and latent variables. The criteria for satisfying external consistency are either defining multiple loading items through employing full measurement models and

modification indices (in AMOS) or discarding items that do not "cluster together in a matrix of sorted or ordered similarity coefficients" (Anderson and Gerbing, 1982).

Applying CFA in the measurement model stage allows the overall validity (e.g. nomological validity) of the model to be assessed. The absolute fit indices may include the Chi-Squared test, RMSEA, GFI, AGFI, RMR, and SRMR; determine how well the priori model fits or reproduces the sample data. The fit indices represent the overall difference between the observed and assumed covariance matrices. Therefore, following Steenkamp and Trijp (1991) suggestion, unidimensionality and goodness-of-fit criteria are considered in the study to clarify the practical usefulness of the model (Steenkamp and Trijp, 1991). Unidimensionality is known as one of the important attributes of a measurement construct, evaluated through reliability testing (i.e. Cronbach's alpha) and factor loadings for each construct to present that there is a single common trait (single latent trait) underlying all indices (Lumsden, 1961; Steenkamp and Trijp, 1991). In addition, model's fit is also an important challenge for researchers. A model with a good fit allows to produce accurate and reliable results. For that reason, a variety of goodness-of-fit criteria have been proposed so that SEMs can be assessed under various assumptions (Byrne, 2001; Kaplan, 2000).

According to scholars (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2006; Kline, 2005; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007), the overall fit of the measurement model was evaluated based on the fit indices as follows absolute fit, incremental fit, and parsimony fit indices. The absolute fit indices measure the overall fit for both structural and measurement models, determine how well the priori model fits, or reproduces the sample data (Hair et al, 1998), predict the correlation matrix and compare the satisfactory fit of the proposed models (Hair et al, 2006). Common criteria for absolute fit indices can be listed as follows: Chi-square (χ^2), goodness-of-fit index (GFI), normed fit Chi-square CMIN/DF (χ^2 /df), adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI), and root means square error of approximation residual (RMSEA) (see table 6.12).

Table 6. 12: Goodness-of-fit measures

	Description	Acceptable fit
Absolute fit measures		
Chi-square (χ^2)	A ‘badness of fit measure’ Minimum value of discrepancy, used to test the null hypothesis that the estimated variance-covariance matrix deviates from the sample. It is sample sensitive. The more the implied and sample moments differ, the bigger the chi-square statistic, and the stronger the evidence against the null hypothesis.	$p > 0.05$ (at α equals to 0.05 level)
Goodness-of-fit index (GFI)	Expresses the overall degree of fit by comparing the squared residuals from predictions with the actual data. Represents the comparison of the square residual for the degree of freedom, obtained through ML (maximum likelihood) and ULS (unweighted least squares)	Value >0.95 good fit; value 0.90- 0.95 adequate fit
Normed fit Chi-square CMIN/DF (χ^2 /df)	Minimum discrepancy divided by its degree of freedom. Value close to one indicate a good fit but less than one implies over fit	Close to 1 is good, but should not exceed to 3
Adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI)	An expansion of the GFI index Adjusted by the ratio of the df for the proposed model and the null model.	Value >0.95 good fit; value 0.90-0.95 adequate fit
Root means square error of approximation residual (RMSEA)	Population discrepancy function, which implies that how well the fitted model approximates per degree of freedom.	Value <0.05 good fit; value 0.08-0.05 adequate fit
Incremental fit measures		
Normed - fit index (NFI)	Compares the proposed model with the null model, without considering the degrees of freedom (not adjusted for df). The effect of sample size is strong	Value >0.95 good fit; Values above 0.08 and close 0.90 indicate acceptable fit
The normed comparative fit index (CFI)	A variation of the NFI, NNFI and identical to the relative non-centrality index (RNI). Represents the comparative index between proposed and baseline model adjusted for df . It is highly recommended index for fitness of model	Value >0.95 good fit; Values above 0.08 and close 0.90 indicate acceptable fit
Tucker-Lewis Index	Opposite of NFI and called non-NFI or	Value >0.95 good fit;

(TLI) or Non-normed fit index (NNFI)	NNFI. Represents the comparative index between proposed and baseline model adjusted for df	Values above 0.08 and close 0.90 indicate acceptable fit
Parsimonious fit measures		
Parsimony goodness-Fit index (PGFI)	Degree of freedom is used to adjust the GFI value using parsimony ratio.	Higher value compared to the other model is better
Parsimony normed fit index (PNFI)	Degree of freedom is used to adjust the NFI value based on parsimony ratio	Higher value compared to the other model is better

Source: Adapted by Hair *et al.* (2006)

According to scholars (Miles and Shevlin, 2007; Kenny, 2015), incremental fit indices, also known as comparative or relative fit indices, are based on comparing the fit of the hypothetical model and the null model. The null model (null hypothesis) has all variables uncorrelated with each other (Hair et al., 2006; Kenny, 2015). Incremental fit indices are often used to evaluate the fit of a structural equation model with alternative models. The absolute fit indices evaluate the model's fit directly, regardless of the fit of the baseline and the null model like incremental fit indices. The criteria for incremental fit indices commonly used are normed fit index (NFI), normed comparative fit index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), or the non-normed fit index (NNFI).

Parsimony fit indices can be considered as relative fit indices, used to measure the overall fit of a model. These indicators are measured to address the overfitting of the model and to assess the adequacy of the model (Hair et al., 2006). There are two relevant indexes of parsimony, the Parsimony Goodness-of-Fit Index (PGFI) and the Parsimonious Normed Fit Index (PNFI).

CFA allows to calculate the reliability and validity of constructs in the measurement model (Hair et al., 1998, 2006) through the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) method, in which model parameter values are estimated from observed data. From the criteria of the measurement model, the analysis is carried out in turn as follows:

6.6.3.1.1. Measurement of the reliability (item level)

Following Hair et al. (2006) suggestion, the researcher conducted a measure of the reliability of the measurement model as a crucial initial step in order to evaluate the internal consistency of the observed variables and eliminate the formation of additional dimensions during factor analysis (Churchill, 1979). According to DeVellis (2016), DeVellis and Thorpe (2021), internal consistency reliability is understood as the homogeneity of indicators in a scale. To evaluate internal consistency reliability, instead of using the split-half method, Cronbach's alpha is considered a more popular and preferable choice because it can determine constructs from different items and yield reliable scores (DeVellis and Thorpe, 2021; Hair et al., 2014). Item-reliability partially reveals the contribution of items to the total variance. The results presented in data tables 6.14 to 6.25 clearly reveal that the correlation between constructs and measured items is greater than the criterion of 0.4. The factor loading, which varies from 0.703 (VAS2 <--- VAS) to 0.932 (ASD6 <--- ADS), complies with the reliability standards (Churchill, 1979).

6.6.3.1.2. Measurement of reliability (construct level)

According to Netemeyer et al. (2003), the construct reliability is also known as composite reliability, which is used to measure the internal consistency of indicators and assure a tighter association between items corresponding to the same constructs. Evaluating composite reliability as well as considering the significance of each load factor allows the researcher to determine the fit of the measurement model more accurately. Like Cronbach's Alpha, the closer the composite reliability value is to 1, the higher the reliability level. As Peterson and Kim (2013) stated, composite reliability is acceptable when the value is greater than 0.7. However, Hair et al. (2014) claimed that composite reliability with a value greater than 0.95 is considered problematic because of possible duplication of observed variables. Besides, it is lacking in internal consistency reliability and should be reconsidered when the value is less than 0.6.

Composite reliability is used in research to evaluate how well the construct is measured through the specified items (Fornell and Larcker, 1981), Cronbach's coefficient α measures the internal consistency coefficients of the multi-item scale (Cronbach, 1951). It can be seen that most of the Cronbach's α values in the tables from 6.13 to 6.24 are all higher than 0.7 (0.880 to 0.958), which meets the criteria for reliability test (Hair et al., 2014; Nunally and Bernstein, 1994). Composite reliability (construct reliability) is measured through the squared multiple correlations (SMC) also known as the item reliability coefficient to explain the influence in the relationship between an observed variable on its construct. The SMC between some structural variables and observed variables (factor loading) in this study ranged from 0.5 or more, implying that there are significant and high multiple correlations between construct and their variables. The squared multiple correlation (SMC) of a manifest item reflects the square of the standardised loading of the indicator. An SMC of 0.5 seems to be about comparable to a standardised load of 0.7.

Table 6. 13: The salesperson performance construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .941			Composite reliability = 0.941				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted	
Salesperson Performance (SPP)			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.696	
Standard factor loading									
SPP6	<---	SPP	.835	1.000			.697		
SPP5	<---	SPP	.851	1.065	.051	20.865	***		.724
SPP7	<---	SPP	.871	1.092	.050	21.700	***		.759
SPP4	<---	SPP	.879	1.105	.050	22.036	***		.773
SPP2	<---	SPP	.848	1.030	.050	20.741	***		.718
SPP1	<---	SPP	.770	.908	.051	17.863	***		.593
SPP3	<---	SPP	.781	.965	.053	18.257	***	.610	

Table 6. 14: The sales strategy construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .952			Composite reliability = 0.953				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Sales strategy (SAST) includes			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.770

Sales model (SAM), Customer prioritisation (CUP), Segmentation (SEG)									
Standard factor loading									
SEG2	<---	SAST	.871	1.000					.758
SEG3	<---	SAST	.922	1.087	.040	26.885	***		.851
CUP3	<---	SAST	.899	1.066	.042	25.434	***		.809
CUP1	<---	SAST	.849	.947	.042	22.650	***		.721
SAM3	<---	SAST	.871	.981	.041	23.776	***		.758
SAM2	<---	SAST	.851	.971	.043	22.723	***		.724

Table 6. 15: The sales skill construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .958				Composite reliability = 0.959				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Sales skill (SASK) includes Interpersonal skill (IPS), Technical skill (TES), Salesmanship skill (SAS), Marketing skill (MAS)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.744
Standard factor loading									
MAS2	<---	SASK	.876	1.000				.768	
MAS3	<---	SASK	.879	.985	.040	24.641	***	.772	
TES3	<---	SASK	.876	.958	.039	24.464	***	.767	
IPS3	<---	SASK	.859	.893	.038	23.510	***	.738	
TES2	<---	SASK	.870	.974	.040	24.127	***	.757	
SAS3	<---	SASK	.863	.930	.039	23.721	***	.744	
SAS1	<---	SASK	.849	.959	.042	22.947	***	.720	
IPS1	<---	SASK	.826	.994	.046	21.786	***	.682	

Table 6. 16: The salesperson characteristic construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .955				Composite reliability = 0.956				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Salesperson characteristic (SACH) includes Empathetic ability (EMA), Cue				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.755
Standard factor loading									

perception ability (CUA), Ability to modify self-presentation (AMS)								
Standard factor loading								
AMS2	<---	SACH	.873	1.000				.763
AMS3	<---	SACH	.914	1.063	.040	26.653	***	.836
AMS1	<---	SACH	.865	1.033	.044	23.691	***	.749
CUA3	<---	SACH	.889	1.020	.041	25.058	***	.790
EMA2	<---	SACH	.826	.949	.044	21.671	***	.683
EMA3	<---	SACH	.876	.994	.041	24.299	***	.767
CUA1	<---	SACH	.836	.946	.043	22.158	***	.699

Table 6. 17: The experience construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .879			Composite reliability = 0.880				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted	
Experience (EXP)			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.596	
Standard factor loading									
EXP5	<---	EXP	.828	1.000			.685		
EXP4	<---	EXP	.813	.991	.056	17.660	***		.661
EXP3	<---	EXP	.769	.991	.060	16.460	***		.591
EXP2	<---	EXP	.730	.833	.054	15.406	***		.533
EXP1	<---	EXP	.713	.896	.060	14.956	***		.509

Table 6. 18: The customer orientation construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .885			Composite reliability = 0.888				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted	
Customer orientation (CUO)			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.665	
Standard factor loading									
CUO4	<---	CUO	.829	1.000			.686		
CUO6	<---	CUO	.849	.908	.047	19.176	***		.721
CUO5	<---	CUO	.852	.968	.050	19.248	***		.725
CUO1	<---	CUO	.725	.871	.056	15.535	***		.526

Table 6. 19: The value-based selling construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .869				Composite reliability = 0.870				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Value-based selling (VAS)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.573
Standard factor loading									
VAS5	<---	VAS	.723	1.000				.523	
VAS4	<---	VAS	.794	1.129	.079	14.275	***	.631	
VAS3	<---	VAS	.721	1.000	.076	13.070	***	.521	
VAS2	<---	VAS	.761	1.077	.078	13.734	***	.579	
VAS1	<---	VAS	.721	.971	.074	13.070	***	.521	

Table 6. 20: The adaptive selling behaviour construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .921				Composite reliability = 0.924				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Adaptive selling behaviour (ADS)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.710
Standard factor loading									
ADS6	<---	ADS	.932	1.000				.869	
ADS5	<---	ADS	.879	.907	.033	27.280	***	.773	
ADS4	<---	ADS	.782	.794	.038	21.013	***	.612	
ADS2	<---	ADS	.834	.909	.038	24.042	***	.695	
ADS1	<---	ADS	.775	.821	.040	20.644	***	.601	

Table 6. 21: The satisfaction with salesperson construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .910				Composite reliability = 0.912				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Satisfaction with salesperson (SWS)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.675
Standard factor loading									
SWS4	<---	SWS	.876	1.000				.767	
SWS5	<---	SWS	.876	.983	.043	22.934	***	.767	
SWS2	<---	SWS	.824	.912	.044	20.649	***	.679	
SWS3	<---	SWS	.776	.898	.048	18.695	***	.603	

SWS1	<---	SWS	.748	.825	.047	17.634	***	.560	
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Table 6. 22: The trust in salesperson construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .880			Composite reliability = 0.883					Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Trust in salesperson (TRS)			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.654	
Standard factor loading									
TRS4	<---	TRS	.903	1.000			.815		
TRS2	<---	TRS	.806	.875	.045	19.349	***		.650
TRS3	<---	TRS	.777	.867	.047	18.312	***		.604
TRS1	<---	TRS	.740	.778	.046	17.040	***	.548	

Table 6. 23: The anticipation of future interaction construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .885			Composite reliability = 0.888					Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Anticipation of future interaction			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.665	
Standard factor loading									
AFI4	<---	AFI	.910	1.000			.827		
AFI2	<---	AFI	.817	.915	.045	20.206	***		.667
AFI3	<---	AFI	.780	.848	.045	18.811	***		.609
AFI1	<---	AFI	.746	.781	.045	17.558	***	.557	

Table 6. 24: The repurchase interaction construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .881			Composite reliability = 0.884					Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Anticipation of future interaction			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.657	
Standard factor loading									
REI5	<---	REI	.914	1.000			.835		
REI2	<---	REI	.816	.902	.045	20.096	***		.666
REI1	<---	REI	.760	.817	.045	18.022	***		.577
REI4	<---	REI	.741	.831	.048	17.334	***	.549	

6.6.3.1.3. Measurement of validity (convergent validity)

Convergent validity reflects construct's homogeneity, which implies that constructs and related indicators are correlated or have a significant amount of variance in common. Convergent validity is an important type of value in evaluating the internal consistent validity by evaluating the factor loading of items with the corresponding construct. Convergent validity is guaranteed when the factor loading is greater than 0.5 (Hair et al., 2014). In addition, the results from Table 6.25 show that the average variance extracted (AVE) of constructs is above 0.5 (from 0.554 to 0.770), fully satisfying the conditions of convergent validity.

6.6.3.1.4. Measurement of validity (discriminant validity)

Along with convergent validity, discriminant validity is also an important aspect of construct validity, reflecting the extent to which constructs are distinct from each other and uncorrelated (Hair et al., 2006, 2014; Steenkamp and Van Trijp, 1991). The principle is that variables should have more to do with their construct than other constructs. According to Hair et al. (2014), Fornell and Larcker (1981), discriminant validity was evaluated in this study by examining and comparing the results obtained between the average variance extracted (AVE) of each construct and their respective square correlation. According to Table 6.25's findings, the average variance extracted (AVE) is noticeably higher than the squared correlation estimates. Discriminant validity is ensured when the average variance extracted (AVE) of each latent variable is higher than all the squared correlations between the latent variables (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Besides, following Kline's (2005) suggestion, the discriminant validity is acceptable when the estimated correlation between the factors is less than 0.92. From the above discussion, discriminant validity exists in the study's measurement model. There is also no occurrence of cross-loading between examined variables. In addition, the estimated correlation value was also considered significant with $p < 0.05$ (Hair et al., 2014).

Table 6. 25: Model validity measure

Construct	CR	AVE	MSV	ASV	CUO	SASK	SACH	SPP	SAST	ADS	SWS	EXP	VAS	TRS	REI	AFI
CUO	0.888	0.664	0.197	0.074	0.815											
SASK	0.959	0.744	0.125	0.041	0.216	0.862										
SACH	0.956	0.755	0.339	0.098	0.381	0.281	0.869									
SPP	0.941	0.696	0.197	0.079	0.444	0.334	0.408	0.834								
SAST	0.952	0.770	0.339	0.100	0.359	0.235	0.582	0.361	0.877							
ADS	0.924	0.710	0.292	0.085	0.431	0.148	0.451	0.325	0.540	0.842						
SWS	0.912	0.675	0.019	0.005	0.024	-0.004	0.017	0.122	-0.004	-0.029	0.822					
EXP	0.880	0.596	0.091	0.024	0.160	0.060	0.219	0.083	0.301	0.276	-0.053	0.772				
VAS	0.861	0.554	0.125	0.047	0.284	0.353	0.278	0.338	0.212	0.228	0.004	0.102	0.745			
TRS	0.883	0.654	0.019	0.004	-0.052	0.038	0.005	0.049	-0.093	-0.025	0.138	-0.002	0.025	0.809		
REI	0.884	0.657	0.016	0.005	0.004	-0.011	0.126	-0.004	0.092	-0.004	0.004	0.001	0.101	-0.071	0.810	
AFI	0.888	0.665	0.017	0.005	0.049	0.043	0.066	0.129	-0.013	-0.024	0.123	0.040	-0.005	-0.006	0.122	0.816

6.6.3.1.5. Measurement of validity (nomological validity)

Nomological validity is formed on the basis of the correlation matrix elements which are supposed to be associated to one another. According to scholars (Chau, 1997; Eriksson and Sharma, 1998; Hair et al., 2006), nomological validity is the degree to which the scale makes accurate predictions about interested constructs in a theory-based model the validity of the model as a whole. It can also be briefly stated as the overall fit of the model. Therefore, in order to verify the nomological validity, it is important in the CFA implementation process to evaluate the overall fit of the model through a measure of goodness-of-fit was found by Steenkamp and Van Trijp (1991).

Maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) is a popular method used in CFA measurement models to estimate the parameter (factor loading) of the statistical model and maximise the likelihood that the model with those parameters produces the data that were actually observed. It is also useful in cases where the sample size criteria were not adopted (with at least five observations for each variable) (Bentler and Chou, 1987; Hair et al., 1998). However, using the MLE method often comes with two potential problems are standard error and unreliable χ^2 (Chi-square) test, which needs to be handled by applying the model fit indicators in the process of validating the model intended use (Bentler and Chou, 1987) (see

Table 6.26). In this study, absolute fit indices such as GFI, AGFI, and RMSEA and incremental fit indices such as NFI, NNFI, and CFI were used to evaluate both structural and measurement models, predict the correlation matrix, measure the specificity of the model and compare the fit with the proposed model (Hair et al, 2006).

Table 6. 26: Goodness-of-fit indices of model modification

Model fit indicators								
Chi-square/ X^2	Df	RMSEA	GFI	NFI	CFI	AGFI	IFI	TLI
2673.695	1886	.033	.831	.873	.959	.814	.959	.956
X^2 – Chi-square; Df – degree of freedom; RMSEA – Root mean square error of approximation; GFI – Goodness-of-fit index; NFI – Normated fit index; CFI – Comparative fit index; AGFI – Adjusted goodness-of-fit index; and TLI – Tucker-Lewis Index								

The normed fit index (NFI) is one of the first fit indexes in SEM proposed by Bentler and Bonett (1980). It calculates the χ^2 value of the proposed model and compares the fit with the significant baseline model (Hair et al., 2006). However, because the χ^2 value of the proposed model does not provide enough information to evaluate the model's fit, the χ^2 value of the empty model is used as a measure for NFI. The NFI index is less commonly used because it does not control degrees of freedom and tends to increase the fit for complex models (Byrne, 2001). The value of NFI ranges from 0 to 1, and the closer to 1, the better the fit. In this study, an NFI value of $0.873 > 0.08$ represents an acceptable fit (Hair et al., 2006). The comparative fit index (CFI) and the root mean squared approximation of error (RMSEA) are the next two recommended fit indexes in SEM, providing sufficient information to evaluate the fit of the model (Garver and Mentzer, 1999; Hair et al., 2010). The CFI is a modified version of the NFI with a value of 0 to 1, measures the fit of a model to an empty model so that can avoid underestimating the fit in the case of small sample sizes like using NFI (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2006; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). Therefore, it is less affected by sample size than NFI. $CFI > 0.9$ is good, $CFI > 0.95$ is very good, $CFI > 0.8$ is acceptable. In this study, the CFI value of $0.959 > 0.9$ reflects a good fit (Hair et al., 2010). RMSEA yields a lower value for a better fit, where its value < 0.08 is good, and < 0.03 is very good. In this study, an RMSEA of $0.33 < 0.08$ represents an acceptable fit (Hair et al., 2010; Jöreskog and Sörbom, 1993; Kline 2005; Steiger, 1990). According to Hair et al. (2010), the goodness-of-

fit index (GFI) evaluates how well one model fits when compared to another (null model). Adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI) is used to adjust degrees of freedom df by the number of observed variables and adjust the results of a complex model. The values of GFI and AGFI both range from 0 to 1, > 0.9 is good. There seems to be no absolute acceptance threshold of the GFI, the greater the value, the better the fit (Hair et al., 2010). However, it is necessary to be greater than 0.7 for complex models (Judge and Hulin, 1993). GFI and AFGI values of 0.831 and 0.814, respectively, are all within an acceptable range (Hair et al., 2010).

Hair et al. (2010, 2016) asserted that there is no specific value of the above indicators that can distinguish whether the model fit is acceptable or not; therefore, it is reasonable to contain at least one incremental index and one absolute index along with the values and relevant degrees of freedom in the study. The model specification as well as the selection of variables that can be included in the model are important and have the potential to affect the model fit. For that reason, marketing scholars argue that it is essential to ensure the model specifications are implemented as closely as possible to the theory being tested instead of focusing solely on promoting the fit of the model (Hair et al., 2016). These measurement results can only serve as additional information for the study because it is challenging to evaluate how well the model fits only on the basis of this information.

Another commonly used fit index in studies is the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), known as the non-normed fit index (NNFI). The features of TLI are appropriate under the influence of complex models. Scholars (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2010) suggest that it is possible to calculate degrees of freedom df , comparing the χ^2 value of the model with the independent model. Thus, as stated by Steenkamp and Trijp (1991), the nomological validity can be assigned to the measurement model with these 3 factors. The TLI value is unrestricted, possibly outside the range 0 to 1. However, it can be similarly interpreted with CFI as values closer to 1, namely > 0.9 , the better the fit to the model (Bentler and Bonett, 1980; Byrne, 1994; Hair et al., 2010). In this study, the incremental fit index (IFI) is 0.959, and the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) is 0.956 are both greater than 0.9 reflecting acceptable fit.

Briefly, the re-specifications were performed for theoretical validation including the salesperson performance (SPP), sales strategy (SAST), customer orientation (CUO), value based-selling (VAS), sales skill (SASK), salesperson characteristic (SACH), experience (EXP), adaptive selling behaviour (ADS), anticipation of future interaction (AFI), repurchase intention (REI), satisfaction with salesperson (SWS), trust in salesperson (TRS). All items are retained in the model following assessment of the measurement model's nomological, convergent, and discriminant validity. This evaluation allows the study to verify that constructs are both statistically and theoretically significant. In addition, underlying latent variables have also been constructed to support model testing in the following stage.

6.6.3.2. Step two: structural model evaluation – hypothesis testing

The second part of testing a model is the structural model for theory development in exploratory research (Hair et al., 2017). The structural model measures the inner model, focuses on significance and the degree of correlation between the exogenous (independent) and the endogenous (dependent) latent variables which are calculated through the path coefficients (Kline, 2010). The proposed structural model of salesperson performance is shown in Figure 6.6. The structural model is known as analysis of covariance structures or casual modelling because it demonstrates the proposed casual relationships (Anderson and Gerbing, 1982; Chau, 1997). Structural modelling allows to test hypothetical structures with the standardised estimate and t-value (critical ratio). The structural equation modelling (SEM) in this study was implemented through analysis of moment structure (AMOS) 24.0 to analyse the hypothesis and evaluate the model's fit. The chi-square (χ^2) test is the only statistically significant measure of fit that can be included in the SEM. According to Hair et al. (1998), it allows to measure the original fit index for structural models because it is directly inferred from the fit function and is the basis of most other relevant indicators. Table 6.27 below shows the results of the predicted model's fit indices with the data collected in the study. It can be seen that the chi-square value (χ^2) from the proposed model is 2861.574 (degrees of freedom, $df = 1930$; $p < .001$), the comparative fit index (CFI) aims to measure the fit of the model to the baseline model (Hair et al., 2010) with a value of 0.952. In addition, the incremental fit index (IFI) is $0.952 > 0.9$ (Bentler and Bonett, 1980), and the

normed fit index (NFI) is 0.865. These indices are all larger than the corresponding general acceptance level, indicating that there is a good fit of the model to the observed data (Byrne, 2001; and Hair et al., 2006).

Table 6. 27: Goodness-of-fit indices of model modification

Model fit indicators								
Chi-square/ X^2	Df	RMSEA	GFI	NFI	CFI	AGFI	IFI	TLI
2841.029	1930	.035	.823	.866	.952	.809	.953	.950
X^2 – Chi-square; Df – degree of freedom; RMSEA – Root mean square error of approximation; GFI – Goodness-of-fit index; NFI – Normated fit index; CFI – Comparative fit index; AGFI – Adjusted goodness-of-fit index; and TLI – Tucker-Lewis Index								

Other absolute fit indexes such as the goodness-of-fit index (GFI) have a value of 0.823, the adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI) is 0.809 representing an acceptable fit. In addition, as a modified index of NFI, Parsimony Normed Fit Index (PNFI) was found with a value of 0.829. The higher the PNFI value, the better the model fit (Hair et al., 2006). The root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) yields a lower value for a better fit, which is $0.035 < 0.08$ represents a reasonable fit (Hair et al., 2010; Kline 2005). Because there is no specific study that shows which model-fit index is the best, and since some of them are likely to be affected by sample size, therefore, it is recommended that researchers use different fit indices for the measure of fitness (Gerbing and Anderson, 1993).

Figure 6. 5: Validated structural model

In summary, the above discussion and measurement results demonstrate that the predicted structural model meets the criteria of model fit. The indicators measuring the fit of the model are all at an acceptable level (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2010). The only significant controversial issue when applying CFA in research process is that there are no established standards for what makes a good fit (Tanaka, 1993). All evaluated hypotheses will be explained in more detail in Chapter VII.

The structure equation modelling tests assumptions about causality and linearity between latent variables with observed data based on validated measures. The path coefficients are standardised regression coefficients. Table 6.28 reveals the results obtained for casual relationship (standardised path coefficients (β), standard error, p-value, and hypotheses result), regression weights as well as the parameter estimate to its corresponding path. The path represents the relationship between the sales strategy (SAST) with the customer orientation (CUO) ($\gamma=0.434$, $t\text{-value}=6.859$), and the value-based selling (VAS) ($\gamma=0.162$, $t\text{-value}=2.302$) was found to be significant. This indicates that H1, H2 are fully supported. The path from customer orientation to value-based selling (H4) ($\gamma=0.238$, $t\text{-value}=3.758$), customer orientation to salesperson performance (H3) ($\gamma=0.309$, $t\text{-value}=5.742$) and value-based selling to salesperson performance (H5) ($\gamma=0.154$, $t\text{-value}=2.939$) were supported. The hypothesised relationship between sales skills (SASK) and salesperson performance (H6) was statistically significant in the hypothesised direction ($\gamma=0.184$, $t\text{-value}=4.313$). In addition, the regression weight for salesperson characteristic (SACH) and experience (EXP) in predicting adaptive selling behaviour (ADS) were found to be significant ($\gamma=0.380$, $t\text{-value}=8.301$; $\gamma=0.225$, $t\text{-value}=3.743$ respectively). Therefore, Hypothesis H7, H8 were accepted. Similarly, hypotheses H9 was also supported because it demonstrated a statistically significant relationship between these two variables ($\gamma=0.188$, $t\text{-value}=3.031$).

The results obtained in Table 6.28 also showed that the hypothesis H10, H11, H12, H13, H16 were accepted ($\gamma=0.129$, $t\text{-value}=2.015$; $\gamma=0.122$, $t\text{-value}=2.170$; $\gamma=0.132$, $t\text{-value}=2.110$; $\gamma=0.115$, $t\text{-value}=2.006$; and $\gamma=0.136$, $t\text{-value}=2.381$). However, the path from salesperson performance (SPP) to trust in salesperson (TRS), and trust in salesperson (TRS) to

anticipation of future interaction (AFI) were not found to be significant ($\gamma=0.035$, t -value=0.547; $\gamma=-0.028$, t -value=-0.491), thence, they are not acceptable.

Table 6. 28: Results of hypothesis testing

Standardised regression paths				Estimate	S.E	C.R	<i>p</i>	Hypothesis
H1	SAST	--->	CUO	.434	.063	6.859	***	Supported
H2	SAST	--->	VAS	.162	.070	2.302	.021	Supported
H3	CUO	--->	SPP	.309	.054	5.742	***	Supported
H4	CUO	--->	VAS	.238	.063	3.758	***	Supported
H5	VAS	--->	SPP	.154	.052	2.939	.003	Supported
H6	SASK	--->	SPP	.184	.043	4.313	***	Supported
H7	SACH	--->	ADS	.380	.046	8.301	***	Supported
H8	EXP	--->	ADS	.225	.060	3.743	***	Supported
H9	ADS	--->	SPP	.188	.062	3.031	.002	Supported
H10	SPP	--->	AFI	.129	.064	2.015	.044	Supported
H11	AFI	--->	REI	.122	.056	2.170	.030	Supported
H12	SPP	--->	SWS	.132	.062	2.110	.035	Supported
H13	SWS	--->	AFI	.115	.057	2.006	.045	Supported
H14	SPP	--->	TRS	.035	.064	.547	.585	Not Supported
H15	TRS	--->	AFI	-.028	.057	-.491	.624	Not Supported
H16	SWS	--->	TRS	.136	.057	2.381	.017	Supported

*** $p < 0.001$

Notes: Path = Relationship between independent variable on dependent variable; β = Standardised regression coefficient; S.E. = Standard error; p = Level of significance.

6.7. SUMMARY

The analysis conducted in this chapter aims to address the main research question and quantitatively test the hypotheses proposed at the beginning of the study. To be able to accomplish the above objectives, the data was included in the analysis based on two main phases, which include a number of sub-stages. Phase one entails data exploration and descriptive analyses of the demographic traits of the research sample. The data were first checked for missing data, which indicated that no missing data in the replies, however, there was some skewness and kurtosis. Evaluations of normality, linearity, homoscedasticity, and

non-response bias were performed in turn to check the accuracy of the collected data. Although some skewness and kurtosis were found during the examination, it was not unusual at a univariate level. There are also only 12 cases of multivariate outliers found through the Mahalanobis D2 value. Most of the variances of the examined data are different and statistically significant through the homogeneity of Leneve's test, except for $AMS < 0.05$. Bivariate Pearson correlation was applied to test the multicollinearity of the variables, showing that the effect of high tolerance and multicollinearity is not a concern of the present study. Non-response bias was assessed through Mann-Whitney-U test, showing that there is a difference in SAM_mean, SEG_mean, TES_mean between male and female participants in the study.

Anderson and Gerbing's (1988) two-step approach were also applied in the analytical processes of this study, which included estimation of measurement models prior to the structural analysis. Initially, exploratory factor analysis method was performed to demonstrate the impact between the variables and the factors, eigenvalues and a scree plot was evaluated to determine the extracted factors. Factors were rotated through using Varimax of Orthogonal approach to show the maximum variance of factor loading. Based on reliability and EFA testing, a total of 5 items were removed from 4 constructs because of low reliability as follows: empathetic ability (EMA1), cue perception ability (CUA2), adaptive selling behaviour (ADS3), repurchase intention (REI3, REI6). Through EFA, a scree plot test is used to evaluate the extracted factors. The convergence and discriminant validity of the measurements scale was clearly revealed through the AVE of the examined variables > 0.5 . Nomological validity was also assessed through a correlation analysis for the relationships between the research variables, with the goal of investigating the potential for multicollinearity.

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted in phase two of this chapter for the purpose of a goodness-of-fit analysis of measurement models. This study applied the analysis of moment structures (AMOS 24) with 385 sample sizes to perform a confirmatory factor analysis of the measurement models and a structural model of the proposed salesperson performance model. All indicators showed sufficient loadings on both the overall goodness-

of-fit indices and their respective factors, implying that the model was acknowledged. The following variables were then tested for reliability and validity, Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability and average variance extracted, showing good results for the instrument. Each construct's convergent, discriminant, and nomological validity were also proven. Most notably, the CFA helped to prove the validity of the structure through providing experimental evaluation results of psychometric properties and measurement model fit for this study.

Implementing and assessing the structural equation model (SEM) was the following stage. SEM was determined through the overall fit model indices, and the path coefficient was assigned to the appropriate causal effects. The suggested model is carried out by the two-step approach of structural equation modelling (SEM). The measurement model is tested as part of the first step of the process in order to establish construct reliability, discriminant validity, and convergent validity. The analysis's findings suggested that the research constructs have a significant hypothetical association. A total of 14 hypotheses out of 16 were approved. The complete model is shown in Figure 6.6. The following chapter will contain discussions, conclusions, and significant contributions from the research.

Figure 6. 6: Final model

CHAPTER VII: DISCUSSION

7.1. INTRODUCTION

This study aims to understand the contribution of salesperson performance to customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. In this chapter, the researcher elaborates on the results obtained as well as solves the research objectives and questions raised in Chapter I and determines the relationships between constructs in the conceptual model. The application of a mixed method approach including qualitative research (in-depth interview) and quantitative research also facilitates the establishment of scales and hypothesis testing (Zinkhan and Hirschheim, 1992). Related theories have been included in chapter II. Along with that, 15 in-depth interviews with academics and marketing experts were also conducted to contribute to the research objective (Table 4.7). The process of selecting participants as well as the nature of the interviews was detailed in Chapter IV. In the previous chapter, the researcher presented how to develop and adjust the items of the scale as well as detect acceptable measurement properties. Then obviously, the reliability and validity of the constructs were also evaluated and confirmed, being $0.875 > 0.7$ which fits the criteria of minimum reliability. Accordingly, the proposed model seems to be adopted, with 14 out of 16 hypotheses being supported. For chapter VII, the layout will be structured as follows: Section 7.2 provides an overview of the study and discusses hypothesis testing results. Hypotheses H1 to H, which are the antecedents that affect salesperson performance, are mentioned first. Section 7.3 deals with hypotheses H through H, regarding the impact of salesperson performance from the customer's point of view (consequences of salesperson performance). Section 7.4 considers the results of hypothesis testing. Finally, a summary of this chapter is presented in Section 7.5.

7.2. OVERVIEW OF STUDY

There are many different theories and definitions of salesperson performance and its dimensions that are investigated in this study. The study also confirmed the precursors of

salesperson performance (sales strategy, sales skills, sales characteristics, experience, adaptive selling behaviour, value-based selling, and customer orientation as well as their strong impact on consequential factors such as anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention in customer perception. The contributions of this study are of paramount importance for salesperson performance acts as a lever for business growth, is an important signal of the company's quality and value to consumers (Hartline et al., 2003; Nunkoo et al., 2020). Research by Buciuniene and Skudiene (2015) also confirmed the significance of salesperson performance on sales volume, productivity, and customer loyalty. As a result, the importance of salesperson performance, its association with customer satisfaction, and their behavioural intentions is receiving increasing attention (Crosby et al., 1990; Hartline and Jones, 1996).

Various scholars have investigated the individual effects of the relationship between sales strategy (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020), sales skill (Basir et al, 2010), or sales characteristic (Echchakoui, 2017) and sales performance on consumer perception. However, there is still no extensive investigation into the complex effects of salesperson performance on consumer perception (Gomez et al., 2004; Jha et al., 2017; Sullivan et al., 2012; Van Dolen et al., 2002). This study strives to address the controversial issue of previous studies by Verbeke et al. (2011) and Churchill Jr (1985): What are the major antecedents of salesperson performance that influence customer's future interaction and repurchase intention. This issue can be broken down into two main research questions as discussed in Chapter I: what factors can directly affect the salesperson's performance? and, what are the main effects of salesperson performance on the customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention? In order to facilitate the investigation and answer the research questions, a multi-method approach was applied in this study (Deshpande, 1983; Zinkhan and Hirschheim, 1992). The study began with a review of related concepts from previous studies.

Qualitative research, which is an important basis for quantitative research to investigate the significance of salesperson performance on customer perception formation was also conducted to develop additional measurement items for the research model. The qualitative

methods were carried out in this study with the participation of Vietnamese academics and experts in the field of marketing, analysing key content in interviews about their experiences in order to evaluate salesperson performance as well as its impact on future customer interaction and repurchase intentions. According to scholars Jaramillo and Mulki (2008), salespeople tend to put in more effort when they know they are dealing with difficult customers, so the diverse characteristics of salesperson performance are also not the same for each customer group. Therefore, to be able to fully meet the research objectives, the examples of items were also discussed with participants during the qualitative research. This approach is not only useful for the researcher to develop new related items but also helps to have a more comprehensive grasp of the research topic.

The next phase of this study was conducted through quantitative methods. Important literature findings were utilised to create a proper theoretical model that demonstrates the relationship between salesperson performance, customer's anticipation of the future interaction, and repurchase intention. Along with that, the results of the in-depth interviews allow the formation of a questionnaire with high practical significance to quantify and support the initial phase of the research (Churchill, 1979). It is also important to conduct a qualitative assessment of the adaptability of the scales from prior studies to determine their usefulness in the current context of the study. In addition, the proposed theoretical model has also been taken into account at this stage. The measurement of research models, as suggested by Foroudi (2012), is to allocate numbers to objects with the aim of reflecting the amount of attributes. It is understood as an important process to discover measurable variables for hypothesis testing. It can be said that the process of measuring salesperson performance is closely related to the empirical context in which the research was conducted as well as to various important characteristics of salespeople that are determined by the company. One of the experts who participated in the interview also expressed his views on the performance of salespeople and confirmed his influence on salesperson performance management decisions. For example:

"Salespeople's performance shows their enthusiasm at work and reflects the company's concern for customers, so it can be an important highlight

to help customers remember the company for a long time. Increasing sales and establishing lasting relationships with customers is the responsibility of the salesperson, therefore, managers like me play an important role in cultivating sales skills for employees as well as developing the right customer-oriented strategies. I can also affirm that salesperson performance is highly constructive and especially important for the positive development of the company. To know the contribution as well as the selling skills of a salesperson, you need to look at the number of products sold per invoice and the average value that the invoice brings. It is as a factor reflects the efforts, consulting and persuasion ability of employees as well as the level of customer satisfaction with the company's service quality. This is what leaders strive to bring to the company and customers".

The above manager's statement clearly shows the responsibility and the importance of salesperson performance to be able to deliver a consistent impact on company growth and positive customer perception. Zallocco et al. (2009) also emphasised the significance of the company's management in measuring sales activities, ensuring favourable sales results, and meeting the company's strategy.

The measurement scales in this study, as described in Chapter IV, were formed through the extraction of items from prior studies' scales and also from the findings of qualitative research (in-depth interview). The face validity of the scale was also evaluated by experts and interviewees resulting in numerous items being excluded from the qualitative investigations. The measuring scales were then purified through a pilot study. The validity of the scales is critical to be ensured in the study, the researcher applied the data reduction technique (EFA) in this stage (pilot study) as well as in primary data analysis (EFA and CFA). The study also performed popular statistical tests such as nomological validity, convergent validity, etc. in order to ensure the reliability and validity of the scales both theoretically and practically so that they can be conveniently used in hypothesis testing.

The analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) statistical software was utilised to evaluate the obtained quantitative data. The findings indicate that the study's salesperson performance (focal construct) is unidimensional. The constructs' convergence, discriminant, and nominal validity tests likewise yielded high results, indicating theoretical and observational significance. Because none of the interviewees contested the importance of adjectives in the interview process, the proposed model can be stated to fully represent the interaction between constructs. Additionally, both the measurement and structural model receive high modification indices, which reflect the model's fit. Finally, a sample size of 385 was used to assess the overall structural model, and the interpretation of these results is discussed in more detail in the following section.

The two-step approach (measurement model and structural model assessment) is applied and detailed in the study, which is a very useful reference source for future research. The evaluation of the measurement model through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) revealed the overall fit of the model with the research data, with chi-square indexes (χ^2) = 2841.029, $p < .001$, CFI=0.952, TLI=0.950, GFI=0.823, RFI=0.860, IFI=.953, AGFI=0.809, NFI=0.866, and RMSEA=0.035 met the recommended criteria (Hair et al., 2006; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

The hypothesis testing finding demonstrate that most of the proposed relationships are supported, specifically: H1 (SAST --> CUO), H2 (SAST --> VAS), H3 (CUO --> SPP), H4 (CUO --> VAS), H5 (VAS --> SPP), H6 (SASK --> SPP), H7 (SACH --> ADS), H8 (EXP --> ADS), H9 (ADS --> SPP), H10 (SPP --> AFI), H11 (AFI--> REI), H12 (SPP --> SWS), H13 (SWS --> AFI), H14 (SPP -->TRS), with corresponding statistical significance ($\gamma=0.434$, $\gamma=0.162$, $\gamma=0.309$, $\gamma=0.238$, $\gamma=0.154$, $\gamma=0.184$, $\gamma=0.380$, $\gamma=0.225$, $\gamma=0.188$, $\gamma=0.129$, $\gamma=0.122$, $\gamma=0.132$, $\gamma=0.1154$, $\gamma=0.136$). However, two of the following tested hypotheses were rejected: salesperson performance (SPP) and trust in salesperson (TRS) (H14); trust in salesperson (TRS) and anticipation of future interaction (AFI) (H15) due to the fact that they were each not statistically different from 0 at the 0.001 significance level ($\gamma=.035$, -0.28 , respectively) (see Table 6.28). The next section briefly presents the

supporting evidence for the hypotheses and qualitative outcomes to provide a more complete explanation of the proposed conceptual model.

7.3. SALESPERSON PERFORMANCE CONSTRUCT (FOCAL CONSTRUCT)

The main driving force behind this research topic is the demand for more precision and detail in the evaluation and measurement of salesperson performance. Salesperson performance has critical implications for business growth but has not been adequately measured in literature studies (Hartline and Jones, 1996; Ingram et al., 2005; Jacobs and Washington, 2003; Zallocco et al., 2009). As a result, the researcher seeks to provide a more comprehensive assessment of salesperson performance and its impact on customers' anticipation of future interactions and repurchase intention. Initial definitions of salesperson performance were presented in the literature review along with its associated analyses in Chapter IV.

The qualitative investigation results (interview) play an important role in establishing a favourable scale for gauging salesperson performance. In addition, quantitative research is undertaken as a primary method to support the previous interview findings. The findings contributed greatly to the clear formation of the research concept and allowed to adjust the simplicity of the salesperson performance scale. Accordingly, the scale of salesperson performance along with related items was established and evaluated based on the practical context of Vincom retail. The experimentally tested scale produces results that favour salesperson performance as a measure of selling high-profit margin items (SPP5) (Evans et al., 2007; Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Singh et al., 2017). The salesperson identifies major accounts in the territory and sells to them (SPP4) (Evans et al., 2007; Singh et al., 2017), succeeds in creating sales revenues (SPP2) and succeeds in meeting the sales target (SPP1) (Evans et al., 2007; Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Kock, 2017; Piercy et al., 2001; Singh et al., 2017), succeeds in expanding the network of customers (SPP3) (Kock, 2017), makes effective presentations to customers (SPP6) (Piercy et al., 2001) and understands customer needs and work processes (SPP7) (Kock, 2017). The factor loading fulfilled the reliability

criteria and was between 0.770 (SPP1 <-- SPP) and 0.879 (SPP4 <-- SPP) (Churchill, 1979) (see Table 6.14 for the items and salesperson performance construct reliability). The findings reveal that the reliability Cronbach's alpha (α) is also greater than the acceptable level ($0.941 > 0.5$), suggesting that the psychometric reliability test criteria were fulfilled. This section demonstrates the implications of the link between salesperson performance components (verified by quantitative research) and salesperson performance construct based on qualitative research results. In particular, the findings from the quantitative research have also identified six key aspects of salesperson performance in relation to Vincom retail in Vietnam.

Further citations from qualitative study indicate that salesperson performance is one of the most critical measures of a salesperson's ability to 'sell high-profit margin product', which also corroborated the findings (SPP5 <-- SPP). For example:

"Sales performance reflects the ability and effort of sales professionals at each stage of the customer engagement process ... if you put in enough effort to show your sincerity and the value of the product that you and your company want to bring to customers, it will have a strong impact on their purchase, for example, Vincom Retail's profit still increases steadily, and even in the first quarter, it tripled from the previous quarter despite an increase in the number of Covid-19 cases."

Through the collected results, it can be said that salesperson performance as one of the important factors that reflects the functional quality of the company, is a bridge to help convey the outstanding values of the company to customers (Bimer, 1990; Bowen and Schneider, 1985; Zeithaml et al., 1985). It helps to define customer perception and contributes significantly to revenue, profitability as well as purchase intention of customers (Buciuniene and Skudiene, 2015; Rodriguez et al., 2012). Therefore, 'The salesperson sells high-profit margin products' (SPP5) is advocated as an item to measure the salesperson performance construct (SPP5 <--- SPP).

This study identifies another factor of salesperson performance as 'the salesperson to major accounts in the territory and sells them' (SPP4). Customers generate opinions on a company's salesperson performance based on its customer-oriented strategy. Interviewees claimed that:

"Every success requires a clear direction... customer orientation, with the backing of management, is the driving force behind salespeople to execute their responsibilities more efficiently, allowing them to achieve a greater level of performance."

"My firm is one of the pioneers in transforming the Vietnamese retail sector. We take pride in what we offer as well as our strong relationship with our customers... enhancing the customer experience through service or product quality improvement, positive interaction of sales staff, all of which reflect the investment in our operating strategy and yields a certain love of our brand to the customers."

The aforementioned statement demonstrates how salesperson performance may be used to analyse the impact of a purchase, capture the prospect's demands, and seamlessly incorporate it into the customer's purchasing process (Buciuniene et al. and Skudiene, 2015; Rodriguez et al., 2012), all of which have a direct influence on sales and give the firm a significant competitive advantage (Dey et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2016; Nunkoo et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the interviews revealed another significant aspect of salesperson performance and also proven by quantitative research. Salesperson performance is not only a reflection of a salesperson's ability but also a proxy for the company's prosperity (Obiageli et al., 2015).

"Their work performance is always recognised even if it is for the simplest actions, as long as they put in their best efforts and have a good oriented

mindset at work. ... It resembles a salesperson's face ... giving customers trust and satisfaction and creating a certain distance from the company's competitors."

The remarks of the participants demonstrated the significance of the concept of salesperson performance, and the item 'the salesperson identifies major accounts in the territory and sells to them' was developed in qualitative interviews and is supported by quantitative research as a gauge of salesperson performance.

Scholars have emphasised how salespeople's ability to understand customers and work processes impact customer perceptions (Limbu et al., 2016; Simintiras et al., 2013; Verbeke et al., 2011). The findings indicate that adaptive behaviour positively contributes to direct interactions that are likely to influence salesperson performance (Echchakoui, 2013; Sujana et al., 1994). As quoted from the interviews:

"Customers are always at the forefront of all operating considerations at Parkson. We focus on a consultative approach, particularly in a global economy filled with uncertainty, anxiety, and complexity."

"It allows to nurture and convert potential customers effectively, especially for high-end mall systems with complex and expensive products like ours. The adaptive selling approach can change your game... You can sell products to anyone who needs them, but they won't come back if you don't care about them. It is important that you reward customers, collect feedback, and offer VIP levels. Customers will have no choice in this case, they will definitely come back because you appreciate them."

This result is supported by the research (Chen and Jaramillo, 2014; Rakesh et al., 2017; Sergio and Pedro, 2014) mentioning that adaptive selling is a feature that has a massive effect on the customer's thoughts and feelings in order to create a good purchasing

response. As a result, 'the salesperson understands customer needs and work processes' is an indispensable element for evaluating the salesperson performance construct (SPP7 <--- SPP).

Some other aspects of salesperson performance in the current study are 'the salesperson succeeds in creating sales revenues' (SPP2 <--- SPP), 'the salesperson succeeds in meeting the sales target' (SPP1 <--- SPP), which was developed from qualitative research and is supported by quantitative research. Moreover, the item 'the salesperson makes effective presentations to customers' which is referenced by research (Piercy et al., 2001), and acknowledged by quantitative research (SPP6 <--- SPP). As expressed by survey participants at Vincom shopping centre:

"Generally, they have a high sense of responsibility and dedication. They are friendly and persistent in the process of approaching and introducing sales... I often shop at Vincom because of their prestige, reputation, and large scale. Vincom has never disappointed me in both product and service quality. I feel comfortable every time I shop and always have good experiences thanks to the service of skilled sales staff. They are not lazy, they do not just like standing around the checkout counter or chatting with colleagues, the salespeople I have dealt with, especially in recent months, they really know how to observe and approach at the right time to help me answer questions about the product and buy the right ones."

"Enthusiastic, polite and friendly. I felt welcomed throughout the shopping process. The staff's enthusiasm is extremely genuine, from the cheerful greeting when I first entered the store to the thank you when I left. I have enjoyed shopping at Vincom because of their respect for customers."

Overall, the research model's modified scale illustrates that the conjunction of items from the factors of salesperson performance is associated with the pertinent group of study objects. The findings from testing the hypothesis are explained in the sections that follow.

7.5. DISCUSSION OF THE HYPOTHESES TESTS

The detailed explanation of the hypothesis test results in this section will be carried out in order to meet the 4 goals: 1) dive into the concept of salesperson performance and its various components, 2) determine the essential factors that most affect performance (antecedents of the salesperson performance), 3) design and conduct empirical testing a conceptual framework for the linkages between salesperson performance, its antecedents and consequences, and 4) explore the effect of a salesperson's performance on a customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention (consequences of the salesperson performance). From the study's stated objectives, researcher seeks to address two major questions a raised in the context of the Vietnamese retail market: Q1) what factors have an impact on salesperson performance? and Q2) what factors primarily affect a salesperson's performance on a customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention.

After discussions on salesperson performance, which serves as the study's main focal point, follow-up examinations and discussions with its antecedents and consequences will be undertaken in turn. The intention of splitting hypotheses into multiple associations is to investigate the relationship-intensive effect of each construct as the salesperson performance on the anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. Table 6.28 briefly describes all the paths in the initial conceptual model that indicate the relationship of the constructs. The findings concerning the antecedents and consequences of salesperson performance are addressed in the next section.

In short, based on the findings of the previous scale purification, the salesperson performance construct was allocated to the model that was used to assess the cause-and-effect link between the sub-dimensions of salesperson performance and others. The hypothesis testing outcomes are discussed, with references to previous studies. Furthermore, in order to acquire a better knowledge of the study phenomenon, results derived from interviews will be utilised to shed light on the aspect of interest.

Briefly about the results that the majority of the study model's hypotheses were authorised (H1, H2, H3, H4, H5, H6, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, and H16), however, 2 out of 16 hypotheses were rejected (H14, H15). The findings indicated that all the predicted antecedent elements have an effect on salesperson performance; nevertheless, it is surprising that customer trust in salesperson is not a mediator between salesperson performance and the anticipation of future interaction. However, all the results explored are consequences of salesperson performance, and all the details of the hypothesis testing outcomes are detailed further in this section.

7.5.1. Antecedents of salesperson performance

The crucial antecedent factors of salesperson performance identified through qualitative study findings include sales strategy (sales model, segmentation, customer prioritisation), sales skill (interpersonal skill, salesmanship skill, technical skill, marketing skill), sales characteristic (empathetic ability, cue perception ability, ability to modify self-presentation, experience), customer orientation, value-based selling, and adaptive selling behaviour.

From the value propositions in marketing materials, salesperson performance is a signal of the quality of the company's functions that enable the transmission of the company's quality and values to customer (Bitner, 1990; Bowen and Schneider, 1985; Gronroos, 1983; Zeithaml et al., 1985), creating a sustainable competitive advantage (Dey et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2016). To address the first problem existing in the study (Q1: what factors have an impact on salesperson performance?), the proposed key antecedents of salesperson performance are discussed in turn in the literature section (chapter II) and qualitative research (chapter V). The obtained interview results showed that participants agreed with the salesperson performance scale, and they also stated that it measures key factors of salesperson performance, resulting in the scale's external validity. The test results indicate that sales skill (H6) is a factor that has a direct impact on salesperson performance. Additionally, customer orientation (H3), value-based selling (H5), and adaptive selling behaviour (H9) were also found to be directly related to salesperson performance and are important mediators of sales. The relationship between sales strategy (H1, H2), sales

characteristics (H7), experience (H8) and salesperson performance are fully supported in the context of the present study. These factors, known as the exogenous latent variable or the independent variable, account for the structure of the salesperson's performance in the model. Test results have shown a significant impact of these factors on salesperson performance as well as improving customer evaluation. The good fit of the research model expressed through the indicators is also confirmed.

This study supports model validity by highlighting the important factors that have a major determinant of salesperson performance such as customer orientation, value-based selling, sales skill, and adaptive selling behaviour.

The first factor identified in the literature relates to the implementation of customer orientation. The findings provide support for the hypothesised antecedent effect of customer orientation on the salesperson performance (see Chapter VI). As a matter of fact, it has been argued that salesperson performance should highlight the significance of customer orientation to lead to long-term success and growth of the organisation (Tseng and Su, 2013). Customer orientation is important and has profound implications for the effective establishment of customer relationships (Athanasopoulos, 2000), and the strong survival of a company (ELSamen and Akroush, 2018; Pekovic and Rolland, 2016; Tseng and Su, 2013). Salespeople with high customer orientation skills are more efficient in achieving their goals, creating value, and maintaining long-term customer relationships (Singh and Das, 2013; Wachner et al., 2009).

This dimension offers perceptions of a salesperson's capacity to execute sales strategies, capture customer needs, and convey company values. Items such as CUO1 'The salesperson tries to give customers an accurate expectation of what the product/service will do' (Periatt et al., 2004; Jha et al., 2017; Terho et al., 2015), CUO4 'The salesperson tries to achieve their goals by satisfying customers' (Periatt et al., 2004) and CUO5 'The salesperson tries to capture and update customer trends' shown a consistently associated with firm's customer.

This association results in the continual growth of the salesperson's abilities and personality traits, while the customer orientation also effectively conveys and deepens the customer's understanding of the firm. Along with the statistical analysis results, the interviews that were done as part of the qualitative research also produced unambiguous comments regarding the link between sales strategy and customer orientation, as well as the relationship between customer orientation and salesperson performance. In other words, the research results have proven the mediating role of customer orientation in the relationship between sales strategy and salesperson performance.

Several items of the sales strategy are examined, including SAM2: 'The salesperson considers the costs and value associated with the customer when setting relationship objectives and develop selling models for the customer' (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Terho et al., 2015), SAM3: 'The salesperson has adapted the selling process to meet the customers' different goals' (Terho et al., 2015) espouses the idea of a sales strategy that communicates a company's outstanding value to customers. The modification of sales models allows employees to transform sales orientations into specific behaviours that satisfy different customer needs (Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010), which promotes performance and long-term positive relationship in the future (Terho et al., 2015). Consequently, sales strategy has the potential to have a positive impact on customer orientation and lead to enhanced salesperson performance. The respondents reported that:

"We aim to make a difference and create pleasant customer experiences, so a flexible sales model can adapt effectively to the rapidly evolving market. Adjustments in the sales model also create a more dynamic and productive working environment. The top sales employees of the organisation may then take advantage of the required resources to identify the appropriate target market and draw in clients."

The aforementioned discussion demonstrates the significance of sales strategy as a factor that influences orientation. The sales strategy H1 test that has a positive impact on the

customer's orientation is adopted. A statistically significant regression path exists between customer orientation (CUO) and sales strategy (SAST) ($\gamma=0.434$, $t\text{-value}=6.859$).

Moreover, a mall manager regarded the significance of sales strategy and customer orientation as a significant management assignment. Customer orientation is emphasised in its sales strategy to highlight the distinct values that the company wants to convey to customers in comparison to its rivals in the same sector. An effective customer orientation creates a positive customer attitude towards employee performance and company operations (Cross et al., 2007; Singh and Venugopal, 2015; Terho et al. 2015; Wang and Miao, 2015). Adapted from a sales executive's statement:

"Customer orientation is a business strategy with sales activities and processes developed by managers to build trust and attract customers. It focuses on the most crucial factor, the customer, in order to research their demands. Customers today are highly proactive, and they will not follow you as easily as they used to. They only buy when they have all the knowledge they need. Therefore, the ingenuity of the salesperson to be able to engage and convince the customer to buy is important. Normally, a salesperson with a good customer orientation will easily gain customer trust, and close sales quickly, they are also more convenient in controlling and improving their own performance."

The explanations provide evidence of how significantly customer orientation affects salesperson performance. The H3 test (customer orientation has positive impact on salesperson performance) therefore, is advocated. Customer orientation (CUO) and salesperson performance (SPP) had a statistically significant relationship ($\gamma=.309$, $t\text{-value}=5.742$)

Besides, the findings also revealed that customer orientation has a considerable influence on value-based selling. Customer orientation is a crucial part of service quality and is used as the main premise to form value-based sales behaviours of salespeople. A salesperson's

customer orientation is created prior to customer interaction as recommendations for reacting to and dealing with various customer demands (Dweck and Legget 1988; Terho et al., 2017). The more customer orientation of the salesperson, the greater the tendency to operate to facilitate the customer, which is the best factor for eliciting value-based selling behaviour (Terho et al., 2012; Zablah et al., 2012). For example, CUO1 'The salesperson tries to give customers an accurate expectation of what the product/service will do' (Periatt et al., 2004; Jha et al., 2017; Terho et al., 2015), CUO6 'Every customer problem is important for the salesperson' (Jha et al., 2017; Donovan et al., 2004) are specific behaviours intended to promote value-based selling. It corroborates the idea that customer orientation is the main driver of value-based selling (Terho et al., 2017; Singh and Venugopal, 2015; Verbeke et al., 2011). The following are the interviewees' explanations:

"...we are still increasing the recruitment and training of a large number of highly qualified frontline staff who can approach and interact regularly with customers, the purpose is so that they can capture changes in customer needs, better adapt to market trends, and importantly, convey the core product values that the company wants to bring to customers."

"There are many types of value that a company can provide to customers and "instant gratification" is exactly what today's shoppers expect to experience. Many buyers are time-critical, so they will choose to shop with sellers who are able to fulfil orders quality and quickly, even if they have to pay more. That is also one of the value orientations that we care about."

The comment demonstrates how crucial customer orientation is to value-based selling. Value-based selling is a key aspect of a company's service quality, and good customer orientation conveys something important that drives the growth of value-based selling. Customer orientation and value-based selling are significantly correlated, and the regression path indicates a positive association between these two variables ($\gamma = 0.238$, t -value = 3.758), proving hypothesis 4 is statistically significant.

Briefly, the SEM results from Table 6.28 provided evidence for the significance of customer orientation. It is not only a key determinant of value-based selling and salesperson performance, but also acts as a mediator in the relationship between sales strategy and salesperson performance. Hypothesis H1 ($\gamma = 0.434$, t-value = 6.859), H3 ($\gamma = 0.309$, t-value = 5.742) and H4 ($\gamma = 0.238$, t-value = 3.758) are accepted. The statistical analysis also proves this assertion, showing that sales strategy positively impacts customer orientation. Customer orientation, in turn, has a positive impact on salesperson performance and value-based selling.

Factor two – value-based selling was found in the study as an important mediator in the relationship between sales strategy and salesperson performance. Value-based selling is expensive and requires a lot of resources as well as a deep understanding of the customer, therefore, a clear portfolio of customer priorities will aid in the development of customer relationships and the transformation of a company's sales strategy into performance (Haas et al., 2012; Terho et al., 2012, 2015). Customer segmentation strategy promotes employee value-based sales behaviour, assists in determining customer purchasing power and provides value-added services, which is the basis for increasing sales and salespeople's performance. (Homburg et al., 2008; Libai et al., 2020; Storbacka et al., 2011)

Sales strategy items such as CUP3: 'The salesperson develops specific selling strategies for each targeted customer (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Katsikea et al., 2019), SEG3: 'The salesperson identifies specific customer groups based on the value that customer expects to receive from buying products/services' (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010) support the idea that sales strategy has a substantial impact on salespeople's value-based selling behaviour as well as performance of salespeople and organisation. An explanation from the participant is as follows:

"A well-defined target market allows M.O.I's marketers to create ideas and promote brands more impressively and effectively than competitors... Each campaign implemented with the assistance of senior MOI sales employees

always conveys certain messages and values to customers. All the campaigns are designed to focus on the emotional and cognitive aspects of customers, assisting them in becoming more confident and loving themselves... We have many potentials for development and competitive advantages since we are knowledgeable about the industry and our rivals."

"Our marketing activities are customer-centric and strive to create complete solutions rather than simply focusing on the customer and trying to identify the right products for their needs... Our sales staff are well trained to be able to approach and understand customers, their thoughts are all based on the customer's interests, not personal preferences, we need to ensure the long-term customer experience is optimised."

The above comments from interviewees also show a direct relationship between sales strategy and value-based selling. The H2 test provides evidence for sales strategy has a positive effect on value-based selling. The standardised regression path between the sales strategy (SAST) and the value-based selling (VAS) is statistically significant ($\gamma=0.162$, t -value=2.302).

Value-based selling significantly affects service quality and is used by companies as a way to create value for customers (Blocker et al., 2012; Terho et al., 2012). Value-based salespeople typically assists customer in achieving better financial outcomes (Terho et al., 2017), demonstrates the company's potential contributions to the goals and interests of its customers, and is a key factor in the effective behaviour of salespeople (Anderson et al., 2009; Terho et al., 2015). Therefore, it can be considered as the aspect that has the most significant influence on the functional quality of the business. Items VAS1: 'The salesperson cares about the customers' processes, focused on developing relationships and connecting with customers post-purchase so customers don't feel forgotten' (Kienzler et al., 2019), VAS2: 'The salesperson actively demonstrates to customers the financial impact of working with them' (Terho et al., 2015) and VAS5: 'The salesperson always actively listens and give the sincerest advice to customers' are typical actions of the company's service

quality. Therefore, the notion of value-based selling as an important dimension for salesperson performance is strongly advocated (Fu et al., 2010; Mullins et al., 2020; Terho et al. 2015). Therefore, its implementation is important, which can support other factors to bring valuable solutions to customers and improve the functional quality of the company (Kuester et al., 2017). As one interviewee explained:

“... It is a firm's intimate relationship with its customers... Value-based selling should simply provide unique value to each customer. We believe that it is competition with each customer for their approval of the product, its intrinsic values, and also all the great things that the company always wants to bring to customers. Therefore, it is long-term.”

This factor was also highlighted in follow-up interviews as an important element of business strategy to help salespeople connect more effectively with customers. Management interviewees observed:

“It supports to connect effectively with customers in a high extent... Typical if you sell a plot of land in out-of-the-way places and no infrastructure was built, compared to selling another plot of land that has completed the planning such as having both airports and amusement parks. Customers now don't buy the company's brand, they buy it because of the value it brings...”

“It is one of the best ways to gain the trust of customers. Do not brag or promise too much about the product, customers are very sensitive, and they will feel your credibility through your honest advice. Purchase, and experience goods value worth the money paid, they have no excuse not to return the following time.”

The comments above show a significant effect of value-based selling on salesperson performance. Also, for the first research question, the H5 test supports that value-based

selling has a positive impact on salesperson performance. The path between value-based selling (VAS) and salesperson performance (SPP) ($\gamma = 0.154$, $t\text{-value} = 2.939$) is statistically significant.

As a result, the research results provide evidence for the impact of value-based selling as an important mediator for the relationship between sales strategy and salesperson performance. Hypothesis H2 ($\gamma = 0.162$, $t\text{-value} = 2.302$) and H5 ($\gamma = 0.154$, $t\text{-value} = 2.939$) are accepted. Statistical analysis also corroborates this statement, showing that sales strategy positively affects value-based selling and value-based selling positively affects salesperson performance.

Factor three – sales skills - an important aspect that signals the company's functional quality and is a must for salespeople; it is quickly identified in the customer's mind by the salesperson's behaviour and is essential for long-term access and connection with customers (Chen and Jaramillo, 2014; Singh et al., 2017; Jhamb et al., 2021).

Sales skill with its sub-dimension (interpersonal skill, technical skill, salesmanship skill, marketing skill) offers insights into employee skills and knowledge to reach and maintain customer interactions, identify information, advice, and resolve sales conflicts, thereby influencing purchase decisions and customer perceptions positively, as well as promote the performance of employees and the company. Hence, it can be a practical aspect that exemplifies a company's service quality. For instance, IPS1 'The salesperson has the ability to control and regulate their nonverbal emotional expressions' (Plouffe et al., 2009; Singh et al., 2017; Basir et al., 2010; Castleberry et al., 1999), IPS3 'The salesperson is calm and professional in delivering their sales presentations' (Høgevoid et al., 2021), SAS1 'The salesperson has the ability to convince customers and close the sale' (Singh et al., 2017; Plouffe et al., 2009), TES2 'The salesperson has knowledge of the product line, including product feature and benefit' (Rentz et al., 2002) or MAS3 'The salesperson has the skills to create and build long-term relationships with customer' (Akroush and Abu ELSamen, 2012) supports the idea that an employee's sales skills reflect a functional quality that aids in conveying the overall value the business aim to provide to customers.

There is also agreement with the point of view promoted by Hargie (2010) that selling skills as a language of customer communication, are a factor that can be observed and assessed by a salesperson's actions and behaviour. It is essential for managers and researchers to understand the significant influence of sales skills on consumers' evaluations of salespeople and company performance (Churchill et al., 1985, 2000; Rentz et al., 2002). One interviewee stated:

“To compete with competitors in the market, we focus on service quality... we strictly manage the recruitment process, open training courses, and improve knowledge for sales staff. A new professional training class of our company took place today, it simply provides the necessary skills and professional knowledge, outlines a clear direction for employees, as well as giving salespeople time to understand diverse needs and enhance the customer experience. With the concept of 'customer-centricity', we believe that the salesperson's performance through improving sales skills in a visible aspect is a reflection of our service quality.”

Some survey participants reflected the importance of sales skills and necessary changes:

"The lack of sensitivity and poor communication skills of the salesperson made me no longer excited to shop here. My intention to return in the next few days left the staff frustrated and unsure of my purchasing decision. She became less enthusiastic in interactions and sales presentations. Instead, she could ask for a way to contact, express her interest or encourage customers like me to come back soon, which would make me sympathetic and bold to return to buy in the future."

"The proficiency of sales personnel should be consistent, and if one of the salespeople's skills is not properly nurtured, customers may lose faith, they

might worry about the firm's reputation, the quality of products or services can also be triggered, and they will no longer support the company."

The quote from the interview and survey shows that sales skills are an integral element of salesperson performance. Salesperson performance reflects the company's service quality, and good salesperson skills help to convey a certain value of the company to customers. The path shows a strong relationship between sales skills and performance ($\gamma = 0.184$, t -value = 4.313), and hypothesis 6 is completely significant. The findings illustrated the importance of sales skills as a key predictor of performance: salespeople's sales skills have a positive impact on sales performance.

The fourth element identified in the literature relates to the salesperson's adaptive selling. The research findings support the assumed antecedent factor of adaptive selling on salesperson performance (see Chapter VI), it was also found to be an important mediator for the positive relationship between personal characteristics and salesperson performance.

Some of the characteristics of the personal characteristic are, 'The salesperson put himself in the customer's shoes to advise and solve the problem' (EMA3), 'The salesperson can always identify customer needs quickly when the customer may not clearly explain what they want' (CUA1), or 'The salesperson has the ability to control the way he comes across to the customer, depending on what the situation calls for' (AMS1) are specific actions that reflect the flexibility of the salesperson. This factor supports the idea that personal characteristics (including empathy, cue perception, and self-monitoring ability) can support salesperson performance (Furnham and Fudge, 2008). This may involve actual sales behaviours. Scholars (Dion et al., 1995; Hollenbeck et al., 1988) also report a weak link between personality and salesperson performance. The following participants explained that:

"All of our frontline staff have the ability to communicate, effectively deal with sales situations, have passion and patience, and empathy for customers... Each person is different in personal interactions. As you

know, most consumers always want to express their views and needs in the buying process to find consensus as well as satisfactory solutions, and obviously that our professionally trained salespeople always know how to listen; they are ready to be influenced by our customers' diverse problems so that they can gain customers' trust in purchasing decisions..."

Adaptive selling is important in shaping and improving salesperson performance (Agnihotriet al., 2017; Franke and Park, 2006; Itani et al., 2017; Jaramillo et al., 2007; Kimura et al., 2019; Limbu et al., 2016). Adaptive salespeople are flexible in communication, can listen actively, adjust sales behaviour and effectively address the actual needs of each customer (Agnihotri et al., 2017; Franke and Park, 2006). These behaviours are associated with positive customer perceptions and purchasing decisions, which are determinants for sales and salesperson performance (Kaynak et al., 2016; Rakesh et al., 2017; Román and Martín, 2014; Sergio and Pedro, 2014). Other comments from interviewees that:

"Adaptive selling can be price customisation based on order quantity. We definitely have standard rates for minimum order quantities, although not all customers have the same requirements, salesperson with good adaptability can also carefully consider and customise prices depending on different sales situations, especially with demanding and demanding customers. This is also a way to retain customers and build a good relationship with them to improve personal sales performance."

"It has a positive influence on salesperson performance in the top extent and becomes a key factor for developing long-term relationships with customers."

"Customers always have a need to be heard and satisfied. Once the seller understands customer psychology, changes behaviour or sales approach to help them achieve positive experiences, they will easily pay for the

product, remember you longer, and definitely come back to you when the need arises."

"How to identify the social styles of different customers is an important feature of adaptive selling. A seller with good adaptive selling ability knows how to take a customer-centric approach, it will be easy to make a good impression, establish relationships with customers and close sales quickly."

The comments above signified a positive result of the importance of adaptive selling, showing a direct relationship between the personal characteristic on adaptive selling behaviour, as well as the indirect effect of the personal characteristic on the salesperson's performance. Hypotheses 7 and 9 are supported because personal characteristics directly impact adaptive selling behaviour, and there is a positive relationship between the salesperson's adaptive selling behaviour and their performance. The relationship between salesperson characteristics and adaptive selling behaviour (SACH ---> ADS), and between adaptive selling behaviour and salesperson performance (ADS ---> SPP) is significant. The path shows a significant relationship between these variables ($\gamma = 0.380$, $t\text{-value} = 8.301$; and $\gamma = 0.188$, $t\text{-value} = 3.031$ respectively).

Furthermore, adaptive selling behaviour also mediates the positive relationship between experience and salesperson performance. Salesperson experience is an important aspect of adaptive selling (Charoensukmongkol and Suthatorn, 2020; Spiro and Weitz, 1990; Simintiras et al., 2013; Weitz et al., 1986). Experience is yet another crucial sub-dimension of a personal trait that influences how the perception and conduct of the sales force are related. The salesperson's expertise provides greater awareness in dealing with customers and enables behavioural change to manage sales circumstances effectively (Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020). Salespeople with more experience show more adaptability (Levy and Sharma, 1994; Sharma, 2001; Weitz et al., 1986), and this also leads to positive effects on sales performance growth rate (Giacobbe et al., 2006; Pöyry et al., 2021; Verbeke et al., 2011). Items such as, 'The salesperson has the ability to identify and analyse customer

needs' (EXP3), 'The salesperson can adapt perception and behaviour to work with different clients (EXP4), or 'The salesperson can easily reach customers and close the sale' (EXP5) demonstrate the adaptability of the salesperson. This factor was also highlighted in follow-up interviews as a tool to help regulate seller behaviour and boost the company's overall performance. Management interviewees observed:

"Our salespeople work quite effectively in communication. They are good listeners, and good at problem-solving, have high self-control in their work and understand what's not being said, therefore, these people are readily persuaded to modify their own actions, tend to be sensitive to others' wants, and put a lot of effort into identifying customer needs. They also know well about the products and services."

The above discussion shows the direct relationship between experience and adaptive selling behaviour, as well as its indirect effect on salesperson performance. For the first research question, the H8 test supports that experience has a positive effect on adaptive selling behaviour. The regression path between an experience (EXP) and adaptive selling behaviour (ADS) ($\gamma = 0.225$, $t\text{-value} = 3.743$) was statistically significant.

7.5.2. Anticipation of future interaction: a consequence of the salesperson performance

Several results of salesperson performance have been identified in the literature review, which indicates the importance of salesperson performance in enhancing customer anticipation of future interaction (Hung et al., 2003; Obiageli et al., 2015) and repurchase intention (Håkansson, 1982). It is consistent with previous studies (Kranton 1996; Netemeyer et al., 2005; Schneider and Bowen, 1999; Salanova et al., 2005; Weitz, 1978; Wallace and De Chernatony, 2009) on the presence of positive association between salesperson performance, customer anticipation of future interaction and their repurchase intention. This study also shows the agreement that salesperson performance can arouse the desire to interact in the minds of consumers as well as drive the customer's intention to

repurchase with the company's products. This demonstrates a positive relationship between salesperson performance and the anticipation of future interaction, which is consistent with research by academics (Biong 1993; Fornell 1992; Kranton 1996).

The testing of hypothesis H10 (salesperson performance has a positive effect on the anticipation of future interaction) with the combined support of a thorough literature review and valuable data from qualitative research allows to grasp more detailed information on direct and indirect relationships between salesperson performance and customer response. For example, one manager commented that:

"A good salesperson knows how to interact, drive customer purchases, and strengthen their relationship with customers, their roles are tied to profits, reputation, and responsibility, and it's important for the company to drive salespeople's performance focusing on that value. I believe that salesperson performance can reinforce the customer's desire for further communication and interaction. A salesperson's efforts to ensure effective service experiences will make the customer feel cared for, and aware of the company's serious investment in the product, they are willing to acquire the product and ready for future interaction. As for the poor-quality customer service and lack of effort and professionalism, it will make customers uncomfortable and lose the credibility of the business. It is certain that salesperson performance may effectively convey to customer the values a company stands for and can strongly influence a customer's desire to continue the relationship."

"Customer happiness and loyalty are both boosted by effective sales performance. The mall's reputation will rise as a result of the higher foot traffic. Consequently, improving service quality is a must for attracting customers and raising their awareness, which requires first bolstering salespeople's performance."

The opinions of the following respondents also support the assertions:

"Sales performance always plays a key role. It is much more significant and special for customers who know and interact with the brand for the first time. Employee attitudes, behaviours, and sales attempts ultimately determine this. Customers are more willing to connect and build on the relationship in the future if they perceive the cooperation and positive attitude of the salesperson. There are many factors that can influence a customer's ability to acquire and develop a relationship with a company."

"In comparison to salesperson performance and repurchase intention, there is a more direct connection between salesperson performance and the anticipation of future interaction. It may be asserted that the expectation of future interactions mediates the link between salesperson performance and repurchase intention. The desire to interact and communicate more arises when you are pleased with the salesperson's performance, and this is followed by the intention to make a repeat purchase and establish a long-term relationship. We all know a strong relationship takes time to establish, the customer's anticipation of future interaction is more direct, showing a strong desire to interact."

Hypothesis H10 indicates the positive effects of salesperson performance. At the same time, a substantial link has been shown between salesperson performance and the anticipation of future interaction ($\gamma = 0.129$, $t\text{-value} = 2.015$). Salesperson performance (SPP) and anticipation of future interaction (AFI) are related, according to data collected from qualitative study and literature (Biong 1993; Kranton 1996).

7.5.3. The relationships between salesperson performance, anticipation of future interaction, and repurchase intention

Hypothesis 11 (Anticipation of future interaction has a positive effect on customer's repurchase intention) is tested to demonstrate the effect of anticipation of future interaction on repurchase intention (Agag and El-Masry, 2016; Ho and Chung, 2020; Sunnafrank and Ramirez, 2004; Sarmiento et al., 2015) (Chapter II, Section 2.5). Repurchase intention is greatly regarded in marketing materials, has a significant influence on the sustainable development of company (Ekaputri et al., 2016).

Anticipation of future interaction is the customer's immediate feeling with the seller, showing their existing satisfaction with the seller and the company's service quality (Min et al., 2020). It may have minimal impact on consumers' desire to communicate and reality (Kellermann, 1986), resulting in the development of favourable results over time (Sunnafrank and Ramirez, 2004). However, repurchase intention is the willingness to make a future purchase (Blut et al., 2015; Chou and Hsu, 2016), which is largely determined by the customer's emotions and previous interactive experiences (Graciola et al., 2018; Shank and Robinson, 2019). Repurchase intention is the overall subjective assessment of customers to re-support the company (Anh et al., 2020, Chen and Chen, 2017; Filieri and Lin, 2017). Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that a customer's thoughts and feelings regarding a salesperson's performance can influence their intentions in the future.

In order to comprehend consumer perception in various aspects and how to increase their repurchase intention, this study provided extensive insights into the dimensionalities and outcomes of customer repurchase intention (see Table 4.11). It indicated that repurchase intention is formed based on impression from the first purchase interaction (Wen et al., 2011), satisfaction with the overall performance of the company's products and services (Hume and Mort, 2010). The primary results of the repurchase intention included the customer's perception of the company's service quality. Items such as REI5: 'I will come back in the future because the salesperson is honest and can understand my preferences well.' (Kim et al, 2012; Eggert and Ulaga, 2002), REI1: 'I plan to continue purchasing products/ services from the company' (Eggert and Ulaga, 2002; Khalifa and Liu, 2007; Kim

et al, 2012; Pavlou and Fygenson, 2006; Sirohi et al., 1998), REI4: 'I will come back in the future because the salesperson is honest and can understand my preferences well.' (Eggert and Ulaga, 2002; Kim et al, 2012) is associated with positive customer impressions.

The tested hypothesis shows a direct effect of anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention ($\gamma = 0.122$, $t\text{-value} = 2.170$). Also, there are some comments on the impact of anticipation of future interaction on repurchase intention:

"Purchasing experience is a significant factor in determining whether or not customers would return to a company. If the customers are already satisfied with the first experience, they highly tend to do the re-purchase from the same shop because they know they can enjoy the same service, good experience, and also time-saving to visit and compare with other shops. Therefore, a good impression in the sales interaction process is what we strive to bring to our customers. By improving the customer's desire to interact, even at a certain point in time of purchase, it is the key to leverage that can enhance their return intention and establish meaningful lasting relationships with customer."

The obtained results revealed a strong and positive association between salesperson performance, anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention, which was supported by several other research (Beatty et al., 1996; Håkansson, 1982; Obiageli et al., 2015; Schneider and Bowen, 1999). Salesperson performance can also influence repurchase intention through the customer's anticipation of future interaction. One interviewee commented as follows:

"... Salesperson performance is linked with anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. The customer's repurchase intention shows how the salesperson's attitude and performance are perceived in the customer's previous experience and demonstrates the customer's commitment to the company... I like the salesperson's professionalism,

patience, and "people first" attitude. I visited two luxury stores before; I am still very impressed with the attitude of the staff there. For store A, what I got was superficiality and no desire to serve customers, the fact that I was dressed quite casually that day, but store B was the complete different, they welcomed me appropriately, really warm and courteous, and were accommodating to my sometimes-challenging requirements. I was really impressed and attracted by their service. I continue to purchase at store B throughout recent holidays, I believe good customer service is the key to a long-term relationship."

Scholars' reports that salesperson performance has a beneficial impact on the attributes that will encourage repurchase intention (Fornell, 1992; Mohr and Bitner, 1995; Netemeyer et al., 2010). Research results strongly support this aspect and certain relationship between salesperson performance, anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention.

Besides, the repurchase intention observed on figure 6.7 (final model), is strongly influenced by salesperson performance through anticipation of future interaction. In other words, the customer's anticipation of future interaction completely mediates the relationship between salesperson performance and repurchase intention. The tested hypothesis shows that customer repurchase intention is improved through functional quality values. The greater the service quality, the greater the company can influence the customer's desire to exchange and their long-term commitment (Bagozzi, 1979; Buciuniene and Skudiene, 2015).

The test results contribute evidence to the relationship between anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention (Table 6.28). Hypothesis 11 is significant ($\gamma = 0.122$, t -value = 2.170). In line with other research (Sunnafrank and Ramirez, 2004; Sarmiento et al., 2015), this study also discovered a positive impact of anticipation of future interaction on repurchase intention.

7.5.4. Satisfaction with salesperson, and trust in salesperson: consequences of salesperson performance

Through the test results, this study identified the main effects of salesperson performance on anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. Based on the proposed model (Figure 3.1), satisfaction with salesperson (SWS), and trust in salesperson (TRS) are considered as two mediating factors for the relationship between salesperson performance and anticipation of future interaction.

Satisfaction with salesperson (SWS), and trust in salesperson (TRS) are considered as two mediating factors for the relationship between salesperson performance and anticipation of future interaction. However, the obtained test results revealed that there is only 1 mediating factor and indirect influence on the relationship between salesperson performance and anticipation of future interaction.

From the assessment, it can be seen that improving salesperson performance leads to consequences such as satisfaction with salesperson (Budur and Poturak, 2021; Terry and Israel, 2004), and trust in salesperson (Katsikeas et al., 2009, Wallace and De Chernatony, 2009). This study examined and showed significant direct effects of salesperson performance on satisfaction with salesperson (SWS) and trust in salesperson (TRS). One interviewee commented on the importance of salesperson performance in “enhancing customer satisfaction with salespeople. Sales performance represents the effective sales behaviour of the salesperson and contributes significantly to the company's value.”

The results of testing hypothesis H13 (satisfaction with salesperson has a positive effect on anticipation of future interaction), and H16 (satisfaction with salesperson has a positive effect on trust in salesperson) show that there is a significant relationship between satisfaction with salesperson and anticipation of future interaction as well as a strong correlation between satisfaction with salesperson and trust in salesperson. Studies on the influence of salesperson on customer perception show that customers who are satisfied and have a favourable perception of the salesperson and their relationship often have a positive attitude and more willing to interact in the future (Delpechitre and Beeler, 2018; Kennedy

et al., 2001). Furthermore, satisfaction is what underpins a customer's trust in salesperson (Garbarino and Johnson, 1999; Román and Ruiz, 2005). The views of the interviewees were also clearly expressed as follows:

"Good service is reflected in the positive reviews and feedback of customers about their pleasant experiences with the company. Personally, I am very concerned about the behaviour of salesperson, it always reminds me, because the standard of living in our country is not high enough, so the professionalism in their sales activities has not been effectively controlled, it greatly affects my emotions to decide whether to or not to keep supporting a company. Beyond the product itself, I may consider trusting what the seller recommends if their service and professionalism satisfy me."

"I frequently visit shopping malls, in contact with a number of salespeople, my opinions and feelings are different for each of them, and this has resulted in my attitude towards each seller and the company also being different."

"In a certain aspect, your product may not be a perfect fit to meet different customer needs, but you can still retain customers because you have good service quality. The majority of customers come back to us just because they are satisfied with the experience they have when purchasing and interacting with our senior sales staff. Although quality of goods is essential, customer services keep the most important role here."

The above statements demonstrate how strong salesperson performance can impact customer perception. According to Crosby et al. (1990), customers who are satisfied with the salesperson will keep up the transactional connection in the future. It proved that customers' positive attachment to a business is not only due to customers' satisfaction with the company's high-quality products but also due to the front-line employees' performance and behavioural traits, which have a significant impact on customers' impression in order to form their future intentions. Satisfaction with the salesperson represents the value of a

relationship, influencing the shaping of the outcome of the relationship (Dwyer et al., 1987). Marketing studies on seller-customer relationships indicated that relational exchange is more collaborative and collaborative, where customer satisfaction and trust in salesperson are implied, leading to the desire to interact in the future (Aggarwal et al., 2005).

Statistical results of hypothesis 13 and hypothesis 16 confirmed the impact of satisfaction with salespeople. The paths from satisfaction with salesperson to anticipation of future interaction ($\gamma = 0.115$, $t\text{-value} = 2.006$) and from satisfaction with salesperson to trust in salesperson are significant ($\gamma = 0.136$, $t\text{-value} = 2.381$).

According to the results of hypothesis testing, customer satisfaction with salespeople (SWS) rather than customer trust in salespeople (TRS) mediates the relationship between salesperson performance and anticipation of future interaction (TRS). This means that hypothesis H14 (SPP--->TRS $\gamma = .035$) was not supported. Along with that, H15 (TRS->AFI $\gamma = -.028$) was likewise disregarded since the results did not substantially deviate from zero at 0.001 (Table 6.27), and there was no association between trust in the salesperson and anticipation of future interaction. However, there is an association between satisfaction with the salesperson and anticipation of future interaction with H13 (SWS -> AFI $\gamma = .115$). Salesperson performance was discovered to affect customer satisfaction with salespeople through the structural model evaluation. Trust in the salesperson, however, had no discernible influence on future interaction expectations and was unable to mediate between salesperson performance and customer anticipation. Therefore, hypothesis H14, and H15 were not suitable and was removed from the model (see Figure 6.7).

Hypothesis 15 (trust in salesperson has a positive effect on anticipation of future interaction) was tested and as a result, no relationship was found between trust in salesperson and anticipation of future interaction. Quote from one participant that:

"A salesperson's performance can have a different impact on each customer, it affects their perspective, intents, and is a factor to encourage as well as

assuring positive thinking and consumer satisfaction in the purchasing process but may not always have an impact on their trust in the salesperson. Previously, salesperson performance in shopping malls was not appreciated and we realised that this needs to be improved to increase the number of customers as well as their participation in the centre's business activities. This yields satisfaction in service quality and helps customers feel more comfortable while interacting with the salesperson, however, it is not obvious whether they can completely rely on the salesperson. Their impression can have a significant impact on repurchase intention and the company's sustainability."

According to Paparoidamis et al. (2019), good sales performance stimulates consumers' initiative to proactively engage in social interactions. The investigation result shows that there is no relationship between salesperson performance and trust in salesperson, and the relationship between trust in salesperson and anticipation of future interaction is not statistically supported.

In addition, the measurement items used in this study might be the reason for unforeseen relationships between trust in salesperson and anticipation of future interaction. Results may vary based on business types and contexts (Vincom JSC). Therefore, this study again thoroughly analysed the literature, qualitative data and the adopted research instrument in order to assess the negligible association between trust in salesperson and anticipation of future interaction.

The measurement items assigned to trust in salesperson have a wide connotation, which may be one of the possible causes of the participants' confusion throughout the reading comprehension and questionnaire completion processes. However, the discriminant validity of the constructs is proven based on the structural model evaluation and highlights the uniqueness between their measurements. Additionally, the estimated correlations were significant ($p < 0.05$). This implies that the construct is completely distinct from the others

(Hair et al., 2006). Cross-loading between SWS and TRS measurements was also not detected (see Table 6.25).

Hypothesis testing confirmed the importance of satisfaction with salesperson, anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention as consequences of salesperson performance (Baldauf and Cravens, 2002; Crosby et al., 1990; Hartline and Jones, 1996; Obiageli et al., 2015) (Figure 6.7, final model).

7.6. SUMMARY

Chapter VII discussed the research results related to theoretical expectations. The results obtained from the survey, interviews, and available literature have been combined for review in this chapter. Interviewees' valuable comments greatly supported the investigation on the topic of interest. The structural equation modelling application provides proof of the proposed relationship between structures and is statistically significant.

The investigation results show that 'salesperson performance' directly affects 'anticipation of future interaction'. The empirical results show the relationship between 'salesperson performance' and 'satisfaction with salesperson' is supported, along with the significant relevance of 'satisfaction with salesperson' and 'anticipation of future interaction'. However, the mediating effect of 'trust in salesperson' on the relationship between 'salesperson performance' and 'anticipation of future interaction' was not found. Finally, the relationship between 'salesperson performance' and 'repurchase intention' existing through anticipation of future interaction was also confirmed. The next chapter presents the conclusions, theoretical and managerial implications. Limitations of the study and suggestions for future studies will be noted.

CHAPTER VIII: CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

8.1. INTRODUCTION

With the retail context in Vietnam market, the relationships between salesperson performance, anticipation of future interaction, and repurchase intention from the customer's point of view have been focused on this study. The researcher's aim is to provide different perspectives on the antecedent factors that can affect salesperson performance, as well as its consequences (satisfaction with salesperson, trust in salesperson) so that filling a research gap. In order to create measuring scales and test proposed hypotheses, a mix methods approach is also utilised in the study, which combines quantitative (questionnaire) and qualitative (interview) research.

From the test results and the detailed discussion given in chapter VII, it can be asserted that this study contributes a certain value to the management of the company managers so that they can improve salesperson performance and promote customers' anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. The main factors identified in the study that have an impact on the facilitation of salesperson performance are sales strategy, sales skill, sales characteristic, experience, customer orientation, value-based selling, and adaptive selling behaviour. Additionally, the anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention were found to be closely linked, and importantly, they both had a positive relationship with salesperson performance.

The research model developed as an important part of this study contributes a practical significance to the topic of salesperson performance, showing its positive impact on customer perception (anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention). Discussions of the test results in particular, and this study in general, provide an expanded understanding of the human research treasure on company functional quality (service quality), and useful support for future research directions.

This study has significant implications for managers trying to assess and enhance salesperson performance. After the evaluation of the study results, it is also desirable that different directions be found in future investigations. This chapter, therefore, focuses on the theoretical, methodological, and managerial contributions to the study. In Section 8.2, the consequences discovered in the study will be evaluated. Section 8.3 presents the limitations of the current study and is followed by providing appropriate recommendations and implications to support future studies. Finally, conclusions will be provided in section 8.4.

8.2. IMPLICATIONS OF THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

This study adds certain insights to human knowledge by closing gaps discovered in the literature including 'what factors influence salesperson performance favourably?' and 'what are the main effects of salesperson performance on anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention?'. The following is a summary of the gaps: 1) there is little research evidence on the definition of salesperson performance; 2) there is lack of knowledge of the relationship between salesperson performance, its antecedents and its consequences (Mohr and Bitner, 1995; Zhao et al., 2018); 3) systematic studies on the influence of salesperson performance on consumer reviews with too little effort (Ekinici and Dawes, 2009; Liao and Chuang, 2004); 4) there is too little acknowledgment of theories and explanatory models around the topic of salesperson performance. This study was carried out with the aim of filling in the above gaps.

The opening of this study presented clear definitions of salesperson performance (the main construct of the study) (see Chapter 2, Section 2.2). Given the significant implications of salesperson performance management for company sustainability, this study also adopted a multidisciplinary approach to develop a more thorough understanding of this phenomenon. Salesperson performance is closely related to company activities because it serves as a functional quality signal to connect company with customer. Moreover, it acts as a bridge to convey the company's profound values to customers, thereby satisfying customers, and their anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention is increasingly promoted.

Related attributes of salesperson performance based on how the customer perceives it and its results were also considered in this study. Qualitative research results revealed the link between salesperson performance and its impact factors. Customers decide whether to continue to support the company or not depends on how well the salesperson performs. The company's service quality is therefore represented by salesperson performance, which is made up of sales strategy, customer orientation, value-based selling, sales skill, sales characteristic, experience, and adaptive selling behaviour. Good salesperson performance effectively conveys the intended business values. Salesperson performance can impact customer perception, their behaviour, and perception (Bitner, 1990; Keh et al., 2013). The impact of salesperson performance on customers' anticipation of future interactions and repurchase intention has not been thoroughly examined in any research; therefore, direct comparisons are not attainable.

The present study contributes relevant knowledge about salesperson performance to the scholarly research (Hartline and Jones, 1996; Hartline et al., 2003; Nunkoo et al., 2020) that salesperson performance is a functional quality of the company that can lead to certain consumer perceptions of future exchange expectations (Bitner, 1990; Crosby et al., 1990; Gronroos, 1983; Keh et al., 2013; Mills and Morris, 1986; Zeithaml et al., 1985). This study employs a holistic approach to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the company's service quality and marketing efforts, by examining the relationship between salesperson performance and customers' anticipation of future interactions and repurchase intentions. In addition, it can significantly enhance understanding by validating and improving the research findings in the field.

Research contribution serves as an important part of doctoral research, reflecting the research results achieved for the advancement and relevance of the industry being studied. This part presents the study's contribution to knowledge expansion, theoretical inferences are first taken for granted before moving on to further methodological contributions. The contributions given for managers' usage are provided after that.

8.2.1. Theoretical contribution of the study

This study has developed 2 main research questions in line with the stated research objectives, namely: 'what are the key factors that have a direct impact on the salesperson performance?' and 'what are the implications of improving a company's salesperson performance on customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention? Accordingly, four research objectives were formed to answer these questions: 1) investigate the concept of salesperson performance; 2) determine the key factors (antecedents) that affect salesperson performance; 3) establish and evaluate a conceptual framework representing the relationship between salesperson performance, its antecedents and consequences; 4) explore the impact of salesperson performance (its consequences) with customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention.

There are three important contributions of this study to the literature including theory extension, concept formation and measurement, and finally theory testing and generalisation.

8.2.1.1. Extending the theory

By examining existing hypotheses and developing additional theoretical results, this study has made useful contributions to the treasure of marketing knowledge. The first contributions can be regarded to extend the theory through assessing the impact of salesperson performance on consumer perception (Ekinici and Dawes, 2009; Liao and Chuang, 2004). Many researchers (Biong 1993; Fornell 1992; Kranton 1996; Herjanto and Amin, 2020; Paparoidamis et al., 2019) has recommended a relationship between salesperson performance and anticipation of future interaction, however this relationship has not been thoroughly investigated (Biong 1993; Fornell 1992; Kranton 1996; Herjanto and Amin, 2020; Paparoidamis et al., 2019). In addition, a number of scholars have focused on salesperson performance but not the associated anticipation of future interaction (Baldauf and Cravens, 2002; Chakrabarty et al., 2013; Román and Iacobucci, 2010). This study therefore proposes a validated framework in order to evaluate the connection between the salesperson performance, the influencing antecedent's factor of the salesperson

performance, and its consequences, and also initiatives to fill up knowledge gaps in the literature.

By examining the effect of salesperson performance, anticipation of future interaction, and repurchase intention, the study reveals a broader and more comprehensive understanding, contributes greatly to the marketing research literature on sales performance. It also significantly adds to the body of knowledge on salesperson performance and firm service quality through performing of experimental research model.

In an effort to redefine and improve the research literature in the field of salesperson performance, this study offers a substantial addition to the literature of salesperson performance and firm service quality by establishing and implementing scale evaluations of the effects of salesperson performance. Although the prevalence of research into the field of salesperson performance is undeniable, there is a lack of systematic studies investigating such consequences as the current study to provide explanatory statements for the complete range of outcomes across all existing investigations. This study's outcome is constituted of a more rigorous and comprehensive approach than heretofore.

The main factors proposed in the research model that determine the facilitation of salesperson performance such as sales strategy, sales skills, customer orientation, value-based selling, sales characteristic, experience, adaptive selling behaviour, and the main consequences of salesperson performance on the customer perception include satisfaction with salesperson, trust in salesperson, anticipation if future interaction, repurchase intention. After the empirical test, the results show that all the antecedents factors proposed in the model have a direct and indirect influence on the salesperson's performance from the customer's point of view (see Section 6.2). Therefore, it can be said that this study's results yield certain advantages in the retail context. In addition, these urge findings extreme caution when applying the salesperson performance framework and any theories created in a setting into practice.

Regarding the lack of theoretical developments and explanatory models in the field of salesperson performance, the current study addresses this gap by endeavouring to conceptualise and present views within the sphere of existing information. It also seeks to create a thorough grasp of salesperson performance and its connection to customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. Moreover, the study also offers an initial effort at establishing a validated model of the salesperson performance construct (see chapter III) to evaluate and test it as an entirely new facet of this study (see chapter VI). Many antecedent factors that could have an impact on salesperson performance were also discovered during the effort to fill this gap.

8.2.1.2. Conceptualisation and measurement level

There are many questions that arose after determining salesperson performance as the main construct of the study. It concerns the importance of salesperson performance. Why is salesperson performance significant in ongoing business? What factors have the potential to affect a salesperson's performance? Will salesperson performance have any significant impact on business operations? All of these questions result in the formulation of the research question (see 8.2.1). In order to answer these questions in turn, a conceptual framework has been built and empirically evaluated (see Chapters III and VI), thereby forming a complete new conceptual framework for the current research (see Figure 6.7, final model), which contributes a new domain of knowledge to the literature by examining the relationship between salesperson performance, anticipation of future interaction, and repurchase intention.

From the research objectives (see 8.2.1), salesperson performance is the first and most important factor to be considered. Next, the study provides and integrates the concepts of salesperson performance, its antecedents, and consequences for customer evaluation. Therefore, a measurement scale of salesperson performance was conceived to evaluate how a company's salesperson performance is managed.

Up to now, the most often discussed topic that deals with a wide range of intricate concerns is salesperson performance. Due to the lack of relevant theoretical models that can describe and account for salesperson performance facilitation, this study therefore develops the conceptual framework and appropriate hypotheses to analyse salesperson performance in further detail through quantitative research. Based on the experimental test results, it is revealed that there is a correlation between the data collected along with the salesperson performance components, implies that the measurements are psychologically responsive and suitable for expressing concepts.

The study's results confirm the importance of salesperson performance as a factor that communicates the company's functional service. This study makes significant contributions to the literature by reviewing and providing reliable measures of salesperson performance and related constructs. It also contributes to its measurement model by combining existing measurement items from previous studies with newly developed items, and testing research scales through data analysis techniques such as Cronbach alpha, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). This study adds important theories about salesperson performance's antecedents and consequences factors. The research model effectively describes the relevant constructs, demonstrating its applicability for both performing in-depth field research and taking into account in other research contexts.

This research has positive theoretical contributions based on the development of the concept of salesperson performance, its antecedents, and consequences. Through studying salesperson performance from the customer level, this study clarifies the role of salesperson performance in forming anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention, provides a clear understanding of the concept of salesperson performance and its relationship with related variables. Therefore, it has contributed positively to the wealth of current knowledge at the conceptual level. Components of salesperson performance that were clearly identified in the study include sales strategy, customer orientation, value-based selling, sales skill, sales characteristic, experience, and adaptive selling behaviour. This also assists managers to manage salesperson performance more effectively so that

salespeople can interact with customers better and improved customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention (see 8.2.3).

The relative weighting of the salesperson performance antecedents was found during the structural model evaluation indicates their varying degrees of influence on salesperson performance. Customer orientation, value-based selling, sales skill, and adaptive selling behaviour are 4 antecedents that directly affect salesperson performance; however, adaptive selling behaviour shows the greatest impact on salesperson performance, followed by customer orientation, sales skills, and finally value based selling. This result makes an important contribution, helping to form clearer judgements for managers to improve sales staff performance in order to enhance customer anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. This outcome supports managers to make more informed decisions in order to enhance salesperson performance, which will increase customer's anticipation of further interactions and repurchase intention.

Besides, through filling research gaps, this research also adds to existing resources by investigating the positive relationship between salesperson performance and its consequences (anticipation of future interaction, satisfaction with salesperson, and repurchase intention).

8.2.1.3. Theory testing and generalisation

This study aims to gain a broader understanding of the relationship between salesperson performance, anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. Through researching of salesperson performance, its antecedents, and consequences in the context of the Vietnamese retail market, this study is not only anticipated to contribute information to the body of literature but also support to assess the hypothesis and generalise the study's topic. Notwithstanding the possibility that differing client characteristics in the Vietnamese market may have an impact on the study's outcome, it can be generalised to the whole retail industry.

The present study fills a knowledge gap on the lack of research on the effects of salesperson performance on customer reviews (Ekinci and Dawes, 2009; Liao and Chuang, 2004). This study adds to the literature by assessing and adjusting salesperson performance, building scales, and assuring the validity of construct measures, this study also contributes to the body of knowledge. Additionally, by conducting qualitative investigations (interviews), several new measurement items of this study have been developed and adopted, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the concept of salesperson performance and its constructs. And even while the number of these items is increasingly different from the original, the statistical findings nevertheless demonstrate each construct's validity and high level of reliability. As a result, these findings may be generalised and applicable to a whole population (Churchill, 1991).

8.2.2. Methodological contribution of the study

The methodological contribution of this study is based on the application of multi-method (pluralistic) research to examine and explain the problem of interest (Zinkhan and Hirschheim, 1992). This study adopted a mixed-method approach, combining qualitative (interview) and quantitative (questionnaire) research methods to address knowledge limitations on salesperson performance, develop measurement scales and test hypotheses developed (see Chapter IV). Performing qualitative research enables for more comprehensive understanding of the concept of salesperson performance as well as efficient research framework customisation. Scholars (Chakrabarty et al., 2013; Román and Iacobucci, 2010) have studied salesperson performance recently but were not mentioned the connection with anticipation of future interaction, thus, this study establishes a new threshold for research in the area.

Besides, this study also provides significant methodological contributions by applying structural equation modelling (SEM) to data analysis and testing the initially established conceptual framework. The conceptual framework illustrates in detail that each of the factors that influence how consumers perceive salesperson performance, suggests that they can individually be successfully utilised in marketing investigations. Along with that,

AMOS is specifically applied to SEM to be able to analyse the paths, thoroughly commenting on the different influences between salesperson performance and related constructs (Ringle et al., 2020; Sardeshmukh and Vandenberg, 2017).

Through SEM, this study can add to the methodology at the measurement level. The widely used two-step approach was first used by specifying and evaluating the unidimensionality, validity (convergent and discriminant), and reliability (item and concept level) to measure the research model. It is detailed and provides useful recommendations for future research. This study also performs structural model evaluations based on testing the explanatory power of model (R²), path significance (β value), and goodness of fit indices (GoF). The non-random sampling/convenience sampling approach was also chosen to be used in the present study to prevent any biases in the scale's validity and generalisability (Churchill, 1999). Each procedure used in this study demonstrates the concern and completeness of the research analysis process, which can be an appropriate reference source for future studies. Overall, the study's usage of AMOS supports both the measurement and structural model levels in a favourable way.

The application of a multidisciplinary approach in the research includes a qualitative study (interview) and a quantitative study (questionnaire) plays an important role in ensuring the completeness of the data gathered. This is followed by structural equation modelling which is utilised as an advanced data analysis tool.

8.2.3. Managerial contribution of the study

The study has managerial implications for sales managers who are concerned with sales success and aim to reinforce the relationship between salesperson performance and related antecedent factors from the customer's point of view as well as its impact on the customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. The study results contribute important managerial implications on how salesperson performance can be improved in a company to achieve positive customer anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. Therefore, it can be claimed that comprehending the dimensions of associated

constructions enables sales managers to increase salesperson performance, to drive future customer engagement expectations and their repurchase intention.

In addition, another management contribution of this study is insights into salesperson performance. Sales managers are in charge of enabling communication between the company and their sales team. They must be able to comprehend the sales process to interact and assist in directing and promoting competitive strategies inside the company. This study's outcomes are intended to assist sales managers in their awareness of research concepts for the purpose of a successful business operation.

Having a good awareness of the market needs as well as the pros and cons of the salespeople, the managers will be able to easily make the right decisions in improving the salesperson's performance, thereby better meeting the different organisational goals and customer needs. Although it has been recognised that some managers have prioritised fostering a perception of common values and communication, managers should concentrate their efforts to salesperson performance and its responsiveness, which is discovered to have a significant impact on the company's results. This study is significant since it supports managers in determining if salesperson performance conveys positive business values to their target customers.

By exposing the key constituents of a salesperson's performance, this study will assist managers of various companies to understand the critical role of salesperson performance. The research offers a useful reference for sales managers who need to be attentive and consider themselves as the company to determine what constitutes a good salesperson performance, then implement the necessary modifications. Managers of companies must also have a comprehensive understanding of their processes for managing salesperson performance successfully.

In term of scales development, this study affirms the use of salesperson performance measures considerably contributes to the accomplishment of the company's goals and promotes the notion that management and decision-makers should place even greater

emphasis on it. This study covers a thorough knowledge of the concept of 'salesperson performance', the primary factor driving future interaction anticipation and repurchase intention. Salesperson performance scales highlight the role of salesperson performance for enhancing evaluations of service quality, identifying, and communicating company values that encourage desired future customer interactions, and more. The scales of salesperson performance and associated structures could be modified and utilised as a valuable reference source for company management to evaluate and track salespeople's activity, as well as to assess customer perspective.

This study acknowledges that there are seven specific components that can influence a company's salesperson performance to create a sustainable competitive advantage: sales strategy, customer orientation, value-based selling, sales skill, sales characteristic, experience, and adaptive selling behaviour. The results of the study revealed different levels of direct and indirect influence of antecedent's structures on salesperson performance. The structure of adaptive selling behaviour has the most direct influence, followed by the structure of customer orientation, sales skill, and finally value based selling. On the other hand, the sales strategy, sales characteristic, experience structures are less dominant in relation to salesperson performance. Accordingly, this study has important implications for managers when setting or adjusting salesperson performance.

Adaptive selling behaviour is one of the direct factors that significantly affect salesperson performance. Because of different customer requirements and preferences, sales managers commented that they focused on adaptive selling during the salesperson's sales interactions to tailor approaches and easily capture customers according to different sales situations, thence, ensuring a positive customer experience and their perception of the quality of the company's services. The present findings indicate that managers should concentrate on training salespeople how to adapt sales, for instance, by advising clients in accordance with a planned approach to comprehend the financial requirements and risk tolerance of customers, thereby connecting better and giving more practical advice to customers, eliciting desired responses, and increasing sales volume.

The next factor that directly affects salesperson performance is customer orientation. Customer orientation is increasingly important and is one of the core tasks of marketing management to create business performance and lasting relationships with customers (Delpechitre et al., 2019; Hughes et al., 2019; Kadic-Maglajlic et al., 2017). Customer orientation is concerned with the behaviour as well as the level of understanding of the salespeople about the customer's needs. It leads to the formation of sales-oriented interactions by finding the right customers and closing deals smoothly (Homburg et al., 2011). The study results on the characteristics of the customer orientation structure acknowledged that it is influential on employee performance perceptions, provided important management implications for salespeople's customer-oriented guidance in a strategic way to ensure a positive consumer response to salesperson performance.

Another important factor found to have a direct effect on salesperson performance is sales skills. This result makes a great contribution to managers in the process of recruiting and training candidates, fostering them to become professional salespeople. Sales skills are important in forming exchange relationships and making good impressions with customers (Jhamb et al., 2021). Based on the appropriate scales, sales managers can assess a candidate's sales skills, thereby identifying their outstanding ability to bring higher sales performance. The study's findings thus provide appropriate scales from which to identify and underline the significance of sales skills for hiring, communicate the benefits of the company's goods and services, and cultivate connections with stakeholders.

Finally, a significant relationship between salesperson performance and salesperson value-based selling suggests that management should emphasise employee value-based selling behaviour, which is known as the customer value-oriented approach at the salesperson level, help transform the company's sales strategy into performance (Terho et al., 2015). Managers should focus on encouraging employee value-based sales to improve customer-perceived value and increase sustainable sales. According to the study's findings, management should be aware of the enormous impact value-based selling has on salesperson performance responses.

There are 2 variables tested in this study, satisfaction with salesperson and trust in salesperson. Empirical test results confirm that there is a direct relationship between salesperson performance and satisfaction with salesperson. However, no correlation between salesperson performance and trust in salesperson was discovered. In this regard, managers should focus on consistency in salespeople's behaviour, providing insight into the interactive nature of sales behaviours so that they can perceive how affect customer satisfaction. The customer satisfaction with salesperson variable is likely to play an important role in encouraging consumer awareness.

This study provides a conclusion regarding the link between salesperson performance and customer satisfaction with salespeople. This finding suggests that managers should pay more attention to salesperson performance as a signal of company service quality (Bowen and Schneider, 1985; Hartline and Jones, 1996). Customer satisfaction with salespeople shows the subjective evaluations of customers before and after experiencing the company's products/services (Amyx et al., 2016; Román and Iacobucci, 2010). A salesperson performance investment will have an impact on the tangible aspects of a service interaction, not only forms customer satisfaction with salespeople, creates positive perceptions of the company's overall value, but also increases the customer's future interaction intentions. Customers are always looking for tangible value in a sales interaction, and the salesperson is the only person who can directly contact and satisfy them by providing functional qualities (service delivery processes). The better the customer's perception of a salesperson performance, the higher the customer's tendency to be satisfied with the salesperson (Obiageli et al., 2015). Therefore, managers should emphasise the performance of salespeople in a retail environment, as a bridge that helps communicate quality and value, and creates customer satisfaction with salespeople.

In summary, this study demonstrates that salesperson performance is influenced by many factors, both directly (customer orientation, value-based selling, sales skill, adaptive selling behaviour) and indirectly (sales strategy, sales characteristic, experience). This study provides in-depth knowledge of the notion of "salesperson performance" and its consequences (anticipation of future interaction, repurchase intention, satisfaction with

salesperson). As mentioned in the previous chapter, this study can offer insightful advice for individuals engaging in the retail industry because of its somewhat novel content. There is a case to be made for the possibility that the relevant elements and items under consideration might alter based on customer perceptions.

Regardless of some people's contention that no single organisation can truly represent all sectors, scholars (Churchill, 1999; Van Riel et al., 1998) argue that research survey research has a high external validity that is applicable to the entire population and to all fields. As a result, different sectors can also benefit from the findings of this study.

8.3. RESEARCH LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study provides an initial attempt at formulating the concept of salesperson performance, focusing on its significance for anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. Nevertheless, it is necessary to take into consideration these results in the context of several limitations that are pertinent for future study on the sampling/analysis process and the measurement of it, as will be discussed below.

8.3.1. Research limitations

This study aims to improve knowledge of the construct of salesperson performance, its antecedents, and consequences, however its results have certain limitations. These limitations can be divided into two main parts: analysis/ sampling method and measurement level.

8.3.1.1. The method of sampling/analysis

The results of the study have some limitations related to the analysis/sampling method. First, the nature of this study is exploratory but only takes place in the context of the Vietnamese market. Results may vary in different markets and countries. Although the measurement items applied in this study were developed based on previous studies with different contexts, and also from qualitative research, Vincom differences can still cause different effects in some aspects of the underlying structures studied, limiting the generalisability of the results. Therefore, future studies should conduct a similar investigation but in different countries to assess the generality of the study results (external validity).

Regarding the research context, this study is applied to one of the high-end shopping centres in Vietnam. The result can be different with a budget mall. Future studies are recommended to extend this study in different research environments where salesperson performance is different by their sales abilities and attitudes.

Another limitation that can be mentioned is research design. This study only focuses on semi-structured in-depth interviews with managers, academics and professionals with marketing knowledge to probe interviewees' information, experiences, and beliefs about research concepts as well as to develop measurement items. Questions tailored for qualitative research may limit interviewees. In addition, results may vary when combined with focus group interviews, which allow the research problem to be discussed in a more diverse, precise, and in-depth manner, discovered many new ideas for generalising measurement items (Powell and Single, 1996). Therefore, combining methods that provide a more comprehensive view is also recommended for future studies.

In addition, this study applies non-probability sampling technique, namely convenience sampling for qualitative research because it is not capable of undertaking a complete sampling framework. The interviewees were selected based on their accessibility and close relationship with the researcher. Although this method is time and cost saving, probability sampling offers certain advantages to be able to estimate the sampling error, prevent biases

in the validity and generality of the scales, allow to express the overall nature of the study (Churchill, 1999).

The customer experience for each retail store integrated into a Vincom shopping centre is different. Quantitative research is limited to customer perceptions of the entire shopping centre rather than individual stores. This may make it difficult for participants to distinguish which store/retail experience they were asked about in the survey. However, the study's results show the customer experience at shopping centre in general can effectively reflect the current research topic rather than individual stores. Future research may consider shopping centre in general or specific stores. There might be differences in the findings that arise from this, thus, caution should be required when interpreting these results.

This study was conducted in Vietnamese with Vietnamese customers, the data for the quantitative and qualitative research were translated in their entirety by the researcher to make it easier for participants. Even though the researcher is a bilingual person with a broad understanding of the culture, society and the research field, self-translation may potentially compromise the excellence of the research results. Discussing and seeking help from another bilingual researcher should be considered for future studies to resolve disagreements and provide other reasonable explanations about the research topic.

Due to the limited resources, this research solely presents the customer's point of view. Research results are measured based on comments from participants (scholars), who are also customers of the company in question. The scope and results of the study are subject to change when management views are included.

8.3.1.2. The measurement level

Regarding the measuring level, this study seeks to clarify the salesperson performance structure, its antecedents, and consequences as there is a shortage of information in the literature, this study undertakes to build new scales from existing literatures and modify them according to the findings of qualitative research. The measurements in this study were

all adopted based on thorough expert judgement before being included in the actual survey. The reliability and validity of the scales were moderated throughout the research design and data analysis processes. The study was restricted to a single sector due to time and survey size restrictions. Along with that, because it is only carried out in the Vietnamese market, the generality of the experimental results is also limited. Therefore, it is necessary to expand the study in different contexts, further research is encouraged to refine and develop the scales, as well as apply these scales to different samples to strengthen the validity.

In brief, this study examined the significance of salesperson performance and its impact on both antecedents and related consequences from the viewpoint of the consumer. The research scales and constructs can be used to infer another conclusion from a subsequent investigation. Notwithstanding the mixed approaches used in this study, further research can assist advance the understanding of salesperson performance. The significance of this study's findings has not been diminished despite some of the resources' limitations. In order to promote further advancements in this field, potential avenues for future study will be taken into account in the following section.

8.3.2. Future research avenues

This study aims to develop the perception of salesperson performance, as well as its relationship with anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention, provides a step towards a more thorough knowledge for future research on this topic. The following are some recommended avenues for expanding the current knowledge of this study.

As for measurement and study validation, this study adopted a mixed methods approach, along with providing thoroughly developed scales of salesperson performance. Future research may thus focus on additional measuring application in relation to salesperson performance.

This study operated the retail context in Vietnam, also included measurements and multiple constructs, therefore, future Vietnamese market researchers should consider these

established and reliable measurements. Playing a significant role in the marketing literature, this study provides an initial attempt at salesperson performance as a key criterion variable, along with its effects on related antecedents and consequences. Therefore, future studies are encouraged to extend the concept of salesperson performance in a retail environment to the presence of some other related aspects (e.g. personal concerns, supervisor leadership, sales training, motivation). In addition, future researchers can also discuss different forms of service. It should be considered whether there is any change in salesperson performance in this manner, and whether the proposed research model's relationship with the salesperson performance of the company under consideration is different. In addition, it is also possible to investigate the existence of relationships discovered in the present study with respect to other country contexts.

This study focused on the salesperson performance of Vincom shopping mall, and future researchers may measure salesperson performance in other areas to ensure the generalisability of the concepts. This study provides a solid basis for future studies to evaluate salesperson performance from the consumer's perspective.

Furthermore, as an exploratory study, it is therefore advisable to replicate this study in the future to increase the validity and generality of the measures and relationships identified. Further examination of the constructed measurement scales of salesperson performance and related constructs is also welcome.

Further research can use the conceptual model of this study as a reference to apply to the salesperson performance in other companies. Along with that, the related constructs can also be adapted for a different research environment by evaluating their validity and reliability.

Some of the findings of this study about the mediating effects of trust in salesperson on sales performance and anticipation of future interaction are unsupported. This may be related to the type or context in which each company operates. Therefore, it can be extended to future studies to evaluate the generality of this result.

8.4. SUMMARY

This study is the first empirical investigation into the retail industry in Vietnam, enriched knowledge of how salesperson performance contributes to driving customer's anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention. The mixed-methods approach was applied in this study in order to give a better understanding of the complex phenomenon being studied and deliver accurate results. This study conducted qualitative research (in-depth interview) to create a theoretical framework on salesperson performance, which was then placed to the test via quantitative research (survey). In this respect, the study established questions and explores more detailed how methodological choices could alter the impact level of the linkages between salesperson performance and its antecedents and consequences. Satisfactory interpretations of the empirical results on the formation and validation of salesperson performance from the customer aspect was also presented. This study applied structural equation modelling (SEM) as a tool to access the data, evaluate the complex relationships between constructs in the research model and provide appropriate psychometric results. The analysis results revealed that there are 7 factors that are likely to affect the performance of salespeople, including customer orientation, value-based selling, sales skills, and adaptive selling behaviour (direct impact), sales strategy, sales characteristic, and experience (indirect impact). The salesperson performance was also recognised as an important corporate bridge to drive customer awareness. It also showed the validity of the construct and the acceptability of fit indices as well as several unsatisfactory pathways were found during the analysis. There is no presence of any theoretical justification from previous studies as this current study is the first attempt to determine the salesperson performance construct.

Because of certain limitations, this study urged future researcher to validate the measures in addition and examine how constructs link together from a variety of perspectives (personal concerns, supervisor leadership, sales training, motivation) in various nations in order to fully supplement the knowledge.

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APPENDIX 4.1:

Interview Protocol: Company interviews question sheet (research questions, hypotheses, and qualitative questions)

Introduction: Hello. My name is Vy Dang, a graduate student at the University of the West of Scotland. I am doing research on the topic **Examining the influence of salesperson performance on anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention: a study of customer perception in the context of the retail industry in Vietnam**. First of all, thank you for taking your time to meet today, and for exchanging with me useful information around this topic. Your comments are extremely useful not only for my research, businesses operating in this field, but also a great help for the development and perfecting the retail industry in Vietnam.

Estimated time for this interview will last no more than 60 minutes. During this time, I have some questions that I would like you to answer sincerely. If time begins to run short, it may be necessary to interrupt you in order to push ahead and complete this line of questioning.

Aim of the research: This study is to identify the factors of salesperson performance, explore its antecedents, as well as its influence on the anticipation of future interaction between customer and salesperson within the context of the retail industry in Vietnam.

Your viewpoint on these issues is critical for me to comprehend the salesperson at a shopping centre in Ho Chi Minh City. I guarantee utmost confidentiality regarding all we discuss today. It would be greatly appreciated if you would allow me to record our conversation. I can pause the recorder if you do not feel comfortable having things recorded. We can move on to other concerns or subjects if you don't feel comfortable discussing certain matters.

About the interviewee

Title:

Interviewer:

Position

Personal responsibilities:

How long have you been with the company?

In how many different countries does this company currently operate?

Have you been involved with the development of salesperson performance in shopping malls? **Yes/No**

Date:

Hypotheses	Major references	Qualitative questions
RQ1 – What are the key factors that have a direct impact on the salesperson performance?		
H1: Sales strategy has a positive effect on the salesperson's customer orientation.	Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Leigh and Marshall, 2001; Panagopoulos and Avlonitis, 2010; Wu and Lin, 2005	To the best of your knowledge, do you have a clear idea of the shopping mall's overall strategy? How would you describe your shopping mall based on the sales activities? Do you follow a specific rigid model or a highly flexible model? How do you feel about the sales team skills and pricing strategy set up for the mall?

<p>H2: Sales strategy has a positive effect on salesperson's value-based selling.</p>	<p>Civaner, 2012; Dong et al., 2018; Gould, 2012; Kuosa, 2017; Moghareh and Haghghi, 2009; Riesterer, 2019</p>	<p>To the best of your knowledge, how would you describe investing company resources for strategic customers?</p> <p>To remain competitive, how could you differentiate your shopping mall from the other shopping mall in Vietnam?</p> <p>How do you define and strengthen your organisation position in the retail market?</p> <p>How important is customer market segment to your customer relationship management strategy?</p>
<p>H3: Customer orientation has a positive effect on salesperson's performance.</p>	<p>Aburayya et al., 2020; Franke and Park, 2006; Jaramillo and Grisaffe, 2009; Pekovic and Rolland, 2016; Tseng, 2018; Yeo et al., 2019</p>	<p>To the best of your knowledge, how would you describe today's retail sector in Vietnam?</p> <p>Do you think your company is keeping up with changes and development of Vietnam's consumer market?</p> <p>Could you please explain to what extent salespeople's customer orientation affects their performance?</p>
<p>H4: Customer orientation has a positive effect on value-based selling.</p>	<p>Goad and Jaramillo, 2014; Itani et al., 2019; Pöyry et al, 2021; Terho et al., 2015; Silver et al., 2006; Verbeke et al., 2011</p>	<p>What are the effects of the salesperson's customer orientation on its implementation?</p> <p>Could you please explain how the salesperson's customer orientation affects value-based-selling?</p>
<p>H5: Value-based selling has a positive effect on salesperson's performance.</p>	<p>Aberdeen Group 2011; Baumann and Le Meunier-FitzHugh, 2014; Davies, 2017; Mullins et al., 2020; Terho et al. 2017</p>	<p>To the best of your knowledge, how do the salesperson pursue the company's mission, target, and values?</p> <p>How will customers benefit from purchasing the company's products?</p>

H6: Sales skills have a positive effect on salesperson performance.		To what extent, do you think valued-based selling can help sellers connect effectively with customers?
	Abdolvand and Farzaneh, 2013; Amor, 2019; Basir et al., 2010; Islam et al., 2016; Jhamb et al., 2021	<p>To the best of your knowledge, how do you implement a salesperson performance management programme?</p> <p>To what extent, do you think interpersonal skill could affect communication to others, such as relieving anxiety or establishing a trusting relationship?</p> <p>Do you think salesmanship skill help improve salesperson performance, and ultimately a good influence on customer's future interaction and repurchase intention?</p> <p>How do you improve to reach customers and increase revenue for your business, especially during the current epidemic?</p> <p>To what extent, do you think the marketing skill of the shopping mall help to attract customer and build rewarding relationships with the various stakeholders?</p>
H7: Sales characteristics have a positive effect on adaptive selling behaviour.	Anaza et al., 2018; Bahadur et al., 2018; Herpertz et al., 2016; Kidwell et al., 2007; Stock and Hoyer, 2005	<p>To the best of your knowledge, how do you feel about your salesperson's aptitude in their daily work?</p> <p>To what extent, do you think empathetic ability help develop relationships, openness and trust with customers?</p> <p>To what extent, do you think cue perception ability can positively affect sales performance?</p>

		<p>What do you think about salespeople's ability to communicate and behave with customers in your company?</p> <p>To what extent, do you think the ability to modify has a positive relationship with sales performance?</p>
<p>H8: Experience has a positive effect on adaptive selling behaviour.</p>	<p>Inyang and Jaramillo, 2020; Ogilvie et al., 2018</p>	<p>To the best of your knowledge, how would you describe today's salesperson in the retail sector in Vietnam?</p> <p>How do you establish trust with customers? What tactics work for your company?</p> <p>What is your least favourite part of the sales process?</p> <p>To what extent, do you think experience help sellers identify and analyse situations effectively, thereby improving sales performance and their adaptive selling skills?</p>
<p>H9: Adaptive selling behaviour has a positive effect on salespeople performance.</p>	<p>Jaramillo et al., 2007; Itani et al., 2017; Sign and Das, 2013</p>	<p>Could you please explain the adaptive sales behaviour of salespeople in your organisation?</p> <p>To what extent, do you think adaptive selling behaviour has a positive influence on salesperson performance, and is a key factor for developing long-term relationships with customers?</p>
<p>RQ2 – What are the implications of improving a company's salesperson performance on anticipation of future interaction and repurchase intention?</p>		
<p>H10: Salesperson performance has a positive impact on customer' anticipation of future interaction.</p>	<p>Hung et al., 2003; Netemeyer et al., 2005; Obiageli et al., 2015</p>	<p>What do the terms 'salesperson performance' and 'salesperson performance management' mean to your organisation?</p> <p>How do you manage your organisation's</p>

		<p>salesperson performance?</p> <p>How do you implement a salesperson performance management programme?</p> <p>What are the benefits of salesperson performance management?</p>
<p>H11: Anticipation of future interaction has a positive impact on customer's repurchase intention</p>	<p>Ho and Chung, 2020; Palmatier et al., 2006; Prentice et al., 2018, 2019; So et al., 2014, Van Doorn et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2008.</p>	<p>How would you define good customer service?</p> <p>Have you ever dealt with an unreasonable customer? Tell me about the situation and the outcome.</p> <p>How is customer satisfaction related to repurchase intentions?</p>
<p>H12: Salesperson performance is positively related to customer satisfaction with salespeople</p>	<p>Bettencourt and Brown, 1997; Hartline et al., 2003; Limbu et al., 2016; Oliver and Swan, 1989b</p>	<p>To what extent, do you think your organisation's salesperson performance can help your organisation in area such as attracting potential customers and increasing profits?</p> <p>How do you think your organisation's salesperson performance, as a tool to achieve competitive advantage, can influence the customers' perceptions of your organisation?</p> <p>To what extent, do you think the salesperson's behaviour, can influence customer' perceptions of the shopping mall?</p> <p>To what extent, do you think salesperson performance has a greatly effect on customer satisfaction?</p>
<p>H13: Satisfaction with salesperson has a positive impact on anticipation of</p>	<p>Hansen and Riggle, 2009; Román and Ruiz, 2005</p>	<p>What does good customer service mean to you?</p> <p>What are the qualities a person needs to deliver</p>

future interaction		strong customer service?
H14: Salesperson performance has a positive impact on customer trust in salespeople	Beatty et al., 1996; Kennedy et al., 2001; Terho et al., 2012	<p>To the best of your knowledge, to what extent does salesperson performance act as a central force that motivates the shopping mall's success?</p> <p>How did your company's salespeople do to gain trust from customers?</p> <p>To what extent, do you think salesperson's performance is positively associated with trust in salesperson?</p>
H15: Trust in salesperson has a positive impact on customer's anticipation of future interaction	Alavi et al., 2019; Kaynak et al., 2016; Rakesh et al., 2017; Rippé et al., 2016	<p>What do you think about the relationship between trust in salespeople and customer's repurchase intention?</p> <p>How is a customer's anticipation of future interaction promoted to their trust in salesperson?</p>
H16 Satisfaction with salesperson has a positive impact on trust in salesperson	Huang and Yu, 2019; Lee and Dubinsky, 2003	<p>How is customer satisfaction related to repurchase intentions?</p>

APPENDIX 4.2:

Questionnaire – Vincom (Reference Company)

Aim of the research

This research is carried out by Ly Dang who is currently a Doctor student at the University of the West of Scotland, UK. The purpose of this study is to examine the influence of the salesperson performance on customer's anticipation of future interaction and their repurchase intention.

In this study, you will be asked to complete a survey about your views and feelings regarding salesperson performance. All the questions below are designed to be simple and easy to understand in order to obtain accurate information for the purpose of the study.

I appreciate you taking the time to fill out this survey as part of the research. Your cooperation is important and greatly aids the success of the study.

By answering the questions below, you agree that the information you provide will be used for the purposes of this research. You have the right to participate or not participate in this survey. Privacy and confidentiality will be guaranteed. All data collected will be anonymized and responses will be presented only in aggregate form. It will only take you 15 minutes to complete the questionnaire.

Many thanks in advance for your contribution!

Yours sincerely,
Miss Ly Dang
The University of the West of Scotland
London
SE1 6NP

1. Have you ever heard about the Vincom Centre Shopping Mall?
 Yes No (Finalise the questionnaire)

2. Below are statements of Vincom's **salesperson performance**. Please indicate your general impressions of this shopping centre.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... succeeds in meeting the sales target	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... succeeds in creating sales revenues	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... succeeds in expanding the network of customers	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... identifies major accounts in the territory and sells to them	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... sells high-profit margin products	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... makes effective presentations to customers	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... understands customer needs and work processes	<input type="checkbox"/>						

3. Below are statements about the **sales model used in Vincom centre**. Please state your general impressions of this company.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... employs different selling models for selling to different customers.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... considers the costs and value associated with the customer when setting relationship objectives and develop selling models for the customer.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... has adapted the selling process to meet the customers' different goals	<input type="checkbox"/>						

4. Below are statements about the **customer prioritisation in Vincom centre**. Please state your general impressions of this company.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... prioritises customers based	<input type="checkbox"/>						

on whom are expected importance to the firm							
... targets their selling efforts to different customers	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... develops specific selling strategies for each targeted customer	<input type="checkbox"/>						

5. Below are statements about the **segmentation in Vincom centre**. Please state your general impressions of this company.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... identifies prospective customer groups based on the expected lifetime value/profitability of each customer to the firm	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... identifies specific customer groups based on the preference and buying behaviour	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... identifies specific customer groups based on the value that customer expects to receive from buying products/services	<input type="checkbox"/>						

6. Below are statements about the **customer orientation in Vincom centre**. Please state your general impressions of this company.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... tries to give customers an accurate expectation of what the product/service will do	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... tries to figure out what a customer's needs are	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... makes every customer feel like he/she is the only customer	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... tries to achieve their goals by satisfying customers	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... tries to capture and update customer trends	<input type="checkbox"/>						

Every customer problem is important for the salesperson	<input type="checkbox"/>						
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7. Below are statements about the **value-based selling in Vincom centre**. Please state your general impressions of this company.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... cares about the customers' processes, focuses on developing relationships and connecting with customers post-purchase so customers don't feel forgotten	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... actively demonstrates to customers the financial impact of working with them.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... uses a value-based selling approach.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... works towards improving customers' bottom line.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... always actively listens and give the sincerest advice to customers	<input type="checkbox"/>						

8. The section below is to understand your impression of **salesperson's interpersonal skill in Vincom centre**. Please state your general impressions of this company.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... has the ability to control and regulate their nonverbal emotional expressions	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... has the ability to manipulate others and control various situation	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... are calm and professional in delivering their sales presentations	<input type="checkbox"/>						

9. The section below is to understand your impression of **salesperson's salesmanship skill in Vincom centre**. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... has the ability to convince customers and close the sale	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... provides prompt feedback in dealing with escalation	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... has the ability to get buy-in	<input type="checkbox"/>						

10. The section below is to understand your impression of **salesperson's technical skill in Vincom centre**. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... has knowledge of the customers' markets and products	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... has knowledge of the product line, including product features and benefits	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... understands product specifications	<input type="checkbox"/>						

11. The section below is to understand your impression of **salesperson's marketing skill in Vincom centre**. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... has a wealth of information on industry trends and important events	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... has a lot of knowledge about social media	<input type="checkbox"/>						

... has the skills to create and build long-term relationships with customers	<input type="checkbox"/>						
---	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------

12. The section below is to understand your impression of **salesperson's empathetic ability in Vincom centre**. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... is available to assist when customer expresses concern about a serious problem exists	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... demonstrates a sincere interest in my customers.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... put himself in the customer's shoes to advise and solve the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>						

13. The section below is to understand your impression of **salesperson's cue perception ability used in Vincom centre**. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... can always identify customer needs quickly when the customer may not clearly explain what they want	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... can easily reach out and participate in customers' buying process and make customer happy	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The cue perception ability is related to the salesperson's cognitive ability, judgement and experience	<input type="checkbox"/>						

14. The section below is to understand your impression of **salesperson's ability to modify used in Vincom centre**. Please state your general impressions of this company.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... has the ability to control the way he comes across to the customer, depending on what the situation calls for	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... has good vision and flexibility in dealing with clients	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... understands their own strengths and weaknesses	<input type="checkbox"/>						

15. The section below is to understand your impression of **a salesperson's experience in Vincom centre**. Please state your general impressions of this company.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							
... has many years of experience in the industry to solve problems quickly and satisfy customers	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... has the ability to distinguish between different kinds of customers	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... has the ability to identify and analyse customer needs	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... can adapt perception and behaviour to work with different clients	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... can easily reach customers and close the sale	<input type="checkbox"/>						

16. The section below is to understand your impression of **salesperson's adaptive selling behaviour in Vincom centre**. Please state your general impressions of this company.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The salesperson							

... can easily modify their sales approaches from situation to situation.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... is very sensitive to the needs of customers.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... tries to understand how one customer differs from another	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... has a clear understanding of the product, potential customers and competitors	<input type="checkbox"/>						
... has the ability to customise prices to meet different sales situations	<input type="checkbox"/>						

17. The section below examines your **satisfaction with salesperson**. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Satisfaction with salesperson							
I have an extremely effective working relationship with the salesperson	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I will continue to do business with the company even if its prices increase somewhat.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I appreciate the expertise and behaviour of the seller	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I prefer to purchase the product he/ she introduces	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Satisfaction with salesperson is the customer's subjective evaluations of the company's products/services	<input type="checkbox"/>						

18. The section below prepares to understand your impression about **trust in salesperson**. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Trust in salesperson							
I trust this salesperson to a large extent	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I believe that this salesperson is	<input type="checkbox"/>						

fair and honest with us							
The salesperson is reliable because he is mainly concerned with the client's interests, rather than his own.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The salesperson is sincere with me.	<input type="checkbox"/>						

19. The section below examines your **anticipation of future interaction**. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Anticipation of future interaction							
I am willing to discuss business with this salesperson again.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I plan to continue doing business with this salesperson.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I will purchase from this salesperson again.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I have a good impression of the company's service and will come back in my next purchase	<input type="checkbox"/>						

20. The section below examines your **repurchase intention**. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Tick the number that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Repurchase intention							
I will most likely buy this service again from the company in the future if I need something similar	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I plan to continue purchasing products/ services from the company	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I intend to recommend the company products that I regularly use to people around me	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I will come back in the future because the salesperson is	<input type="checkbox"/>						

honest and can understand my preferences well.							
I won't buy it again because I had a bad service experience from the salesperson.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I would like to work with this salesperson on my next purchases	<input type="checkbox"/>						

21. How would you describe the salesperson's performance at Vincom?

.....

22. In your opinion, what should Vincom adjust to their salesperson?

.....

A FEW THINGS ABOUT YOURSELF

In order to get a full understanding of your opinion on the salesperson performance, please answer the following questions.

1. Your gender Female Male

2. Your age: years

3. Please state the last degree you have earned.

High school Undergraduate Postgraduate and above

4. Please specify the most appropriate option below that indicates your employment status (tick only one).

I am currently employed

- Top executive or manager
- Owner of a company
- Lawyer, dentist or architect etc.
- Office/clerical staffs
- Worker
- Civil servant
- Craftsman
- Other

I am not employed

- Student
- Housewife
- Retired

I would like to thank you again for your kind cooperation and valuable time.
The sequence of the questions was based on recommendations by Krueger (1994)

APPENDIX 6.1:

Missing data (Expectation-Maximisation) analysis at item level

Items	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Percent	Items	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Percent
SPP1	385	3.89	1.493	0	0.00%	AMS1	385	5.69	1.277	0	0.00%
SPP2	385	4.12	1.538	0	0.00%	AMS2	385	5.79	1.224	0	0.00%
SPP3	385	3.87	1.564	0	0.00%	AMS3	385	5.74	1.243	0	0.00%
SPP4	385	3.95	1.592	0	0.00%	EXP1	385	5.71	1.035	0	0.00%
SPP5	385	3.9	1.584	0	0.00%	EXP2	385	5.65	0.94	0	0.00%
SPP6	385	3.96	1.517	0	0.00%	EXP3	385	5.59	1.062	0	0.00%
SPP7	385	3.88	1.588	0	0.00%	EXP4	385	5.62	1.004	0	0.00%
SAM2	385	5.64	1.212	0	0.00%	EXP5	385	5.64	0.996	0	0.00%
SAM3	385	5.63	1.196	0	0.00%	ADS1	385	5.86	1.02	0	0.00%
CUP1	385	5.53	1.184	0	0.00%	ADS2	385	5.7	1.05	0	0.00%
CUP3	385	5.51	1.259	0	0.00%	ADS3	385	3.84	1.983	0	0.00%
SEG2	385	5.61	1.22	0	0.00%	ADS4	385	5.84	0.977	0	0.00%
SEG3	385	5.53	1.252	0	0.00%	ADS5	385	5.78	0.994	0	0.00%
CUO1	385	5.05	1.489	0	0.00%	ADS6	385	5.79	1.033	0	0.00%
CUO4	385	5.11	1.495	0	0.00%	SWS1	385	3.9	1.543	0	0.00%
CUO5	385	5.24	1.408	0	0.00%	SWS2	385	4.17	1.549	0	0.00%
CUO6	385	5.45	1.324	0	0.00%	SWS3	385	3.89	1.619	0	0.00%
VAS1	385	3.76	1.686	0	0.00%	SWS4	385	4.03	1.597	0	0.00%
VAS2	385	4.73	1.617	0	0.00%	SWS5	385	3.96	1.57	0	0.00%
VAS3	385	3.55	1.736	0	0.00%	TRS1	385	4.01	1.495	0	0.00%
VAS4	385	3.89	1.781	0	0.00%	TRS2	385	4.2	1.543	0	0.00%
VAS5	385	3.96	1.801	0	0.00%	TRS3	385	4	1.587	0	0.00%
IPS1	385	3.21	1.691	0	0.00%	TRS4	385	4.05	1.575	0	0.00%
IPS3	385	2.92	1.461	0	0.00%	AFI1	385	4.66	1.493	0	0.00%
SAS1	385	3.07	1.588	0	0.00%	AFI2	385	4.41	1.597	0	0.00%
SAS3	385	2.99	1.515	0	0.00%	AFI3	385	4.65	1.549	0	0.00%
TES2	385	3.04	1.574	0	0.00%	AFI4	385	4.54	1.568	0	0.00%
TES3	385	3.01	1.537	0	0.00%	REI1	385	4.12	1.53	0	0.00%
MAS2	385	3.08	1.603	0	0.00%	REI2	385	3.88	1.574	0	0.00%
MAS3	385	2.99	1.575	0	0.00%	REI3	385	4.03	2.002	0	0.00%
EMA1	385	3.76	1.98	0	0.00%	REI4	385	4.13	1.598	0	0.00%
EMA2	385	5.78	1.227	0	0.00%	REI5	385	3.99	1.559	0	0.00%
EMA3	385	5.73	1.213	0	0.00%	REI6	385	4.05	2.089	0	0.00%
CUA1	385	5.73	1.21	0	0.00%						
CUA2	385	4.02	2.018	0	0.00%						

CUA3	385	5.73	1.226	0	0.00%	
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APPENDIX 6.2:

Normal probability Q-Q plot

APPENDIX 6.3:

Univariate variables

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Missing	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
				Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
SPP1	3.89	1.493	0.00%	0.156	385	0	0.93	385	0
SPP2	4.12	1.538	0.00%	0.159	385	0	0.917	385	0
SPP3	3.87	1.564	0.00%	0.163	385	0	0.929	385	0
SPP4	3.95	1.592	0.00%	0.167	385	0	0.921	385	0
SPP5	3.9	1.584	0.00%	0.156	385	0	0.925	385	0
SPP6	3.96	1.517	0.00%	0.154	385	0	0.931	385	0
SPP7	3.88	1.588	0.00%	0.144	385	0	0.92	385	0
SAM2	5.64	1.212	0.00%	0.376	385	0	0.717	385	0
SAM3	5.63	1.196	0.00%	0.358	385	0	0.759	385	0
CUP1	5.53	1.184	0.00%	0.363	385	0	0.762	385	0
CUP3	5.51	1.259	0.00%	0.369	385	0	0.747	385	0
SEG2	5.61	1.22	0.00%	0.373	385	0	0.731	385	0
SEG3	5.53	1.252	0.00%	0.368	385	0	0.751	385	0
CUO1	5.05	1.489	0.00%	0.273	385	0	0.868	385	0
CUO4	5.11	1.495	0.00%	0.278	385	0	0.85	385	0
CUO5	5.24	1.408	0.00%	0.301	385	0	0.827	385	0
CUO6	5.45	1.324	0.00%	0.375	385	0	0.749	385	0
VAS1	3.76	1.686	0.00%	0.19	385	0	0.911	385	0
VAS2	4.73	1.617	0.00%	0.27	385	0	0.852	385	0
VAS3	3.55	1.736	0.00%	0.175	385	0	0.921	385	0
VAS4	3.89	1.781	0.00%	0.186	385	0	0.897	385	0
VAS5	3.96	1.801	0.00%	0.181	385	0	0.9	385	0
IPS1	3.21	1.691	0.00%	0.225	385	0	0.892	385	0
IPS3	2.92	1.461	0.00%	0.225	385	0	0.885	385	0
SAS1	3.07	1.588	0.00%	0.231	385	0	0.892	385	0
SAS3	2.99	1.515	0.00%	0.224	385	0	0.887	385	0
TES2	3.04	1.574	0.00%	0.229	385	0	0.891	385	0
TES3	3.01	1.537	0.00%	0.228	385	0	0.887	385	0
MAS2	3.08	1.603	0.00%	0.225	385	0	0.884	385	0
MAS3	2.99	1.575	0.00%	0.231	385	0	0.882	385	0

EMA1	3.76	1.98	0.00%	0.155	385	0	0.912	385	0
EMA2	5.78	1.227	0.00%	0.387	385	0	0.696	385	0
EMA3	5.73	1.213	0.00%	0.382	385	0	0.705	385	0
CUA1	5.73	1.21	0.00%	0.37	385	0	0.728	385	0
CUA2	4.02	2.018	0.00%	0.144	385	0	0.913	385	0
CUA3	5.73	1.226	0.00%	0.381	385	0	0.701	385	0
AMS1	5.69	1.277	0.00%	0.382	385	0	0.701	385	0
AMS2	5.79	1.224	0.00%	0.378	385	0	0.67	385	0
AMS3	5.74	1.243	0.00%	0.377	385	0	0.714	385	0
EXP1	5.71	1.035	0.00%	0.223	385	0	0.851	385	0
EXP2	5.65	0.94	0.00%	0.208	385	0	0.855	385	0
EXP3	5.59	1.062	0.00%	0.195	385	0	0.868	385	0
EXP4	5.62	1.004	0.00%	0.2	385	0	0.859	385	0
EXP5	5.64	0.996	0.00%	0.197	385	0	0.863	385	0
ADS1	5.86	1.02	0.00%	0.418	385	0	0.641	385	0
ADS2	5.7	1.05	0.00%	0.388	385	0	0.713	385	0
ADS3	3.84	1.983	0.00%	0.151	385	0	0.915	385	0
ADS4	5.84	0.977	0.00%	0.403	385	0	0.68	385	0
ADS5	5.78	0.994	0.00%	0.407	385	0	0.697	385	0
ADS6	5.79	1.033	0.00%	0.399	385	0	0.697	385	0
SWS1	3.9	1.543	0.00%	0.141	385	0	0.929	385	0
SWS2	4.17	1.549	0.00%	0.159	385	0	0.922	385	0
SWS3	3.89	1.619	0.00%	0.147	385	0	0.925	385	0
SWS4	4.03	1.597	0.00%	0.16	385	0	0.923	385	0
SWS5	3.96	1.57	0.00%	0.143	385	0	0.926	385	0
TRS1	4.01	1.495	0.00%	0.156	385	0	0.928	385	0
TRS2	4.2	1.543	0.00%	0.161	385	0	0.915	385	0
TRS3	4	1.587	0.00%	0.173	385	0	0.921	385	0
TRS4	4.05	1.575	0.00%	0.148	385	0	0.918	385	0
AFI1	4.66	1.493	0.00%	0.225	385	0	0.867	385	0
AFI2	4.41	1.597	0.00%	0.209	385	0	0.882	385	0
AFI3	4.65	1.549	0.00%	0.234	385	0	0.868	385	0
AFI4	4.54	1.568	0.00%	0.221	385	0	0.874	385	0
REI1	4.12	1.53	0.00%	0.145	385	0	0.921	385	0
REI2	3.88	1.574	0.00%	0.167	385	0	0.903	385	0
REI3	4.03	2.002	0.00%	0.146	385	0	0.915	385	0

REI4	4.13	1.598	0.00%	0.156	385	0	0.918	385	0
REI5	3.99	1.559	0.00%	0.158	385	0	0.918	385	0
REI6	4.05	2.089	0.00%	0.141	385	0	0.903	385	0

APPENDIX 6.4:

Univariate outliers

Variable		Case Number	Standardised values	
SPP (Salesperson performance)	Highest	1	57	2.29415
		2	115	2.29415
		3	239	2.29415
		4	379	2.18713
		5	292	1.97308
	Lowest	1	366	-2.20075
		2	264	-2.20075
		3	209	-2.20075
		4	139	-2.20075
		5	93	-2.20075
SAM (Sales models)	Highest	1	7	1.20942
		2	10	1.20942
		3	30	1.20942
		4	33	1.20942
		5	39	1.20942
	Lowest	1	366	-4.12218
		2	173	-4.12218
		3	93	-4.12218
		4	58	-4.12218
		5	25	-4.12218
CUP (Customer prioritisation)	Highest	1	7	1.28723
		2	30	1.28723
		3	33	1.28723
		4	39	1.28723
		5	72	1.28723
	Lowest	1	366	-3.92487

		2	173	-3.92487
		3	93	-3.92487
		4	58	-3.92487
		5	25	-3.92487
SEG (Segmentation)	Highest	1	3	1.2267
		2	7	1.2267
		3	10	1.2267
		4	30	1.2267
		5	33	1.2267
	Lowest	1	366	-3.92544
		2	184	-3.92544
		3	173	-3.92544
		4	93	-3.92544
		5	58	-3.92544
CUO (Customer orientation)	Highest	1	103	1.45027
		2	114	1.45027
		3	115	1.45027
		4	118	1.45027
		5	121	1.45027
	Lowest	1	348	-3.41557
		2	344	-3.41557
		3	318	-3.41557
		4	70	-3.41557
		5	373	-3.01008
VAS (Value-based selling)	Highest	1	42	2.16472
		2	30	2.02157
		3	234	2.02157
		4	291	2.02157
		5	257	1.87842
	Lowest	1	348	-2.12976
		2	302	-2.12976
		3	298	-2.12976
		4	265	-2.12976
		5	197	-2.12976
IPS (Interpersonal skills)	Highest	1	146	2.70795
		2	239	2.70795

		3	71	2.36387	
		4	178	2.36387	
		5	269	2.70795	
	Lowest	1	384	-1.421	
		2	373	-1.421	
		3	366	-1.421	
		4	355	-1.421	
		5	348	-1.421	
	SAS (Salesmanship skills)	Highest	1	146	2.75503
			2	239	2.75503
3			269	2.40829	
4			344	2.40829	
5			4	2.06155	
Lowest		1	384	-1.40589	
		2	373	-1.40589	
		3	366	-1.40589	
		4	355	-1.40589	
		5	348	-1.40589	
TES (Technical skills)	Highest	1	146	2.73795	
		2	239	2.73795	
		3	269	2.73795	
		4	344	2.39358	
		5	10	2.04921	
	Lowest	1	384	-1.39447	
		2	375	-1.39447	
		3	373	-1.39447	
		4	366	-1.39447	
		5	360	-1.39447	
MAS (Marketing skills)	Highest	1	146	2.65546	
		2	239	2.65546	
		3	249	2.65546	
		4	178	2.32026	
		5	269	2.32026	
	Lowest	1	384	-1.36691	
		2	375	-1.36691	
		3	373	-1.36691	

		4	366	-1.36691
		5	355	-1.36691
EMA (Empathetic ability)	Highest	1	146	1.87969
		2	171	1.87969
		3	220	1.87969
		4	291	1.87969
		5	339	1.87969
	Lowest	1	209	-4.02254
		2	37	-3.69464
		3	132	-3.36674
		4	318	-2.71094
		5	295	-2.71094
CUA (Cue perception ability)	Highest	1	13	1.76894
		2	106	1.76894
		3	121	1.76894
		4	125	1.76894
		5	176	1.76894
	Lowest	1	37	-3.99717
		2	58	-3.67683
		3	111	-3.35649
		4	373	-3.03615
		5	355	-3.03615
AMS (Ability to modify self-presentation)	Highest	1	2	1.09758
		2	13	1.09758
		3	14	1.09758
		4	39	1.09758
		5	55	1.09758
	Lowest	1	373	-4.14087
		2	366	-4.14087
		3	209	-4.14087
		4	58	-4.14087
		5	37	-4.14087
EXP (Experience)	Highest	1	7	1.64196
		2	13	1.64196
		3	15	1.64196
		4	16	1.64196

		5	24	1.64196
	Lowest	1	320	-5.12938
		2	93	-4.16205
		3	279	-2.95288
		4	355	-2.46921
		5	309	-2.46921
ADS (Adaptive selling behaviour)	Highest	1	223	1.88705
		2	233	1.88705
		3	301	1.88705
		4	77	1.68176
		5	153	1.68176
	Lowest	1	196	-4.2716
		2	139	-4.06631
		3	111	-3.65573
		4	93	-3.45044
		5	267	-3.24515
SWS (Satisfaction with salesperson)	Highest	1	45	2.2261
		2	57	2.2261
		3	115	2.2261
		4	239	2.2261
		5	272	2.2261
	Lowest	1	348	-2.2115
		2	304	-2.2115
		3	173	-2.2115
		4	83	-2.2115
		5	78	-2.2115
TRS (Trust in salesperson)	Highest	1	125	2.20703
		2	196	2.20703
		3	239	2.20703
		4	343	2.20703
		5	261	2.01904
	Lowest	1	300	-2.30468
		2	265	-2.30468
		3	206	-2.30468
		4	116	-2.30468
		5	102	-2.30468

AFI (Anticipation of future interaction)	Highest	1	130	1.8173
		2	142	1.8173
		3	256	1.8173
		4	377	1.8173
		5	113	1.63058
	Lowest	1	343	-2.66411
		2	304	-2.66411
		3	185	-2.66411
		4	93	-2.66411
		5	83	-2.66411
REI (Repurchase intention)	Highest	1	175	2.52677
		2	324	2.52677
		3	52	2.36679
		4	308	2.36679
		5	296	2.20682
	Lowest	1	239	-2.59242
		2	278	-2.11249
		3	231	-2.11249
		4	81	-2.11249
		5	19	-2.11249

APPENDIX 6.5:

Multivariate normality

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
			Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Salesperson performance						
SPP1	3.89	1.493	0.013	0.124	-1.04	0.248
SPP2	4.12	1.538	-0.133	0.124	-1.101	0.248
SPP3	3.87	1.564	0.036	0.124	-1.087	0.248
SPP4	3.95	1.592	0	0.124	-1.165	0.248
SPP5	3.9	1.584	0.002	0.124	-1.136	0.248
SPP6	3.96	1.517	0.012	0.124	-1.007	0.248

SPP7	3.88	1.588	0.01	0.124	-1.154	0.248
Sales strategy						
SAM2	5.64	1.212	-1.901	0.124	3.907	0.248
SAM3	5.63	1.196	-1.696	0.124	3.34	0.248
CUP1	5.53	1.184	-1.573	0.124	2.699	0.248
CUP3	5.51	1.259	-1.63	0.124	2.56	0.248
SEG2	5.61	1.22	-1.805	0.124	3.479	0.248
SEG3	5.53	1.252	-1.641	0.124	2.757	0.248
Customer orientation						
CUO1	5.05	1.489	-0.865	0.124	-0.039	0.248
CUO4	5.11	1.495	-0.996	0.124	0.184	0.248
CUO5	5.24	1.408	-1.207	0.124	0.967	0.248
CUO6	5.45	1.324	-1.543	0.124	1.991	0.248
Value based selling						
VAS1	3.76	1.686	0.093	0.124	-1.207	0.248
VAS2	4.73	1.617	-0.718	0.124	-0.698	0.248
VAS3	3.55	1.736	0.221	0.124	-1.12	0.248
VAS4	3.89	1.781	-0.011	0.124	-1.344	0.248
VAS5	3.96	1.801	-0.04	0.124	-1.359	0.248
Salesperson skills						
IPS1	3.21	1.691	0.565	0.124	-0.79	0.248
IPS3	2.92	1.461	0.785	0.124	-0.077	0.248
SAS1	3.07	1.588	0.603	0.124	-0.548	0.248
SAS3	2.99	1.515	0.741	0.124	-0.282	0.248
TES2	3.04	1.574	0.685	0.124	-0.452	0.248
TES3	3.01	1.537	0.709	0.124	-0.382	0.248
MAS2	3.08	1.603	0.664	0.124	-0.613	0.248
MAS3	2.99	1.575	0.725	0.124	-0.425	0.248
Salesperson characteristic						
EMA1	3.76	1.98	0.2	0.124	-1.245	0.248
EMA2	5.78	1.227	-2.029	0.124	4.497	0.248
EMA3	5.73	1.213	-2.016	0.124	4.608	0.248
CUA1	5.73	1.21	-1.909	0.124	4.288	0.248
CUA2	4.02	2.018	-0.008	0.124	-1.303	0.248
CUA3	5.73	1.226	-2.033	0.124	4.611	0.248
AMS1	5.69	1.277	-2	0.124	4.22	0.248
AMS2	5.79	1.224	-2.261	0.124	5.716	0.248

AMS3	5.74	1.243	-1.946	0.124	4.129	0.248
Experience						
EXP1	5.71	1.035	-0.904	0.124	1.212	0.248
EXP2	5.65	0.94	-0.748	0.124	2.04	0.248
EXP3	5.59	1.062	-0.794	0.124	1.175	0.248
EXP4	5.62	1.004	-0.615	0.124	0.795	0.248
EXP5	5.64	0.996	-0.754	0.124	1.57	0.248
Adaptive selling behaviour						
ADS1	5.86	1.02	-2.26	0.124	6.327	0.248
ADS2	5.7	1.05	-1.836	0.124	3.924	0.248
ADS3	3.84	1.983	0.187	0.124	-1.206	0.248
ADS4	5.84	0.977	-1.973	0.124	4.882	0.248
ADS5	5.78	0.994	-1.815	0.124	4.022	0.248
ADS6	5.79	1.033	-1.905	0.124	4.333	0.248
Satisfaction with salesperson						
SWS1	3.9	1.543	0.055	0.124	-1.072	0.248
SWS2	4.17	1.549	-0.128	0.124	-1.075	0.248
SWS3	3.89	1.619	0.049	0.124	-1.152	0.248
SWS4	4.03	1.597	-0.039	0.124	-1.166	0.248
SWS5	3.96	1.57	0.012	0.124	-1.124	0.248
Trust in salesperson						
TRS1	4.01	1.495	-0.032	0.124	-1.074	0.248
TRS2	4.2	1.543	-0.155	0.124	-1.146	0.248
TRS3	4	1.587	-0.063	0.124	-1.174	0.248
TRS4	4.05	1.575	-0.046	0.124	-1.183	0.248
Anticipation of future interaction						
AFI1	4.66	1.493	-0.778	0.124	-0.332	0.248
AFI2	4.41	1.597	-0.482	0.124	-0.972	0.248
AFI3	4.65	1.549	-0.719	0.124	-0.543	0.248
AFI4	4.54	1.568	-0.651	0.124	-0.65	0.248
Repurchase intention						
REI1	4.12	1.53	-0.027	0.124	-1.141	0.248
REI2	3.88	1.574	0.158	0.124	-1.249	0.248
REI3	4.03	2.002	-0.055	0.124	-1.281	0.248
REI4	4.13	1.598	-0.041	0.124	-1.2	0.248
REI5	3.99	1.559	0.038	0.124	-1.185	0.248
REI6	4.05	2.089	-0.016	0.124	-1.363	0.248